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BALKANISTIC FORUM - INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY SEMINAR
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<https://bf.balkanistica.com>
e-mail: bf@balkanistica.com, bforum1992@gmail.com

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INCLUSION, ISOLATION, AND LONELINESS

Editors:
Kristina Popova and Anastasiya Pashova

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Michaela Wolf
University of Graz, Austria
[michaela.wolf@uni-graz.at]

Lebensspuren – Traces of Life¹

Abstract: *The article that follows is Michaela Wolf's introduction to the volume Visions of Historical Anthropology in Southeastern Europe. Karl Kaser – Continuing the Discussion,² a collection she edited as a way of carrying forward Karl Kaser's scholarly vision and research approaches. Our sincere thanks go to LIT Verlag for kindly allowing us to reprint and translate this text.*

Keywords: *Karl Kaser; Historical Anthropology; Black Sea region.*

Karl Kaser's untimely death on April 11, 2022, has left gaps that are, in many ways, impossible to fill, not only in scholarly terms, but above all on a human level. The reactions to his death bear impressive witness to this.

As Karl Kaser's long-standing partner, confidante, friend, listener and constant companion also in academic matters, as his travel companion and discussion partner, it is important to me after his passing that he be honoured as a scholar and colleague and that his research be continued. Karl Kaser's thinking, actions, and being were always forward-looking and future-oriented. Therefore, this book should also not be understood as a commemoration of his life, nor as a retrospective of his scholarly achievements. Rather, it continues along paths whose course Karl himself conceived and mapped out. Most of the contributions in this volume take up again and develop further discussions and conversations with Karl Kaser that were interrupted or left unfinished; some of them do so critically and question aspects of his statements. This, and the wide range of formats this volume set out to include, reveals a kaleidoscope of relationships between Karl and the individual authors.

¹ I would like to express my sincere thanks to Julia Kölbl for translating this text.

² Wolf, Michaela (2024) „Lebensspuren“, in: Wolf, Michaela (ed.) *Visionen Historischer Anthropologie im südöstlichen Europa. Karl Kaser – Die Diskussion weiterführen*. Wien: LIT Verlag, 1–9.

Karl Kaser and Historical Anthropology

Karl Kaser has opened up many new fields of research: from being originally an expert in regional everyday history, he became a pioneer of the historical anthropology research approach in Southeastern Europe, particularly influenced by Joel M. Halpern (University of Massachusetts Amherst) and Michael Mitterauer (University of Vienna). The topics he addressed in the context of this approach ranged from the role of family and kinship to gender issues and studies of visual heritage in the Balkans. At the same time, he expanded the geographical areas addressed in his re-

search and focused intensively on the Mediterranean region, the Middle East, and the Black Sea region, especially the Caucasus. In doing so, he was keen to counteract a persistently Western-biased historiography, which, in the context of his work on visual anthropology, led him to develop “elements of decentralized theory formation” (Kaser 2013a).

Historical anthropology, as his central field of scholarship, was closely aligned with Karl’s approach to life: to place people at the centre, as the starting point for a multi-layered and differentiated understanding of human coexistence and of the social, cultural, political and economic conditions and interrelations that shape it. One of the reasons why Karl began to focus consistently on the field of historical anthropology was, in his own words, the nationalism that emerged during the political transition of 1989 and soon spread rampantly in the “post-socialist” countries, replacing communism as the ruling ideology. As he explained in a conversation with his Bulgarian colleagues, historian Kristina Popova and ethnologist Anelia Kassabova, this led to a kind of alienation from his own discipline, which was now “intensively engaged in research on nations and identity” (Kaser, Popova, and Kassabova 2020: 39). He continues: “I found this abhorrent, in that the breadth of human strategies for coping with existence was reduced to national identity and thus to the demarcation from the Other” (ibid.). The complete departure from the concept of nation coincided with the

stroke of luck that anthropologist Joel M. Halpern entered Karl's life and, through intensive exchanges with him and Michael Mitterauer, "the long-awaited research alternative to the study of nations, which only further divides people" (ibid.) emerged. In addition, Halpern's wish to pass on a vast amount of data from his family research conducted in the Balkans to the department in Graz could be realized. This paved the way for many externally funded projects and countless publications within the framework of historical anthropology and its central category of "human beings".

In his *Apology of History*, Marc Bloch succinctly notes that his primary concern is "humanity [...] in time" (Bloch 1949/1985: 30). Even though Bloch does not use the term, this can nevertheless be regarded as an initial definition of "historical anthropology", and Bloch can be seen as one of the pioneers of this approach (Tanner 2004: 9). The dimension of time was also a primary concern for Karl in his historical-anthropological view of human beings, namely "human beings in their historical, i.e., temporal conditionality and change, as well as cultural diversity" (Grandits and Kaser 2003: 13). In the second edition of his volume *Südosteuropäische Geschichte und Geschichtswissenschaft* (Southeast European History and Historical Science), he emphatically refers to humans as the focus of historical-anthropological research and specifies:

[...] humans in their knowledge and [their] forms of action, in their perception and aesthetic forms of expression, in their social, political, and economic existence, in their naturalness, their sexuality, their fundamental experiences and subjective interpretations of the world and phenomena, humans as historically creative beings. (Kaser 2002: 203)

For many years, these existential moments formed the cornerstones of his research, enabling him to explore a wide range of subject areas. The path he took was not easy, as can be seen in the volume *Between the Archives and the Field* (Jovanović, Kaser, and Naumović 1999), among other works. Some of the contributions in this collection openly question the necessity of historical anthropology and reflect the difficulties and doubts that arose in the course of the gradual establishment of this particular field of research. Above all, the exploration of possibilities and scope for action, as well as the investigation of the ambiguities and contradictions of the actors involved and the constantly changing *conditio humana*, have found expression in many ways in Karl's work.

Despite the long-standing lack of recognition for historical anthropology as a field of research, not least at his own university³, research into humans as actors in history – and the resulting insight that humans should be seen “as structured and structuring actors in a diachronic perspective and in relation to their living environment in a regional, continental, or global context” (Grandits and Kaser 2003: 22) – has gained ground. Historical anthropology can now no longer be excluded from the historical canon.

In his lecture “Historical Anthropology”, which was regularly attended with great interest by large numbers of students from various fields of study, Karl postulated “Five social tasks of Historical Anthropology”:

- to contribute to a better understanding of the present;
- to highlight culturally conditioned human behaviour;
- to offer strategies for individual problem solving;
- to promote engagement with difference;
- to contribute to the democratization of society.

This shows once again how seriously he approached political considerations when selecting topics for research and teaching (starting with “Die Findelkinder der Oststeiermark (vom 19. bis ins beginnende 20. Jahrhundert)” [The Foundlings of Eastern Styria (from the 19th to the early 20th century)], Kaser 1987). At the same time, these postulations also reflect his consistently self-reflective approach to science. When asked in an interview what his early life had taught him for his academic work, he replied: “personal modesty and the conviction that all science is political, especially when it pretends to be apolitical and objective” (Kaser, Popova, and Kassabova 2020: 25).

In addition to political acumen, other considerations – not least pragmatic, research-related ones –, also played a role in his everyday decisions about the direction of his work. Although such considerations are undoubtedly part of a scholar’s daily routine, and Karl certainly took them into account, they were rarely decisive. Rather, both “Die anderen Blicke” (2013b) and a desire to experiment with research-guiding questions often exerted a decisive influence. He thus never renounced his passion as a scholar.

³ It was not until 2011 that Karl Kaser succeeded, after a long and often conflictual process of persuasion and many discussions with colleagues, deans, and rectors, in renaming the research area at the Department of History from “Southeast European History” to “Southeast European History and Anthropology.”

This, it seems to me, outlines the field in which Karl created many paths and followed others that already existed: some of them paved and broad, others barely discernible trails that disappear into the distance. These, too, are to be followed and continued by future researchers. Some of these paths are already taking shape in the contributions to this volume.

The Contributions to the Volume

The process of selecting individuals to invite to contribute to a publication is always a delicate matter. This book is no exception. Overall, it features persons who had a collegial or amicable relationship with Karl: friends, colleagues, companions, project collaborators, former students, and others.

In inviting contributions to this volume, I asked the authors to reflect on Karl's work in historical anthropology and, at the same time, to take a visionary perspective on future intellectual projects. The contributions should not be traditional academic articles, but rather take the form of a fictional conversation with Karl, a fictional interview with him or a third person, an essay, polemic, reportage, serialized story, field notes, or another format, including mixed formats. Most authors opted for a fictional interview or a hypothetical conversation with Karl, thus choosing the most direct way of engaging with him and his work.

The 27 contributions demonstrate the breadth of the field of historical anthropology, and, in some cases, even extend beyond it. The following overview is intended to offer an initial impression of this breadth of topics addressed. The first section focuses on "Fields of research" in historical anthropology that are linked to topics such as migration, ageing, health and illness, the environment, and emotions in the research process. Particular attention is given to the area of "Family research" (section two) which raises questions regarding inheritance systems and family and household in the demographic and urban context of what Karl refers to as the "Balkan family" (a term that is often discussed critically). Karl's exploration of the "other gaze" is taken up in the (third) section of "Visual anthropology as historical anthropology", where the engagement with images is also linked to future developments (keyword: AI-generated images). Several other contributions focus on field research as the most important method in historical anthropology both retrospectively and prospectively (section four), and on "Terminological aspects". The latter section comprises articles that,

from gender-specific, spatial, and patriarchal perspectives, offer a detailed discussion of terms to which Karl devoted considerable space in his publications. The concluding section, “Encounters”, illustrates the many personal and professional points of contact with Karl from the perspective of long-standing colleagues as well as younger scholars. Their contributions open up further avenues for reflecting on Karl’s work.

Against this backdrop, several visions for future work can be identified in the contributions to this volume. These are often articulated as research desiderata and primarily concern the discussion of sources and methods. For example, the potential of autofictional or autobiographical texts in the sense of narrative ethnography is highlighted, as is the need to give greater consideration to urban sources in comparison with rural ones. From a methodological perspective, participatory approaches in field research (keyword: *visual life-story telling*) and an intensified use of digital methods in demographic family research, particularly in AI-based visual studies, are outlined as visions for future work. The increased incorporation of approaches informed by the history of emotions and more differentiated gender-specific perspectives in historical anthropology can likewise be regarded as visionary.

From the diversity of the contributions and, above all, from the visions formulated here, it becomes clear that the authors, through the writing of their texts – some of them based on an intensive engagement with Karl’s work – have each experienced a personal encounter with him. In this sense, what is remembered as the last encounter was not necessarily the final one. At the same time, there is also some truth in the idea that no one who has left a lasting mark on the biographies of others is ever truly forgotten. This book bears witness to that by showing in which (academic) biographies Karl has left his mark, and how this mark enables a form of continuity and, in a certain sense, an enduring presence.

Finally, the many personal references and connections in the contributions shall be linked to some reflections on Karl Kaser’s personality.

Karl

Karl was aware that the knowledge-generating process which he was constantly engaged in sometimes conflicted with his own personal aspirations. This was particularly the case in relation to his main area of research, historical anthropology. As much as Karl’s work focused

on human beings, he hardly ever placed himself at the centre of his own reflections. He rarely considered himself the centre of attention, even though he certainly enjoyed recognition; but in personal exchanges, he tended to be reserved and modest. Or, as Anelia Kassabova and Kristina Popova describe it in their contribution: “About himself, he rarely spoke”.

The positions described here reflect contradictions that Karl embodied both consciously and unconsciously. They are also evident in his attitude toward family: although he was a family historian, he repeatedly emphasized his scepticism towards the idea of having a family of his own. And yet, especially in his later years, he took a keen interest in his own family history. His working style was generally characterized by consistency and continuity, even during his illness. Karl regarded his illness as an irritating distraction – albeit one that was constantly growing. Nevertheless, his willingness to work and his scholarly output (he was, among other things, in the process of drafting a new project proposal) remained unbroken until his passing – which still came unexpectedly.

This book is intended above all as an initial attempt to build on the enthusiasm that Karl brought to his scholarly work with unwavering and continuous dedication. This was visible not only in his tireless preparations for the 10th InASEA (International Association for Southeast European Anthropology) conference in Graz, which he did not live to see, but also in his passionate work on his last article, “Bosnia-Herzegovina and Dalmatia. Visual Oscillation between ‘Orient’ and ‘Civilization’” (Kaser 2023), which he completed and submitted only a few days before his death. He seemed, even then, to be propelled by a thought he had expressed in a commemorative publication for his colleague Elisabeth Katschnig-Fasch (Kaser 2013c: 207): “Life [seems] to be endless for us who are constantly driven”.

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Vlad Mitric-Ciupe

Center for Historical and Architectural Studies, Bucharest (Romania)
[vlad.mitric@adproiect.ro], ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4011-9041

Proceduralizing Evil, Proceduralizing Dignity: Memory, Trauma, and Post-Conflict Ethics in a Shared Biography

Abstract: *This article analyzes how large-scale violence in Central and Eastern Europe becomes administratively thinkable – and how dignity is later re-instituted – through a shared biography that fuses two extreme trajectories in postwar Romania: a Holocaust survivor (Nazi camps) and a former political prisoner subjected to the Pitești Reeducation and forced labor. Rather than juxtaposing sealed histories, the study traces the proceduralization of evil (lists, approvals, selection, transport) and the proceduralization of dignity (measured utterance, micro-solidarities, routines of care). Methodologically, it advances a triangulation of archives, memoir, and oral history, paired with an ethics of measure (tempered voice, economy of qualifiers, disciplined detail). Conceptually, it foregrounds relations between victims and persecutors beyond rigid binaries by mobilizing the gray zone of distributed responsibility and the banality of procedure. The analysis shows how written testimony (a deliberately “low voice”) carries memory from the communicative to the cultural register, while post-1989 silence – read through moral injury – relocates testimony into lived practice (care, work, continuity). Addressing reconciliation and transitional justice, the article argues for “slow infrastructures”: archival openness with clear finding aids, editorial standards that keep document and evocation apart, curricula that teach operations alongside narratives, and ethically curated memorial sites (including former communist prisons). On the question Is forgiveness possible? the article follows Minow and Teitel: forgiveness is a personal ethical option, not a public policy tool; recognition, truth, and accountability are prerequisites, and no substitute for justice.*

Keywords: *Balkans; Central and Eastern Europe; Holocaust; communist repression; Pitești reeducation; cultural memory; ethics of measure; gray zone; reconciliation; transitional justice.*

In recent decades, the historiography of the Holocaust and of communist repression in Central and Eastern Europe has shifted away from “grand” chronologies and broad institutional topographies toward a finer-grained attention to the everyday mechanisms of violence: lists, regimentation, files, interrogation protocols, bureaucratic approval

flows – “micro-infrastructures” through which evil becomes administrable and, precisely for that reason, efficient (Braham 1994; Hilberg 1985; Tismăneanu 2003). In this sense, such fine mechanisms are not mere administrative details but conditions of possibility for violence: registers and indexing generate a documentary trajectory that normalizes the exception, while approval flows transform arbitrary decisions into bureaucratic routine (Hilberg 1985). The standardization of evil – that is, its transformation into verifiable and auditable sequences – accounts simultaneously for operational efficiency and for the illusion of technical neutrality within the apparatus (Arendt 1958). This mutation is equally visible in studies of the Holocaust, which emphasize the bureaucratic capacity of Germany’s allied states to implement ghettoization and deportation with unprecedented speed, and in research on East European Stalinism, which traces – beyond the apex of the pyramid – local networks of control, documentary language, practices, and the “economies” of coercion.

The theme at stake – memory, trauma, and reconciliation in post-conflict societies – explicitly requires an articulation between this procedural understanding of violence and a reading of lived reality in its domestic, professional, and relational registers. The present article responds to this call through two explicit methodological commitments: (1) the renunciation of rigid oppositions (“victim” vs. “perpetrator,” “guilt” vs. “innocence”) in favor of mapping constrained positionalities; and (2) a focus on slow, domestic reconciliations rather than official scenarios of forgiveness. In this respect, the article situates itself within the tradition of East European memory studies attentive to the relationship between direct experience and institutional language (Assmann 1992, 1999).

This study deliberately inscribes itself within that thematic field, taking as a double case study Alis (Skamperl/Hamburg) Nisipeanu, a survivor of Nazi concentration camps, and Toni Nisipeanu, a student subjected to the Pitești Reeducation experiment (a carceral program of “re-education” through torture and “unmasking,” in which detainees, under the coordination of the Securitate, were coerced into self-accusation, denunciation of comrades, and repudiation of identity, with the aim of annihilating solidarity), followed by forced labor in the Danube – Black Sea Canal colonies. It traces the interweaving of extreme suffering and slow processes of repair, of institutional constraints and micro-practices of dignity. Our contribution is integrative: we revisit the Holocaust and communist repression not through mere juxtaposition

but through a comparative reading of bureaucratic infrastructures and coercive techniques that structure concrete biographies – an approach that, beyond their differences, makes possible a shared grammar of repair (Braham 1994; Tismăneanu 2003). The aim is not to oppose two self-contained histories (state antisemitism and repressed anticommunism) but to observe how these regimes of violence – racial dehumanization, on the one hand, and political de-subjectivation, on the other – produced comparable forms of life and survival techniques which, despite their divergences, can be read through the same ethical lens.

Our wager is to combine archival rigor with a responsible reading of testimony. Methodologically, we propose a triangulation that interweaves three types of sources and three levels of analysis. (1) The documentary – institutional level: criminal and intelligence files from the archives of the National Council for the Study of the Securitate Archives (CNSAS), as well as personnel files and administrative materials from the archive of the Romanian Radio Broadcasting Corporation (SRR). These corpora are read critically, searching for the human voice behind the apparatus and twisting the standardized idiom of documents (Ricoeur 2000). (2) The memorialistic level: *Planeta Auschwitz* (Nisipeanu 1998), with emphasis on its “low voice,” devoid of pathos, as an ethical option that preserves the proportions of suffering and the credibility of the witness (Levi 1989). (3) The oral history level: an interview conducted by the author with a witness, which, alongside factual information, conveys the texture of the domestic – tones, gestures, reciprocities – impossible to reconstruct solely from files and reports.

Operationally, a critical reading of the files entails decoding administrative jargon and relating it to scenes of lived experience: formulas such as “atitudine rezervată” (“reserved attitude”) or “contacte cu străinătatea” (“contacts abroad”) are recontextualized through triangulation with oral history and memoir materials in order to restore their meaning (Felman, Laub 1992). Ethically, we adopt a restrained tone and write in a tempered register: we avoid sensationalism, competitive victimhood, and exemplifications that over-personalize individual cogs within the mechanism (Levi 1989). We do not substitute moral judgment with descriptive neutrality; rather, we calibrate evaluation to documentable constraints, maintaining a distinction between decision-making responsibility and that of lower-level executants (Arendt 1958). The theoretical framework includes cultural memory (Assmann 1992, 1999), the ethics of testimony and “crises of listening” (Felman, Laub

1992), trauma and repetition (Caruth 1996; LaCapra 2001), the “gray zone” of intermediate responsibilities (Levi 1989), the “banality of procedure” as an institutional warning (Arendt 1958), “tragic optimism” (Frankl 1959), and a consequence-oriented ethics of responsibility (Weber 1919).

In Northern Transylvania (1940–1944), the Horthy administration prepared – through norms, abuses, and propaganda – a lightning ghettoization carried out after the German occupation of Hungary (March 1944). From Cluj/Kolozsvár, several successive convoys departed for Auschwitz-Birkenau following a phase of inventorying, concentration, searches, and confiscations, at a tempo that compressed social time to the point of its abolition (Braham 1994; Hilberg 1985). The scholarship emphasizes the operation’s exemplary character – the fluid transition from list to wagon – as a sign of local bureaucratic efficiency integrated into the Reich’s infrastructure (Braham 1994; Hilberg 1985). The local particularity – a Magyarized, educated, plurilingual Jewish bourgeoisie – was annulled by a cohesive racial grammar. To describe the mechanisms of this annulment with rigor and without melodrama, we fix several terminological markers, used in a restricted sense: banality of procedure (the apparatus’s impersonal operability: Arendt 1958), gray zone (fractured responsibilities under constraint: Levi 1989), cultural memory (institutionally stabilized forms: Assmann 1992, 1999), and tragic optimism (the orientation of suffering toward meaning, within realistic parameters: Frankl 1959).

After 1945, Romania entered a phase of accelerated communization: the abolition of the monarchy and proclamation of the republic, purges, nationalizations, the rewriting of the cultural field, the constraining of the university, the formation of a capillary security apparatus (Tismăneanu 2003), political trials, and a very high number of convictions. Within the Romanian carceral universe, the Pitești Reeducation experiment (1949–1951) became the limit-case laboratory of “unmasking,” while the Danube – Black Sea Canal labor colonies transferred coercive pressure onto work performed under compulsion (Stănescu 2010). In parallel, other states in the East European bloc operated similar mechanisms of control – nomenclature and cultural licensing, information networks, mobilization indicators, broadcasting as symbolic engineering – with local variations in timing and intensity (Ramet 1995; Verdery 1991).

The Nisipeanu family’s case traverses these two grammars of annihilation and two registers of survival. The article advances in four

movements: (1) Alis's portrait – becoming, camp, profession, ethos; (2) Toni's portrait – arrest, reeducation, forced labor, reinsertion; (3) couple life, 1967–1989 – the ethics of care and the paradox of cohabiting in proximity to former high-ranking officials of the Reeducation; (4) post-1989 – the translation of memory into public life, followed by a close reading of *Planeta Auschwitz* and theoretical conclusions. Each section is constructed as a node between archive, memoir, and oral history. In Alis's case, the stake is to preserve the credibility of the witness: a sober style, a moderated tone, refusing the aestheticization of suffering and turning testimony into a public duty (Nisipeanu 1998; Delbo 1970). For Toni, the stake is moral reframing after the breaking of identity under constraint: a reconstruction through work, care, and discretion, which trauma psychology reads as “identification with the aggressor” followed by a re-appropriation of the self (Caruth 1996; Frankl 1959). Together, their biographies contour an ethic of regained normalcy: rigor, discretion, care, and an economy of speech.

The research limitations are structural: administrative documents privilege the apparatus; memoir writing privileges the witness; oral history privileges a narrative negotiated within the interview setting. Precisely for this reason, their triangulation pursues a stratified truth compatible with verification and suitable for public use. The stake is not only academic but civic: in a landscape where competing memories can be instrumentalized, the standard of measure – a tempered voice, exactitude, and a clear demarcation between document and evocation – becomes a condition of memory's hygiene (Assmann 1999).

Born in 1927, Alis (Skamperl/Hamburg) came of age in the multicultural Cluj of the 1930s–1940s: schooling, music, libraries, and an urban politeness of coexistence. Within this plurilingual ecology – Romanian, Hungarian, German – the family's Jewish identity projected itself naturally into schooling and cultural practices, without an explicit ideological or religious program. The regime change of 1940, however, made visible the “fault line” of citizenship: legal status contracted, and social interactions were reordered by the criterion of origin (Braham 1994). The “gains” accrued to Hungarian nationalist elites (the recovery of the province, the reintegration of institutions), while the “losses” unfolded on two planes: for the Romanian state – territory, population, administrative infrastructures; for minorities – and especially for Jews – an abrupt degradation of legal status through the immediate application of anti-Jewish legislation. After Germany's occupation of Hungary (19 March 1944), the Sztójay government, together with the

Csendőrség (Gendarmerie) and the SS special unit led by Adolf Eichmann, implemented ghettoization and deportation at an accelerated pace.

In Cluj, the ghetto was organized on the grounds of the Iris Brick Factory; inventorying, concentration, searches, and confiscations unfolded according to a standardized protocol, within a logic the scholarship describes as the “bureaucratic efficiency of annihilation” (Braham 1994; Hilberg 1985). Between late May and early June 1944, successive waves of convoys departed for Auschwitz-Birkenau. Embarkation was carried out in sealed freight cars, seventy to one hundred persons per wagon, with minimal water and food rations, a single container for bodily needs, and blocked windows; stops were rare and brief, under gendarmerie guard. The journey typically lasted two to three days; for many, time contracted into a succession of suffocations, fainting, whispered prayers, and continual negotiations over vital space. Survivors’ testimonies converge: “the doors were nailed shut; we were on our way,” notes Elie Wiesel – deported from Sighet in those same weeks – in a formula that condenses the entire grammar of transport: hermetic closure, withholding of information, the annulment of dignity (Wiesel 2007). Upon arrival at the Birkenau ramp, the mechanical choreography of selection resumed, followed by disinfection, shearing, uniformization, and allocation; at this juncture, the “gaze” becomes both a bureaucratic instrument and an ethical sign of structural culpability (Hilberg 1985; Arendt 1958).

A thread of the young woman’s identity can be traced through the succession of names: as the daughter of Arthur Skamperl, she appears in school records up to 1944 as Alis Skamperl; after her parents’ divorce (or at least a familial reordering hastened by the conjuncture of persecution), she enters the administrative circuit as Alis Hamburg – her mother’s surname – as attested by Buchenwald records; probably Katz (following a very brief marriage); she then reverts to Skamperl and, after marriage, becomes Alis Nisipeanu. Historically, this passage is not merely biographical but symptomatic of the period: the name, as a juridical and ethnic marker, functions as an instrument of classification and as a resource of protection – minimal “adjustment” with maximal effect in an apparatus that decides in its own name. Memorially, the layering of names operates as a palimpsest: *Skamperl* (a Central European, domestic filiation), *Hamburg* (the maternal line and a quietly lived Jewishness), *Katz* (a brief conjugal interlude – a marriage to another camp survivor; a name borne for a short time, signaling an attempt

at a life in two within the limits of wound), and *Nisipeanu* (the relaunching of life within a postwar Romanian horizon). This sequence does not mark identity “victories,” but temporalities of survival: prudent choices reconfigured as life demands distance from repetition and continuity without grandiloquence. Philosophically, this “mutation of names” shows how the person is caught between two registers of truth: the “file of the apparatus” (which fixes identities by rubric) and the “file of life” (which negotiates continuity through loyalties and ties). Without relativizing self-continuity, the plurality of names expresses the pressure of history upon biography: an identity that defends itself by precision rather than by emphasis, preserving its ethical core beyond the boxes that contain it.

On disembarking at the ramp, facing selection, Alis and her mother adopted a micro-strategy of action: “we passed as sisters in order to stay together, knowing that mothers were the first to be sent to death” (Nisipeanu 1998: 45). Within the logic of extermination, the detail becomes an ethical instrument: the form of address, the mode of looking, the step; the correct reading of the sign determines trajectories. The figure of the selection “eye” – often abbreviated to the name of Mengele – appears in Alis’s account as a function of the mechanism: “procedural banality” (Arendt 1958). In counterpoint, consider Nyiszli Miklós – prisoner-physician and distant relative – whose name becomes lodged in the “gray zone”: a professional compelled to operate within a criminal apparatus, at times saving by falsifying a symptom, at others recording loss (Nisipeanu 1998; Nyiszli 2011). The juxtaposition produces nuance: anonymous power versus responsibilities fractured under constraint (Levi 1989). Alis’s father was selected separately, transferred to another camp, and perished there – an event that permanently reconfigured the family’s affective architecture (Nisipeanu 1998, *passim*).

The volume marks, with clarity, a double register of accountability: the impersonal mechanism (the functional gaze of selection) and the constrained personal – Nyiszli Miklós, a man caught between professional ethos and the obligation to work within a criminal apparatus. Nyiszli’s memoirs, read together with Alis’s narrative, render the gray zone visible: there are micro-decisions (a signature, a gesture, a symptom entered in a file) that can effect punctual rescues without the power to halt the mechanism (Nisipeanu 1998; Nyiszli 2011; Levi 1989), culpability in this register being stratified. At the apex stand decision and command – the normative architecture of extermination; at the base, procedural execution – the administrative “work” of lists, signatures,

and the gaze that separates the columns. Between the two lie intermediate functions (kapos, orderlies, constrained medical personnel) that can mimic collaboration without choosing it. *Planeta Auschwitz* maps precisely this scale: without suspending judgment, it refuses to simplify it. Alis's Jewishness remains unobtrusive and is expressed ethically: not occupying another's place in the story; not cosmetizing the moral difficulty of everyday resistance; not converting suffering into rhetoric (Braham 1994; Nisipeanu 1998).

After the selections, the universe of the camp was composed of regimes of the body and techniques of the mind: the rationing of hunger, the economy of gestures, the accounting of energy; and, correspondingly, the reduction of conversation to functional sentences, the avoidance of self-delusion, and the preservation of a small economy of hope (Nisipeanu 1998; Delbo 1970). In Alis's account, these practices are not romanticized as "heroism," but explained as a discipline of everyday resistance (Nisipeanu 1998; Delbo 1970). At Buchenwald, minimal techniques of preservation included micro-solidarities: the efficient sharing of rations, covering for an absence at roll call by interposing one's body, shielding someone from an impossible chore. When she notes that "each additional day meant a new test of moral endurance" (Nisipeanu 1998: 103), Alis does not deploy a heroic rhetoric but advances an austere pedagogy of survival.

A cardinal episode, transmitted through oral history, is the vow between Alis and her mother: if one were to be selected, the other would go "to the very end," so as not to be separated (Mitric-Ciupe 2021). In terms of the anthropology of trauma, the vow functions as a transitional object of loyalty: it converts the terror of separation into a promise. Its reframing, decades later, from thanatology into "care" signals the ethical maturation of memory – fidelity proven through shared life, not through the replication of death (Felman, Laub 1992; Frankl 1959). In Bucharest, with her mother on her deathbed, the reactivation of the vow acquires an extreme intensity: the request is not symbolic but an explicit invitation to suicide. Alis's refusal to literalize the promise – to turn fidelity into co-participation in death – marks the ethical pivot of her life: loyalty is tested by the sustaining of life, by life shared, not by reenacting the end (Mitric-Ciupe 2021).

Liberation in April 1945 is not experienced as triumph but as an exigency of restrained testimony, whose public articulation is suspended, for historical and personal reasons, until the 1990s. The return to Cluj meant scattered or definitively lost kin, poverty, and a faltering

resumption of studies¹. Meeting another camp survivor, which became a brief marriage, does not yield an idealizing register but a life-for-two marked by trauma: a shared alphabet of suffering that can support co-regulation and, at the same time, the risk of co-reactivation. The loss of a child deepened the rupture: mourning became a secondary trauma, and the couple oscillated between silence and testimony, withdrawal and re-approach. In the logic of an ethics of measure, the fact that the marriage ended in divorce is not merely private biography but a pedagogy of the boundary: an attempt to protect life from the compulsion of repetition and to prevent the transformation of fidelity into co-participation in death. Separation functions as an act of responsibility – fidelity is verified through care and the husbanding of possible life, not through reenactment of the ending. Thus the conjugal relationship remains a laboratory of moral memory, in which measure orders what can be borne together and what must be allowed to fall away. This succession of losses imposes, in the immediate postwar years, a discipline of silence. Later, when Alis writes, she will ask of the text what she asked of life: measure, proportion, sobriety (Nisipeanu 1998, *passim*).

In February 1949, Alis entered, as a functionary, an infrastructure of cultural translation: the Romanian Association for Strengthening Ties with the Soviet Union (ARLUS), an intermediary institution that disseminated Soviet language, literature, and science while working with mobilization indicators (subscriptions, circles, lectures) – a school for the exact sentence and the tempered tone (Vasile 2010). In practice, ARLUS files quantified “impact” through attendance cards, subscription ledgers, and standardized reports organized by rubric (topic, lecturer, conclusions, proposals), circulating vertically through the network. It is precisely this accounting of forms – seemingly anodyne – that trained the textual discipline which, later, became the infrastructure of Alis’s written memory (Vasile 2010). Operationally, such institutions functioned as ideological “transducers” with measurable indicators: language courses, reading soirées, “scientific” exhibitions, lectures with sign-in sheets and “impact” reports. After a few months, she transferred to the ARLUS General Council. Analytically, her placement as an “activist” must be read within the register of constrained positionalities: not as evidence of doctrinal zeal, but as pragmatic accommodation within an institutional field that rewarded procedural conformity and

¹ ASRR, Personnel Files Collection, file Alis Nisipeanu, n.p. The document records the obtaining of the diploma from Boys’ Secondary School No. 7 in Cluj only in 1955.

the capacity to deliver quantifiable results. Benefits (professional networks, symbolic capital, access to resources) came bundled with risks (visibility, surveillance, loyalty tests), establishing that gray zone in which bureaucratic competence and ethical prudence co-exist and, over time, shape the economy of testimony: enumerative, controlled, attentive to proportion, and reticent toward spectacle.

Beginning in 1952, she joined Romanian Radio² and remained there for more than three decades. She initially worked as an editor in the Children's and School Youth Editorial Office, then as a controller in the Broadcast Control Service, Hungarian-language broadcast controller, editor in the Programs and Syntheses Service, and subsequently lecturer and editor, ultimately reaching the highest grade. The socialist radio was an apparatus of signs: broadcast schedules, chain approvals, ex-ante and ex-post censorship, lists of interdictions – yet also a structural need for infrastructural professionalism (SRR 1998; Vasile 2010). In the “safe” editorial departments (culture, education, science), professionalism functioned as hygiene: broadcast brief, editorial visa, timing, lexical verification, followed by ex-ante/ex-post control. There was no freedom, but there existed a margin within which “good form” diluted the density of propaganda – the space in which Alis would install her ethos (SRR 1998). She specialized in “safe” perimeters (cultural, educational, scientific), practiced an ethics of responsibility (Weber 1919), and navigated the “gray zone” of conformity without zeal (Levi 1989). Internal evaluations record her as “disciplined,” “cooperative,” and “proactive.” An investigated fire ended without sanctions, confirming that procedures had been respected at her level³.

This episode highlights not only technical “correctness” but also her relation to the institution: respect for procedure as a way to preempt arbitrariness and, at the same time, a strategy of self-protection within an apparatus predisposed to collective sanctions. Alis's statement⁴ on this occasion – drafted in the dry register of the official record – retains only the essentials: she entered, left the room to attend to other tasks, returned after an interval; she found a localized fire, extinguished quickly, and succinctly described the damage, without causal hypotheses or imputations. The vulnerable detail – she had left the door open –

² *Ibidem*, n.p. Employment record dated 05.08.1952. At that time, the institution was named the Radio Committee attached to the Council of Ministers of the People's Republic of Romania.

³ *Ibidem*, n.p. Report on the fire dated 26.12.1952.

⁴ *Ibidem*, n.p. Statement dated 29.12.1952.

functions as tempered honesty and self-protection in an apparatus inclined toward collective punishment; the outcome without sanctions confirms the match between her textual style and the institution's expectations.

A second relevant episode occurred a few years later. The loss of her free-pass card – issued by the Radio Committee attached to the Council of Ministers of the RPR, therefore a document with major political weight – exposed Alis to real risk in a regime of suspicion. Her statement⁵ responds exactly to the apparatus's expectations: it reconstructs the object's trajectory, marks the effort to verify, accuses no one, and explicitly assumes "lack of vigilance" – a key formula of ideological vocabulary. It is calibrated honesty: sufficient assumption of fault to defuse the hypothesis of intent, without supplying sacrificial scapegoats. The sanction received – a written reprimand – indicated that the institution read the episode as negligence rather than sabotage, a sign that Alis already possessed a reserve of trust derived from reliability and procedural conformity. The episode foregrounds self-control, rigor, and responsibility: Alis internalized the norms of the apparatus (formulating her fault in its terms) yet refused utilitarian denunciation, opting instead for an ethics of measure – saying what is necessary, assuming her share, and shielding the collective from cascading disciplinary effects. Her relationship to the regime appears as pragmatic loyalty: she knew how to speak the "language" of a propaganda institution without rhetorical zeal, negotiating reentry into bureaucratic normalcy by accepting a symbolic penalty and implicitly promising increased discipline. Concluding with a written reprimand, the episode shows how her way of life and of writing – clear, measured, without theatricality – functioned as a strategy of self-protection in a field where minor errors could become pretexts for exemplary punishment.

Normatively, the same preference for disciplined accuracy would guide the demands she later placed on memory (Ricoeur 2000). In a technically oriented, male-dominated institution, Alis built authority through reliability, clarity, and continuity, but also through a technique of voicing that introduced measure and calm into public discourse (SRR 1998). Rhythm, breath, articulation – a sober register with a grave timbre – softened official language without frontal defiance. The effect was practical: the public received information without hyperbole, and cultural programs remained intelligible and circulable in an ideologically

⁵ *Ibidem*, n.p. Statement dated 08.03.1954.

saturated environment (SRR 1998; Vasile 2010). In sum, Alis's trajectory shows how a quietly lived Jewish identity before the war was re-configured, after the camps, into an ethical sense of utterance: to speak exactly, not to occupy another's place in the story, not to convert suffering into rhetoric. Hence the volume's key intuition: the truth of memory lies less in "effect" than in proportion (Nisipeanu 1998; Levi 1989).

Before colliding with the repressive apparatus, Toni Nisipeanu – born in 1927, like Alis – emerges as a young man formed within the post-1945 student milieu, at a moment when the university became both a space of education and a terrain of ideological reconfiguration. Beginning in 1948, waves of purges, the proliferation of "mass" organizations, and the reform of higher education shifted the emphasis from academic performance to political loyalty, turning the student into a privileged target of the apparatus (Stănescu 2010). Toni's arrest in May 1949 – when he was a third-year student at the Faculty of Medicine in Bucharest – occurred within the logic of the period's student "lots": coordinated roundups, searches, seizure of correspondence, isolation, interrogations. The standard investigative repertoire entailed sleep deprivation, cascading inquiries, staged confrontations, pressures of every kind, and, above all, the use of violence, all aimed at producing the "convergent statements" required for the juridical construction of the case (Stănescu 2010: 314–318).

The accusations against Toni concerned his participation, from January 1948 until his arrest, in several meetings among young men who sought to lay the groundwork for a royalist organization in the wake of the forced abolition of the monarchy⁶. At the time, investigations into student (and other) anti-communist initiatives targeted less acts already consummated than the potential for association. Apartment meetings or discussions of "organization" sufficed to generate charges. The routine practices of the apparatus rarely transpire in the final documents, but they can be read in the texture of the statements: standardized formulas, cautious delimitations, selective memory. In this key, Toni's declarations during the inquiry must be read as products of a coercive regime rather than as a free autobiography.

They reveal a strategy of minimal admission and maximal denial: he confirms presence at several meetings and adopts the terminology of

⁶ ACNSAS, Criminal Files Collection, file no. 1465, vol. 1, ff. 2-13. Record dated 29.06.1949.

“organization,” yet he systematically refuses any “active” step (he recruited no one, took no oath, drafted or distributed no manifestos). Psychologically, the discourse is defensively controlled: it inventories interlocutors and settings, marks divergences (“I did not agree with the action”), and then folds back onto the identity of the student (“we resumed our university activity”). Ethically, the tone avoids both heroization and denunciation: he assumes his own positioning without burdening others with additional accusations – a measured stance that seeks to mitigate harm within a punitive field.

At the organizational level, the text shows that Toni understood the alphabet of risk: he differentiates between “organization” (discussion, scheme) and “action” (manifestos); he describes the initiator as oriented toward the spectacular gesture; and he situates his own profile in the register of prudence. Philosophically, the statements practice an ethics of limited responsibility: they acknowledge participation in conversations while refusing a violent teleology, attempting to preserve a minimal space for professional life. As documents of their time, they speak as much to the institutional scenography of testimony – what could be uttered in order to remain within the bounds of the tolerable – as they do to the facts themselves. Taken together, the case places Toni in the gray zone of constrained positionalities: neither militant nor collaborator (voluntary or otherwise), but an actor seeking to limit exposure, negotiating between everyday loyalties and an apparatus that transformed conversation into offense⁷.

The trial was summary: the evidentiary record relied on statements obtained under coercion and on the “testimonies” of co-defendants from connected files; the defense had minimal latitude, and the sentence reproduces the indictment almost verbatim, condemning Nisipeanu to five years’ correctional imprisonment for conspiracy against the social order⁸. His carceral trajectory included Jilava – the notorious former subterranean military fort near Bucharest – the Pitești penitentiary, where the political regime aimed to restructure/reeducate students and transform them from enemies/opponents – real or imagined – into communist adherents and activists, and the forced-labor colonies along the Danube – Black Sea Canal route, until his release in 1954.

What occurred in the Pitești prison – the limit-case laboratory of “unmasking” (Stănescu 2010: 314-324) – also targeted the annulment of moral identity. Under total pressure, Toni entered a state of “total

⁷ *Ibidem*, ff. 268-269. Statement dated 29.06.1949.

⁸ *Ibidem*, vol. 2, ff. 219-223. Criminal sentence dated 25.11.1949.

submission”: not an ethical choice but a survival mechanism comparable to “identification with the aggressor” (Felman, Laub 1992; Caruth 1996). In this phase, Nisipeanu was caught in the choreography of unmaskings: coerced participation in rituals, replication of formulas of self-accusation, internalization of a vocabulary of culpability, the torture of fellow inmates, self-indictments, denunciations. The theoretical framework of “identification with the aggressor” does not exonerate, but it does explain the mechanism: under torture, the subject alters his strategy of self-preservation, ceding language in order to save life (Felman, Laub 1992; Caruth 1996).

Transfer to the Danube – Black Sea Canal colonies shifted the emphasis to labor exploitation, this time within a particular micro-universe (the Peninsula camp) where the “student brigades” included numerous former detainees who had passed through the Pitești Reeducation. Norms were both technical and political: failure to meet one’s quota attracted sanctions (ration reductions, isolation, assignment to harsher sectors). The “construction site” rhythm generated its own temporality: roll call – mobilization – quota – report – meeting. In these meetings, the leading scholar of the subject notes the continuity of unmaskings in domesticated formats: analyses of conduct, self-criticisms, political instruction, and discussions of conscience (Stănescu 2010: 325-328). Although violence no longer matched the intensity of the Pitești laboratory, the function remained the same: control of language and the internalization of culpability. The students’ educational capital made them useful for measurements, centralizations, and reports, while simultaneously rendering them visible to the apparatus; the “brigade leader” mediated the quota, productivity, and micro-rituals of control. In this ecology, signs of return appeared for some who had “fallen”: within the exhausting repetition of days, interstices of minimal solidarity opened (task-swapping for an exhausted comrade, shielding a sick prisoner at roll call) – gestures that, for Toni, marked the beginning of moral reframing.

Toni’s trajectory exemplifies a structural biographical rupture: a brilliant medical student at the moment of arrest, he became – after conviction and passage through Reeducation – a professional deliberately kept at the margins of his vocation. The resumption of studies was obstructed, the carceral stigma remained active, and informational surveillance did not cease; the “file” functioned as an anti-title, converting scholastic capital into political risk. Sociologically, this is the mecha-

nism of professional closure: merit is decoupled from mobility, and scientific work is permitted only in subordinate, closely supervised forms. The result is a “controlled de-qualification”: blocked access to the desired profession and forced acceptance of the status of laboratory technician in a contemporary institute – not because of incapacity, but because the political order demanded docility and low visibility.

Psychologically, we see the loss of a professional identity and the recalibration of hope: the promise of medical practice narrows to technical gestures, yet continuity is salvaged through rigor, exactitude, and usefulness. In Frankl’s (1959) terms, this return is a “tragic optimism”: suffering is oriented toward meaning through quiet work, care, and fidelity rather than rhetoric. He spoke little of the carceral experience at the time (Mitric-Ciupe 2021), and he neither wrote nor published after 1989. In a clinical-narrative key, the post-1989 silence can be read through the lens of “moral injury” (Shay 1994): the episode of unmaskings wounded the relationship to language, such that silence becomes a “guarding of speech,” not an evasion of responsibility. Taken as a whole, his fate shows how the apparatus rewrites biographies through administrative barriers, while the feasible response remains an ethics of modest continuity: doing well what can still be done, within imposed limits.

Although the circumstances of their first meeting in the early 1960s remain unknown, the marriage of Alis and Toni in 1967 inaugurated a trajectory of domestic reconstruction under constraining institutional conditions. In the early years, the couple lived in the attic of the villa owned by Gavril and Eva Birtaş (Alis’s cousin). Gavril’s biography traces the path of the “professional revolutionary”: interwar illegality, imprisonment for communist activity, and then an accelerated career after 1948 within the Securitate, rising to head both Directorate I and Directorate III – precisely the structures that supervised the Reeducation. By the mid-1950s he was purged and sidelined, though later rehabilitated, with full recognition of his communist activity (Stănescu 2010: 401-410). Eva Birtaş also operated in the communist underground; in 1949 she was appointed deputy head of the Securitate’s prisons and camps (the Operative Service), likewise indicating a link to the Reeducation. She later headed personnel in the General Directorate of Penitentiaries and then spent several years in the cultural-ideological apparatus – the Directorate for Cultural Guidance (Stănescu 2025: 259). The paradox is evident: a victim of Pitești cohabits in the home of a family once located at the very center of the repressive mechanism. And

yet, today's oral testimony preserves genuine gestures of hospitality: "Eva treated them as her own, and Gavril, though taciturn, took care that nothing was lacking" (Mitric-Ciupe 2021). This is the "gray zone" and the "banality of procedure" in a domestic register: not exoneration, but a complication of judgment (Levi 1989; Arendt 1958).

In 1969, the couple's daughter, Diana, was born; her adolescence was broken by a severe neurological condition involving progressive paralysis and dependence on care (Mitric-Ciupe 2021). Relatives abroad became vital for medication, and precisely these contacts kept the family in the Securitate's sights. The dossier's language fixes ritual formulas – "reserve," "influences from outside," "suspicious correspondence" – which, read critically (Ricoeur 2000), appear as euphemisms for the desperation of procuring treatment and for the verbal hygiene of a family cautious under surveillance⁹. For Alis and Toni, an ethics of care took form: time, work, resources, and sociability were redistributed around caregiving. Care became the matrix of decisions: it reordered priorities, regulated rhythms, and shaped communication (how much is said, to whom, and how). This was not a declaration but a structure: legible in the household budget, in fatigue, in absences from work, and in the obligatory discretion of conversation. Alis continued her work in radio until 1982 (cultural/educational programming), then retired; Toni provided material stability in a mid-level position. A holograph declaration in the Securitate archive retains the same administrative idiom – "contacts abroad," "reserved attitude" – without capturing the reality: medication and the burdens of care for a sick daughter. The 1980s – shortages, cold, queues, power cuts – rendered caregiving invisible labor. Discretion became a strategy of protection: caution in conversation, a narrowed circle. In parallel, the Auschwitz pact returned as a weighty family memory: the recollection of the promise "not to be separated" was reabsorbed into the ethics of care, avoiding the thanatologization of memory (Mitric-Ciupe 2021).

December 1989 found Alis and Toni in a discreet maturity in which the reflexes of prudence coexisted with a new sense of public breathing space. Regime change reset the relationship between memory and the public sphere: partially opened archives, more permissive editorial rules, and a cultural field in search of new measures. In this ecology, old age was no longer only withdrawal but also a time to offer testimony with civic vocation. For Alis, the transition took the form of a memory project: she finalized – cast as epistles to her daughter – the

⁹ ACNSAS, Informative Files Collection, file no. 4404, ff. 21-22.

manuscript that would become *Planeta Auschwitz*. The stylistic choice – short sentence, affective economy, factual precision – was explicitly ethical: “not a cry, but testimony” (Nisipeanu 1998: 207–210). Her death in 1995 transformed the volume into a moral testament. The book appeared posthumously in 1998 through the care of Hanna and Peter Hamburg, whose editorial work – preserving the timbre, drawing a clear line between document and evocation, avoiding rhetorical inflation – secured the passage from communicative memory to cultural memory (Assmann 1992, 1999).

For Toni, the transition confirmed the choice of silence: he remained near the work of care, far from the public accountings of Pitești. This choice can be read through the category of moral injury (Shay 1994): the unmaskings wounded language, forcing it to betray the person. Under such conditions, silence becomes a form of guarding speech and fidelity to lived life – an ethic close to “tragic optimism,” which orients suffering toward meaning: work, care, continuity (Frankl 1959). A witness describes him as “a man who carried silence with dignity,” refusing both the capitalization of suffering and simplistic allocations of guilt (Mitric-Ciupe 2021). The absence of a written confession can be understood through the lens of the moral injury produced by the unmaskings (Shay 1994), the mistrust of language after its perversion under coercion, and the priority of care as a form of repair. Silence does not annul testimony; it relocates it into the registers of life. In the post-1989 public sphere, *Planeta Auschwitz* operates as a standard of measure, offering a way to tell the truth without hyperbole – useful to historical education and civic hygiene. Alis’s written testimony and Toni’s ethical silence become complementary: one teachable, the other livable – together sustaining a culture of memory resistant to instrumentalization (Assmann 1999).

Alis Nisipeanu’s volume functions simultaneously as document, as a mode of speaking about evil, and as a lesson in method. The “low voice” – short sentences, an economy of qualifiers, a preference for transitive verbs and concrete nouns – is not a stylistic caprice but an ethical choice meant to keep the text close to brute facts and to their proportions. Compositionally, the text avoids both heavy metaphor and rhetorical pathos: sequences are linked by cuts that mimic documentary montage, while transitive verbs compress actions into verifiable units. Spatiotemporal indicators are kept to a minimum (rarely “there,” “then”) precisely to avoid universalizing the experience. The configuration of space-time remains anchored in the concreteness of logistics

(timetable, roll call, route, physical setting). This austerity is a form of epistemic responsibility: reading should produce knowledge, not a substitute emotion (Delbo 1970). The reader is not pushed to feel but invited to understand: tension is created by exactitude, not by hyperbole (Felman, Laub 1992).

The “gaze” is the narrative’s structural operator. *Planeta Auschwitz* does not anthropomorphize evil; it shows it as procedure, as a set of standardized practices. The “eye” of selection – monumentalized publicly in the figure of Mengele – appears as a function within a decision chain: an optic-administrative threshold that “turns” bodies from one column into another (Hilberg 1985). In Hilberg’s terms, the “gaze” is one link in an administrative operation: signal-flow (the body set in motion) → verification (the gaze) → sorting (the column) → recording (the list) → transport (railway routine). Reducing the “gaze” to a function does not attenuate guilt; it distributes it through the apparatus: from order to execution, from SS physician to scribe, from guard to locomotive (Arendt 1958). In counterpoint, the figure of Nyiszli Miklós (prisoner-physician and distant relative) introduces the nuance of the “gray zone”: a liminal position in which the medical act can, through a bureaucratic falsehood, save a life or, under constraint, record an inevitable loss (Nisipeanu 1998; Nyiszli 2011; Levi 1989). The discreet references to Nyiszli ennoble precisely the difficulty of judgment: a prisoner-physician forced to operate within a perverted medicine, he occupies the point where “saving” and “recording loss” can alternate within the same day. In Levi’s reading, this is exactly where “moral compromise” becomes a condition of survival without becoming an excuse (Nyiszli 2011; Levi 1989). The distinction between “function” and “proper name” redistributes responsibility: the mechanism is impersonal, yet it does not cancel individual consciences; their capture within the apparatus explains moral ambivalence without absolving it.

The thread of survivor’s guilt runs through the book as a criterion of proportion, not as self-flagellation: a prudence about calling micronormal gestures “heroism” – shielding someone at roll call, calculating the sharing of rations, a practical piece of advice with life value. Consistently, the text refuses to capitalize on the “exceptional”: the small successes of conservation (an avoided chore, an efficient division) are presented without halo. Guilt becomes an anti-myth: it prevents moral overbidding and maintains measure between “what could be done” and “what was no longer possible” (LaCapra 2001). At the level of identity, Alis’s Jewishness is unobtrusively expressed; a social

and cultural belonging struck by an administrative ontology of “origin,” hence the emphasis on proportion and on avoiding the moral “winging” of the text. Accountability is stratified: decision-making actors are distinguished from intermediate functions; local Hungarian institutions appear under the rubric of procedural complicity (Braham 1994).

The “economy” of survival techniques is rendered as an inventory: rationing hunger, economizing gestures, reducing speech to functional sentences, calculating effort in relation to roll-call schedules. In the women’s camp, “minimal techniques” include the intelligent redistribution of tasks, covering for a lack of clothing, and protecting the vulnerable from impossible assignments. Solidarity is not mythologized; it is described as risk-calibrated practice (Nisipeanu 1998; Delbo 1970).

Behind this aesthetic stands an ethics of utterance that facilitates the passage of memory from the communicative register (fragile, familial) to the cultural one (stable, citable): a text that does not succumb to the rhetoric of the “spectacle of pain” has a chance to become teachable, discussable, and integrable into educational programs without relativizing evil (Assmann 1992, 1999). Here the network of “late witnesses” plays a decisive role. Magda Stroe supplies the texture of the domestic: the way Eva Birtaş “received them as her own,” Gavril’s practical silence, the small rituals of care in a house with a heavy history. She also clarifies the lexicon of the Securitate – “contacts abroad,” “reserved attitude” – translated in real life into medication and prudence (Mitric-Ciupe 2021). Magda is, moreover, a “Righteous Among the Nations” for the rescue of Hanna Hamburg (Alis’s cousin) in 1944 – an act that, by Yad Vashem’s criteria, entails personal risk, the absence of any material reward, and independent corroboration (Yad Vashem 2010). Within this frame, Hanna’s rescue functions symbolically as a premise for the “rescue of Alis’s voice”: without the person saved, the posthumous editor would not have existed (Yad Vashem 2010).

Hanna and Peter Hamburg are the ones who transformed the manuscript into a book. Their postface makes explicit the decisions of “care for the voice”: preserving the timbre, rejecting rhetorical intensification, drawing a firm line between document and evocation. Thus *Planeta Auschwitz* becomes not only testimony but also a manual of proportion – a standard of measure for cultural memory. Alongside these “late witnesses,” another type of witness takes shape – the “silent witness.” In our narrative, this is Toni Nisipeanu himself. His post-1989

silence, understood through “moral injury,” does not negate testimony; it relocates it into the registers of life (Shay 1994; Frankl 1959).

Conclusively, the Nisipeanu case demands a change of scale: beyond the “great violences,” the micro-infrastructures that enable them and the micro-practices through which life is recomposed after them become legible. The shift is methodological: evil appears as networks of repetitive operations, while repair emerges in rituals of the ordinary (order, routine, care). The proceduralization of evil finds its counterweight in a proceduralization of dignity – domestic choreographies, an economy of words, a sober montage of testimony – without conflating regimes: racial dehumanization and political de-subjectivation remain distinct as mechanisms, even if they converge in the need for rhythm, work, care, and measured speech.

The study’s contribution is threefold. First, it proposes an analytic bridge between Holocaust studies and research on communist repression by comparing bureaucratic ecologies and coercive techniques that structure experience. Second, it advances an “ethics of measure” as both an epistemic and civic standard – a tempered voice, an economy of qualifiers, a discipline of detail – compatible with cultural memory and resistant to instrumentalization. Third, it treats the ethics of editing as part of historical truth: a “double loyalty” to the witness’s voice and to the context of publication becomes a condition for the public transmissibility of trauma.

Here the victim – persecutor relation is decoupled from a rigid dichotomy: Toni’s cohabitation with the Birtaş family (former elites of the apparatus) indicates forms of postwar proximity without exoneration and without declarative “reconciliations.” “Victim identity” is not essentialized but assumes a civic role: the right to bear witness (Alis) and, conversely, an ethics of silence as the protection of language (Toni). Within this architecture, the “late witness” (transporting communicative memory into cultural memory) and the “silent witness” (testimony through life rather than phrase) are complementary.

Theoretically, the conceptual set is refined: the “gray zone” as a topology of distributed responsibility (judgment calibrated to constraints); the “banality of procedure” as a caution against personalizing guilt without mechanical analysis; “tragic optimism” as an orientation of suffering toward meaning by operationalizing care; and “moral injury” as an explanation for post-1989 silence. Methodologically, the archive – memoir – oral history triangulation remains productive if accompanied by two prudences: decoding “administrative truth” (where

formulas such as “reserve” or “contacts” mask concrete objects of care) and tempering the cathartic effect in interview through “responsible listening.” The limits are assumed: not totality, but demonstrative sufficiency; exactitude precedes exhaustiveness.

The institutions of reconciliation appear on two planes. At the macro level: open archives, editorial standards, educational policy, memorialization, and (limited) forms of accountability within transitional justice. At the micro level: ethical editing, pedagogies of practice, and oral history without cathartic pressure – “slow infrastructures” that stabilize public truths in the absence of expansive penal solutions. Is forgiveness possible? In Minow and Teitel’s sense, forgiveness is a personal ethical option, not an instrument of public policy: it can arise only after recognition, truth, and accountability, and it does not substitute for justice (Minow 1998: 14-18; Teitel 2000: 4-7). In the case at hand, measured coexistence (not rhetorical reconciliation) becomes a realistic form of living together: the protection of language, care, continuity – an ethic of repeatable dignity that prevents both re-victimization and hasty rehabilitations.

For Romania, the infrastructural asymmetries between the memory of the Holocaust and that of political prisoners call for common standards and the avoidance of a “competition of suffering.” Public utility is decided in verifiable micro-institutions: documentary doubling, a firm demarcation of document and evocation, a tempered voice, and curricula that teach ecologies of practice. Thus, post-catastrophe repair rests less on spectacular gestures and more on the conscientious institution of the small orders through which dignity returns as a daily practice.

In light of the foregoing, two clarifications and one practical implication follow. First, the evidentiary field is structurally asymmetric: administrative files foreground the apparatus; memoirs, the witness; oral history, a negotiated narrative. Silence – imposed or chosen – registers not as neutral absence but as missing data. Our archive–memoir–oral-history triangulation mitigates, without eliminating, these biases; accordingly, our claims aim at demonstrative sufficiency rather than totality – exactitude precedes exhaustiveness. Second, reading “procedure” across regimes risks flattening difference. We guard against this by keeping the mechanisms distinct (racial dehumanization vs. political de-subjection) while comparing their operational grammars. The analytic gain is portability: the categories *banality of procedure*, *gray zone*, and *ethics of measure* travel across cases without collapsing them;

where portability fails, we mark the seam rather than smooth it. The practical implication is direct: if evil is proceduralized, repair must be proceduralized as well – through “slow infrastructures” such as archival openness with clear finding aids; editorial standards that separate document from evocation; curricula that teach operations (lists, approvals, quotas) alongside narratives; and oral-history protocols that temper catharsis with responsible listening. In this sense, dignity is not a remainder after catastrophe but a routine to be instituted: measured utterance, calibrated care, and small orders performed again and again.

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Claudia-Florentina Dobre

“Nicolae Iorga” Institute of History, Bucharest (Romania)

[cfdobre@gmail.com], ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6778-3466

Hegemonic or Marginal Perspective!? **The Many Shades of Nostalgia in Post-communist** **Romania**

*Ceașescu n-a murit!
Ne veghează îndârjit
Ceașescu e o școală
Ceașescu e o boală.*

*E în mine e în tine
E în fabrici și uzine
Azi îl poartă fiecare
Ceașescu-n veci nu moare.*

(Ceașescu is not dead!/He watches over us fiercely/Ceașescu is a school/
Ceașescu is a disease./ He is in me, he is in you/
He is in factories and plants/Today everyone wears him/Ceașescu never dies.)
(Ada Milea, 2003, Ceașescu has not died)

Abstract: *In Romania, communism was declared, on December 18, 2006, an ‘illegitimate and criminal regime’. From this moment on, the main paradigm of remembering communism in the public space was anticommunism. However, ordinary people seem to remember communism in a more positive tune as shown by the various polls which measure a constantly increasing appreciation for the fallen regime. The explanations for this nostalgia are various: from ‘longing for a lost past’ to a form of counter-memory, as a critique of the present, and a fear for the future. Another explanation is the commodification of communism which became another merchandise to be consumed. A more subtle form of nostalgia was fuelled by the Romanian intelligentsia in the 2000s, which can be explained by a change of generation, which did not feel represented either by the anticommunist discourse or the regret for a fallen regime measured by the polls. My article deals with the various forms of nostalgia recorded in Romania in the last 36 years since the fall of communism aiming at describing them, offering some explanations while trying to understand the trends and mechanisms of both ‘reflective’ and ‘restorative’ forms of nostalgia.*

Keywords: *Anticommunism; Dominant Narratives; Intergenerational Memory; Pink Nostalgia.*

Introduction

In July 2025, a survey by INSCOP Research and the Institute for the Investigation of Communist Crimes and the Memory of Romanian Exile (ICCMER) revealed surprising perceptions of communism in present-day Romania. The results indicated that 55.8% of participants view the communist era as a time marked by more positive than negative things, values, and events. Additionally, 48.4% believe that living standards were better during that period, while 66.4% feel the state provided better care for its citizens (sic!). A significant 77.2% assert that Romania was wealthier at that time. Despite these positive views, 59.2% recognize that the government committed crimes and abuses against its people, with 82% aware of instances of killings and torture, and 80.9% acknowledging a lack of freedom compared to today (IULIE 2025: Sondaj, 2025).

The mentioned results indicate an increasing appreciation for the communist regime, necessitating thoughtful explanations that extend beyond the typical critiques of ungratefulness and lack of education of the majority of Romanians often voiced by public intellectuals and the media. This situation calls for a meticulous analysis and a nuanced interpretation. My article seeks to offer several explanations and proposes hypotheses that can be further explored through in-depth researches on the memory of communism in Romania.

The State of Art: Nostalgia as a Social and Cultural Phenomenon

The nostalgia as a individual emotion and a social and cultural phenomenon was analyzed broadly since XVII century (Arnold-Foster, 2025). Its political implications and impact on people everyday life were also investigated by scholars (Tanner, 2021; Boym, 2001; de Certeau, 1984). Some of them concluded that the nostalgic discourse became a characteristic of the contemporary societies (Gaston, Hilhorst, 2018, p. 11; Lowenthal, 2015, p. 31), a “clever instrument of the merchandiser’s toolbox”, acquiring a “recycling dimension” (Appadurai, 1996, p. 78), the ‘new opium for the people’ (Gabriel, 1993), a sign of the present-day decay (Cohen, 2021), but also a stylized presentation of the present (Jameson, 1989).

If in the Western World, the nostalgia concerns the 1970s, the 1990s or even the Middle Ages, in Central and Eastern Europe it is the communist epoch that stirs regret and longing for its lost. The nostalgia for communism is frequently assessed through surveys (The Pew,

2009), as well as by the popularity of museums that showcase daily life, which openly assume a nostalgic stance, created mainly by private individuals and/or institutions such as: Museum of Life under Communism from Warsaw, The Museum of Communism in Bucharest, Museum of Communism in Prague, The Communist Consumers Museum in Timișoara, DDR Museum, Tales of Communism Museum from Brașov, The Red Flat in Sofia, Budapest Retro Museum, Zagreb '80s Museum, etc. This sentiment is also reflected in products marketed with a nostalgic appeal (Goulding, 2001; Puhl, Kraske, 2005) and in the rhetoric of populist politicians (Kenny; van der Velden, Lopez Ortega, Roth, Guldemon, 2023). It seems that the further we get from the moment of the collapse of the communist regimes in the region, the stronger nostalgia manifests itself (Arnold-Forster, 2025, p. 204). What are the explanations for this memorial trend and which are the consequences are two important questions to which my article aims to find an answer, focusing on a case study, namely on Romania.

David Berliner provides some explanations about the Western nostalgia in his seminal book, *Losing Culture. Nostalgia, Heritage, and Our Accelerated Times*. The French anthropologist argues that there are two types of nostalgia: 'endonostalgia', which refers to the "nostalgia for a past that has been experienced personally", and 'exonostalgia' that is the longing for "a past that one has not personally lived, entailing feelings of loss that are detached from the direct experience of loss" (Berliner, 2020, p. 62). For David Berliner 'endonostalgia' is a discourse which transforms the longing for a past into an impetus for present-day political purposes. Furthermore, he argues that 'exonostalgia' was perpetuated by the anthropologists who constantly invoke the "paradigm of the last", and the specificity of the local which eventually contributed to the transformation of the preservation of the heritage into a dominant perspective about the past (Berliner, 2020, p. 62-63).

Svetlana Boym, who analyzes nostalgia in the former Soviet countries, also distinguishes between two types of nostalgia. She argued that people who lived during communism manifest either a 'restorative nostalgia', that aims at "rebuilding the lost home" or/and a 'reflective nostalgia' which dwells in longing and loss. Boym believes that 'restorative nostalgia' is due to the fact that, faced with sudden and difficult to understand changes, individuals feel the need to take refuge in an era they have experienced and know well (Boym, 2001, p. 58-64).

Research into nostalgia in the West began to gain traction among social science scholars in the latter half of the 20th century (Davis,

1979). In contrast, the exploration of nostalgia for communism in Central and Eastern Europe emerged as a significant area of study in the early 2000s (Brunnbauer and Troebst, 2007; Volcic, 2007; Spaskovska, 2008; Barney, 2009; Sierp, 2009; Koleva, 2011). In 2006, a conference held at the Free University of Berlin, organized by Stefan Troebst and Ulf Brunnbauer, focused on the theme of nostalgia as it pertains to the former Yugoslavia and GDR as well as to Hungary and Bulgaria. One of the scholars dealing with this issue, Predrag Marković, aiming to find an explanation to the growing Yugonostalgia, argued that nostalgia is based on the ‘Seven S’, namely social security, solidarity, stability, social inclusions, self-respect, sociability and solidity, all in contrast with the post-communist bleak realities. In the Serbian researcher’s opinion, these assumptions were certainly myths, which, nevertheless, had a real foundation, but bear negative consequences for the development of the society (Markovic, 2007, p. 153-164).

Another book edited by Maria Todorova and Zsuzsa Gille, *Post-communist Nostalgia*, also deals with various forms of nostalgia in Central and Eastern Europe. Focused on Bosnia, Bulgaria, Romania, Hungary, Kosovo, former Yugoslavia and Russia, it aims at analyzing the particularities of this social phenomenon in the former communist countries not only as a scholarly endeavor but also as a political issue (Todorova, 2010, p. 10-11).

In Romania, the communist nostalgia was analyzed from several perspectives: of reversed nostalgia (Popescu-Sandu, 2010), of marketing the past (Bardan, 2018, 2020; Marin, 2013, 2016; Morariu, 2012), of counter-memory as a response to the official anti-communist paradigm (Georgescu, 2010; Rusu, 2015; Morariu, 2012), as a complementary form of memory and new practices of memorialization of the communist past (Asavei, 2016), as a critique of the present (Dobre, 2017; Anton, 2020), but also as a form of collective irony and a reassessing the communist past (Dobre, 2024; Petrescu, 2017) as well as a fear for the future (Dobre, 2025). It was also analyzed through the lens of arts (Preda, 2015), and of its instrumentalization by museums dedicated to communism (Preda, 2025; Dobre, 2024). The societal causes of nostalgia were examined by Cioflâncă (2010) as well as by Marin (2019) and Anton (2020).

Following Boym and Berliner assumptions that there are two types of nostalgia, I argue that in Romania, one can speak about a ‘restorative’ nostalgia but also a ‘reflexive’ one, which I call ‘the pink

memory of communism'. Studying both aspects of nostalgia of communism in conjunction can highlight the interaction between public and private, the social effects of public policies as well as the evolution of political/cultural representations of the past. It can emphasize that the past (at least in democratic societies) is neither a burden nor a biased construction but a re-construction through negotiation in a specific context (Bonnard, Jouhanneau, 2017). I argue that the nostalgia felt by individuals is linked to the myth of golden age while the social nostalgia is created and disseminated by certain groups belonging to a specific generation especially when the dominant narrative do not include them or dissatisfy them. The nostalgia used by politicians is a tool, a stake in the struggle for power, and it is instrumentalized in order to legitimize but also to attract unsatisfied voters.

Measuring Nostalgia in Romania

Despite the official condemnation of communism as an 'illegitimate and criminal' regime, on December 18, 2006, the perception of communism of the majority of the Romanian population is not that of a traumatic experience, but rather of a 'golden age' which people regret and long for it. Opinion polls from the last 27 years measure an increasing appreciation of communism, seen in most cases as a good idea, poorly applied. The interest in products from the communist era is another argument in favor of positive representations of the fallen regime among Romanians. The explanations for this state of affairs are multiple and depend on numerous factors that I will analyze below, not before presenting the results of various polls conducted over time.

One of the first opinion polls, from 1998, commissioned by the Open Society Foundation, measures a positive perception of communism. According to it, 51% of Romanians said that life was better under communism (Radio Free Europe, 1998). An explanation for this positive evaluation, at this specific moment, can be found in the destabilizing socio-economic situation of that period. After the Democratic Convention came to power in Romania (in 1996), reforms of all kinds led to a decrease in living standards, but especially to social insecurity and destabilization. Researchers who have studied the nostalgia for communism in post-communist countries believe that sudden changes at the political, social, cultural and economic levels represent a cause and an explanation of this phenomenon. Gerald W. Creed stated that nostalgia is a symptom of the social trauma experienced by those who experienced the transition from totalitarianism to democracy and from

socialism to capitalism, but also a sign that this period was coming to an end (Creed, 2010, p. 35). The sociologist argued that nostalgia makes its presence felt at times when communities and individuals realize the impossibility of returning to the past, when the future presents itself as a real break with the past. Nostalgia manifests itself when the future knocks on the door and returning to an era that has already passed is practically impossible (Creed, 2010, p. 37).

The repeated waves of change and social insecurity maintain and even increase the nostalgic feeling among the Romanian population, as evidenced by the survey conducted in September 2003 by Gallup and the Open Society Foundation, which counted two-thirds of Romanians as nostalgic for communism (Radio Free Europe, 2003).

In 2006, the year communism was condemned in Romania, the nostalgic feeling persists, and the positive assessment of communism stands in stark contrast to the anticommunist public discourse. Duncan Light and Craig Young explained this nostalgia as a form of ‘counter-memory’ (Light, Young, 2015, p. 221-243), defined as a refusal to conform to the official memory (Legg, 2007, p. 456-466). Thus, in 2006, according to a survey conducted at the request of the Open Society Foundation, 12% of Romanians considered communism a good idea, well applied, 41% believed communism a good idea, poorly applied, and only 34% considered communism a bad idea, poorly applied. Only 8% of people over 34 years old declared that they had suffered during the communist period (Fundăția pentru o Societate Deschisă, 2007).

In 2010, a poll concerning the perception of communism show that 63% believed that people lived better during communism. Furthermore, 41% of them would have voted for Ceausescu if he was a candidate for the presidential election. Only 9% of those interviewed believe that life was worse during communism (Sondaj, 2010).

Another 2011 survey conducted by CSOP on behalf of IICCMER indicated that 61% of Romanians perceived communism as a good idea, and 37% of them considered the establishment of communism as a positive event. At the same time, 29% of those interviewed were unaware that there had been repression in Romania (Manolache, 2011).

The November 2013 poll showed that 45.5% of respondents considered communism to be a good thing for Romania and 44.4% of them believed that life was better under communism. In September 2014, another poll measured Romanians’ appreciation of the regime that collapsed in December 1989: 69.5% of respondents believed that life was

better under communism, and 68% believed that there was more justice under communism than in post-communism (Boghiceanu, 2017).

A 2021 INSCOP poll continued to record a positive assessment of the communist period. According to it, 63% of those surveyed believed that life was better under communism. In September-October 2022, the same public opinion polling institute measured an appreciation of the Ceaușescu era by Romanians at a rate of 57.4% (Ecurile, 2023).

A survey from November 2023 showed that 48.1% of Romanians considered communism a good thing, while 46.4% estimated that life was better under communism (Sondaj, 2023). A poll conducted by The Romanian Institute for Strategic Evaluation (IRES) in November-December 2024 shows that almost half of Romanians view communism in an idealized light, attributing numerous positive aspects to it. An overwhelming 80-90% of the respondents agree with the existence of positive aspects of the communism (such as safeness, healthy eating, free time dedicated to reading, or human solidarity), the appreciation transcending generational boundaries (Hurezean, 2025).

The already mentioned survey, conducted in June-July 2025, reveals a growing sense of nostalgia for communism among Romanians, particularly among those over 30 years old. The highest levels of nostalgia are found in the 60+ age group, with 67% expressing positive sentiments towards the past regime. Additionally, individuals with lower educational attainment (72%), those residing in rural areas (60%) and small towns (61%), and people whose incomes are insufficient to meet basic expenses (70%) exhibit stronger nostalgic feelings. In contrast, younger individuals under 30 tend to view the communist era negatively, with 48% holding this perspective, alongside 53% of Bucharest residents and 59% of university graduates. Furthermore, a significant 55% of high-income individuals also assess communism unfavorably (IULIE 2025: Sondaj, 2025).

Few Explanations about Present-day Nostalgia in Romania

Despite people's positive representations of communism, statistical data shows that life was not better under communism, compared with the countries in the West or to European integrated Romania. The historian, Bogdan Murgescu, who analyzed the available data, stated that in 1989, Romania ranked last in terms of the value of industrial manufacturing production and classic indicators of living standards. Romania ranked last among European countries in social indicators

such as infant mortality (after Albania) or in the Human Development Indicator, after Albania and Bulgaria (Murgescu, 2010, p. 329, f. 48). The gross national product per capita in the year of the fall of communism was 1567 dollars in Romania, while the European average was 8298 dollars (Murgescu, 2010, p. 330).

People's representations of communism are not based on statistical data, which are otherwise little known, as Bogdan Murgescu argued, but on affects, feelings and perceptions. The analyses carried out by economists and sociologists have not really been adopted neither by the educated public nor the larger audience but only by a narrow circle of specialists (Murgescu, 2010, p. 328). Therefore, nostalgia for communism must be understood and explained and not considered a symptom of backwardness, ignorance or ill will on the part of citizens.

I argue that in Romania, the nostalgia for the communist era also comes from a partisan view of the past. Most Romanians benefited from communism, climbing the social ladder. At the time of the communists' installation in power, approximately 80% of Romanians were peasants: 18.6% of them lived in poverty, owning less than one hectare of land, while 33.6% lived on the edge with the income obtained from their properties that ranged between 3 and 5 hectares (Murgescu, 2010, p. 229). The communists gave them land through the 1945 agrarian reform, which divided up the land confiscated from those convicted of war crimes, those who fled abroad, and those who owned more than 50 hectares (Dobre, 2023, p. 49). However, most peasants remained poor, with 91.1% of them owning properties under 5 hectares, and 36.4% owning even less than 1 ha (in 1948) (Murgescu, 2010, p. 362). Forced industrialization and urban development offered the latter the opportunity to change their social status. The historian Cosmin Popa stated that the regime favored the industrialization out of a need of political leaders to ensure an economic base of power. To a large extent, the idea of communist industrialization was subordinated to the idea of national consolidation of the regime (Popa, 2024, p. 104).

Due to the communist state policies, a majority of Romanians accepted the regime and adapted to it, especially since the repression targeted a small percentage of the population. If we take into account, the findings of the Final Report of the Presidential Commission for the Study of the Communist Dictatorship in Romania, the figures would be "about 600,000" political prisoners, 200,000 administrative internees, approximately 44,000 deportees and several tens of thousands of displaced persons. The report gives a total number of 2 million politically

persecuted persons, which would represent a little more than 10% of the population (Raportul Final, 2006, p. 463).

After the fall of communism, the political instrumentalization of repression by historical parties (Dobre, 2023, p. 32-49), the neo-communist amnesia (Dobre, 2018, p. 155-173), the loss of experience, as Giorgio Agamben (1989, p. 19-23) called it, its failure to be transmitted across generations, as well as the blockage of ‘communicative memory’ due to structural changes in society, have left their mark on the way communism is remembered, memorialized and displayed. The memory of repression has often not been transmitted from one generation to another, even within families that were persecuted. And even if they had wanted to, the links that would have facilitated such transmission no longer existed (Dobre, 2024, p. 92).

Communism destroyed not only traditions, collective memory, but also the spirit of togetherness. The interference in private life through state policies and constant surveillance led Romanians to no longer be interested in the helping each others. And not only did individuals no longer show interest in helping others, but also in finding out about their past, which could affect them if it had not been in accordance with ideological standards (which also changed from one period to another). Therefore, Romanians lived under communism in a kind of continuous present (Petre, 2005; Hartog, 2003), without showing any interest to the past and without thinking about the future. The 1989 revolution caught them off guard, as did the social and economic transformations that followed. Keen to adapt to the new realities, most Romanians left the past behind, ignoring communism with its crimes and abuses. Considering themselves all victims of the regime, as they were officially told by some anticommunists and neo-communists, Romanians viewed the persecuted as profiteers, considering the granting of rights to the oppressed individuals as an unjustly obtained privilege (Dobre, 2019, p. 139).

The appreciation of communism also quantifies a criticism of the present, as well as a revitalization of the myth of the ‘golden age’ (especially among those who were young in the 1960s and 1970s), but also a fear of the future that is increasingly bleak. Taking refuge in the past can represent a compensatory mechanism on a psychological level, the human psyche having the tendency to keep in memory the positive aspects that are easily accessible, the negative ones being repressed and harder to bring to the surface.

Manuela Marin believed that Romanians' nostalgia for communism was due to their appreciation for the well-being "that the paternalistic communist state ensured for them: from the stability of a job and living conditions that they considered decent to what they perceived to be a certain equality within Romanian society" (Marin, 2013, p. 12).

Nostalgia of communism is also a sign of consumerism, of a commodification of communism. Manuela Marin, analyzing the perceptions about communism promoted in the newspaper *Libertatea*, stated that there is a media and mercantile interest in disseminating a nostalgic image of communism, whose memory is transmitted selectively, focused on positive aspects such as education, economic and social equality, public decency, morality, work ethics, all in contrast to the values of the present (Marin, 2013, p. 14). In the opinion of Gerald W. Creed, this type of consumerist nostalgia contributes to the consolidation of neo-liberalism by promoting products and services that are based precisely on these feelings of loss and refuge (Creed, 2010, p. 39).

In analyzing this nostalgia, however, age, social status, and the questions asked in the surveys must be taken into account. Specific analyses show that these general statements of those interviewed in the opinion polls are much more nuanced when referring to the shortages of the 1980s, the ban on abortions, and even the preservation or removal of communist symbols in post-communism (Rusu, Croitoru, 2022, p. 165).

Research shows that young people do not seem to be interested in a real knowledge of this period, as Mihai S. Rusu and Alin Croitoru found, who consider that for young Romanians the communist past "is a foreign country". Instead, the two researchers measured a false nostalgia of the older generations who demonstrate an unexpected anticommunism, speaking out in large numbers in the survey they conducted, in favor of removing communist symbols from public space: "our research found that Romanians who lived during communism convincingly approve of the revision of the spatialized memory associated with the former regime. This result underlines a critique of the communist nostalgia thesis centered on emphasizing the fact that people may not be nostalgic for the political regime, but rather long for their irretrievable youth" (Rusu, Croitoru, 2022, p. 165).

Other Explanations of Nostalgia: Women's Remembering Communism

Between 2015 and 2017, I carried out 20 structured and semi-structured narrative interviews, along with one focus group, involving women who experienced life during the communist era in Romania. The participants were categorized into three generational cohorts: those born between 1938 and 1950, those born from 1951 to 1964, and those born between 1965 and 1975. This research was part of the international project titled “Regaining the future by rebuilding the past: Women’s narratives of life in communism”, supervised by Izabela Skorzynska (Project number: NCN nr/no. 2013/10/M/HS3/00482) (Dobre et al., 2019). The interviews took place in Timișoara, Brașov, Bucharest, Călărași, and Târgu Mureș. The selection of informants was based on the specified age groups, their willingness to engage in the project, and the opportunity to connect with women who could share their experiences in (un)familiar cities for me. As regards their social status, these women could be classified as middle class, encompassing a range of professions such as engineers, teachers, researchers, civil servants, and white-collar workers.

The analysis of their interviews regarding daily life under communism revealed a complex and often contradictory image of the regime among the participants. The women I interviewed hold an ambiguous view of the communist times, reflecting both positive and negative aspects. Their perceptions are influenced by the specific communist era they lived through, their family status, and personal achievements (Dobre, 2020).

Women born in the late 1930s and early 1940s, who experienced childhood during World War II and its aftermath, tend to hold a negative perception of communism. In contrast, those born in the 1950s and early 1960s recall communism more favorably, viewing the 1960s as a time of relative prosperity and freedom during their formative years.

According to Magdalena Man (born in 1952 in Brașov), times were better during her childhood which correspond to a period of stability and growth of the country (1955–1965):

“Our childhood and adolescence were relatively good from a socio-economic point of view... I can’t say that I feel any physical or moral effects on my childhood. I think we are a generation that hasn’t gone through many deprivations”.

Her opinion is confirmed by Niculina Bordeianu (born in 1951, locality Barza, county of Călărași):

“I had a happy childhood, my parents had no problems, they got along well, I was protected. My parents were middle-class peasants, they had 7 hectares of land, they had horses, a cart, they worked their land. ... Later I experienced some scenes that marked me as a child, during the collectivization”.

The good old times were also recalled by Mirela Rădulescu (born in 1957 in Bucharest) who stated that:

“Between 1972-1977, I was a teenager. We didn't have many opportunities, but we made the most of them. Young people who came from educated backgrounds had the opportunity to discuss things. It was a beautiful period. We didn't have the freedoms we have now, but we enjoyed meeting for tea, that's what we called parties, we met every week, to go to the movies, to shows. ... We went to the theater, the opera or the Athenaeum more often than we do now. I had a beautiful adolescence because I had a lot of friends.

We went to the mountains, to the sea thanks to this group of friends”.

Magda Andreescu, born in 1967 in Bucharest, challenges the favorable views on communism held by the women born in the 1950s. Having lived through her childhood and adolescence during the late 1970s and the 1980s, a time characterized by increased restrictions and a prolonged period of shortages, she offers a contrasting perspective shaped by her personal experiences:

“I experienced during my youth both the good and the bad parts of the system. ... When I was little I caught the period when there was some kind of abundance. I remember there was a store where I used to buy cheese but after that it was no longer available. ... In the '80s, ... I remember the lines at the gas cylinders, my father would go in the evening. We didn't have gas in the neighborhood back then. No one will convince me that those were rosy times. Not even for the party activists who had their own canteen and the order house where they bought Cuban candies and Chinese chocolate. And they smoked Kent under the covers so that no one would see them because they also lived with the sword of Damocles over their heads. Those were the times. ... I experienced communism to the fullest, the system was wrong, it wasn't just Dej's or Ceaușescu's fault.

I don't know where we will end up, but I hope we never go back there!”

Women who experienced communism during the 1980s tend to hold a predominantly negative view of the regime. Born in the late 1960s and early 1970s, they often portray communism in bleak terms and express criticism of its governance. This perspective can be attributed to their coming of age during a time marked by significant shortages in the 1980s, followed by a tumultuous youth in the 1990s characterized by frustration and deprivation.

All women I interviewed, regardless of age and status, described the 1980s as dark years, marked by deprivation, cold and fear. Florentina Şuteu (born in 1942 in Braşov) remembered the difficult times when people had to stay in line for hours but could not find enough food, because it was rationalized:

„Mom and dad would get up in the morning and stand in line, or leave the milk bottle, a bag to stay in line for us. ... We only ate meat 3 times a year. We kept the piece of meat frozen since January and ate it in May. Once, I was on the street, I even remember the place where I heard this conversation because it stuck in my mind because it impressed me, and there was a child with his mother, and he said, "Mom, I would eat an egg today". And she answered him: "My dear, we don't have any more, don't you know that I gave it to you last week, we don't have any more eggs". You were entitled to 7 eggs for I don't know how long, half a pack of butter... How can you live like that!? What's that child supposed to understand that he ate the egg two weeks ago and now he had no right to?!"

In the same vein, Magdalena Man (b. 1951) remembered that:

„...things started to get worse economically, with a reflection on social life, in the '80s. Every year, life became more and more gray. ... And in a concrete way it got grayer in the sense that people started wearing duller colors. The color was disappearing from clothing because the clothes in the stores were getting grayer and grayer. ... Grocery stores were starting to empty, products were disappearing from the shelves. ... The meat had disappeared from the butcher's shelves, the cold cuts had disappeared, everything was starting to be harder and harder to find.

The stores with those gray metal or glass shelves, almost empty. In this context, people's faces had lost their smile, plus the eternal state of worry, of looking over their shoulder, you never knew who was listening to you, how they were listening to you and what could happen. A state of fear had begun to dominate among people”.

An extensive examination of the perceptions and views on communism reveals that the women I interviewed hold a nuanced perspective shaped by their personal and familial experiences across different eras. Those who spent their formative years from the late 1950s to the mid-1970s generally view this time positively. In contrast, individuals who experienced the late 1970s and 1980s often recall this period with discomfort and tend to assess the communist era unfavorably. Women born in the late 1970s, who experienced childhood in the late 1980s, tend to recall a different perspective on time and space, one that diverges from the hardships and abuses associated with communism. Their memories reflect a sense of abnormality that, while distinct, can be easily understood and can be transformed into a realm of personal freedom and togetherness. For all women I interviewed there was a personal golden age within the communist regime which might fuel nostalgia, be it restorative, be it reflective.

The 'Reflective' Nostalgia or the Pink Memory of Communism

*Noi în anul 2000
Când nu vom mai fi copii
Vom face ce-am văzut cândva
Toate visele îndrăznețe
În fapte le vom preschimba.*

(We in the year 2000/When we are no longer children/We will do what we once saw/All the bold dreams/We will turn them into deeds.)

(„Anul 2000”, a communist song composed in 1970 by Horia Moculescu, lyrics by Mihai Maximilian)

The feeling of yearning for a personal ‘golden age’ may help explain the phenomenon of ‘restorative nostalgia’ measured by polls and interests in items and in museums of daily life during communism. This longing not only reflects a wish to return to earlier times, but also might create a ‘reflective nostalgia’ (Boym, 2001, p. 41). The latter represents a type of reference to the past that encourages self-reflection, as well as a different perception of space and time (Boym, 2001, p. 49-50).

Such an approach to the communist past asserted itself in the Romanian public space in the 2000s, being the result of a generational change (Dobre, 2024, p. 95). Individuals born in the late 1960s and 1970s (the so-called people of the decree-*decreței*, born after 1966 ban of abortion) came of age during the late 1980s while asserting themselves in the public space in the early 2000s, a period when they began to reflect on their childhood and experiences under communism. Their recollections do not align neither with the dominant anticommunist narrative of the 1990s, nor with the nostalgic longing for the lost past. Instead, they approach the communist era with a sense of (auto)irony and humor, often targeting figures like Ceaușescu as well as the broader spectrum of communist propaganda, literature, and art. Maria-Alina Asavei points out that “there are various invocations and enactments of Ceaușescu’s name and image in Romania’s public sphere: from theatrical performances, rock music and film production to advertising campaigns, country branding and the souvenir industry” (Asavei, 2016, p. 34). Bogdan Murgescu underlines that this form of memory focuses on the everyday experiences of the 1980s, emphasizing a rejection of the Ceaușescu regime and its absurdities. It also underscores the notion that, irrespective of the prevailing regime, individuals can carve out personal spaces of freedom, navigating various obstacles and potential risks (Murgescu, 2010, p. 327). I argue that what characterized the most

this memorial trend is its subjectiveness and the ironic self-centered memories and narrations.

Ceaușescu selling chocolate Rom, a very appreciate chocolate from the communist time. Poster on the Dâmbovița river, in front of the Parliament, June 2007. Photo: CFDobre, 2007.

In my publications since 2011, I have called this memorial trend ‘the pink memory of communism’, inspired by the title of the volume coordinated by Gabriel Horațiu Decuble (b. 1968, professor at the University of Bucharest), *The Pink Book of Communism* (Decuble, 2004). To this can be added collective volumes such as, *O lume dispărută*, coordinated by Ioan Manolescu (b. 1968, professor at the University of Bucharest), Paul Cernat (born 1972, professor at the University of Bucharest), Angelo Mitchievici (b. 1972, professor at the University of Constanța), and Ioan Stanomir (b. 1973, professor at the University of Bucharest) (Manolescu et alii, 2004); *În căutarea comunismului pierdut* (Cernat et alii., 2001), *Cum era? Cam așa... Amintiri din anii comunismului românesc*, coordinated by Călin-Andrei Mihăilescu (b. 1956 in Bucharest, writer and professor at the University of Ontario) (Mihăilescu, 2006), which resume, as Paul Cernat observed, “common obsessions” and which tell the story of communism “from the grass-roots”, being centered on the universe of the 1980s and the ego-stories of its last witnesses (Cernat, 2004).

This reflexive-nostalgic, playful and ironic perspective is also to be found in the film of Cristian Mungiu (well acclaimed director, born in 1968) and his colleagues who directed, “Amintiri din Epoca de Aur” (Tales of the Golden Age), released in 2009. The 6 episodes directed by Hanno Hofer (b. 1967), Răzvan Mărculescu (b. 1976), Cristian Mungiu,

The Hydra Installation by Costin Ioniță. Photo: CFDobre, 2012.

Constantin Popescu (b. 1973), and Ioana Uricaru (b. 1972) tell cinematically several urban legends of the 1980s. Grouped into two parts, “Comrades, Life is Beautiful!” and “Love in Your Free Time”, the films enjoyed both public and critical attention. According to the data of the Romanian National Office of Cinema, 18,256 viewers went to see it in theaters (Centrul Național al Cinematografiei, 2019). The mini-series was also available on Netflix and on DVDs. The film was broadcasted at the Cannes Film Festival, the Toronto Film Festival, and

at the Transylvania International Film Festival (TIFF) in Cluj.

The Pink Memory trend can also encompass the twenty artistic installations that were showcased on the former pedestal of the Lenin statue, which was inaugurated in 1960 and dismantled in March 1990. These installations were displayed in front of the Press House, previously known as the House of Sparks, between 2010 and 2014. “Project1990”, conceived by Ioana Ciocan (b. 1980, curator and university lecturer), started on January 26, 2010 (Nicolae Ceaușescu’s birthday) and ended on April 14, 2014. For 4 years, 20 projects drew attention in a playful and deliberately exaggerated way to several aspects of communism and its legacy.

The project was defined as “a space of collective memory, of awareness of the present” (Sânc, 2014, p. 4), which “is part of this corpus of contemporary artworks that question the past and, at the same time, propose critical reading keys for it, provoking a reflection on it” (Preda, 2014, p. 65). Magda Cârnci argues that these artistic installations played a cathartic role, of remembering in a different, friendlier

and more relaxed setting, the communist past, but also the post-communist transition (Cârneci, 2014, p. 18-19).

The 'Pink Memory' trend, which successfully fostered debate and encouraged reflection, has largely faded from public space. This decline was marked by the removal of Lenin's pedestal and the subsequent installation of the monument "Wings", designed by Mihai Buculei and commissioned by Association of the Former Persecuted People of Romania (AFDPR), with funding from the neo-communist government (2000-2004) led by Adrian Nastase, a former member of the nomenklatura. This monument honors the victims of communism in Romania and the Republic of Moldova and was inaugurated on May 30, 2016, by Romanian President Klaus Werner Johannis, in the presence of politicians from various parties, former political prisoners, and numerous European officials.

As I argued elsewhere, the 'Pink memory', often a source of debate and discontent, presents a unique viewpoint on communism that encourages both personal and collective introspection regarding the past. This phenomenon acts as a societal mirror, reflecting lived experiences and fostering awareness of the complexities associated with communism, including its cultural trauma. Pink memory served as a cathartic experience, eliciting discussions that could lead to both humor and discomfort, while consistently prompting challenging questions about the implications of this historical period (Dobre, 2021, p. 261). An elitist trend, it promoted a critical memorialization of communism that encourage self-reflection, irony, and new narratives about the past. However, it has not deeply resonated within Romanian society, which engages with the communist era through personal, familial, and collective lenses. These perspectives have been shaped by decades of national-communist propaganda that emphasized the uniqueness of the Romanian nation, its distinctiveness among neighboring countries and great powers, and the perceived equality of all citizens. Furthermore, the historical myths propagated during and after the regime's collapse in December 1989, coupled with the frustrations stemming from a challenging transition to democracy and the subsequent migration of over five million Romanians, have compounded these views. Additionally, the education system has struggled to instill democratic values, further entrenching the legacy of the past in the collective consciousness. The political consequences of these societal challenges, along with cultural and memorial viewpoints and individual beliefs, became apparent in November 2024.

The Georgescu Effect and the Nostalgia for Communism

On 24 November 2024, Romania conducted the first round of its presidential elections, featuring 13 candidates from various political parties and independents. Among them was Călin Georgescu (born in 1962 in Bucharest), an outsider who gained significant popularity through TikTok and other social media platforms, which were reportedly influenced by the Russian Federation and various national and international entities. The vote count on the evening of November 24, 2024, ultimately declared him the winner of the first round which stirred astonishment, misunderstanding and even despair. The combination of these mixed emotions, along with the irregularities and illegalities surrounding his electoral campaign, ultimately resulted in the annulment of the first round of the presidential elections. This led to a new election scheduled for May 2025, in which Călin Georgescu was barred from participating.

Although he has voluntarily retired from politics in May 2025, his speeches have significantly influenced the Romanian public sphere and left a lasting impression on his supporters. His discourse was a complex amalgamation of various ideologies, intertwining new wave beliefs with traditional Orthodox Christian practices. It showcased an appreciation for communism alongside references to interwar Romanian far-right (legionnaires), while also blending nationalist economic policies with neo-liberal strategies for interstate economic interactions.

Georgescu's opinion about the communist regime was constantly positive, expressing regret over its condemnation in December 2006 and characterizing the 1989 Revolution as a Coup d'État (Toşa, 2025). He advocates for a return to economic nationalization, a more autonomous foreign policy, and a lifestyle governed by state oversight. He has praised Ceaușescu for his foreign policy, highlighting its purported independence from other nations. Additionally, he embraced Ceaușescu's commitment to global peace while expressing a deep appreciation for the Russian Federation and its culture (Despa, 2022).

The recourse to Ceaușescu served Georgescu well because, as David Kideckel has argued, Romanians have historically shown a tendency to seek refuge in the arms of paternalistic figures. Ceaușescu strategically used his representations as a paternal figure in order to create devotion among his people although this approach also gave birth to hatred and frustration (Kideckel, 2004, p. 123-147). The revival of the Ceaușescu paternalistic image by Călin Georgescu had a reverse effect making not only Georgescu popular but increasing the popularity of

Ceaușescu himself as shown by the July 2025 survey. It is true that Ceaușescu's persona haunted the Romanians since his execution on December 25, 1989. In a 2006 poll by the public television channel TVR1, Nicolae Ceaușescu was ranked 11th among the "100 greatest Romanians", significantly outpacing notable figures such as King Ferdinand, who placed 24th, liberal prime minister Ion C. Brătianu at 29th, and Peasant Party leader and former prime minister Iuliu Maniu, who was 32nd (Maniu died in Sighet political prison in 1954) (Mari Români, 2006). A subsequent survey in 2014 revealed that if Ceaușescu had run for the presidency, 66% of Romanians would have voted for him (Sondaj IRES, 2014). Furthermore, a 2018 study by the Institute of Social Studies (ISOGEPI) indicated that 64.3% of respondents held a positive view of Ceaușescu (Sondaj, 2018).

In the July 2025 survey, 66.2% of participants expressed the belief that Ceaușescu was a good leader. This sentiment is particularly prevalent among individuals aged 30 and older, with 67% of those aged 30-44, 65% of those aged 45-59, and 71% of respondents aged 60 and above sharing this view. Additionally, 80% of individuals with only a primary education and 65% of secondary education hold similar opinions. The belief is also strong among rural residents, with 74% supporting the notion, and among those facing financial difficulties, where 89% agree with the assessment of Ceaușescu's leadership (IULIE 2025: Sondaj, 2025).

The revival of a favorable perception of communism, coupled with a reassessment of its modernization aspects and the public policies advocated by Ceaușescu, contributed to a resurgence of nostalgia for the communist era. This sentiment was embraced by Călin Georgescu's supporters as a means of distinguishing themselves from Georgescu's adversaries, serving as a unique marker of identity, although being an expression of a retrograde nationalism and undemocratic values.

Final Remarks

In post-communist Romania, nostalgia manifests in various forms, reflecting both individual and societal viewpoints. This multifaceted sentiment reveals how individuals and communities grapple with their past, often oscillating between idealization of the communist era and critical reassessments of its legacy. Nostalgia serves not only as a personal reflection but also as a lens through which the broader socio-

political landscape can be understood, highlighting the tensions between remembrance and critique in a society navigating its historical complexities.

The communist past has consistently played a crucial role in power dynamics in post-communist Romania. During the 1990s, the legacy of communism was leveraged for legitimization and to shape political, social, and cultural identities. By the 2000s, communism transitioned into a topic of irony and critical discourse, often treated as a form of entertainment and as a consumerist practice.

Following its condemnation in 2006 as an ‘illegitimate and criminal’ regime, communism was memorialized under the sign of anticommunism. This transformation was reflected in public policies aimed at crafting a negative image of the recent past for future generations. However, official memory in pluralistic societies does not always enjoy a plenary and univocal reception from the general public. In Romania, although anticommunism became the official paradigm for describing the regime that disappeared in December 1989, many Romanians show nostalgia for it, regretting an ordered and stable time in the face of a labile present and an uncertain future. Fear of the future plays an important role in appreciating the communist past. At this stage, refuge in communism can be more reassuring than the leap into an unpredictable future.

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George Gotsiridze

Iakob Gogebashvili Telavi State University (Georgia)

Teaching-Research Institute for Interdisciplinary Humanities (Georgia)

[giagotsiridze67@gmail.com], ORCID ID: 0000-0001-8151-2232

Papers of the Struggle for the Strengthening the National Identity. In the Archives of Georgian Public Figures

Abstract: *The article examines the struggle for the consolidation of national identity reflected in the archives of outstanding Georgian public figures of the 19th-20th centuries. The unfiltered and authentic narratives documented in personal letters and other archival material provide a clear picture of the challenges faced by a nation caught in the grips of an imperial regime and the daily efforts Georgian figures made to overcome these difficulties.*

The documentary material presents the efforts of scientists-historians, writers, and many Georgian representatives of the Russian military-bureaucratic elite to resolve various issues related to the preservation of national identity, namely: to restore the autocephaly of the Georgian Orthodox Church, to increase the rights of the Georgian language in the educational system, to publish Georgian books, to preserve the items of the national spiritual and material culture, to increase the awareness of Georgia abroad, etc.

The emigrant archives, which were handed over to Georgia after the collapse of the Soviet Union, provide information about how Georgian emigrants abroad, escaping the Soviet regime, tried to establish a patriotic narrative different from the imperial one prevailing at that time. This cultural diplomacy, while still part of the empire, created the conditions for the rejection of the self-absorbed imperial heritage and the rise of nationalism based on a healthy, authentic heritage.

The issue is studied based on the personal letters of Platon Yoseliani, Dimitri Bakradze, Zakaria Chichinadze, Theodore Jordania, Grigol Orbeliani, and the materials of the emigrant archive.

Keywords: *National Identity; Georgian Public Figures; Emigrant Archives; Imperial Regime; Authentic Heritage.*

Introduction

Georgia, due to its strategic location, was the battleground of great empires for centuries. There is no great conqueror left in history who did not fight against Georgia. Romans and Byzantines, Parthians and Iranians, Arabs and Mongols, Ottomans and Persians tried to wrest

the country situated at the crossroads of Asia and Europe. Georgia withstood their invasions, but from the second half of the 18th century, the situation became complicated. Georgia's northern neighbor, the Russian Empire, under the mask of common faith, successfully gained a foothold in Georgia, in 1801 annexed it, and declared it an ordinary Guberniya (province) of Russia. The latter was essentially different from other conquerors. None of them tried to destroy the statehood of Georgia, cancel the independence of the Georgian kingdom-principalities, overthrow the royal Bagrationi dynasty and the throne of the Catholicos-Patriarch, and replace the Georgian language with their own. They were satisfied only with tribute and the participation of Georgians in their wars.

The article examines the struggle for the consolidation of national identity reflected in the archives of outstanding Georgian public figures of the 19th–20th centuries. The unfiltered and authentic information documented in personal letters and other archival material presents the efforts of scientists-historians, writers, and many Georgian representatives of the Russian military-bureaucratic elite to resolve various issues related to the preservation of national identity, namely: to restore the autocephaly of the Georgian Orthodox Church, to gain the right to conduct teaching process in the Georgian language in schools, to publish Georgian books, to preserve national spiritual and material culture, to increase the awareness of Georgia abroad, etc.

The emigrant archives, which were handed over to Georgia after the collapse of the Soviet Union, tell us about how Georgian emigrants abroad, avoiding the Soviet regime, tried to establish a patriotic narrative different from the imperial one prevailing at that time. This cultural diplomacy, while still part of the empire, created the conditions to reject forced imperial heritage and raise nationalism based on a healthy, authentic heritage.

Research methods: I studied the issue based on the private letters of Platon Yoseliani, Dimitri Bakradze, Zakaria Chichinadze, Theodore Jordania, Grigol Orbeliani, and the materials of the emigrant archive. The addressees of the letters are well-known writers, historians, and public figures, representatives of politics, culture, and art, military and political officials of the Russian Empire, as well as people little known or unknown to Georgian readers. The letters along with a lot of other information related to various aspects of the political, socio-economic, and public-cultural life of Georgia, the sad present and uncertain future of Georgia, contain important data about the struggle of Georgians to

strengthen their national identity. The special importance of the letters is determined by the fact that in them, there are clearly outlined the details of the daily life of the country caught in the ravages of the colonial regime, the light and shadows of that time, the problems the population of Georgia faced, as well as the methods and measures that our leaders used to overcome them and preserve national identity.

Discussion

Struggle for national identity

Our research aims to manifest the facts of the struggle of Georgian patriots in the Russian pincers to preserve and strengthen their national identity both within the country in the 19th century and beyond its borders, during their stay in political exile in the 1920s–1930s. Despite the different periods, our issue is united by one thing - the struggle of Georgians to preserve their national identity in the conditions of the conquering policy of the Russians, first in the 19th century with Tsarist Russia, and after 1917, with "White" and later with "Red" Russia, which in the form of a new empire, the Soviet Union, appeared before the mankind.

Struggle for national identity in the 19th century

Georgian public figures of the 19th century had to overcome many challenges faced by the country due to the colonial regime. The most important thing was to save the national spirit, which they saw in various measures, such as: establishing the Georgian schools, banishing so-called 'dumb' method and process teaching in the Georgian language in schools, creating textbooks in the Georgian language, collecting deeds and chanters, to read out the inscriptions from the stones of churches-monasteries, to write the history of Georgia, maintain and protect the church museum, to publish scientific articles in Georgian and Russian languages throughout the empire on urgent issues, establish a Georgian-language press, develop national literature, etc.

The preservation of national identity in 19th-century Georgia required, first of all, the protection of its main markers – language and culture – on the guard of which Georgian patriots stood. They fought selflessly for the restoration of the limited rights of the Georgian language in the educational sector. The Georgian historian Theodore Jordania made the greatest contribution to this work. In 1896, he was appointed as the supervisor of the parish schools of the Guria-Samegrelo

Eparchy. His letters show how many problems Georgian figures had to overcome in their relations with the local and Russian authorities. In 1897, he writes to Alexander Kiphshidze that "the spread of the persecuted Georgian literacy in Samegrelo has a thousand-thousands of enemies... both at home and abroad", that "the Georgian language is in a terrible state in Samegrelo during this barbarism" (Gigashvili, Gotsiridze, 2021, pp. 170-171). As a result of his selfless work, the number of schools and pupils increased as far as possible, the rights of the mother tongue were restored, and the so-called 'dumb' method was limited. 'My work in Samegrelo has been fruitful so far: we have opened many new schools, where the Georgian language has a prominent place. We created so many difficulties for the Ministry that it was forced to introduce Georgian in some schools. We sent several important documents to the government to protect the language and local church customs, and almost all of them were tolerated' – he wrote (Gigashvili, Gotsiridze, 2021, p. 184).

Two years after the appointment of Theodore Jordania to the above-mentioned position, there were already 192 schools in Samegrelo, that is, three times more, where more than 6,000 students studied (Gigashvili, Gotsiridze, 2021, p. 174). "We have a lot of obstacles from Levitskyi and the police, they send wrong information, accuse me of patriotism, and make the government doubt," – he wrote to Tedo Sakhokia in 1897 (*Ibid.*). He constantly requested free school textbooks and notebooks from the "Society for Spreading Literacy among Georgians." In case of delay, he openly expressed his displeasure. Regarding this issue, he wrote to Tedo Sakhokia, whom he highly valued and often asked for mediation: "If Gogebashvili is reconciled, ask him to send the textbook "Kokori" (Buttonhole-flower) and "Dedaena" (mother tongue), free of charge... and then I will show you how many schools I can open" (*ibid.*).

The nature of the linguistic colonization policy of the Russian tsarism has been clearly seen in the letter sent by the Georgian historian Dimitri Bakradze to the Exarch of Georgia, Alexi Ilinsky, on September 3, 1864, where it can be seen that the presence of Russian-speaking teachers was a necessary component for opening schools in Georgia (Gigashvili, 2019, p. 114).

The deplorable state of the Georgian language in the conquered country is well testified by the Georgian grammar printed in parallel columns, written by Platon Ioseliani to the order of the clerical author-

ities. In this fact, the goal of tsarism – the universal spread of the Russian language in Georgia can be recognized. No matter how paradoxical it sounds, Georgians had to learn the Russian language using Georgian grammar! The request of the clerical authorities to compile a Georgian grammar with a Russian translation, I think, was a response to the educational resource compiled by Platon Ioselian for the students of this seminary – "Georgian alphabet." This was argued by Konstantin Pobedonostsev, chief prosecutor (ruler) of the Holy Synod of the Russian Orthodox Church, adviser to the emperor, and member of the State Council, 1892 "Georgian school should be considered as a tool for the spread of the Russian language" (Sharadze, 2001, p. 53).

Platon Ioseliani laments the decline of the Georgian language and literature in a letter sent to Marie Brosset on April 14, 1838. He considers it the duty of every Georgian "to do his best to take care of the public affairs to restore the lost language and writing (literature)" (Gigashvili, 2019, p. 16).

Earlier, on February 2 of the same year, he wrote to Marie Brosset, who was interested in the history, language, and culture of Georgia: "The fact that you gave priority to my language, which was almost completely abandoned by Georgians, proves that you, sir, are (and I say this without any pretension) one of those men who love science for science's sake" (Gigashvili, 2019, pp. 14-15).

During the campaign against the Georgian language in the 1870s, the Georgian poet, the representative of the Russian military-bureaucratic elite, general Grigol Orbeliani actively engaged in the struggle for the protection of the native language. In one of his letters, he writes: "In Georgia, Jews, Tatars, Armenians, and others pray in their own languages, and no one interrupts them; Even the Frenches sing in Georgian, and should only Georgians be deprived of the right to pray in Georgian? Why? There a no sense here, only dimming, rusting of mind?" (Meunargia 1054, 106).

The poet expresses dissatisfaction with the government's policy in the field of education. In his mind, the existing education system only ensured the obedience of the population and did not contribute to the economic development of the country, which was supposed to improve the socio-economic condition of the inhabitants (*Ibid.*, p. 158).

He is particularly critical of the judicial system and openly states his opinion on the need to separate Georgian justice from the common Russian judicial system. In his opinion, the court, where the criminal does not understand the language of the judge and the latter does not

know the language of the criminal, cannot deliver a fair verdict. "What would the Russian people in Moscow say if courts were held in English," he wrote on November 20, 1882. Grigol Orbeliani was dissatisfied not only with the fact that court proceedings were not conducted in Georgian but also with the fact that these proceedings were taking too long (*Ibid.*, pp. 156-157).

Maintenance of monuments of national writing and culture and their promotion was one of the important forms of resistance in the way of preserving national identity. For this purpose, Platon Ioseliani began the historical and geographical description of Georgia based on Georgian and foreign sources, searching for old Georgian books and historical documents and purchasing them with his funds, copying inscriptions from the stones. It was not an easy task. Moreover, the colonial government created barriers on this path. One of such hindering factors was the control imposed by the tsarism on the use of Georgian historical documents. From the letter written by Platon Ioseliani to Marie Brosset on May 12, 1838, we learn that the deeds of churches and monasteries, including the "deeds of donations" of the Georgian Kings, were kept in the office of the Tiflis Synod for internal use, and their viewing was allowed only by order of the St. Petersburg Synod (Gigashvili 2019, 20).

Zakaria Chichinadze's merit in finding the historical heritage of Georgia and passing it on to his descendants is invaluable. On February 26, 1880, he reported to Marie Brosset about his work in this direction. By the 1880s, he had already published Dimitri Bakradze's works "The Mirian King and Saint Nino" and "Poems of Noble Gr. Orbeliani"; In 1873, he started the study of ancient Georgian writing, for which he bought 300 handwritten books from persons, and compiled a directory of 1,200 handwritten books, which were placed in the private libraries of monasteries of Georgia. He found the 6th-century Gospel parchment written in Khutsuri alphabet, 10th and 13th century books, and in 1878, he started writing biographies of Georgian writers. In two years, he had already written the biographies of 169 Georgian writers of the 9th-18th centuries (Gigashvili, Gotsiridze, 2021, pp. 14-15).

The struggle for the restoration of the autocephaly of the Georgian Orthodox Church was one of the most important activities of Georgian intellectuals in the 19th century. Zakaria Chichinadze's letters clearly describe the deplorable situation in the churches. The letter sent to Alexander (Alex) Okropiridze, the bishop of Guria in 1882–1885, on March 27 1883, shows that he explains the basis of the anti-national

mood in the churches by the loss of Georgia's independence and autocephaly of the church. Here, we get acquainted with his explanation of the reasons for the strength of Christianity in the past and the decline of Christianity in the present: "Our old time, the church arena and the priesthood of that time stood high because the religious love was tied to the love of the estate, that's why it seems clear from our history that the clergy of Georgia always worked unswervingly" (Gigashvili, Gotsiridze, 2021, pp. 17-18).

This letter is important because of another factor: it reflects the dissatisfaction of the Georgians of Tbilisi due to the unusability of the native language in liturgy in the churches and monasteries: "The Georgians of Tbilisi miss the mass in the Georgian language, a great rebuke is heard among the people." In a letter dated June 5, 1883, he expresses his protest with heartache: "Oh, why won't God or the nation retaliate that there is no single Georgian bishop in the capital of Georgia?" (Gigashvili, Gotsiridze, 2021, p. 21).

The letters contain rich information about how Georgian patriots tried to raise national consciousness in the historical territory of south-western Georgia, which after the Russian-Turkish war of 1877-1878, Russia seized from Turkey and returned it to Georgia, thus expanding the territory of its colony.

In the letter sent to Mikheil Machabli, Zakaria Chichinadze asks for 300-400 rubles for the publication of materials related to Georgian Muslims and emphasizes the importance of this "historical task": "It is necessary to publish such books because Georgian Muslims read them" (Gigashvili, Gotsiridze, 2021, pp. 55-56). He reflected the results of his ten-year selfless work in his book: "The Conversion of Georgians to Islam" (Chichinadze, 1915).

Legal and illegal Georgian magazines and newspapers of the 19th century played an extremely large role in strengthening the national identity of Georgians, about the importance of which the recognized leader of the national liberation movement of Georgia, Ilia Chavchavadze, wrote in 1862: "For many years, our society has not had a single living thought, a single sober feeling in its heart. We turned to crumbs in such a way that we even split the great word "motherland" into pieces. This word did not mean our homeland, but the property of each person. It will not be four or five years since such a miraculous word regained its lost meaning. This is a merit of magazine "Ciskari" (Chavchavadze, 1988, p. 461).

These publications strengthened and raised even higher the flag of the national liberation movement directed against the tyrannical regime of Tsarist Russia, fiercely fought against social and national oppression, for protection of the Georgian language, publication of Georgian books, creation of Georgian schools, new national institutions: Georgian Bank, Society spreading literacy among Georgians, Georgian dramatic society and others, for curbing the reactionary Russian press inciting against the dignity and interests of Georgia, for the organization and proper celebration of great national holidays, and so on.

Struggle for national identity in the 20th century

The press remained one of the most powerful forms of resistance in the 20th century. Because it was difficult to talk about the national program and problems in Georgia due to political conditions, a part of Georgian patriots spread these ideas from abroad. Georgian magazines-newspapers published by them in Western Europe (Paris, Geneva, Berlin) served to strengthen the national liberation movement of Georgia and the national identity of Georgians, tried to introduce European progressive thinking in Georgia (Sharadze, 2005, p. 12), declared a struggle against Russification, loss of territory, political-economic and cultural persecution of Georgians on their own land. The sources testify to the participation of a significant part of the Georgian intelligentsia in this process, their active involvement in collecting money and solving other organizational issues for the publication of national magazines and newspapers abroad and for the distribution of the published copies among the population of Georgia (Sharadze, 2001, pp. 23, 28).

In order to expose the "violence and injustice" committed by the Russian government against Georgia (Sharadze 2001,38), their activities awakened the Georgian people, and ideologically prepared them to move to a new stage of the struggle for national identity. The newspaper "Sakartvelo", published in Paris, in the 6th issue of 1903, writes the response of "Droshak", the body of the Federation of Armenian Revolutionaries, to the publication of the newspaper. Armenians welcomed the goal of establishing the newspaper to "awaken Georgians' national consciousness and prepare the ground for Georgia's autonomy" (Sympathy of Armenians, 1903, p. 4). It was in the throes of the empire that the Georgian Independence Committee prepared agreements with the governments of the Ottoman and German empires stating that in case of the victory of the German bloc in the First World War, these states would recognize the independence of Georgia. As Kalistrate Salia

wrote about the activities of the Georgian Independence Committee: "Georgia received real help from Europe for the first time in its long history. The West helped the Georgian nation to restore its suppressed rights" (Salia, 1962, p. 30). Thus, the Georgian patriots gradually stuck the national identity from simple demands to the restoration of Georgia's state independence.

The newspaper "Tavisupali Sakartvelo" in the 4th issue of April 1914 (Geneva) wrote: "One of the goals of positive action is to make the past spiritual work of the Georgian nation assimilated, studied and embodied by modern Georgians. This establish a broken thread of Georgian creativity and will give us a way to give our own national existence an indigenous soil."

Data Vachnadze in the 2nd issue of the magazine "Samshoblo" in 1929 evaluates the political situation of that period and the importance of getting rid of Russian domination: "After a long wait, we have stepped into such a historical era, when the national self-establishment of the nations enslaved by Russia, in the space of the former Russian Empire rushes to its logical conclusion. Even the core of the Slavs is experiencing a crisis. The ancient, strong, and rich branch of Slavism, the nation of Ukraine, this barn of the territory of the Slavs, the former cradle of the so-called Russian history, culture, the basis of its economic and political strength, is unstopably escaping from the yoke of Moscow and must create its own Ukrainian state. This sacrificing struggle between Ukraine and Moscow is growing day by day. This struggle is nurtured by the objective conditions of life of these two Slavic nations, their historical past, national difference, and political ideal. Their separation should be followed by the disintegration of the huge and Conqueror Moscow state" (Vachnadze, 1929, p. 5).

As a result of the pressure of the dictatorial ideological policy, a number of issues in Georgia were covered in an unobjective and tendentious manner. Georgian historians working in Georgia were limited to evaluate historical events impartially. Due to the current conjuncture, in many cases they were forced to present the real historical situation unilaterally, beautified, from a pro-Russian and Marxist-Leninist point of view. This is especially true when studying the issue of Russian-Georgian relations. Georgian historians working in the West had the opportunity to express their opinions and views freely. They exposed the historical injustice because of which the Georgian people became victims after the conquest of Georgia by Russia. They wrote the authentic history, created objective works depicting Russia-Georgia relations.

For example, we can name Al. Manvelishvili's "Russia and Georgia", the first volume of which was published in Paris in 1951 and which "successfully filled the great gap in our historical science of the Soviet period" (Nikoleisvili, 2007, p. 271). Aleksandre Manvelishvili testified the Russian sources to reveal the negative aspects of the Russian-Georgian relationship, which once again emphasizes the non-tendency of the author and the truth of his reasoning, shows the academic nature of the work.

Criticism of Russia's aggressive policy on the pages of the press contributed to preserving national identity. In 1926, Giorgi Gvazawa wrote in newspaper "Mamulishvili": "Russia conquered the Caucasus twice in a century and it will always be like this until the nations of the Caucasus cannot rise to the awareness that only the whole Caucasus can break the path of Russian imperialism. The time has passed when Georgia looked to Russia as a savior and protector; the days have also passed when the nations of the Caucasus looked to Georgia as a source of income and an arena for invasion. Now everyone has learned that their freedom and property will be secured only when Russian imperialism is blocked in the Caucasus" (Gvazawa, 1926, p. 1).

The former ambassador of independent Georgia to Germany, Vladimir Akhmeteli, in the article "Action Program of the Caucasian Nations" published in the 2nd issue of "Caucasian" magazine in 1937, especially distinguished "divide and conquer" policy from the threats coming from Russia. He wrote: "If they paid any special attention to any nation, they did it to sow envy and bitterness among the others. By such actions, first the king's officials, and now their epigones, only tried to give a fatal blow to the first nationalistic and indivisible idea of the unification of the nations of the Caucasus. Such a system is used even now, not only in our country, but in all parts of Russia, wherever those who, according to their estimation, are called "foreigners" live. Here is the danger! This is who our main enemy is – the power that shows such expansions and such depressing potency. Getting rid of this power by common measure is the need of our time! This should be the content of the active program of the Caucasian nations. This task is not so easy to give ourselves to other implicit fears. Caucasians should not be scared. If we overcome this difficult task, Caucasian nations desiring a free and independent life, with the same united force, will not find it difficult to prevent another threat from wherever it may be (Akhmeteli, 1937).

Conclusion:

Thus, the personal letters of Georgian scientists-historians and writers of the 19th–20th century contain important information about the struggle of Georgian patriots for the preservation and strengthening of national identity, the knowledge of which expands and makes our understanding of them more complete. If we take a look at the long-term struggle of Georgians for national identity, the logic of the actions of Georgian patriots can be seen: at first, they tried to restore the broken thread with the past by collecting historical documents, copying inscriptions from tombstones, to raise the national culture to a new height and the broad strata of the population by developing folk creativity, ancient writing, and modern spoken language. They engaged in a liberation struggle against Russia and their own degenerate renegades to restore free national statehood. This is a classic way of tempering the national identity of any nation under the colonial yoke.

This battle in Georgia was not easy. It was not easy to fight for identity in other countries either. The merits of Georgian patriots are determined by the fact that they correctly saw the epochal challenges and took thoughtful steps. Their actions and events were absolutely adequate, which brought positive results, such as: the increase in the number of like-minded people, the establishment of national institutions, the raising of the national spirit among the population, later their active involvement in the process of building the national state, and after the conquest of the country by the modernized Russian empire, raising the flag of the national liberation movement again. Even today, Georgia is facing huge challenges. Totalitarian thinking creates serious problems in the way of building a democratic state. In this case, the protection of democracy is vital for the civilized world.

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Marija Martinović¹

Philosophy and Slavic Studies at Sorbonne University (Paris)

CEFRES, UMIFRE 13, UAR 3138 CNRS-MEAE

[marija.sorbonne@yahoo.com], ORCID ID: 0009-0007-0389-7617

Philosophical Reflections on the Social Bond in Tito's Yugoslavia: Žižek's Critique of Ideological Unity and the Principle of *Agapè*

Abstract: *This article written as a philosophical dissertation examines the concept of social bond as a central question of collective existence, using Tito's socialism as its historical and ideological framework. It analyzes how Yugoslav socialism sought to produce unity through the political ideal of "Brotherhood and Unity," aiming to establish an inclusive social bond as the foundation of its social order. However, as Slavoj Žižek demonstrates, this ideology of fraternity used a mechanism of exclusion and assimilation that erased singularity and transformed the idea of inclusion into conformity. The study explores Žižek's philosophical critique of this socialist model of cohesion and his redefinition of the authentic social bond through the concept of *agapè*, a universal and unconditional love that respects differences rather than suppressing them. Through Žižek's reading of Christian love and its political implications, the article offers the only possible foundation for a genuine social bond, one that unites individuals without abolishing their singularity. By contrasting the ideological illusion of unity in Tito's socialism with the inclusive universality of *agapè*, this study seeks to clarify the philosophical necessity of an ethics of love as the true principle of political and human community.*

Keywords: *social bond; socialist Yugoslavia; Slavoj Žižek; agape; inclusion.*

Regret over the disappearance or dissolution of a certain "social bond" in contemporary societies is not an extravagant concern. The social bond can commonly be defined as what pertains to the connection

¹ Marija Martinović is a PhD candidate in Philosophy and Slavic Studies at Sorbonne University (Paris) where she has been pursuing her doctoral research since 2023 under the supervision of Professor Daniel Baric. Her dissertation, titled "The Philosophy of Yugoslav Socialism: Between Unification and Disunion," is conducted within the junior research laboratory "Passage" of the UMR Eur'ORBEM (UMR 8224). Her work examines the dynamics of inclusion and exclusion in Yugoslav socialism, the construction of collective identity, the philosophical logic of the social bond and the socialist state. More broadly, her research investigates the dialectical relation between ideology, universality, and the ethics of socialist humanism in Yugoslavia.

between citizens, their relationships, and thus their impact on society. The entity called society that they create by coexisting in relation to one another. Bond is often subject to various ideologies, even utopias, and while it is diversely interpreted as a concept and generates much debate, it is interesting to identify precisely what defines its essence, what makes it ultimately desirable to maintain and promote a social bond. If the concept and the idea are ultimately desirable, then they must be clarified in light of socialist regimes that have extensively used them.

If the social bond is commonly criticized for its failure, it is because individuals imagine or know what it is when its existence is effective, when the social bond is evident, present, and widespread. For the social bond to be authentic, it must by definition be the bond between all citizens, without discrimination or marginalization; it naturally conveys the concept of citizens' union, unity, and inclusion. Given the political nature of human life and the omnipresence of society and others, the social bond appears as an existential question. To make coexistence and communal life inspired by, or even governed by, the existence of a social bond possible, it is necessary to consider the foundation and the conditions of possibility for the feeling of citizens' union. If citizens live under the acceptance and recognition of their union, then the tendency towards collective life becomes possible, insofar as different individuals, the "I"s, reciprocally feel a connection that attests to a shared character, a kind of common similarity that unites them and encourages them to assign symbolic value to the "we" they create simply by coexisting together in the form of a political state, civil state, or society. The political body that citizens create together through their collective life acquires a particular pronoun and becomes a subject, becomes a being; a "we" is born from the social bond.

However, the practical action of the social "we", meaning precisely the collaborations and actions necessary for survival, the "doing", does not always testify to the presence of the social bond, that is the feeling of sharing a common character in the "we" among all the "I"s inspiring life together. Beyond sharing a common character, the social bond that enables the "we" testifies to a common pronoun, a shared identity, and thus is rooted not only in some collective action but in the existential essence of individuals. Indeed, if one focuses only on collaboration and cooperation, one is simply talking about the actions of individuals interacting with each other. These actions may be unreflective, mechanical, and it is possible to collaborate or create among indi-

viduals without them having any sense of togetherness, union, or symbolic contribution to a whole. Within the social bond, there is another dimension of relation with others that does not reduce to practical interaction. It is a matter of identifying, within the concept of the social bond, what truly motivates the feeling of the common, of the union of all into a social body of shared characters. What is the shared character of the “I”s operating as the foundation for the possibility of the social bond?

In Tito’s Yugoslavia, it is undeniable that the feeling of a collective identity was a central ambition of socialist ideology. The issue of “brotherhood and unity” [*bratstvo i jedinstvo*], in Tito’s motto focuses on the necessity to create and to bring forth a collective identity. This principle was most forcefully applied from the end of World War II through the 1960s, when the regime sought to build a supranational socialist identity and suppress nationalist divisions. The 1963 Constitution marked its institutional consolidation. From the 1970s onward, despite its continued rhetorical prominence, the slogan’s integrative power weakened with the growing decentralization of the federation. This shared, united identity naturally gives rise to collective action, then perceived as a driving force of beneficial collective movements for the “we”. In other words, this “we” stemming from the ideology of “union” operates not only as a feeling of identity belonging but also as a ferment that drives collective action, a necessary operational force for socialist work, for the construction of the socialist state. In the context of Yugoslav self-management, aiming both at political and ideological independence as well as agricultural and somewhat economic self-sufficiency, a dual strategy is observed in the implementation of this ambitious project: a reorganization of production and collective life based on worker participation, distinct both from liberal capitalism and the Soviet model. Thus, collective action becomes a priority, a condition, and its motivation lies in the ideology of the “we”. The creation of this “we” emanating from the political body is then a pioneering challenge of Titoist ideology.

Clarification of the Concept of the Social Bond and its Conditions

The social bond appears to demand more than mere coexistence and collective action derived from cooperation; it belongs to another dimension.

In the effort to create or identify the possible origins of the social bond, it is insufficient to rely solely on a society in which coexistence and collaboration are present, that is a merely tolerant, peaceful, even passive society. The question becomes what, in a society already at peace and tolerant, goes beyond these principles and testifies to a real and active social bond. We are not seeking to bring peace and tolerance out of a society at war or one in which coexistence is impossible or conflictual. A society must first have a credible foundation of stability before one can require the construction of a social bond. This may explain the “brutalizing” character of the establishment of socialist ideology and politics in Yugoslavia, as Sacha Markovic notes (2024, 145). Hence the importance of an outlook that seeks to make a clean slate of the past and rebuild social relations from a new, modern, innovative, and socialist beginning.

If tolerance and peace are already somewhat established, to go further and push these principles toward union and the social bond, it becomes necessary to identify what unites individuals, what precisely makes them be together, in common, sharing a collective identity. This insistence highlights a distinction from practical collective action, which alone cannot serve as a true sign of a social bond. A collective action testifies merely to the coexistence of simultaneous participation; it shows that something has been done together with others, but it does not necessarily carry existential meaning or transform the participants’ sense of belonging. Indeed, it is possible for political enemies to collaborate temporarily under political compromise while continuing to consider one another as adversaries (Badiou and Truong, 2016, 59-78). No collective action can, by its practical nature, fundamentally testify to a true social bond. The existence of the social bond therefore seems to precede such actions, providing the foundation for genuinely authentic collective acts directed toward unity and common prosperity. Yet, this sequence should not be understood too rigidly: the bond does not necessarily emerge fully formed prior to political action, but is often co-constituted with it, shaped and reshaped through collective mobilization itself. In this sense, the social bond and political action are deeply intertwined, their temporal relationship less linear than reciprocal.

If there exists a natural principle according to which individuals share something in common, something that might serve as the foundation of the social bond, this foundation would be undermined by regimes that promote disunity, those that discriminate against or marginalize dissident individuals. To allow and honor the social bond means

therefore to promote a certain shared nature, a shared characteristic, a common identity that manifests the existence of a “we” formed by individuals into a united political body, a totality consciously created by the consent of individuals, who recognize and accept the pronoun “we” as the social counterpart of their individual pronouns “I.” The social bond would thus be found wherever there exists a sense of union, a shared element of identity or nature among the “I”s, making possible coexistence and harmony with the “we,” in balance with the integrity of both the collective and the individual. The tolerance of the “I”s is therefore an essential point in recognizing an inauthentic or authoritarian social bond. The core of a true social bond lies in the principle of inclusion, the inclusion of all the “I”s within the “we,” along with the respect for the integrity of each of these numerous and diverse “I”s. If the “I”s prevail over the “we,” society becomes disunited and individualistic; collective interactions and participation are limited, and the social bond is nonexistent.

Conversely, if the “we” suppresses and nullifies the “I”s, the resulting social relations, however omnipresent and necessary, reflect not a true social bond but a mere illusion of interdependence rooted in ideological and authoritarian origin. It thus becomes essential to identify the essential consistency of the social bond, the feeling of sharing and possessing a collective identity that respects the integrity of its individual parts while illuminating the political conditions most conducive to its flourishing.

Imposed Social Bond and the Danger of Identity Ideology

The Titoist slogan “Brotherhood and Unity” appears at first glance as the expression of a noble fraternity, a moral commitment to shared life and the rejection of nationalist division. However, upon closer inspection, this call for “unity” functions as an ideology of inclusion that simultaneously conceals an ideology of exclusion. What pretends to unite individuals often excludes them in practice. Behind the image of universal love and unity hides an authoritarian injunction to identify with the collective body. Under the guise of fraternity, this unity becomes an obligation to belong to a homogeneous political subject, to the detriment of individual differences.

The logic of identity that underlies this type of unity was not particular to Yugoslavia. It reflects a more general tendency in socialist regimes to conflate political cohesion with moral conformity. This ideology of identity seeks to impose a model of the collective body in

which the individual “I” loses its singularity in order to become a component of the “we.” The “we,” in turn, becomes a totalizing figure that admits no exteriority or divergence. In this sense, the social bond, rather than uniting through inclusion, transforms into a mechanism of assimilation and control. Žižek was the first philosopher to theorize the socialist ideology of union in Yugoslavia and to expose its corruption of the social bond. In his critique, the Yugoslav project of unity appears not as genuine inclusion but as an ideological construction that conceals exclusion beneath the language of fraternity. As Slavoj Žižek points out, ideology often operates by presupposing a universal foundation for humanity, a mysterious “factor X” that supposedly expresses what all humans share in common (2007, 102-103). This “factor X” functions as a theological placeholder: it names an essence that can never be defined but that everyone must nonetheless embody. In socialist Yugoslavia, this universal element was articulated through notions of the “people,” the “worker,” and the “comrade.” These abstractions allowed the regime to claim an inclusive universalism while enforcing a very specific image of what counted as truly “human” or “Yugoslav.” Those who did not conform to this official image, such as ethnic minorities, political dissidents, or independent intellectuals, were implicitly or explicitly excluded from the collective “we.” In *The Fragile Absolute*, Žižek interprets this paradox as intrinsic to the ideological functioning of socialism itself (2006, 79-81).

Every ideology of equality risks producing its own hierarchy by determining what constitutes the legitimate form of the universal. By pretending to dissolve all difference, it must first define which differences are acceptable and which must be erased. Thus, the supposed universality of the socialist social bond was in fact based on exclusion: one could only belong by renouncing one’s singularity and aligning with the official image of the collective.

This process of assimilation was masked by the rhetoric of love and fraternity. Love, in socialist discourse, became a political instrument, a means of integration. To “love one’s comrade”² was to submit to the shared ideology. The emotional register of love replaced the legal and rational structures of inclusion, transforming an ethical feeling into a political command. Such a mechanism of imposed love is precisely what Žižek identifies as the ideological perversion of Christianity in

² Loving one’s comrade means recognizing in the other not only an individual, but a political subject engaged in a shared cause ; it is a form of political love structured by socialist fraternity and equality.

modern politics: the translation of the command to love into an obligation to belong. In other words, love ceases to be the recognition of the other in their difference; it becomes an order to recognize the other only as an identical reflection of oneself.

Consequently, the Yugoslav model of unity appears not as the realization of the social bond but as its negation. Instead of inclusion, it produces a form of symbolic violence that denies individuals their particularity. The social bond is replaced by ideological cohesion, and fraternity becomes a moral disguise for political conformity. By erasing the singularities of its members, this collective body destroys the very condition of the social bond: the coexistence of difference within unity.

Žižek criticizes the establishment of this “X factor,” which he describes as highly abstract and even metaphysical, arguing that it does not exist and that once the masks fall, nothing remains but emptiness. This false information, belonging to the order of fantasy, lies at the origin of the socialist illusion, an illusion that defends equality through the imposition of identity and uniformity, thus producing a radical and alienating equality. In this sense, this factor functions as the primary principle, the absolute axiom of the socialist regime and of the social bond it claims to promote through fraternity and unity as its ultimate aims. According to this logic, one would need to conceive and establish a new regime founded on radical union, more precisely on homogenization and uniformization, which in turn results in the total exclusion of subjective differences, of the “I”s, and in an extreme dependence of the “I”s upon the collective “we” of the socialist people. The concealment of subjectivities in favor of the glorification of the X factor becomes an enterprise directed toward emptiness. The social bond is therefore forced and imposed by the regime, which, through the erasure of the past, proposes a new figure of citizenship, of collective life, and of morality, embodied in the figure of the socialist man: “Is he not the emblem of the so-called ‘totalitarianism’ that seeks to free itself of the contingent layer of ‘inessential’ history in order to free the ‘essence’ of man?” (Žižek, 2006, 192).

Žižek describes this system as a “regime-army” to characterize the way the socialist order operates. In doing so, he marks an essential difference from the principle of inclusion, which represents what should truly be sought in order to allow, within society, the expansion of individual tolerance and the creation of an inclusive and authentic social bond. In an army, soldiers function according to the following principle: “We against Them, under the banner of egalitarian universalism

(we are all equal before the enemy). The army is fundamentally exclusive; it seeks to destroy the other.” (Žižek, 2010, 180). The army therefore has an authoritarian character, as it dominates a territory by force and by annihilating whatever does not align with its model of citizenship and morality, whatever it identifies as its enemy. The presence of individual differences, the variations among the “I”s, is thus perceived as undesirable, harmful, and dangerous for unity, which explains the desire to erase them in favor of a suffocating new socialist “we.”

***Agapè* as the Foundation for the Principle of Inclusion in Society**

Despite his critique of Tito’s regime and of the Yugoslav socialist illusion of fraternity, Slavoj Žižek remains a committed communist thinker who seeks to recover the original meaning of inclusion that socialism claimed to defend. Far from rejecting the idea of the social bond, Žižek redefines its authentic foundation. In his interpretation of Christian love, particularly through Saint Paul, he discovers a model of universality that does not depend on identity or assimilation but instead on unconditional inclusion, *agapè*. This notion of love offers a radically different foundation for the social bond, one that is inclusive not by erasing difference but by affirming it as the very condition of coexistence (Ibid.).

For Žižek, the Christian concept of *agapè* is not just sentimental but structural and universal. It is not love for the similar or for the neighbor in a moral sense but rather the recognition of the singular other beyond all symbolic categories (Ibid., 195). The “factor X,” which ideology claims to embody as a universal substance of humanity, does not exist. In *Fragile absolu*, Žižek argues that the universal emerges only through the singular rupture that escapes ideological identification (Ibid., 197). True universality is not based on a shared essence but on the act that transcends every established identity (Ibid., 183).

In *La marionnette et le nain*, Žižek develops this insight further by showing that Christianity, in its most radical form, is not an ideology of unity but the very negation of ideological community. It breaks the organic totality that binds individuals through imposed roles and symbolic identifications (2006, 196). Only by detaching from these artificial ties can human beings truly honor humanity itself and avoid the fundamentally immoral atrocities, such as wars and genocides, that result from collective illusions of unity. Žižek therefore maintains that *agapè* is not the love of sameness but the love of difference. “We

are all different” (Ibid., 193), he writes, and this difference is the only authentic foundation of equality.

In *Fragile absolu*, Žižek describes *agapè* as a crucial intermediary term between faith and hope: “*Agapè*, a pivotal term between faith and hope: it is love itself that calls upon us to ‘disconnect’ from the organic community in which we were born.” (2010, 176).

Through *agapè*, the subject becomes free from the ideological totality that defines individuals by the functions assigned to them by society: occupations, family roles, and social obligations. Love, in this radical sense, is an act of subtraction, an interruption of the symbolic order that determines subjectivity (Ibid.). By freeing the subject from these external determinations, *agapè* allows the emergence of an authentic universality founded on the recognition of each person’s singularity. For Žižek, this is exemplified in the demonstration of *agapè* for the figure of the father: love that suspends the symbolic function of authority in order to encounter the father as a vulnerable human being, beyond his social role. He writes : “That is, the purposes attributed to individuals by society in order to make it function, such as a profession, or a family role. The role of the father is then a function in the socio-symbolic structure of the family” (Ibid., 183). Žižek explains that one ceases to hate the father when looking beyond his symbolic role of familial authority and encounters him as the unique subject that he is. In that moment, one can only love him unconditionally, for the core of his singular subjectivity is “disconnected” (Ibid.) that is, removed and set apart from any social framework that might make it appear displeasing.

Thus, *agapè* becomes a principle of inclusion precisely because it suspends the hierarchy of symbolic positions. It invites subjects to relate to one another not as functions within a social system but as singular beings capable of mutual recognition. The universality of love, then, is not imposed from above but created through acts that acknowledge difference. In contrast to the ideological “brotherhood” of Yugoslav socialism, *agapè* forms, as envisioned by Žižek. The foundation of a genuine social bond, one that includes by recognizing the irreducible uniqueness of each subject.

Conclusion

Despite its common usage, the concept of the social bond remains ambiguous and open to misuse. Under an intolerant and authoritarian regime, it becomes alienated and inauthentic as it is imposed and assumes an exclusive character, seeking to eliminate whatever does not

conform to the identity and homogeneity promoted by ideology. The very essence of the social bond is to preserve the “I” within the totality of the “we” in a harmonious dynamic of respect and co-creative, non-annihilating participation. Beyond mere tolerance, the social bond involves a genuine relationship of recognition toward the other insofar as something is shared with them, a common attribute exists. Without falling into a false ideology of equality that encourages the homogenization of individuals in the name of a supreme “we”, defending what is truly shared within a “we” means placing the principle of inclusion at the center of a more nuanced appraisal. It is only in accordance with this principle that a genuine social bond becomes possible, one that regards the necessary subjectivity of the “I”s constituting the “we” as the ultimate shared principle, characterizing all individuals. Indeed, if there is one thing all individuals have in common, it is their respectful singularities. In the full acceptance of these singularities and differences lies *agapē*, which embodies the recognition of the “we” as a whole, powerful and meaningful, through the richness of the diversity of the “I”s it includes.

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Tamila Davitadze

Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University, Batumi, Georgia
[tamila.davitadze@bsu.edu.ge], ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3486-1696

Nana Mazmishvili

Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University, Batumi, Georgia
[nana.mazmishvili@bsu.edu.ge], ORCID ID: 0009-0000-3233-2702

Psychological Portrait of Dystopian Society in a Totalitarian Environment

Abstract: *Dystopian novels represent a hyperbole of evil and violence through the psychological portrait of humanity. Authors, while developing the principle of the supremacy of free choice, literarily mask their message and, through the example of protagonist heroes, demonstrate various methods and means intended to suppress protest. They expose the state where violent means are used to attempt to "correct" people. Often, through antagonists, they also show the relationship and confrontation between the individual and the state. In such cases, a significant place is occupied by the artistic image of the leader, who is one of the leading figures in dystopian novels, such as Mustapha Mond in Huxley's "Brave New World," O'Brien in Orwell's "1984," Colonel Beatty in Bradbury's novel "Fahrenheit 451," and others. In dystopian genre books, authors frequently extrapolate existing problems into the future. This technique enables them to critique various aspects of contemporary society, whether it be totalitarian regimes, control over the individual, ecological catastrophes, or the degradation of social norms. Dystopian fiction compels readers to contemplate the possible consequences of our current actions and choices; to develop critical thinking, social responsibility, and the importance of fighting for a better future. In today's chaotic world, where numerous states control their citizens through censorship, propaganda, intimidation, or indoctrination, dystopian literature and the study of such issues as dystopian politics, totalitarian government, and anti-intellectualism gain even greater significance and relevance, which we illuminate and highlight in comparative perspective through specific works, emphasizing the innovation that individual authors contributed to the development of the dystopian novel through their creativity.*

Keywords: *Dystopian novel; totalitarian government; antagonists; protagonist; state.*

The artistic and psychological analysis of individual characters in dystopian novels reveals how a person loses freedom as a result of a violent regime, while the reader encounters the question/feeling – is this

happening or could it happen around them?! Approximately 400 dystopian works were written in English alone by 1900 and thousands in other languages. Today this number has increased even more, as the world faces greater threats, and from this perspective, the warning-book gains greater significance, which is the fundamental characteristic of dystopian works. As a novelty of the work, we consider the examination of dystopian writers in a comparative perspective.

Dystopia is a genre of fiction that depicts an undesirable, terrible, or frightening societal structure; however, dystopian reality is now our reality, since in the contemporary world "seized by fear," the state already controls its citizens in every way. Unlike utopia, which depicts an ideal society, dystopia serves to present the possible negative consequences of social, political, or technological tendencies. The concept of dystopia is found in ancient philosophy, though it formed as a literary genre later, in the 19th–20th centuries (Ratiani, 2005). Early dystopian novels, such as Thomas More's "Utopia" and Jonathan Swift's "Gulliver's Travels," are characterized by relatively minor dystopian elements, while later dystopian novels are constructed entirely on dystopian elements, including the dystopian novels of interest to us: Aldous Huxley's "Brave New World," George Orwell's "1984," Ray Bradbury's "Fahrenheit 451," Margaret Atwood's "The Handmaid's Tale," which present to us a destructive society existing beyond idealism. Through utopian and anti-utopian worlds, their authors show us how easily harmonious stability can be achieved at the cost of suppressing freedom and eliminating individualism. Often, the governing power of the state, in order to maintain authority, resorts to such methods as the deliberate destruction of history and culture. It is precisely such a political system that requires people to believe the following – living in harmony is possible, however, at the cost of the doctrines listed below:

- There will no longer exist a different opinion;
- There will no longer be history;
- There will no longer be freedom;

Therefore, the goal of such a society is completely clear:

- Create a controllable environment;
- Convince people that the need for change does not exist;
- Offer such harmony that they will never refuse.

From this perspective, the images of the main characters are extremely interesting, their typology, which together with others creates dystopian society, embodies the writer's ideas and reveals those values

whose sacrifice achieves stability and happiness, as we find in O. Huxley's "Brave New World" and not only. Overall, through the satirical portrait of society and the psychological image of individuals, that future world is outlined where there is a danger of establishing totalitarian order, while society is formed according to the will of the controllers. When discussing dystopia, we cannot bypass Sigmund Freud's research, which concerned previously unknown discoveries about human psyche and psychology. It is precisely Freud who considers the 20th century as the stage of transition from utopianism to dystopian pessimism, and in his work "Civilization and its Discontents," his skeptical description of human society reminds us of dystopian literature. Humans are constantly in search of happiness, but Freud is convinced that achieving happiness is impossible because the main desire of civilization and government is to restrict human freedom. There does not exist an ideal state concerned with human well-being, and the attempt to establish a perfect state brings only evil instead of good. Reform of social institutions and rules does not lead us to happiness because civilization opposes human impulses and represents the source not of happiness but of unhappiness (Freud, 2022). Freud's views on "crowd psychology" go even further, directly indicating to us the foundation of 20th-century totalitarianism. The scientist compares humans to helpless infants who need a strong protector like a father. Because of this, the crowd develops fanatical admiration toward leaders like Adolf Hitler and Joseph Stalin. The totalitarian government described in dystopian literature fulfills the father's role, which protects humans from perceiving painful reality. "Humans are aggressive by nature, and the establishment of totalitarian government helps them free themselves from aggression. The human aggressive instinct finds a scapegoat onto which to transfer aggression. The phenomenon of the scapegoat is frequently visible in dystopian literature, where the government always attacks the distinguished and different individual" (Booker, 1994, 28-29). Thus, the question becomes even more relevant: how do we avoid utopias and how do we return to a non-utopian, less "perfect" and freer society?

The word "dystopia" was first used in history in 1868 by English philosopher John Stuart Mill during parliamentary debates (Amiranashvili, 2022, 208-224), and its emergence may be connected with transitional periods of human development. Before the term dystopia, the term cacotopia appeared (Greek *κακός* "bad" + Greek *τόπος* "place," meaning "bad place," kakotopia – Oxford Dictionaries, 2012), which translates from Greek as "bad," "evil." Then the term dystopia appears,

along with which cacotopia is also used. It should be noted that dystopian novels are sometimes referred to as "apocalyptic novels," however, American novelist Benjamin Kunkel in his article "Dystopia and the End of Politics" considers that dystopian and apocalyptic novels are absolutely different scenarios. The end of the world, that is, the apocalypse, actually brings the collapse of order, chaos, while almost all dystopian novels represent a perfectly evil order (Kunkel, 2008); however, if we recall Margaret Atwood's "Oryx and Crake," we are dealing with a post-apocalyptic scenario there, and her "The Handmaid's Tale" is no exception, where life changes completely after an apocalypse that has occurred. Also interesting from this perspective is Bradbury's "Fahrenheit 451," at the end of which we encounter the apocalypse itself. On what is the perfect order based according to dystopian novels? "Social stability is unthinkable without individual stability" (Huxley, 2021, 39), says Huxley, and convinces us that human individuality and freedom, religion and culture, art and literature, are sacrificed to technical progress, to the apology of stability and well-being. Family, feelings, and human relationships are victims of modern technologies, new sexual traditions, and artificial fertility. In his "Brave New World," where the new calendar is rejected, history, while society has Ford and Freud identified with God, no one is alone, in this "paradise" everyone is happy through the state-officially encouraged drug "soma." Through this satirical and psychological portrait of society, Huxley highlights the influence of technological progress and science on humans and their values; however, Huxley's dream was to use scientific and technological progress to liberate humans and not to enslave them. Thus, his novel is more a call to sobriety and reflection. Huxley, Orwell, and along with them the authors of other dystopian novels show us two completely different faces of the future industrial world: real and unreal. A book about the future is doubly interesting when it contains a supposed prophecy that comes true. Joseph Adams's definition of dystopian society is interesting: "In a dystopian story, society itself is typically antagonist; it is actively working against the protagonist's aims and desires. This oppression frequently is enacted by a totalitarian or authoritarian government, resulting in the loss of civil liberties and untenable living conditions, caused by any number of circumstances, such as world overpopulation, laws controlling a person's sexual or reproductive freedom, and living under constant surveillance" (Adams, 2011, 12). Only the progressive part of society realizes that the training-formation of newborns

and narco-hypnosis is a more effective weapon in the hands of authorities than handcuffs and prisons. "Community, Identity, Stability" (Huxley, 2021, 9), we read in "Brave New World," the motto sounds effective at first glance; however, stability and community here are achieved through the sacrifice of individuality. As a result of the loss of individuality, society creates a unity of disfigured people: "People are happy, they receive everything they want and never want what they can never receive" (Huxley, 2021, 15), thus, the anti-utopian world seems perfect but is actually the most dangerous and deadly because individual freedom has completely disappeared in it. People who appear (and are not born) with predetermined biological and social status naturally become obedient. They no longer fight for a better life. First, because they don't know, and secondly, the governing system has ensured the following:

- Programming of people;
- Disappearance of the desire for individualism;

Thus, one of the main problems of the society in "Brave New World" is the loss of individualism - complete suppression of personal peculiarities and the implantation of collective consciousness, while in Bradbury's novel "Fahrenheit 451," unlike dystopian novels created in the first half of the 20th century, in future America the population voluntarily participates in implementing the state's policy of crushing individual thinking. Bradbury convincingly assures us that hatred and indifferent attitude toward books comes not from a distorted system but from the people themselves, while later the uneducated mass easily fell under the influence of the state. Thus, according to "Fahrenheit 451," the main problem is not the confrontation between the individual and the state, as found in previous and generally dystopian novels, but the conflict here takes a different form - the intellectual opposes the uneducated mass. People here so resemble each other that it is impossible to distinguish them from one another (Bradbury, R, 2013). Undoubtedly, the author borrowed elements of the dictatorial state from Hitler's and Stalin's regimes; it is also noteworthy that the appearance of the work coincides with the era of the beginning of television's dominance, for during this period the television screen seriously threatened the printed word?! Therefore, the novel "Fahrenheit 451" can be considered about the struggle between technology and nature. Thus, in future America, television enjoys great popularity because people are much happier when watching it, unite, and do not think critically. In Huxley's dystopian world, the government also satisfies the needs of the masses

through the use of the drug "soma" and through free sex, while in Orwell's Oceania ("1984"), the subjugation of the population is accomplished through endless wars and fear. In Huxley's novel, people are programmed from infancy, which is why people do not have the desire to fight against the state. Accordingly, the government does not have to use such violent actions as in Orwell's novel. In "Brave New World," the devil is masked because no one is physically harmed; this is a world where everyone gets everything they want. People live in this society not by compulsion but by temptation. There is no disease and social conflict, there is no depression, mental illness, loneliness, or emotional experience, here sex is unlimited. There even exists a ministry to ensure that the time between desire and its fulfillment is minimized. Unlike Atwood's dystopian book "The Handmaid's Tale," which we will discuss below, religion is no longer taken seriously by anyone here, no one is an introvert, the biological family no longer exists, no one reads Shakespeare anymore, and except for the main character of the book, Savage John, no one here remembers the meaning of faith, hope, fear, and struggle. Huxley shows us two sides of the utopian and anti-utopian world, which in the same time segment transformed differently: real and unreal. The writer draws a boundary between the island and the world created by Ford. Their connecting link is the conditional perception of civilization and freedom because in each place different rules operate. A quite interesting psychological portrait of society is created, which embodies different worlds: the main hero of the real world is "Savage John." He is a tragic figure inspired by Shakespeare's tragedies. He believes in love, family, and true emotions. It is precisely through this that he tries to understand the world, but he becomes a victim of civilization. He can adapt neither to the natural nor to the artificial world. John perishes while fleeing from the modern world because his actions, which have become a spectacle, are unacceptable to a society devoid of values. For him, happiness exists in solitude, he tries to find salvation in cleansing himself with cold water and preserving traditions. John was led to the end by his difference and individuality and became a symbol of failure. Savage John was sacrificed to the struggle against personal freedom. Thus, John is a symbol of true, real civilization, while other characters, for example, Lenina – a symbol of stability and obedience, while Bernard, surrounded by internal and external conflicts - creates the image of a weak person. England here is a civilized, sterile state where different customs operate; hypnotized Alphas, Gammas, Betas, and Epsilons mechanically, unconsciously perform their work.

While, unlike them, the Indian reservation, which represents the so-called savage society, has preserved naturalness, freedom, family, they are not programmed and obedient. Therefore, harmony in the first world is an illusory sensation, which "soma" establishes to avoid emotional conflicts, and as a result, the characters of the work are always happy. Lenina is an incomparable example of this. But the fact is that this is only the result of mind manipulation and not a feeling of internal stability. The psychological image of the characters revealed that they represented different worlds. It is noteworthy that in this world, art is neglected, which in itself implies the means of freedom and emotional expression. For understandable reasons, we will not follow the plot line to the end, but we must certainly discuss how realistic Huxley's prophecy about the world's future is. We think that comparison with Orwell's "1984" will help us properly understand this issue: in general, the nightmare of Orwell's "1984" ultimately resembles the nightmare of the world presented in "Brave New World." This novel, one of the greatest of the 20th century, and warning-book, is desperate about humanity's future. The novel reveals the author's hatred and critical attitude toward totalitarianism and communism. The reader experiences a terrible feeling of powerlessness toward violence, torture, and inhumanity. Let us return to the issue of prophecy in dystopian novels; the philosophy of the ruling minority described in "1984" is sadism, which reaches its logical result with the complete prohibition and rejection of physical relationships (as we know, in the novel, the issue of couples' marriage is also decided by a special commission; they do not give the right to marry to people who have physical attraction toward each other, because the main purpose of marriage is only reproduction and the birth of a child). In reality, the indefinite continuation of such savage politics is doubtful. The ruling power will find lighter and more effective means to satisfy its irresistible striving for power, approximately like what is described in "Brave New World": training-formation of newborns and narco-hypnosis; we must also not forget the possibility of biological and atomic war, to which Huxley used to allude; therefore, one can think that the theme of his novel is not scientific progress but its influence on the individual; according to American writer and culturologist Neil Postman, the reality of 1984 corresponds less to Orwell's prophecy. Even without "Big Brother" (Orwell, 2014), freedom, thought, and history can be taken from people (Postman, 1985); according to Huxley, this can be achieved through people's love of their own "controllers" and technologies. With Orwell, the fear of banning books is traced,

while with Huxley, that there would be no reason to ban books because there would be no one who would want to read books; Orwell feared the prohibition of information, while Huxley – such an abundance of information that humans could not cope with; Orwell reveals the fear of hiding truth, while Huxley - the uselessness of this truth; Orwell condemns slavish culture, while Huxley flees trivial culture, which implies recreational sexual relationships and meaningless entertainment. As we know, in "1984," people are governed by inflicting pain, while in "Brave New World" – by granting pleasure. Thus, Orwell thought that people would be destroyed by their own fears; Huxley thought by their own desires. Therefore, Huxley's prophecy about the world's future is more realistic than Orwell's. According to Japanese-origin American philosopher and writer Fukuyama, Orwell's prognosis about politics was not fulfilled. In just a few years from 1984, the fall of the Berlin Wall became the symbol of the collapse of the world's greatest totalitarian state. Thus, George Orwell's information-technological prognosis was fulfilled in reverse: in the 1980s, the personal computer that went on sale gave humans themselves the means to observe "Big Brother," democratized information and deprived the idea of totalitarianism based on information monopoly of its foundation, unlike the "telescreen," which was an instrument of tyranny and centralization (Fukuyama, 2002); as for Huxley's prophecy, his biotechnological prognoses – in-vitro fertilization, surrogacy, psychotropic medications, and genetic engineering for "producing" children already represent reality; Huxley declares: "A truly revolutionary revolution can be accomplished not in the external world but only in the human soul and body" (Shanidze, 2017), in "Brave New World" precisely such "revolutionarily" transformed people live.

Thus, against the background of totalitarian regimes depicted in the novels, writers described two different future technologies that radically changed the world in just two generations. Orwell described what we today call information technologies; "Orwell's 'telescreen' was actually a modern personal computer connected to the internet, and this technology determined the success of the greatest totalitarian empire" (Fukuyama, 2002). Huxley prophesied another kind of great technological revolution. This was "the biotechnological revolution – the development of genetic engineering, in-vitro 'production' of humans, neuropharmacology" (Shanidze, 2017), which conditioned the existence and stability of a totalitarian state diametrically different from that described in "1984." Thus, seeing the danger of the biotechnological revolution,

we fear those consequences that dehumanization will bring to people. On the one hand, humans can exercise caution and moderation in using technologies – for example, nuclear weapons, nanotechnologies, and even biotechnologies – and subject to their control the obvious dangers caused by these technologies; on the other hand, biotechnologies are characterized by such typical dangers that Huxley well described in his novel. As Fukuyama notes, the practical application of biotechnologies, that is, pharmacology, genetic engineering, stem cells, and reproductive technologies, which is expressed in granting happiness to humans, prolonging their life, and improving genetics, is always accompanied by side effects, and it is precisely because of these side effects that it demands a very great sacrifice from humans – all this sacrifices the human soul (Fukuyama, 2002).

That in dystopian society humans are powerless and violence is everyday life is well visible from the discussed examples, but it is interesting what the feminist vision of totalitarian regime is and how a female hero fights it, what result this struggle ultimately brings both for her and for society? We examine this issue according to contemporary Canadian writer Margaret Atwood's "The Handmaid's Tale," which gives quite interesting development to the dystopian genre. Published in 1985, this novel quickly attracted the attention of readers and critics due to its content, characteristic manner of narration, and relevance of social and political issues to modernity. In the book, the author raises contemporary society's problems – religious fundamentalism, feminism, consumerism, and abuse of power, which are actively discussed from the mid-1980s, which made the novel almost prophetic. "The Handmaid's Tale" is about what can happen if we constantly turn a blind eye to violence, fear to see problems, close ourselves off and do not notice how religious extremists gather strength and expand their influence. By relying on others' hope, people contribute to the formation of a totalitarian regime, while later the individual living in this system has difficulty liberating themselves from the dictatorial regime and must make great effort to gain freedom. Through the description and characterization of Offred, Moira, and Offred's mother, Atwood indicates to us that passivity is dangerous because inertia facilitates the establishment of dictatorship. In the work, the action takes place in the near future, in New England, in a patriarchal, totalitarian state, the Republic of Gilead. The book's main character - Offred, belongs to the caste of handmaids, who are obliged to bear children for men – for the ruling class of Gilead. Her real name is June. She was named Offred in Gilead;

the name Offred signifies belonging to that man (Fred) for whom she must bear a child. Her narration is characterized by fragmentality, and the reader themselves must arrange and then comprehend Offred's story. Atwood's book once again reminds us of the horrors of Orwell's novel and makes us feel that we should expect nothing good from the future. For the protagonists of both artistic creations, for Offred and Winston Smith, memory is the only means of resisting the government because knowledge of the past gives them the opportunity to compare the old and new systems and, accordingly, to see the flaws of the new system. The ending of both novels shows us that the totalitarian regime came to an end. The novel "1984" ends with an appendix about "Newspeak," which is written in past tense in ordinary language, which indicates to us that the government of Oceania no longer exists and in the future a researcher conducted scientific analysis of the characteristics of this regime. Atwood's book also ends with detailed discussion of one of the reports at a conference studying Gilead, from which it is clear that Gilead's totalitarian government also collapsed, though the ultimate fate of the main character Offred remains unknown to the reader. Moreover, these two works have in common: unbearable torture of people with different opinions, spreading false information through media, turning people into a crowd and crushing individualism; however, compared to Atwood, Orwell's and Huxley's political satire is sharper; moreover, it is more difficult to imagine the connection of events depicted in "The Handmaid's Tale" with the present than "Brave New World" or "1984." We must also note that like other writers, Atwood also employs the technique of extrapolation and based on what has already happened presents to us how events will develop in future America. This is natural; in this case, it once again raises the issue of complete equality between women and men. However surprising it may not be, for a country like America, according to the constitution, the issue of women's rights remains a relevant issue even today. This is why Atwood creates the American theocratic regime – Gilead, whose establishment was conditioned by the world's unsolvable problems, environmental pollution, and universal infertility. She depicts for us the picture according to which we imagine how the American government and generally the American people undergo transformation if an organization similar to the "Moral Majority" or authorities with Puritan ideology come to power. In order to govern the individual, Gilead's government corrects history and controls media. Through state television, they broadcast only victory stories. To make people lose the desire to fight

against the regime, Gilead's system also resorts to the method of threat and intimidation. Torture of opponents of the system is frequent. They also hang human corpses at the main gateway, presumably of those people who did not obey the system's rules and fought tirelessly to overthrow it. Thus, Gilead's regime attempts to turn people into a crowd and eliminate their individualism. The authorities do not ease women's lives but psychologically influence them and convince them that they are incapable of doing anything other than the function granted by the government. Like robots, women have only one activity assigned; they perform the action with which they were programmed. Such division of women's functions reminds us of the divided classes (castes) in Huxley's novel "Brave New World" – Alphas, Betas, and Gammas. The difference lies in the fact that in Huxley's novel, people are programmed from infancy, so they are satisfied with their life from birth, while in Atwood's novel, women are not resigned to their fate and for many of them performing the role that the state demands from them is insufficient for self-realization. The most thought-provoking and outrageous fact of violating women's rights in future society is the prohibition of literacy for them. In case of being caught in the process of reading, the punishment is amputation of limbs because cutting off hands and feet does not represent a hindering factor in reproduction. What is the author's main appeal and what does she indicate to us? Probably that Gilead's dictatorial system would not have formed if people had fought against it, and with their passivity they, on the contrary, contributed to Gilead's strengthening. From this, is Offred a strong character? Is she a rebel or a powerless victim of the system? Despite all prohibitions, Offred tries to preserve memories, makes notes about Gilead's system, and keeps information, which already indicates Offred's unyielding character. Then she starts a romance with Nick, which seemingly should signify rebellion because in Gilead, a love relationship implies going against the system. However, isn't this for Offred an attempt to escape from reality? The author indicates to us with this that people will endure everything if they receive compensation, even in small form. At the same time, she introduces a new stroke in dystopian novels politically and exposes the government disguised as religion, which oppresses women; male authority that narrows women and uses them to implement its own goals. Thus, what is Offred's psychological image here? We think that her own life is important to her because she does not intend to get involved in the machinations of the organization "Mayday" fighting against Gilead's regime and does not want to share the fate of

those who were punished, tortured, and destroyed: "Dear God, – I say in my mind, – I will act as you wish. Because this time you saved me, I will wash everything out of my heart, I will be as they command me. I will completely empty myself, I will really become a vessel. I will leave Nick alone, I will forget the rest too, I will no longer complain. I will submit to my lot. I will sacrifice myself, I will repent of sins, I will refuse to think, I will refuse principles" (Atwood, 2015, 383). Thus, Offred is more a powerless victim than a rebel, and unlike characters in dystopian novels, she is more passive. Here we must add that it is easy to judge Offred; it is possible that many of us in her situation would have acted like her or worse. Ultimately, like Offred, many live constantly bowed down in silence and obedience to save themselves. Although Offred imagines such ways of escaping from Gilead's power as burning the house or suicide, ultimately she does not do this, but if we recall Moira from the "Red Center," her rebellion against the existing system, who dares to escape from this closed system, we will see wonderful courage for freedom, since her capture means inevitable death?! We cannot bypass Offred's mother either, whose fighting and unyielding character Gilead's government could do nothing about, though they still "silenced" her by sending her to a colony polluted with toxic chemicals. Here let us recall Montag from "Fahrenheit 451," who so feels living in falsehood, is so alienated from the external world, that he dares unimaginable rebellion, kills his fire chief and flees, escapes from the mechanical hound, from which escape is actually impossible. A fighting hero is also Winston in Orwell's "1984," who seeks like-minded people, despite the fear of torture cannot stop and begins secret struggle against the authorities. Here we must underline that Winston is the deepest character among other protagonists. Therefore, these characters believe that it is possible to overthrow the dictatorial regime or escape from this society; although they are lonely, in rare cases they also have like-minded people, for example, Montag has Faber and other professors, Offred has several handmaids and the entire secret organization "Mayday," Winston has Julia and the secret brotherhood, and they continue the struggle to the end. However, the culmination, that is, the concluding part, which is the most interesting element of the dystopian genre, looks like this: the problem remains unsolved, the hero flees, is caught, tortured, or killed. Dystopian society continues to exist. Winston is terribly tortured in prison, Montag flees (it is noteworthy that he does not refuse his goal), Offred also flees and leaves her story

recorded on tape, though the recording breaks off and we ultimately do not know how her life developed.

The role of language in establishing totalitarian regime must also be highlighted. If we rely on David Sisk, it is precisely language that plays a great role in turning people into a zombified mass (Siski, 1997). Thus, authors of dystopian novels, when imagining the future world, create a language that will be in correspondence with the social relationships of future society. The best example of this is Oceania's "Newspeak," which was created in accordance with the ideological needs of English Socialism. Orwell creates a forcibly impoverished language; grammar and lexicon are very simplified, reduced, and adapted to totalitarian regime. Its goal is the gradual elimination of different opinion, and this happens by removing from the lexicon such words that express rebellion, freedom, and similar content. Reinterpretation and word creation represent instruments of violence. Day by day their imprinting in consciousness occurs. The authorities manipulate public consciousness. By inversion of signs included in the concept of a word. For example, it says "well-being," they read "deficit," it says "temporary difficulties," they read "permanent crisis." Thus, Newspeak is an artificial product created for correction of human memory and their representations about the world. Therefore, the creation of new speech language was intended to forget Oldspeak: "Newspeak was not created to expand the range of thought; on the contrary, it was created to reduce the stock of words to a minimum" (Orwell, 2017, 343); this was precisely what "A vocabulary," "B vocabulary," and "C vocabulary" served (Orwell, 2017, 344), for the needs of everyday life, political, and scientific-technical terms. The Party's main goal is to eliminate from language such words as "equality," "independence," because if these words do not exist, accordingly, people will not know their meaning and will never desire to fight for independence and equality. Thus, "Newspeak" fights against the formation of thought and words. In another dystopian novel, say, in "The Handmaid's Tale," the speech of future people does not differ from the speech of Americans of the 1980s. It is possible that author Atwood deliberately does not create a unique language so that by using identical language she helps society recognize themselves in the inhabitants of Gilead. Instead, the state of Gilead, which uses the Bible as a guarantor of state stability, resorts to biblical language in everyday phrases. For example: standard greetings among neighbors are as follows: "Blessed be the fruit," "May the Lord open," police in Gilead are called "Guardians of the faith," and all stores in Gilead have Bible-inspired names:

"Lilies of the field," "Milk and honey," "all flesh." In war, military units have the following names: "The angels of the apocalypse, Fourth division," "The twenty-first battalion of the angels of light" (Atwood, 2015). Similar biblical nomenclature is less commonly found in dystopian works. Thus, language and the face of dystopian society are determined by government engaged in personal interests, disguised with lies, corrupt authorities who resort to every trick, do not avoid even violating law in order to preserve power: for example, Mustapha Mond in Huxley's book "Brave New World," O'Brien in Orwell's "1984," and Colonel Beatty in Bradbury's novel "Fahrenheit 451." Mustapha Mond violates the supreme law established by himself and reads books forbidden for ordinary citizens, as he himself says: "...because here I establish laws, I can also violate them" (Huxley, 2021, 225). According to O'Brien's explanation, when coming to power, the Party's only goal is to seize power and not to bring well-being to the people.

Thus, the novels under discussion are unified by the depiction of totalitarian regimes and authoritarian rule: the absence of free speech, constant surveillance, meticulously calculated daily schedules, pervasive monotony, food shortages, the presence of underground organizations, and attempts to escape or break free from the regime. From an ideological and thematic perspective, they are connected by the portrayal of restrictions on individual freedom, wherein the sacrifice of the individual for the so-called welfare of society becomes particularly striking. They reveal the destructive dominance of surveillance and propaganda, a moral and ethical crisis, the cultivation of fear, the disintegration of the family institution, the neglect of art and creativity, and the denial of the past.

Each character serves as a symbolic figure and represents:

- Humanity
- Freedom
- Power
- Obedience
- Otherness

All the authors – George Orwell in particular – investigate the underlying causes of totalitarian governments and conclude that the roots of tyranny lie in the human desire for and attachment to power.

Ultimately, dystopian novels help us to critically assess our own capabilities and to recognize that freedom is the greatest achievement of humankind. They also serve as warnings: technology exposes the darkest aspects of human nature, strengthens hierarchies, increases

mechanisms of control, and harms nature, human nature, and the environment. The unintended consequences of technology are predominantly negative; new technologies do not solve the problems of old ones – on the contrary, they generate new issues. In conclusion, it must be emphasized that literature – in this case, dystopian literature – is essential for politics, as it awakens politicians, exposes their actions, and holds them more accountable for what they attempt to conceal.

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Kamelia Petkova

**Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
[kamelia.petkova@gmail.com], ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3108-3887**

Voices from the Ghetto: Stories of Loneliness, Stigma, and Belonging in Six Bulgarian Cities

Abstract: *This paper examines experiences of loneliness, stigma, and belonging among residents of Roma ghettoized neighborhoods in six Bulgarian cities – Lom, Dobrich, Ruse, Asenovgrad, Kyustendil, and Straldzha. The analysis is based on qualitative research methods: 36 in-depth interviews (six in each city) conducted with different members of the Roma community – men and women of various age groups, informal Roma leaders, educational and health mediators. This approach provides in-depth insights into the social realities of ghettoized neighborhoods, moving beyond superficial public perceptions. The study traces how spatial isolation and institutional stigma shape the sense of the “ghetto” – simultaneously as a place of social exclusion and of collective identity. At the center of the analysis are personal narratives of silence and fear, but also of faith and hope. Theoretically, the article builds on the concepts of social stigma, moral boundaries, and territorial marginalization. Its aim is to demonstrate how “voices from below” articulate their lived experiences and to give visibility to a frequently neglected social world.*

Keywords: *Roma; stigma; marginalization; belonging; ghetto; Bulgaria.*

Introduction

In recent years, urban inequalities in Bulgaria have increasingly taken on a clear spatial dimension. In a number of cities, stable ghettoized neighborhoods have emerged. These are marginalized territories, inhabited predominantly by members of the Roma community, and characterized by high levels of poverty, poor infrastructure, and symbolic exclusion. Their formation is linked not only to spontaneous processes but also to long-term institutional inaction. In the context of deepening social polarization, climate transformations, and digital transition, ghettoized neighborhoods are becoming increasingly visible markers of unsustainable urban development and structural vulnerability. Although they are part of the urban fabric, they often remain invisible to institutions, while their inhabitants remain unheard in public debate (Picker, 2017; Powell & Lever, 2017).

The study of ghettoized neighborhoods and life within them is particularly relevant in the context of efforts toward social integration, just transition, and the implementation of policies aimed at reducing inequalities. Nevertheless, the voices of residents of these neighborhoods rarely reach public attention and even more rarely are truly heard. The present article seeks to give voice to these residents by focusing on their experiences, narratives, and perceptions related to loneliness, stigma, and belonging. The research was conducted in six Bulgarian cities – Lom, Dobrich, Ruse, Asenovgrad, Kyustendil, and Straldzha – and approaches ghettoized neighborhoods not merely as territorial units but as social worlds with their own internal structure, boundaries, and identity (Wacquant, 2007). At the center of the analysis are the personal accounts of neighborhood residents and representatives of local government, who share what it means to live “in the ghetto” – in material, emotional, and moral terms. Their perspectives provide insights into the ways in which social exclusion is experienced, articulated, and at times overcome (Goffman, 1963; Yuval-Davis, 2011). In the text, the terms “ghetto” and “Roma neighborhood” are used interchangeably. The term “ghetto” refers not only to a geographic space but also to a socially constructed zone of isolation and stigma.

Theoretical Framework

To understand the social processes unfolding in Roma ghettos and the lived experiences of their residents, the article draws on a theoretical framework that integrates concepts and methods from urban sociology, studies of marginalization, stigma theory, and research on belonging and identity. The aim is to demonstrate how spatial positioning within the city, public perceptions, and institutional practices jointly shape the status of the ghetto neighborhood and influence the way its inhabitants are perceived.

Central to this framework is the concept of the “ghetto,” which has undergone significant historical and theoretical transformations. The term originated in sixteenth-century Venice as a designated place of compulsory residence for Jews. Later, it became established in sociology as a category denoting isolation, ethnic concentration, poverty, and stigma (Marcuse, 1997). In contemporary critical urban studies, the ghetto is seen not only as a geographic territory but also as a socially, politically, and morally constructed zone, where racial relations, institutional inaction, and social hierarchy intersect (Wacquant, 2007; Duneier, 2016).

In the Bulgarian context, Roma ghettoized neighborhoods function as double markers: on the one hand, of exclusion, danger, and “otherness,” and on the other, of shared identity, local community, and mutual support. This dual meaning makes them specific social spaces in which the tension between stigmatization and resilience, between alienation and belonging, becomes particularly visible (Picker, 2017; Vincke, 2013).

The concept of social stigma, formulated by Erving Goffman (1963), is key to understanding processes of symbolic exclusion. Stigma denotes a characteristic that devalues a person in the eyes of others and excludes them from accepted notions of normality. In the case of Roma neighborhoods, stigma is multidimensional: it is simultaneously ethnic (Roma origin), social (poverty, low education), territorial (address and neighborhood), and institutional (disparaging treatment by administration and public services). Stigma is sustained through moral boundaries – symbolic lines that separate “us” from “them,” the “acceptable” from the “deviant” (Lamont, 2000). These moral boundaries are not merely cultural perceptions but social mechanisms that maintain distance, hierarchy, and control. In this sense, the ghetto represents a boundary through which society legitimizes the rejection and silencing of its inhabitants. It is both a symbol of social problems and a concrete space where inequalities are clearly visible.

The study also draws on the concepts of territorial marginalization and advanced marginality, introduced by Loïc Wacquant (2007), according to whom spatial separation is not a side effect but a central mechanism of social exclusion. Ghettoized neighborhoods are formed and reproduced through a combination of residential segregation, institutional neglect, and unequal access to basic public resources such as healthcare, education, transportation, and cultural infrastructure. As a result, peripheral social worlds are created within otherwise central urban territories – worlds with limited horizons and high barriers to social mobility.

As a counterpoint to this logic of exclusion, the study introduces the notion of belonging, understood not as a fixed identity but as a dynamic process of rootedness, recognition, and participation (Yuval-Davis, 2011). Belonging does not always imply equality, but it provides a sense of being part of a community, that one’s place has meaning, and that one’s presence has value. In Roma neighborhoods, belonging is built through trust and mutual support, enabling residents to construct an identity that resists stigma.

Methods

The study is based on the application of qualitative methods aimed at gaining an in-depth interviews understanding of the experiences, perceptions, and sense of belonging among residents of Roma ghettoized neighborhoods in six Bulgarian cities: Lom, Dobrich, Ruse, Asenovgrad, Kyustendil, and Straldzha. In each city, six in-depth interviews were conducted, resulting in a total of 36 interviews. Participant selection followed a purposive sampling strategy, with the aim of capturing diverse perspectives on life in Roma neighborhoods and the ways in which belonging, loneliness, and social stigma are experienced.

The respondents included:

- Roma residents of ghettoized neighborhoods—men and women from different age groups (youth, women, men), with varied social status, education, and employment. They shared personal stories, emotions, and coping strategies related to isolation.
- Educational and health mediators, often members of the same neighborhoods. They provided insights into the internal dynamics of the community and the institutional barriers faced.
- Informal Roma leaders, who offered critical interpretations of living conditions in the neighborhoods and of social inclusion policies.

All interviews were in-depth and conducted with open-ended questions, allowing participants to speak freely about their life experiences, perceptions of (non) belonging, discrimination, and intra-community relations. The interviews were conducted face-to-face between June and October 2023, with participants' informed consent, and were transcribed verbatim. The analysis was carried out using qualitative thematic coding, in line with theoretical concepts of stigma, moral boundaries, ghettoization, belonging, and social visibility. All interviews were anonymized, following ethical principles of informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. The interpretation of the data does not aim at representativeness, but rather at a deeper understanding of the meanings that respondents themselves attribute to the spaces they inhabit.

Limitations of the Study

Due to its qualitative nature and purposive sampling, the findings cannot be generalized to all Roma ghettoized neighborhoods in the country. The analysis focuses on six specific cases, with the aim of providing contextualized insights into social realities. The geographical

and cultural diversity of such neighborhoods suggests that different forms of belonging and stigma may exist in other contexts. The study centers on the perspectives of members of the Roma community in the selected neighborhoods, along with the views of local authorities. As the analysis is based on narratives, it is shaped by subjectivity, yet this subjectivity is precisely what makes it valuable for understanding the mechanisms of social exclusion. In interpreting the data, efforts were made to conduct a critical analysis that takes into account the broader social and cultural context.

Results and Discussion

The analysis of the in-depth interviews conducted in six different cities reveal a multilayered picture of the social reality in Roma ghettoized neighborhoods. Despite differences in geographic location, settlement size, religious affiliation, and local policies, the narratives of respondents highlight similar experiences and social attitudes. Loneliness, social isolation, stigma, institutional neglect, and spatial marginalization emerge as recurring themes in the lives of ghetto residents. At the same time, the interviews also reveal countervailing patterns – forms of belonging, local networks of support, mediation efforts, and social resilience built in spite of systemic exclusion.

This section examines how these experiences manifest in different local contexts, not by seeking mechanical generalizations, but by closely engaging with the voices of the respondents. The themes presented – loneliness and social isolation, stigma and institutional neglect, the role of mediators, the invisibility of the ghetto within the urban structure, and lived experiences of belonging – are not only analytical categories but also carriers of concrete social experience. They allow for a deeper understanding of Roma ghettoized neighborhoods not simply as confined spaces, but as complex social worlds where vulnerability and dignity, loss and meaning, rejection and resilience are intertwined.

Loneliness and Social Isolation

Loneliness and social isolation are among the most frequently reported experiences in Roma ghettoized urban neighborhoods, regardless of their location or the size of the city. Despite differences in local infrastructure, social services, and municipal policies, the feeling of being excluded – from the city, from institutions, and sometimes even from the community itself – recurs across all the analyzed cities. The

results, however, reveal certain variations. For instance, in Dobrich, social isolation appears mainly through limited inter-neighborhood contacts and physical distance. According to the words of an informal Roma leader, the “Izgrev” neighborhood is often perceived as a “dark zone” on the city map, where institutional presence is minimal and public services are reduced to mere formalities. A common attitude among residents is that this neighborhood is not considered part of the “real city”:

“No one wants to deal with the problems of the neighborhood; we seek support from the institutions, but unfortunately our problems receive no public attention. We want a cleaner neighborhood, better streets, but there is no one to pay attention to us. Most of the young people look for salvation abroad, and when they save some money, they come back and want to invest it in their homes. But how can you invest when the streets are in terrible condition? How can you build a nice house when there are problems with the sewage system?” (Informal Roma leader, Dobrich).

Similar views were expressed in Ruse. According to a resident of the *Selemetya* neighborhood, there is a prevailing sense of lost connection with institutions and a feeling that the problems of the neighborhood are not treated with sufficient seriousness. Loneliness is experienced most acutely by women and elderly people, who are often excluded from the labor market and live in conditions of extreme poverty and isolation from the rest of the city. Many describe a sense of symbolic “invisibility”:

“We are here, but no one sees us... they only come before the elections” (Roma resident, Ruse).

According to an educational mediator from Ruse, there is a pronounced form of structural vulnerability affecting mainly women in some of the ghettoized communities, such as *Druzha 2* and *Trite Galaba*.

“The mothers here are alone with their children. There are no jobs and no one to help them. They are just trying to survive. There is discrimination in the labor market, and it is very difficult to find someone willing to hire them, especially when they have small children” (Educational mediator, Ruse).

This perspective draws attention to several interconnected deficits: lack of access to the labor market, absence of social and institutional support, and isolation within the community itself. In this context, the loneliness of Roma women does not necessarily mean the absence of a partner, but stems from social isolation – they often bear almost the entire responsibility for childcare and household work without

institutional support, while their opportunities to participate in social and economic life are severely limited due to discrimination, low levels of education, and lack of access to services. The expression “*they are just trying to survive*” reveals the everyday struggle for survival, where the horizon of the future is overshadowed by the immediate effort to cope with scarcity and isolation. This is not merely poverty, but a condition of prolonged exclusion in which loneliness becomes a social norm rather than a deviation.

A profound sense of institutional estrangement and symbolic rejection is also shared by an unemployed Roma woman from the Trite Galaba neighborhood in Ruse:

“When you go to the municipality, they look at you as if you are a problem. There is no one you can talk to normally, and asking for help is even harder. I was registered at the labor office for quite a while, but they didn’t manage to find me a job, and I remain unemployed” (Roma resident, Ruse).

The quotation reflects two clearly distinguishable yet interrelated levels of experienced marginalization. The first is stigmatizing treatment – the informal but recognizable language of body posture, gaze, and tone, through which institutional representatives mark the Roma visitor as “annoying,” “guilty,” or “superfluous.” The second level is actual institutional silence – the lack of access to understanding, dialogue, and real support, particularly for someone who has been long-term unemployed and economically inactive. The phrase “*there is no one you can talk to normally*” shows that the barrier is not only administrative, but also communicative, cultural, and even human. Ultimately, the quotation testifies not only to the denial of assistance but also to an experience of complete institutional distance, where the very act of seeking support becomes a humiliating effort.

In many of the cases studied, the experience of cultural and social isolation is dominant, especially among older members of the Roma community. For example, in Kyustendil, in the *Iztok* neighborhood, some Roma residents describe the absence of close interethnic relations as well as isolation within the neighborhood itself, which continues to expand. Its inhabitants feel not only physically separated but also emotionally and symbolically excluded:

“The older people from the neighborhood don’t feel like part of the city. They only go as far as the neighborhood center and that’s it. And we think that we are not very welcome” (Roma resident, Kyustendil).

A similar situation exists in Asenovgrad, where interviewees speak of barriers between the community and the majority that hinder

participation in the local economy, educational institutions, and public spaces. These boundaries are transmitted across generations, resulting in intergenerational loneliness – among the elderly who remain on their own, and among young people who see no prospects for realization.

In Lom, isolation manifests itself on several levels – both in terms of the city’s position within the region and internally within the Roma community itself. The division between different neighborhoods leads to a lack of trust and interaction, while social services often fail to reach all areas equally. One of the interview participants, a long-standing educational mediator, noted:

“In the city there are several Roma neighborhoods, and each is its own separate world. Each neighborhood is specific, since in the three neighborhoods people speak differently. In Mladenovo and Khumata one dialect is spoken, while in Stadionia another dialect is used, different from the other two neighborhoods” (Educational mediator, Lom).

The overarching framework of these experiences outlines not merely physical isolation, but a structural loneliness stemming from poverty, segregation, institutional neglect, and the absence of prospects for change. In these urban peripheries, loneliness is not only a personal emotion – it is a socially structured reality, whose consequences are reflected in the lack of trust, social withdrawal, anxiety, and the sense of living “outside society.”

Stigma and Institutional Passivity

Stigma and institutional passivity manifest not only as a sense of discrimination but also as an accumulated social experience of being ignored, excluded, and left without commitment on the part of state and local authorities. In the narratives of respondents from the six studied cities, very similar views emerge: institutions are not simply absent but are often perceived as inaccessible and hostile. In Lom, a Roma activist shared:

“People don’t trust institutions. They tell me: You’ll write a complaint, you’ll go around, and what will happen? When there is a flood, we are the first to be forgotten. And yet, we are still here” (Informal Roma leader, Lom).

This distrust is structurally embedded – it is not accidental but rooted in years of inaction, insufficient infrastructure, unequal treatment, and limited access to services. In Straldzha, a local Roma leader emphasized:

“They make promises before the elections, and afterwards nothing. They come here, shake hands, smile, take pictures with the children, promise they

will listen to our needs and that things will change. And then, once again, we are left alone” (Informal Roma leader, Straldzha).

Here is another similar opinion:

“While I was deputy mayor, on my initiative we created a framework for the whole region – each municipality had to identify what was needed and then submit projects or specific requests. For example, which street needed asphalt, or which school needed renovation. We called it the Framework Program for the Integration of Roma in the Montana region. We focused on 7–8 areas, including media. That was during the King’s administration. At that time, there were many deputy mayors from the minority. After the change of government, everything was cleared out, and for many years there were no people from the minority in such positions. You have to know the root of the problem, not just its fruit. Because you can taste the fruit, but you won’t understand where it came from. To do this, you need to go to the people who planted the problem. Right now there is only a strategy on paper. Nothing is actually being done” (Informal Roma leader, Lom).

In some cases, space itself becomes an indicator of social status, and infrastructure a language of belonging or exclusion. A resident of the *Izgrej* neighborhood in Dobrich shared the following view:

“We ask: why are most of the streets in the neighborhood in this condition, and the answer is silence. But if the neighborhood were in another part of the city, the next week there would already be asphalt and new lighting” (Roma resident, Dobrich).

The shared account clearly illustrates the experience of structural inequality, grounded in spatial discrimination and institutional unequal treatment. This narrative does not merely point to the poor state of infrastructure – muddy and unpaved streets – but frames it in a sharp contrast: “us” and “the other part of the city,” where the state reacts quickly, and needs are recognized and met. The phrase “*the answer is silence*” is particularly telling. It highlights not only administrative inaction but also a silent, institutionalized denial of the right to voice and of equal living conditions. Here, silence is symbolic – it reflects the refusal of institutions to listen, respond, or commit. The comparison with the other part of the city underscores territorial inequality, manifested in the stark difference between areas with paved streets and those without. This quotation is emblematic of how space becomes an indicator of social status, and infrastructure a language of belonging or exclusion. The problem is not only the mud itself, but the way it permanently marks the neighborhood as “second-class,” as a place toward which local authorities remain passive. What emerges here is a territorial form of institutional discrimination, where the ghettoized neighborhood is not

only physically separated but also symbolically excluded from the city – from its priorities, concerns, and allocation of resources. Similar infrastructure problems are also observed in other cities under study, such as Asenovgrad and Straldzha (see *Figure 1* and *Figure 2*).

Often, the lack of additional support in the educational process is also perceived as a form of institutional neglect. In Kyustendil, one of the educational mediators shared:

“The school needs more assistant teachers to help Roma children who do not speak Bulgarian and who struggle to adapt to the learning process, but they are not hired. They say – there is no budget. And yet the children need support, translation, trust” (Educational mediator, Kyustendil).

In most cases, manifestations of territorialized stigma – where the very place of residence becomes a social marker of undesirability – are especially palpable among young Roma. They often face rejection when applying for jobs, seeking rental housing, or simply trying to be treated with respect. Such cases have been reported in Ruse and Asenovgrad. Here are some of the views expressed by interviewees:

“It’s not enough that some Roma neighborhoods are already more isolated, but when we go to the institutions, it’s as if they look at us under a magnifying glass. They ask: Which neighborhood are you from? And as soon as you say Trite Galaba, their attitude immediately changes” (Roma resident, Ruse).

“I know a boy who graduated with honors and wanted to become a teacher, but he lived in Loznitsa. They told him – ‘You are not suitable to be the face of the school.’ And that was only because he was from the neighborhood” (Informal Roma leader, Asenovgrad).

These examples outline a form of institutional passivity that is expressed not only in the lack of resources but also in deeper social exclusion. Local authorities not only fail to compensate for the vulnerable position of Roma ghettoized neighborhoods but, in some cases, actively reproduce their isolation through formal, disengaged, and discriminatory practices. Stigma here is not only interpersonal – it is institutionalized. It manifests itself through bureaucracy, formal refusals, lack of flexible measures, and neglected zones in urban planning. This makes marginalization persistent and difficult to overcome.

Figure 1. Part of the streets in the Roma neighborhood of Straldzha
Source: Author's fieldwork, 2023.

Figure 2. Part of the streets in the Roma neighborhood of Asenovgrad
Source: Author's fieldwork, 2023.

Loneliness and Emotional Experiences

The loneliness described by interview participants is not simply the absence of social ties – it is a state of deep emotional estrangement that often turns into a feeling of redundancy and invisibility. This is loneliness in the context of marginalization – born of the repeatedly accumulated sense of being left outside public attention. It is particularly in larger cities that the social distance between the Roma community and the rest of the residents is most pronounced and often palpable in everyday interactions. In one case, a young woman described how shopping becomes a trial, and how urban infrastructure amplifies her sense of exclusion:

“They look at us as if we are not human. My skin is a little darker, and I immediately stand out. When I go into a store, they follow me. At the bus stop, people sit far away. I feel very uncomfortable, as if I am different” (Roma resident, Asenovgrad).

This social distance becomes a habit, as another participant from the same locality observed:

“Loneliness here is a habit. We are used to being alone. We are used to the fact that there is no one to protect us or to do something to improve the conditions in some parts of the neighborhood” (Informal Roma leader, Asenovgrad).

In Straldzha, an interviewed member of the Roma community spoke about the intergenerational transmission of emotional withdrawal and lack of participation in public life:

“My father lived like that – home to work, work to home. Never to the community center, never to meetings. He used to say, We don’t exist” (Roma resident, Straldzha).

The phrase “*We don’t exist*” reflects a deeply rooted sense of social invisibility, passed down as a legacy.

The results of the in-depth interviews show that there are numerous cases in which even within the community, loneliness is reproduced through a lack of mutual support and fear of vulnerability:

“People here don’t help each other anymore. Everyone has shut themselves off. If someone has a problem, they don’t say it because of shame. And shame is loneliness” (Educational mediator, Straldzha).

“I feel alone, even when I’m with people. Because we don’t talk about the real things. Everyone carries their own pain alone. Life has become hard – there’s no work, it’s difficult to earn money if you don’t have an education and if you can’t read. The only way is to go abroad and struggle there, but when you come back, you have money and can buy many things” (Roma resident, Dobrich).

Although some participants in larger cities have had opportunities to take part in NGO initiatives or educational programs, emotional isolation does not disappear. One respondent described the cycle of hope and disappointment:

“When elections come and the politicians arrive, they all ask us about our problems. Afterwards – silence. And you are left alone with yourself again” (Roma resident, Ruse).

The interviews from Asenovgrad add to this picture – here, loneliness is linked to religious boundaries that isolate young people even within the community. An educational mediator noted:

“There are young people who never leave the neighborhood. They are afraid of being insulted, and their parents don’t let them out either. Everyone stays silent. And the silence becomes a wall” (Educational mediator, Asenovgrad).

What all these accounts have in common is the sense that loneliness in Roma ghettos is not a personal issue but a consequence of social exclusion. It has become part of everyday life and is often perceived as something normal. This is why social interventions rarely succeed – they do not address the deep emotional wounds that sustain the feelings of abandonment and lack of belonging.

Local efforts and mediation: the role of mediators

In the context of limited institutional access and the systemic failure to resolve problems, educational and health mediators in Roma neighborhoods emerge as key figures of mediation between the community and local authorities. Their role goes far beyond their formal duties and often turns into a personal mission, motivated by a sense of belonging to the community and a conscious sense of responsibility:

“People come to me when they have no one else to turn to. I measure blood pressure, give advice, send them to the doctor. I’m like an emergency service here” (Health mediator, Dobrich);

“Sometimes I feel like a translator – I explain to people what the letter from Social Services means, and to Social Services why the person didn’t respond. They don’t talk to each other – I’m in the middle” (Health mediator, Lom);

“I’m not just a mediator, I’m also a parent for some children, and a sister for their mothers” (Educational mediator, Straldzha).

These voices reveal the multilayered and often informal function of mediators in ghettoized neighborhoods. They are not merely a “link” between the community and the institutions but become key figures of advocacy, trust, and practical protection for vulnerable residents. In the

absence of active institutional presence, mediators take on the role of translators – not only in the linguistic sense but also in cultural and emotional terms – of the needs, fears, and realities of the neighborhood.

“They often call me to translate or to accompany them, but no one invites me when decisions are made about the neighborhood. Yet I know the problems best” (Educational mediator, Asenovgrad);

“I talk to the principals, I beg them not to expel the children. I explain that the mother is alone, that there is no one to take them to school. Sometimes I take them myself. For me this is not a job – it is a responsibility” (Educational mediator, Straldzha).

Similar testimonies from Straldzha highlight that mediators often carry the burden of social inequalities on their own shoulders – without formal status, yet with enormous importance for the community.

“There have been cases when I went from house to house to gather students because they were about to be expelled. No one wants to go into the neighborhoods, but I am there every day” (Educational mediator, Lom).

In Ruse, the figure of the health mediator also gains public visibility – through an active stance, participation in policymaking, and strategic thinking. She not only identifies the problems but also proposes solutions – from mobile fieldwork to the need for physical infrastructure for activities within the neighborhood. Her commitment is not merely professional but also value-driven. Among her proposals are:

- Organizing more discussions on human trafficking;
- Conducting health literacy trainings aimed at reducing early pregnancies;
- Carrying out mobile fieldwork with neighborhood residents;
- Holding conversations with parents and employers;
- Engaging children through activities close to their interests.

The interviewed mediator emphasized that achieving real results requires building a supportive environment for mediation – teams, facilities, logistics, and continuous institutional backing. A telling example is the social housing project in Ruse, where housing allocation is tied to conditions of social engagement – school attendance, choosing a family doctor, and participation in programs. Mediators there play a key role in implementing this model of mutual responsibility.

Despite the different contexts, one common thread stands out across all studied cities: mediators are burdened with expectations that exceed their resources. They face institutional neglect, yet at the same time, they are seen as “the visible face of the state” (respondent,

Straldzha) and are often the only ones addressing the community's urgent needs in real time. Mediators act as a social bridge between two worlds that rarely meet, but whose connection is essential for inclusion, belonging, and trust.

Invisibility and Marginalization in Urban Space

Across all the studied locations, Roma ghettoized neighborhoods represent spaces of social neglect, marked by a lack of infrastructural investment, zones of isolation, and minimal presence in urban policies. Although physically part of the city, these neighborhoods function as internal peripheries – materially segregated yet culturally burdened with negative stigma. In Dobrich, residents describe spatial exclusion as chronic and highly visible:

“No one comes here unless it's for something urgent. We are outside the city, even though we're just five minutes from the center” (Roma resident, Dobrich).

A similar situation is observed in Asenovgrad, where, although the neighborhood is formally part of the city's territory, the sense of being peripheral remains strongly present.

“The sewage system in the neighborhood needs improvement. In many of the streets, dirty water runs freely, which is dangerous for our health. This is not accidental – no one thinks that we are part of the city” (Educational mediator, Asenovgrad).

This experience reflects not so much a geographical, but rather a symbolic and infrastructural peripherality – a sense that the neighborhood lies outside the scope of institutional concern.

In Kyustendil, the “Iztok” neighborhood also carries a symbolic burden in public discourse:

“The moment you say you're from 'Iztok,' people look at you differently. As if you're from another country” (Roma resident, Kyustendil).

An informal Roma leader from Kyustendil noted:

“The neighborhood is constantly growing, there is an old and a new part, and the problems are many. There are still many illegal houses, which are by no means small in size, and if they have to be demolished it could become a big problem, because people have invested a lot of money in them” (Roma resident, Kyustendil).

In Straldzha, marginalization is even more direct:

“We are the last in line – if there is even a line for us at all. Here even the ambulance comes more slowly, because they know we are from Izgrev” (Roma resident, Dobrich).

The case of Ruse is indicative of institutionalized segregation. According to a health mediator, even social housing projects, which are presented as instruments of integration, contain elements of selective inclusion – only “proven” families are given the opportunity to leave the neighborhoods. This creates a new form of spatial stratification within the community itself. What is common across all the studied cities is that the space of the ghetto not only reflects social isolation but also reproduces it. Its urban morphology – the lack of connections with the city, public infrastructure, and institutions – turns isolation into a material reality and sustains the feeling that residents are in a permanent “other” position.

Belonging Despite Alienation

Despite the strong spatial and social isolation, residents of Roma ghettoized neighborhoods express a deep sense of belonging to the place where they live. This belonging is not based on recognition from the outside world but arises from emotional, kinship, and network ties with neighbors, family, relatives, and the local community. The ghetto is “their place” – marked by its deprivations, yet also by its anchors of security, predictability, and social support. In Dobrich, this attachment to the neighborhood is expressed through a sense of long-term inhabitation and mutuality:

“I don’t want to live anywhere else. I was born here, my children are here, everyone knows each other here. It may be dirty, but it is ours” (Roma resident, Dobrich)

The phrasing “I was born here, my children are here, everyone knows each other here” outlines the rootedness of the connection to place. It is not based on comfort, but on shared history, intergenerational continuity, and interpersonal bonds. The neighborhood is experienced as a world of the familiar, providing security in a context of external uncertainty. The expression “but it is ours” is particularly revealing, as it does not deny poverty and isolation but reframes them through symbolic appropriation and the affirmation of space as one’s own. In this sense, the ghetto is not merely a place of residence but becomes a site of social meaning and personal history. It is rejected from the outside but embraced from within – as a stage of life, dwelling, belonging,

and reciprocity. This quotation also challenges the widespread perception that residents of ghettoized neighborhoods necessarily wish to leave them. On the contrary – for many, the territory of the ghetto represents both limitation and protection, a space where ties, significance, and the sense of “home” are preserved in cultural and emotional terms. In some cases, even with a clear awareness of the poor material conditions, leaving is not perceived as an easy or desirable move:

“Where should we go? Even if they give us housing, it won’t be the same. People there won’t accept us. This is our home, just the way it is” (Roma resident, Dobrich).

In Lom, social mutual aid in the “Humata” neighborhood forms the basis of the sense of belonging:

“If you don’t have bread – you will get it from your neighbor. If you are sick – they will help you. This doesn’t exist in the city” (Roma resident, Lom).

A local educational mediator emphasizes that this form of “social security in insecurity” is paradoxically resilient:

“They are poor, but they are not alone. The system abandons them, but the neighborhood holds them together” (Educational mediator, Lom).

In Kyustendil, the sense of identity is even more directly tied to the space of the ghetto:

“The neighborhood is nasty, but at least there you know who you are. Outside you are nobody” (Roma resident, Kyustendil).

At the same time, the stigma that comes with the neighborhood’s name is a painful reminder of external rejection:

“When you say you are from there, they immediately put you under the same label. But they don’t know what life inside is like” (Roma resident, Asenovgrad)

In Straldzha, belonging is built on shared experience, common celebrations, and a different rhythm of life:

“We have our own holidays, our own order, our own way. Here no one looks at the clock” (Roma resident, Straldzha).

Some respondents expressed their sense of belonging with open pride, even when it is marked by marginalization:

“Yes, I am from the ghetto. So what? I work, I take care of my children, I am no worse than anyone else” (Roma resident, Straldzha).

In Ruse, despite the absence of basic infrastructure, in some neighborhoods such as “Druzha 2,” people find meaning in cohabitation and support networks:

“There is no sewerage, but here we are our own people. We have our people, there is someone to listen to you, we support each other when needed” (Roma resident, Ruse).

In Asenovgrad, the neighborhood may appear dangerous and forgotten to outsiders, but for those who live there, it is home – a place of identity and family history:

“They think we are bad just because we are from the neighborhood. But our roots are here. My mother was born here, I was too. How can I leave it?” (Roma resident, Asenovgrad).

For younger respondents, the neighborhood is sometimes the only space where they feel secure – not because of physical safety, but because of the familiarity of social ties:

“Outside I feel lost. In the neighborhood at least I know who my neighbor is, who my relative is, who will help me” (Roma resident, Asenovgrad).

These quotations portray the neighborhoods as both marginalized and protective spaces – deprived of institutional care, yet rich in social ties and a sense of “one’s own.” Belonging here is not a product of external recognition but of everyday resilience – of rhythm, reciprocity, and inner orientation that provide a sense of identity. For many members of the Roma community, this is the only place where they feel belonging and security, despite the constant external rejection.

Conclusion

The results of the in-depth interviews demonstrate that Roma ghettoized neighborhoods in the studied cities cannot be understood solely through the lens of deficits, poverty, or problematics. On the contrary, they emerge as complex social territories where marginalization and resilience, stigma and belonging, fear and hope coexist. The analysis of 36 in-depth interviews conducted in six cities reveals the multi-layered nature of social experiences, shaped not only by spatial isolation but also by the ethical and moral boundaries reproduced by institutions and society. The interviewees shared experiences of living in invisibility – manifested both through the lack of adequate infrastructure and social services and through the dismissive attitudes encountered in interactions with local authorities. The ghetto is perceived as an “other territory” – often excluded from the normal rhythm of urban life,

marked by fear, shame, and distance from outsiders. And yet, for many respondents, this territory is a place of social belonging – of family and neighborly ties, of mutual aid, traditions, and a sense of home. Despite the hardships, life in these neighborhoods is bearable and comprehensible, while the outside world often appears hostile, distant, and unpredictable.

Particularly important is the role of local intermediaries in the form of Roma mediators, activists, and informal leaders, who not only connect institutions with the community but also often represent, defend, and support it in encounters with bureaucracy, discrimination, and institutional indifference. Their voices are a source of knowledge, understanding, and local expertise, without which integration policies would hardly succeed.

The stories from the ghetto reveal that loneliness is not only social or physical. It is also symbolic, tied to the feeling of being “beyond the boundary of significance. In this sense, Roma neighborhoods function not merely as places of deprivation but as spaces where members of the Roma community are denied recognition. And yet, within these very spaces forms of resilience, solidarity, and hope are born.

Therefore, to understand Roma neighborhoods, we must move beyond simplified representations and listen to the people who live there. Their stories reveal a world that is at once difficult and filled with humanity. Recognizing this presence is not merely a matter of empathy but the first step toward a more just and inclusive society. In the context of growing social inequalities in Europe, the voices from the ghetto remind us that the future of cities depends on visibility, respect, and the right of every community to be heard.

Acknowledgements

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Milena Angelova

New Bulgarian University (Bulgaria)

[mangelova74@yahoo.com], ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0208-1989

“An Obstetrician of the Cultural Revolution”: The Physician, Biopower, and Muslim Women in Communist Bulgaria during the 1960s

Abstract: *This article examines the case of Dr. Gani Ganev, a rural physician in the village of Bezvodno (Kardzhali region), whose activities in the 1960s were elevated into a propaganda model of the so-called “cultural revolution” directed at Bulgaria’s Muslim population. Drawing on Ganev’s unpublished “diary-novella” (1961–1965) preserved in the Kardzhali State Archive, the study analyses how biomedical authority, socialist modernisation, and national-communist biopolitics intersect in everyday practices of surveillance, disciplining, and assimilation. The diary reveals an unusually explicit articulation of what Foucault terms biopower: systematic monitoring of women’s bodies, aggressive interventions in reproductive practices, the creation of a female “sanitary intelligence” network, and the pathologisation of religious and cultural norms. The text also exposes how Soviet minority-management models – especially the Soviet (Azerbaijani) “Geokchay experiment” – were imported and adapted to the Bulgarian context. Dr. Ganev’s self-fashioning as a “doctor-hero” illustrates the fusion between medical, ideological, and administrative functions within the communist project of ideological homogenisation. By reading this diary both as a self-serving political performance and as a rare documentary trace of localised state power, the article offers a more nuanced account of the 1960s – a period often overshadowed by later assimilation campaigns – and highlights the centrality of women’s bodies in the national-communist reordering of muslim minority communities.*

Keywords: *Muslim minority; Bulgaria; 1960s; Biopower; Women’s bodies and reproductive surveillance; Cultural revolution; Soviet minority-management models (Geokchay experiment); National-communism.*

Милена Ангелова

Нов български университет

**„Акушер на културната революция”: лекарят,
биовластта и мюсюлманките в комунистическа
България през 1960-те години**

Преднамереният „дневник“ на селският лекар-визионер и „образцовите“ политики в микромащаб – доктор Гани Ганев в село Безводно, 1962–1972¹

В предложения анализ на конкретния случай с лекаря от село Безводно и „санитарния надзор“ над жените мюсюлманки предлагам по-нюансиран биомедицински прочит на противоречивите политики, които променят живота на турската общност в България през сравнително слабо изследвания период на 1960-те години, скрити зад заетия от съветската теория и практика евфемистичен термин „културна революция“.

Никому неизвестният днес д-р Гани Ганев в края на 1960-те години се превръща за кратко в пропагандна „звезда“ на комунистическия режим в провеждането на „културната революция“ в с. Безводно, Кърджалийски окръг. За „образцовата“ му дейност са публикувани десетки репортажи и очеркови статии², на него е посветен и късометражният документален филм „Лекарят от село Безводно“ (1971, реж. Начо Папазов). В основата на изследването на случая с Гани Ганев³ е непубликуваният „дневник-повест“ (според

¹ Статията е подготвена в рамките на проект *Политически репресии над жени-мюсюлманки по време на комунистическия режим, женски мрежи на съпротива и гражданска реабилитация*, финансиран от Български фонд за жените, Програма „Ценности“ 2024, Договор № 24–PROP-000610/30.08.2024.

² „За мен и работата ми в Кърджалийски окръг бяха публикувани редица очерци: във вестник „Нов живот“, вестник „Здравен фронт“, вестник „Труд“, вестник „Йени ъшък“, сп. „Йени Хаят“ и „Поглед“.... Докато бях в Кърджалийски окръг написах стотици материали, които са публикувани във вестник „Нов живот“ и другаде...“ – пише Г. Ганев в писмото си до директора на архива в Кърджали през 1977 г. (ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 1, л. 3).

³ Гани Ганев (1928–1990), роден с. Блъсково, Варненско. Работил в периода 1961–1972 г. в селата Костино, Русалско и Безводно. Автор на книгата *Село Безводно в миналото и днес* (1969). Учи в Педагогическото училище в Шумен (1946), но прекъсва и заминава в Чехословакия по кампанията за набиране на земеделски работници. Там работи „като бригадир на немски момичета, чакащи изселване в Германия“ (Български бригадирски батальон „Клемент Готвалд“, 1946-1947), и в уранова мина – като ръководител на бригада от немски военнопленници (1948)“. По препоръка на Крум Кюлявков следва медицина в гр. Храдец Карлове (1948 до 1950) и в София (1951). След прекъсване и военна служба (сапърор и разузнавач, ст. лейтенант), през 1955 г. Г. Ганев подновява следването си във Висшия медицински институт в София и завършва медицина през ноември 1961 г. Според автобиографията му, той самият е пожелал да работи в Кърджалийски окръг. От януари 1962 до ноември 1972 г. завежда Общинската здравна служба в с. Безводно. След това е лекар във Варненската

литературната диагноза⁴ на неговия автор) в маломерния личен архивен фонд (частично постъпление) на Гани Ганев, съхраняван в Държавен архив – Кърджали.⁵ Написан в услужлив идеологически слог „Дневникът на един селски лекар“ е воден почти всекидневно от дипломирането на д-р Ганев в края на 1959 г. до 1965 г., когато, според него, завършва „битовата революция“ в с. Безводно.

Още докато е селски общински лекар (до 1972 г.) д-р Г. Ганев успява да напише и да публикува издадената от Националния съвет на Отечествения фронт многотиражна книга „Село Безводно в миналото и днес“ (1969), която дълго време е единствената публикувана история на селото и е представителна за пожелателния образ на партийно-политическата линия към турската общност в България през 1960-те г.⁶ През 2016 г. е публикувана и книгата на Реджеп Арифов⁷ „*Bezvodno-Ata diyarım /Безводно – земя на предците*“ – на турски и на български език (Arifov, 2016). В кратката глава, озаглавена „Тайната мисия на д-р Ганев“, той посочва: „Книгата за Безводно на д-р Ганев, написана през 1969 г. под диктата на тогавашното комунистическо правителство на Тодор Живков, включва и своя разказ за Безводно. Тогав поръчковият творчески проект получава много широка подкрепа от културните институции на социалистическата система, но не и от местните жители, които са объркани... Тази политика се основаваше на безпочвена идеология (Arifov, 2016, 123).

работническа болница. – ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 2, л. 1-6.

⁴ ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 2.

⁵ ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161. Фондът се състои от общо 4 архивни единици – кореспонденция между д-р Г. Ганев и директора на архива Т. Ингилизов по набирането на архивни документи и библиографски справки за публикациите на д-р Ганев (1974–1982) (15 листа); автобиография на Г. Ганев (1975) (6 листа); снимки (5 бр.); непубликуван ръкопис в машинопис „Дневник на селския лекар, 1959–1965“ (275 л.)

⁶ От кореспонденцията на д-р Ганев с директора на Държавния архив в Кърджали става ясно, че освен ръкописа на *Дневника на селския лекар*, той е подготвил и два романа – *Сините очи* (81 стр.), *Халиде* (94 стр.) и пиесата *Агрономката* (49 стр.). Тези книги съм писал докато бях в Родопите и действително им се развива в Кърджалийски окръг... Притежавам брошура „История на здравното дело село Безводно“, която възнамерявахме да издадем чрез Окръжен музей Кърджали, но така остана... – ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 1, л. 2.

⁷ Реджеб Ариф (1932–2022), роден село Кадънка (останало под водата на язовир „Боровица“). Учи в ардинското село Русалско, а по-късно в Медресето в Кърджали. През 1950 г. завършва Педагогическото училище в град Стара Загора. Дълги години, до пенсионирането си, е бил учител в различни населени места в областта, включително и в родното си село Кадънка и в с. Безводно.

Реджеп Арифов разказва алтернативната версия на събитията от този период – изселването на част от жителите на селото в Турция и във вътрешността на страната след кооперирането през 1959 г., идеологическият натиск над местните „партийни кадри“ и религиозни представители, режисирането на „преобличането“ на жените и на преименуването в „смесените“ бракове от селото и др. (Arifov, 2016)

Село Безводно се намира на раздела между източната и западната част на Родопите. Почти обезлюдено при насилственото изселване през 1989 г., в разпръснати по склоновете махали през последните години живеят по-малко от 30 души. През 1960-те години, когато д-р Ганев е общински лекар, в състава на Безводенски народен съвет са включени селата и махалите: с. Безводно, с. Кадънка, мах. Ряка, мах. Бозва, мах. Гоганлар, мах. Саръ кая, мах. Пъндък йеря, мах. Узун сърт и изселената махала Костан чеир (Ганев, 1969).⁸ Към 1962 г. в Безводно живеят 1620 жители⁹ – турци, чийто основен поминък е тютюнопроизводството и в по-малка степен – животновъдство (овце и кози, както и мулета и катъри за самарски превоз). Селото се намира в изолиран и труднодостъпен район – по това време без шосеен път – и пътуването до селото е по катърски пътеки през селата Комунига, Женда, Соколите и Ка-

⁸ През 1960-те години административно Безводенският народен съвет граничи със селата Горна сполука и Ненково от Русалски общински съвет; село Соколите от Комунигски съвет на Кърджалийски окръг; с. Три могили на Новаковски съвет от Пловдивски окръг; и селата Шарен нос, Рибен дол и Рибарка от Загражденски съвет на Смолянски окръг.

⁹ Според преброяването от 1946 г. жителите на селото са 1946 души, но при изселването на турците от 1951 г. две от махалите обезлюдяват, а след кооперирането част от жителите се изселват и към вътрешността на страната (Arifov, 2016). През м. март 1963 г. Гани Ганев предприема собствено „Преброяване на действителното живеещо население в района“ и го представя в *Дневника*. Според събраните от него данни в с. Безводно живеят 665 души, като са включени жителите на махалите Саръ кая и др. В с. Кадънка – 234 жители; махала Ряка – 116; в махалите Бозва и Гоганлар – общо 225 души. „В целия Безводенски съвет живеят 1200 души – с родените до края на 1963 г. Поради изселванията през есента на миналата година и в началото на тази, броят на населението е значително намален. В тези данни не са включени и учениците, които учат извън Безводно, студентите, войниците... Не са включени и изселените от района, но водени за жители на общината... Така, близо 260 души се водят за Безводенци, които от 6-7 години не живеят тук“ – ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 207.

дънка. По тая „тебеширена пътека“ разстоянието е 27 км. от свързаното със шосе с. Комунига.¹⁰ В *Дневника* на д-р Г. Ганев усилията му да се започне прокарването на път до Безводно (десетки писма до всички нива на партийната йерархия, вкл. и 3 писма до Тодор Живков), а после и за електрифицирането на селото, са изведени като водещи теми. Особен акцент в записките на доктора е и осъществяването на „културната революция“ (David-Fox, 1999; Fitzpatrick, 1999) – писанията на доктора могат да бъдат четени в най-голяма степен като показан опит за реализиране на партийните предписания по отношение на турската общност и по-специално по отношение на медикализиращия надзор над женските тела ... и умове.

Националкомунизмът като културната революция – политиките към турската общност в България, 1956–1971

Асимиляцията на мюсюлманските общности е процес, „възпалявал“ периодично политиките на различни режими на управление в България през XX век (Иванова 2020, 137). Историята на кампаниите за културна асимиляция по време на комунистическия период е сравнително добре документирана, хронизирана и изследвана, вкл. и ескалирането на проектите за религиозна и етническа хомогенизация и формирането на националната държава и нейните най-репресивни форми през 1980-те години (Вж. Аврамов, 2016; Груев, 2003, 2014; Груев и Калъонски, 2008; Neuburger, 2004; Иванова, 2002; Sygkelos, 2011; Lubanska, 2015; Erolova, 2025 и др.).

Когато на 9 септември 1944 г. доминираният от комунистите Отечествен фронт взема властта, в България живеят около 750 000 турци, предимно селско население, компактно населяващо югоизточните административни райони около Кърджали, Хасково, Стара Загора, Пловдив, Сливен и североизточните области Разград, Русе, Шумен, Търговище, Силистра, Добрич и Варна. След 1944 г. българското комунистическо управление привидно следва зададената от Москва доктрина за „пролетарския интернационализъм“, която изтъква *приоритета на класата над нацията* (Маринов, 2019; Иванова, 2020, 138). Конституцията от 1947 г. дава формално на *националните малцинства* правото на културно изразяване, образование и печат на собствен език. Паралелно с това и следвайки логиката на националната сигурност в контекста на

¹⁰ ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 16-18.

Студената война, комунистическата власт разселва принудително около десет хиляди помаци (и турци) от южната граница в други части на страната (Груев и Калъонски, 2003, 20-21). В началото на 1950-те години, когато в разгара на изселването към Турция над 155 000 турци, помаци и роми мюсюлмани напускат страната¹¹, съветската страна насочва българското ръководство към нов вектор на политиките спрямо турското население: „превъзпитание и включване в задачите на режима“ – по примера на съветския опит с „нацмен“ (съкращение от *национальное меньшинство*) на основата на признаване на националните особености („културна автономия“), стимулиране на културното и икономическото развитие и „активно участие на различните националности в изграждането на социализма“ (Волокитина, 2016, 353-254; Зафер, Муратова, 2022). Така, през 1950-те и частично през 1960-те години преобладават усилията за „спечелване“ на мюсюлманското население чрез активна „модернизаторска“ политика. Полагат се специални грижи за формирането на послушен местен партийен елит от турската общност. В същото време действа с нарастваща сила държавният атеистичен натиск (Назърска, 2022).

Постсталинисткото управление бележи отчетлив завой в посока заличаване на „културната автономия“ и поставя началото на серия от асимилационистки мерки, следващи етнонационалистическа логика и изместването от „интернационализъм“ към национализъм (от „класа към нация“), и към промяна на политиките към религиозните и етнически малцинства (Груев, 2014; Иванова, 2002; Маринов, 2009). След Ноемврийското решение на Политбюро на ЦК на БКП от 1956 г. за „издигането на политическото, културното и материално положение на българо-мохамеданското население“ в пропагандната реторика на управляващия режим, като „евфемизъм“ за политическата линия на принудително „приобщаване“ на мюсюлманското население в страната, се налага терминът *културна революция* – обобщаващ политиките за модернизация, насочени към ускоряване на съветизацията и изграждането на безкласово атеистично общество.¹²

¹¹ Въпреки че политическият режим представя изселването като доброволен акт, на практика то е инструмент в ръцете на режима за „национална“ хомогенизация чрез намаляване на дела на турското малцинство в общото население (Ivanov, Önsoy, 2022, 33; Зафер, 2021).

¹² В този контекст антирелигиозните кампании, провеждани от началото на комунистическия период, прерастват в „борба с исляма“. Чрез забранителния

Отначало привнесеният от съветските политики към малцинствата термин изглежда твърде абстрактен, но с течение на времето в тази дефиниция се включва приоритетно системата от мерки за премахването на традиционното облекло и свързаните с него традиции и начин на живот на мюсюлманите в страната. Това означава, че основният фокус на тези политики се оказват жените – неслучайно „разфереджаването“ и „преобличането“ се превръщат в дериват за резултатност на *културната революция* и на важни за режима външни белези на „комунистическата модерност“. Така, зад *културната революция* се скрива по-широк спектър от инструменти за насилствена асимилация и българизация на мюсюлманското население (Пашова, Муратова, 2023, 132; Ciddi, 2021).

На 4 октомври 1958 г. пленум на ЦК на БКП разглежда т. нар. „Тезиси за работата на партията сред турското население“¹³. Този документ очертава коренна промяна в политиката на „приобщаване“ – променят се нагласите за „преодоляването“ на националните, религиозните, езиковите и битовите особености на турската общност в България. Моментът едва ли е случайно избран, доколкото малко преди приемането на тезисите България е посетена от съветския партийен ръководител Н. Хрущов, а в Съветския съюз по това време се провежда политика на „русификация“ и реформа на училищното образование, която води, наред с другото, до ограничаване на преподаването на неруски езици, най-вече сред „нетитулярните общности“¹⁴ (Волокитина, 2016, 357-358).

С приемането на „Тезисите“ от 1958 г. следва цяла поредица от (официални и неогласени) решения и мерки до средата на 1960-те години: сливане на турските с българските училища и постепенно свеждане на майчиния език до избираем предмет; чистки сред учителите; свиване на броя и периодичността на турскоезичните издания – публичната употреба на турския език системно е ограничавана под претекст за *интегриране* на турското малцинство в българското общество (Хаджъ, 2022); настъпление срещу мюсюлманската религия и традиции, а атеистичната пропаганда

Закон за вероизповеданията от 1949 г. религиозните дейности на мюсюлманите са поставени под строгия контрол на Службата на Главното мюфтийство, която вече не е избираем, а бюрократичен, назначен от БКП, орган (Ivanov, Önsoy, 2022).

¹³ ЦДА, ф. 1Б, оп. 5, а.е. 353, л. 350-470.

¹⁴ За съветските политики към „нетитулярните общности“ в социалистически Азербайджан вж. Goff (2021).

громи "реакционната същност" на исляма (Ялъмов, 2002, 328-330; Воденичаров, 2011; Назърска, 2022).

През октомври 1961 г. на XXII конгрес на КПСС е приета нова *Програма* на съветската комунистическа партия, отразяваща разчетите за изграждане на комунистическо общество в Съветския съюз до 1980 г. В сферата на „националните отношения“ се очертава нов етап на заличаване на етнокултурните различия чрез „ускорено сближаване на националностите“ в отделните републики, за да се създадат предпоставки за създаване на нова „съветска социалистическа нация“ на основата на руския език. В светлината на изразеното намерение на КПСС за „интегриране и укрепване на световната социалистическа система в политическата, икономическата и културната сфера и за все по-голямо сближаване на социалистическите нации“, на конгреса е изказано предложение съюзниците от Източния блок да последват съветския пример. Българското партийно ръководство, вярно на блоковата дисциплина и заявявайки, че програмата на КПСС е и програма на БКП, поема курс към създаването на „единна комунистическа нация“ (Волокитина, 2016, 361). Тези промени в партийните политики се развиват на фона на първия опит за насилствено преименуване на помаците през 1964 г., приключил с временно отлагане на насилствени действия и известно смекчаване на курса. Като повратна в това отношение се пропагандира известната в онези години реч на Т. Живков в село Владимировци, Разградско, озаглавявана в партийно-просветната литература с идиличното „*Дружни и единни през вековете*“ (Груев, Калъонски, 2008, 113; Петров, П., М. Мюсюмов, 1966). В този дух се предприемат мерки и „за повишаване на жизненото равнище“, отново се обръща специално внимание на кадровата политика и „етническото“ представителство на различни нива, а и за кратко се организира отделът към ЦК *За работа с масовите организации и турското население* (1966–1968) (Ялъмов, 2022, 343-347).

През февруари 1969 г. се очертава нова ограничителна линия чрез решението на Политбюро „*За по-нататъшното подобряване на работата сред турското население и пълното му приобщаване към българския народ в борбата за социализъм и комунизъм*“.¹⁵ В началото на 1970-те години режимът на Т. Живков въвежда нови политики с трайни последици за малцинствата в страната, най-

¹⁵ ЦДА, ф. 1Б, оп. 35, 558 – Протокол № 84 от 25 февруари 1969 г. от заседание на Политбюро (ПБ) на ЦК на БКП.

важната от които е адаптирането на Брежневата теза за „единния съветски народ“ към българския случай – социалистическа държава с един народ и един език чрез премахване на отличителните белези на малцинствата (Стоянов, 1998, 143). Конституцията от 1971 г. кодифицира перспективите на хомогенизационния проект и за *гражданите от небългарски произход* поддържането на турска национална култура в България практически спира (Маринов, 2009). Първите жертви на асимилаторската политика през 1970-те години са помаците, а през следващите почти две десетилетия верига от политически реформи и събития води до ескалация на асимилационистките политики и към турците в България. Така, дори в периодите, когато официалният идеологически слоган е за *пролетарския интернационализъм*, при управлението на комунистическите режими от съветски тип (1944–1989 г.), същностната ендемична проекция е тази на *националкомунизма*.

(Про)съветските национални (био)политики и медицинската пропаганда: жените мюсюлманки като обект на „културната революция“

След 1956 г. политиките, насочени към националните малцинства в Съветския съюз скъсват окончателно с „утвърдителното действие“ – както Тери Мартин определя по-ранните съветски политики на *коренизация* (Martin, 2011)¹⁶. Постсталинистският контекст в СССР в сферата на езика и образованието утвърждава руската националистическа посока, заличава политиките на поне привидно национално различие, автономност и самоопределение, и задълбочава русификацията (Smith, 2017). Биомедицината също се оказва важен ключ в комплекса на *културната революция*. Така, въпросите за хигиената се оказват преплетени с „културните проблеми“ и държавния контрол, а здравно-санитарният дискурс в „социалистическото строителство“ се разглежда като безпроблемно партньорство в рамките на рускоцентричните политики към другите националности в съветската страна (Дергалова 1963; Goff, 2021).

¹⁶ Тери Мартин изследва съветската *коренизация* – политики за „подкрепа за формирането и развитието на малцинствени езици и култури“ (Martin, 2011, 9-27). В съветския случай на политиките на *коренизация*, както показва Юри Слезкин, често се изобретяват националности и се конструират „национални“ култури в контекста на новоформираните „етно-териториални единици“ (Slezkine, 1994).

В изследователските дискусии върху съветските *национални* политики към мюсюлманските общности в Кавказкия регион и в Централна Азия по време на сталинисткия период и след това, се откроява изследването на Пола Майкълс върху „медицинската пропаганда и културната революция“ в съветски Казахстан (Michaels 2000) като пример, илюстриращ политическия контекст на агресивното въвеждане на *биомедицината* – разбираана като важен сегмент на *културната революция*, която във всички региони се стреми да създаде общосъветска идентичност.¹⁷ Лишен от суеверия, от „новия съветски човек“ се очаква да вярва в способността на съветската държава и на комунистическата партия да доведат гражданите до по-високи нива на икономическо и културно развитие. Заедно с това медицинската дейност е съпровождана от постоянни атаки по отношение на традиционния начин на живот на съветските мюсюлмани, заклеявяван най-често като „религиозен фанатизъм“ и определян като основна причина за разпространението на социалните и инфекциозните болести. Ето защо здравните работници не само трябва да прилагат конкретно медицински знания, но и да се борят срещу „социалните условия“, които се смятат за „провокатори“ на тези болести. Както показва анализът на Майкълс, в казахстанския случай въпросите за хигиената се оказват тясно преплетени с културните въпроси, а „борбата с обичаите“ (обряждането, „негативните последици“ от постенето по време Рамазан, раждането в домовете и др.) се превръща в унищожителни политики за казахската традиционна култура и цели засилване на централизирания държавен контрол над региона (Michaels 2000). *Културната революция* се оказва не просто партийна политика за обща „модернизация на бита“, но цели и заличаването на различията в новото атеистично общество (Tokareva, 2024; Gross, 2018). След кратък период на облекчаване на отношението към религията по време на и непосредствено след Втората световна война, съветският режим подновява усилията си за изкореняване на исляма и следване на твърдите атеистични политики от 1954 г.¹⁸

¹⁷ Вж. Hoffmann (2014); Prozorov (2014).

¹⁸ Макар че тази кампания не е толкова агресивна, колкото болшевишката атака срещу религията през 1920-те и 1930-те години, режимът на Хрущов създава огромен функциониращ апарат за насърчаване на атеизма на всички нива на обществото (Abman, 2024, 130; Grossman, 1973, 383; Northrop, 2004). Вж. и Климович (1958). За късните съветски политики и антирелигиозните кампании вж. Martin, Beliakova (2024); Dudoignon, Noack (2011).

В книгата *Принудително освобождение: Мюсюлманките в Съветски Таджикистан* Зинаида Абман изследва методите и реториката на антирелигиозната кампания при управлението на Хрущов, която е насочена специално към жените в републиката, като тя разглежда и някои от последиците, които стават по-очевидни при режима на Брежнев (1964–1982) (Abman, 2024, 131). Както и при изследването на П. Майкълс, и тук се открояват фокусите на пропагандата в подкрепа на *биомедицината* в съветските периферии и се акцентира върху ролята на лекарите (Michaels, 2000, 59). Официозните биографии на „лекарите-герои“ от страниците на партийния печат – „осъществяващи самоотвержено“ *културната революция* – са толкова сходни и се разказват по толкова съгласуван начин, че създават образа на почти *архетипен герой*, чиято работа придобива почти митични измерения.¹⁹ Деконструкцията на мита за лекаря-герой в биомедицинската пропаганда предлага възможен ракурс към ролите и ценностите, пропагандирани от режима и отразяващи усилията му да предефинира нагласите и практиките сред мюсюлманската общност и в България – какъвто е случаят и с д-р Гани Ганев.

В своя анализ на мястото на жените в съветската система Мери Бъкли също припомня, че жените са ключов залог на *културната революция* (Buckley, 1989, 26), а и по-късните изследвания за „съветските“ мюсюлманки го потвърждават (Tohidi, 1998; Paert, 2004; Edgar, 2006; Kandiyoti, 2007; Kamp, 2011; Behzadi & Direnberger, 2020).

Със завършването на процеса на насилствена колективизация в България (за с. -Безводно това е 1959 г.), ежедневието на преобладаващо селската турска общност започва да се променя драстично. Заради кооперирането, относителната независимост на ежедневните жизнени навици на селяните се променя. В изследването си за турската общност в България Волфганг Хьопкен обяснява въздействието на тази промяна: „Колективизацията е не само посегателство върху собствеността на дребните селяни, но и оказва много по-голямо влияние върху ежедневието и обичаите на

¹⁹ В своето изследване на сталинистката литература Катерина Кларк нарича този архетип "положителен герой" (*positive hero*). Кларк определя положителния герой като „относително скромна фигура, ... но колкото и скромна да е той, биографията му символично пресъздава етапите на историческия прогрес, описани в марксистко-ленинската теория”(Clark, 1981, 49-50).

турците, отколкото на българите. Например включването на жените в трудовите бригади е в сериозно противоречие с тяхната традиционна роля. То било съзнателно използвано, за да разклати „консервативното поведение“ на турската общност“ (Hörken, 1997, 66). Освен създаването на колективни земеделски стопанства (ТКЗС), в рамките на един постепенен процес започват да се прилагат и много „социални реформи“. Кампаниите за разфереджаване са част от този комплекс от мерки. Анализирайки „разфереджаването“ на мюсюлманките в България, Мери Нойбъргър отбелязва съветския опит и прилагането му в българския случай: „Стремежът да се активизират мюсюлманите и особено „най-изостаналият“ елемент от тях – жените, да изпълняват първите петгодишни планове и да бъдат продуктивни в новите колективни стопанства, е съчетан с ограмотяване на турски и български език, за да се пропагандират догмите на новата държавна идеология. ОФ изпраща ... част от женотделите или женските секции в турските райони, за да изнасят лекции като „Турската жена – активен строител на социализма“, „Ислямът – реакционен враг на жените“, да водят курсове, да провеждат събрания и да организират комитети за привличане на мюсюлманките в работата на партията“ (Neuburger, 1997, 175). Централно място в тези политики се отрежда именно на жените, тъй като без тях е невъзможно да се овладее и промени „битът“ и нагласите на членовете на семействата, особено на подрастващите (*новото поколение*).²⁰

Изследвайки партийните политики към жените мюсюлманки, Нурие Муратова посочва, че те са „група, която е трудно да бъде контролирана, а същевременно е видима, заради „външните белези“ (Муратова, 2013). Тези жени в най-голяма степен се свързват от управляващите с религиозната „изостаналост“, а носенето на традиционно облекло е подложено на атаки с твърдението, че то е символ на „патриархално подчинение“ (Eminov, 1997, 58-59). Относително затвореният живот в техните общности, религиозността, която противоречи на официалната комунистическа идеология, както и естетическата конфронтация със социалистическия идеал за модерна жена, превръщат мюсюлманките в трудно контролируема група. Под лозунга за модернизация на мюсюлманките се прилагат различни административни „мероприятия“: специални курсове за „жени-активистки“, курсове за „битова култура“, мерки

²⁰ Вж. и Петров, Мюсюлюмов (1966); Юнузов (1980); Алиев (1980) и др.

за привличане на жените за членство в Комсомола и БКП (Муратова, 2013; Nahodilova, 2010). Както образно се изразява и Теа Хаджиристич: „Телата на мюсюлманките се превръщат в публична сцена не само за еманципацията на жените, но и за социализма, и всичко, което той обещава“ (Hadžiristić, 2017, 196).

Ключови „агенти“ за достигането до жените и тяхното всекидневие са преди всичко учителите и главно учителките. Учителките се оказват важни фигури за провеждането на политиката към жените, особено за ограмотяването, пропагандирането на „разфереджаването“ и модернизиранието на бита (Муратова, 2012; Попова 2021, 120). Важни задачи за провеждането на тези политики се възлагат и на лекарите (и акушерките). Именно в този фокус женското тяло се оказва важен символен терен, върху който се разиграват идеите и политиките на управляващите за прогрес и еманципация.

Дневникът на селският лекар – санитарното „разузнаване“ за женските тела, „битовата революция“ и „пътят“ в междуредието на партийното доктринерство

*„Този дневник е започнат на 21.11.1961 г. от деня на дипломирането ми и свършва на 1.09.1965. В него е записано всичко подробно през този период по дати. Според мен, той би заменил спомените ми за работата в Кърджалийския окръг през посочения период отлично. Даже възнамерявам да го предложа за публикуване“.*²¹ От уговорките на Гани Ганев личи преднамереността на водените в дневника бележки, а крайната дата на записките е показателна – според него тогава той завършва успешно „битовата революция“ в Безводно²², а заедно с това достига и до важен биографичен праг – след почти десетилетно отлагане, амбициозният Ганев става член на БКП.²³

²¹ ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 1, л. 2.

²² 5.07.1965: *Дали е необходимо да се пише по-нататък дневник. Струва ми се, че не ще бъде необходимо. Та дейността на здравните служители в района постигна онова, което се извършва в най-развитите здравни служби в страната. Вече дейността на здравната служба в района е равна на образцовите... Здравната служба в Безводно постигна онова, за което са се борили други здравни служби 30 години... (ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 271).*

²³ От 1955 г. Гани Ганев е кандидат-член на БКП, но през 1957 г. амбициозният студент е разочарован: *„отпаднах от кандидат-партийния състав поради*

В края на ноември 1961 г. току-що дипломираният лекар с журналистически амбиции пристига в Кърджали и настоява да бъде изпратен в някой от селските здравни участъци на окръга: *Не бе случайно, че при разпределението на нашия курс за работа пожелах Кърджалийски окръг. Зная, че в този окръг социализмът се строи по всички показатели на живота... културната революция в цялата страна... предизвикателството... Моето отиване в Кърджалийски окръг от едни се считаше за ‚вестникарска жертва‘, а от други – ‚лудост‘, ... ‚самозаточение‘.*²⁴

Първото му назначение е в с. Костино за около 2 месеца, а в самото начало на 1962 г. е пренасочен към с. Русалско. Там Ганев не успява да се сработи с фелдшера, акушерката и с „местните партийци“ и само след половин месец потегля по 15-километровата катърска пътека към с. Безводно.²⁵ Д-р Гани Ганев пристига в с. Безводно малко след приключването на кооперирането в селото и след първата вълна на административното „преобличане на жените“.²⁶ Част от Безводно по това време е и обезлюдено – една от махалите например е изцяло изселена в месеците преди идването му.

Още в началото на дневника докторът представя накратко историята на здравния участък в Безводно до неговото пристигане на 22.01.1962 г. Фелдшерският пункт в селото е открит през лятото на 1959 г. с първи назначен лекар д-р Иван Иванов – според информацията на Ганев – той „по наказание е понижен във фелдшер“ и работи в селото около 3 месеца. Малко по-дълго (от ноември

някакво решение на ГК на БКП в София за намаляване на интеллигентския състав на партията в столицата. През 1966 г., по предложение на ОК на БКП в Кърджали, е приет за член на БКП – Вж. ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 2, л. 5-6. В записките от дневника, обявявайки подпечатването на партийната му книжка, той патетично обявява: „И от 25 февруари 1965 г. съм в редовете на Партията. Отново в железните редици на Партията!“ – ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 268.

²⁴ ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 9-10.

²⁵ Пак там, л. 10-14.

²⁶ След някои опити от 1958 г., реализацията на планираната „културна революция“ започва през следващата година с т.нар. „разфереджаване“, т.е. насилствено премахване на традиционното облекло (фереджета, шамии, шалвари, фесове, кюляфи). Кампанията продължава през първата половина на 60-те години и в нея са обхванати не само помаците, но и турците, и другите мюсюлмански общности. Всъщност тя никога не приключва напълно, понеже всяко отслабване на административния натиск води до възстановяване на носенето на отличително облекло. Вж. Маринов (2009), Муратова (2010).

1959 до януари 1961 г.) в Безводно остава фелдшерът Вилхелм Евтимов. Според дневниковите записки, тогава са оборудвани фелдшерският пункт и родилният дом, и започват редовните прегледи, имунизации и реимунизации. Г. Ганев цитира и водената по това време статистика, като отбелязва високата детска смъртност. Новодошлият лекар на Безводно поема здравната служба от „новозавършилия“ д-р Хр. Цветански, който прекарва в селото точно една година, като по това време фелдшерският пункт е преобразуван в *Общинска здравна служба*.²⁷

При назначаването на д-р Г. Ганев здравната служба (от 1959 г.) се помещава в постройка от 1935 г. (първата административна сграда в селото), в която преди това се е помещавало кметството. Освен лекарският кабинет, там е подготвен и стационар с 5 болнични легла в 3 стаи. На 200 метра от здравната служба, в изоставена при изселническата вълна двуетажна къща, е оборудван и родилен дом (открит през 1960 г.). Към момента, в който д-р Ганев „поема службата“, там няма медицинска сестра, а последната акушерка е напуснала малко преди това. Той отбелязва, че за 1961 г. е имало едва 12 раждания в родилния дом и че „починалите две родилки през тази година оказват лошо влияние върху авторитета на здравната служба“.²⁸

30.01.1962. Направих БЦЖ на детето, което се роди на 28.01. Това е първото родено дете след идването ми в Безводно. Родил се у дома. Съобщиха ми на другия ден след раждането. Ходих в дома, направих му противотетаничен серум... Кръстих детето Вилдан...²⁹

08.02.1962. Тая сутрин втора бременна роди в дома си. Раждането бе укрито от мен. Съобщиха ми след като жената е родила. ... Предложих хоспитализация на родилката и новороденото, но близките категорично отказаха.³⁰

В следващите страници на *Дневника* буквалното преследване на бременните жени и „вкарването“ им в родилния дом е представено като най-съществена част от усилията на „образцовия“ лекар.

След почти 6-месечна кореспонденция и телефонни разго-

²⁷ ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 28-29.

²⁸ Пак там, л. 30. Малко по-късно и след няколко писма до Окръжния народен съвет да изпратят акушерка в селото, Гани Ганев отбелязва: „12.02.1962г. Няма изгледи в Безводно да се изпрати акушерка. Нямамо кадри, в окръга се чувствал голям недостиг от такива медицински работници...“ – Пак там, л. 42.

²⁹ Пак там, л. 33.

³⁰ Пак там, л. 38.

вори с Окръжния комитет на БКП в Кърджали и със Здравното министерство, в селото е командирована акушерка от окръжната болница.³¹ През февруари 1963 г. пристига и специално назначената акушерка – Юмю Х. от Момчилград, завършила акушерско образование в Пловдив през 1961 г. Докторът не се въздържа да екзотизира в записките си при описанието ѝ: „... черни очи и млечно-бяла кожа. От нея лъха югът и страстта на испанките“.³²

Рекапитулирайки първата си година в Безводно, д-р Ганев посочва, че са починали 2 деца от 35 родени през 1962 г., като само 7 от ражданията са в здравния център. Това, което той нарича „метод на активно издирване на болни, деца и възрастни“, е не просто всекидневно обхождане и проверки по къщите и организиране на здравни беседи (74 за 1962 г.³³), а и – по израза на доктора – мобилизиране на „санитарен актив за ранно откриване на бременни жени и раждане в родилния дом“. В женското „разузнаване“ към началото на 1963 г. той разработва „актив“ от 22 жени, които плътно да следят бъдещите родилки в селото:

Задачите им са следните. Жените обикновено си споделят дните за менструация, закъснението и т.н. Тия закъснения да ми се съобщават. Заедно с това да ми съобщават някои прояви в края на бременността. Например санитарният актив в последния месец ще наблюдава всеки ден дадена бременна: ако някоя сутрин бременната не отиде за вода или не се яви в двора – да ми се сигнализира за този факт. Заедно с това всички жени около бременната ги обвързвам в наше разузнаване. В това отношение ще използвам най-вече враждебно настроените към бременната – обикновено враждующите изнасят тайни от семействата на противниците си. С една дума: мощно разузнаване около бременните и вадене от домовете им, като с въдица и довеждане в родилния дом“.³⁴

Особено осъдителен е тонът по адрес на семействата на партийните функционери и служителите в селото: „жената на бригадира Ибрям Г., родила в дома, ще порицавам на български и турски език“ – посочва той, а заради раждането у дома на Мюмюня Ю.

³¹ Пак там, л. 108-109.

³² Пак там, л. 150.

³³ Пак там, л. 132.

³⁴ Пак там, л. 135.

заплашва да предложи за наказание съпруга ѝ – служител в общинския съвет.³⁵ С особено задоволство докторът описва, че в здравния дом е родила снахата на имама Реджеп Ф.³⁶

Месец след идването в Безводно, д-р Ганев започва и бурна „кореспондентска“ дейност. На 3 февруари 1962 г. той отбелязва изпращането на първата си дописка за вестник „Нов живот“ – очерк за високодобивника в тютюнопроизводството Салим И.³⁷ Въпросът за ражданията в селото докторът огласява в дописка в същия вестник от декември 1962 г., озаглавена „В плен на суеверието“.³⁸ В *Дневника* той отбелязва, че в статията си критикува конкретно и председателя на Селския общински народен съвет (СОНС) „за това, че другарката му е родила у дома, че дъщеря му е родила у дома“.³⁹ Напрежението между лекаря и представителите на местното ръководство очевидно ескалира – в дневниковите записки на няколко места той ги нарича „реакционери с партиен билет“.⁴⁰ Разразилият се малко по-късно конфликт за известно време е отложен, защото, само няколко дни след публикуването на статията, името на Гани Ганев „се чува“ в национален ефир – заради тежко раждане и невъзможното придвижване по затрупаната от снега катърска пътека, докторът „урежда“ (чрез първия секретар на БКП в Кърджали) в Безводно да пристигне „вертолет“ с лекар от София и да се извърши на място животоспасяваща операция. Въпреки очевидно спешната ситуация, на място успява да дойде и журналист – кореспондент от Кърджали и още същата вечер Радио София отразява подобаващо събитието. Докторът гордо отбелязва:

„Цяла България узна за героичния подвиг на нашите смели летци, за грижите на Партията и народното правителство, които полагат за турското население в нашата страна... Юнзиле С. бе спасена благодарение грижата и

³⁵ Пак там, л. 134.

³⁶ Пак там, л. 146-146.

³⁷ Пак там, л. 36. Докторът твърди, че само през 1962 г. подготвя, изпраща за публикуване „206 дописки и статии, от които 186 бяха поместени в окръжния и други вестници...“ (л. 133)

³⁸ Ганев, Г. (1962) В плен на суеверието. *Нов живот*, 01.12.1962.

³⁹ ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 131.

⁴⁰ Пак там, л. 121, 131. Сред стотиците статии и дописки на д-р Ганев през следващите години са публикувани и няколко в специализирания медицински печат. Вж. Ганев, Г. (1967) Проучвания върху раждаемостта сред жителите туркини и детската смъртност в района на здравната служба в с. Безводно, Кърджалийски окръг. *Акушерство и гинекология*, бр. 3, 272-276; Ганев, Г. (1969) Десет години здравна служба. *Здравен фронт*, бр. 19, 17 май, 1.

вниманието, което ни оказа др. Георги Петров, първия секретар...“⁴¹

Амбициозният „отличник в бяло“⁴² не се задоволява само с тясно медицинските аспекти на работата си в Безводно. Съдейки по размаха, прочетен в *Дневника*, той е амбициран да осъществи на практика в Безводно партийните директиви за „социалистическата културна революция“. През май 1963 г. той организира „седмица на съветското здравеопазване“⁴³, а месец по-късно представя специална програма за изграждане на „Здравна служба за комунистически труд“:

*Ще започнем колективно изучаване на решенията на Осмия конгрес на БКП... Ще изучаваме опита на челните здравни служби в България и в Съветския съюз, ще се изградим като нови и истински строители на новия живот.*⁴⁴

Още през 1962 г. Г. Ганев чертае амбициозен „План за Подобряване битовите условия на семействата от Безводненски съвет и хигиенизирае на района му 1962–1964 г. От записките в *Дневника* става ясно, че той е добре запознат с „челния“ опит – съветския азербайджански модел на т. нар. „Геокчайски опит“⁴⁵, приложен вече малко по-рано в България като „почина от с. Обнова“⁴⁶:

*Общественият характер на нашето здравеопазване намери своя конкретен израз в разгърналото се през последните 12 години всенародно движение за висока санитарна култура, за хигиенизиране, благоустрояване и озеленяване на населените места. Изучавайки и внедрявайки опита на Геокчаевския район на Азербайджанска ССР, това движение превърна и превръща нашите изостанали в миналото райони в благоустроени в санитарно-хигиенно отношение... Отзовавайки се на всичко това от 1962 г. насам в района на Безводненския съвет се извършиха големи мероприятия за подобряване на битовите условия на населението. Основна роля за това изигра приетия на сесия план за подобряване на битовите условия на населението от Безводненски съвет и полагане основите за изграждане Безводненски съвет образец като хигиеничен до 9.09.1964 г.*⁴⁷

⁴¹ ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 127-129.

⁴² Цитатът е от дописка с такова заглавие в „Нов живот“ (бр. 92, 29 август 1963).

⁴³ ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 159.

⁴⁴ Пак там, л. 173.

⁴⁵ Повече за ролята на „лекарят като възпитател“ и за здравните кампании в Съветски Азербайджан вж. Braun (2009: 135-138).

⁴⁶ ДА – Кърджали, ЧП 161, оп. 1, а.е. 4, л. 176.

⁴⁷ Пак там, л. 226.

Доктринерският проект за „битовата революция в с. Безводно“⁴⁸, ръководен от д-р Ганев, разбира се, е отразен подобаващо в партийните документи и във всички достъпни медии на регионално и национално равнище. Докторът подробно изброява и цитира в *Дневника* кореспонденцията си за набавянето на дефицитните стоки не само с окръжния партиен „актив“, а и с „отговорни другари“ на централно равнище⁴⁹. Той екзалтирано описва кервана от почти 150 катъра, натоварени с легла, тюфлеци, шкафчета, маси и столове, който се проточва между селата Комунига и Безводно на 18 юни 1962 г.: *За пръв път откакто съществува Безводно, както твърдят старците, толкова много катъри в един ден отиват в Комунига за стоки. Цялото село се насъбра да посреще и да гледа огромния керван, изпълнил 7-8 км.*⁵⁰ До края на 1964 г. д-р Ганев с гордост отчита, че табелки за “образцови и хигиенни домове” получават 56 къщи („1/3 от домовете в района“⁵¹). В записките си с почти маниакална скрупулозност той инвентаризира „битовата революция“:

*„През 1944 г. има 1 легло в селото... До края на юли 1965 г. – 432 легла пружинени, 7 спални и 11 детски легла. ... Но тия, които се изселиха, взеха със себе си и закупените си по нашия план легла... Дюшеци – 463 двойни и 145 единични; 325 кухненски шкафчета; 300 маси; 1860 столове; 125 готварски печки; 128 мивки; 141 радиоапарати; 68 шевни машини; 240 ламаринени корита; 672 одеяла... Не се изпълни само доставянето на гардероби – докараха само 2 и с голяма трудност ги продадохме. Не се изпълни и планът с банята – не можяхме с катъри да извозим казаните“.*⁵²

Режисираната от доктора локална „културна революция“ се оказва само една от насоките в мащабните му намерения. Още през 1962 г. той решава, че Безводно може да се свърже със шосеен път, и че именно той е човекът, който може да осъществи този амбициозен план. Започва дълга преписка между него, Окръжния народен

⁴⁸ Пак там, л. 31.

⁴⁹ В *Дневника* Ганев публикува и писмото си изпратено до министъра на вътрешната търговия Пeko Таков за намирането и доставянето в с. Безводно на легла, шкафове, гардероби и др. – Пак там, л. 252, 260.

⁵⁰ Пак там, л. 86. Д-р Ганев не пропуска да изброи докараното с „кервана“: „От информацията на магазинера докарани и продадени са 160 легла – пружинени от персон и половина, 180 тюфлеци, 120 шкафчета, 86 маси, 340 стола, 1250 вилици, 1250 лъжици, 600 чинии, 80 одеяла, 50 юргани, 220 чаршафа и др.“ – Пак там, л. 99.

⁵¹ Пак там, л. 102.

⁵² Пак там, л. 264.

съвет, Министерския съвет и Държавния комитет по планиране. Докторът с нескрита гордост „споделя“ в дневника и трите пространни писма (1962, 1963 и 1964 г.), които изпраща и до Тодор Живков. Пътят наистина влиза в държавното планиране и започва неговото трасиране още докато д-р Ганев е в Безводно, но остава под въпрос дали това е показан резултат конкретно от неговите усилия, или намеренията му следват заложените вече държавно-партийни политики за региона.⁵³

Още в първите месеци на престоя си в Безводно д-р Гани Ганев се опитва буквално да „кадрува“ в общината като главен „модернизатор“. Всяко изразено несъгласие или недоволство от представителите на местната администрация е следвано от оплаквания (някои са откровени доноси) за качествата им, които той изпраща към по-високите партийни инстанции, а и дословно пренася в *Дневника*. В записките си, след като „се е опознал“ с местните ръководители, той дава кратки биографични данни за всеки от тях – в жанр, напомнящ по-скоро „оперативна“ служебна характеристика, като в края оценките варират от „отърсен от мюсюлманската изостаналост и школуван комунист“⁵⁴ до „реакционер с партиен билет“⁵⁵ или „неграмотен догматик“⁵⁶. През февруари 1964 г. д-р Ганев присъства и активно насочва директната чистка и дирижирана смяна на ръководствата в Общинския партийен комитет, Общинския народен съвет и ТКЗС, проведена в присъствието на Зиа Харунов от ОК на БКП – Кърджали.⁵⁷

„Докторът от Безводно“ в преднамерените си дневникови записки регистрира грижливо и друга открояваща се линия, свързана преди всичко с жените в селото. Още при първото лекарско обхождане на къщите в общината през февруари 1962 г., д-р Ганев отбелязва, че част от снахите в селото са от съседните помашки села и угоднически адаптира наблюденията си към „пулса“ на партийно предписаните трактовки:

Населението от Безводненски съвет е от турска народност. То говори турски, изповядва мюсюлманска религия. Наред с това обаче и в самото население има запазени черти от чисто славянски характер: свободолобивият дух, чистосърдечие, с което посрещат външни

⁵³ Пак там, л. 155, 189, 257-258 и др.

⁵⁴ Пак там, л. 65.

⁵⁵ Пак там, л. 121.

⁵⁶ Пак там, л. 191.

⁵⁷ Пак там, л. 192-195.

лица, безграничното гостоприемство. Наред с това, правят впечатление и личните външни характерни черти на местните хора, които са специфични за славяните: бяла кожа, руси коси и вежди и др. ... По-голямата част от населението на Безводенски съвет е с такива външни черти, които по нищо не се отличават от българомохамеданите например от съседното село Рибен дол. Наред с това, в района на Съвета има много стари и млади жени, които са чисти българомохамеданки и говорят български език. Някои семейства имат роднини – българи от Пловдивски окръг, с които още се родяват. Всички тия неща показват, че населението от този съвет, макар в днешния си вид да се нарича турци и да живее по турски, то е потомък на потурчените Българи от Родопа.⁵⁸

Всички жени мюсюлманки, говорещи български език от махалите на Безводно, подробно и поименно са представени от доктора в перфидни изчисления и формули за процентна „българскост“ на семействата:

26.02.1962. Вчера в 18.00 дойде при мен Салих М. от махала Гоганлар. Той ми съобщи, че майка му е тежко болна и ме помоли да отида да я прегледам... Зекия – болна след грип – с пневмония... Заговори ме на български – българомохамеданка... Горе лежаха болни двете деца на Салих. Лежеше болна и снаха му Азизе. В семейството се говореше само на турски... Децата въобще не знаят български... Та защо децата на тази стопроцентова българка да се считат само за турци?...

От 16-те къщи, в които влязох в Гоганлар, в 9 от тях майката е българка /българомохамеданка/. Та, 50 на 100 в тия 9 къщи по майчина линия са българи?! Не е ли време тия хора да осъзнаят българския си произход?... Престъпно е в годините на народната власт, в годините на свободата, да се затрива от паметта на децата българския произход на майките им и бабите им, да се потурчват и днес тия българчета и българки... Сигурно тия българомохамеданки ги пишат в паспортите туркини. Това ще бъде повече от жестоко. По такъв начин се узаконява официално потурчването тия българки!...

В Гоганлар има и такъв случай. Исуф Д. по майка е българин, неговата жена Асиле е също българка. При това положение децата на тия двама души се водят турци. Та това е съвсем неправилно. От кръстосването те 75 на 100 са българи...

Може би като се прочете дневника ми за деня, ще се остане с впечатлението, че проявявам национализъм. Не бих желал да се помисли така от никого. ...Нима ние, които сме тук и народната власт трябва да се намеси в тази историческа неправда, намираща и днес форма на потурчване? Нима това трябва да се премълчава, трябва да се търпи?⁵⁹

Тези наблюдения, макар и в някои по-омекотени формули-

⁵⁸ Пак там, л. 48-49.

⁵⁹ Пак там, 55-57.

ровки, д-р Ганев споделя и в третото писмо, което изпраща до Тодор Живков в края на февруари 1965 г. Макар официалният повод за писмото да е отново въпросът за прокарването на пътя, набраният визионерско самочувствие лекар-графоман (по неговите думи към онзи момент – автор на хиляди „дописки“) прилага и допълнителни материали (с копие до ЦК на БКП), озаглавени от него „*Някои мисли по въпроса за турското население в България*“. Представяйки се като експерт, който е „в непосредствен контакт с турците и живея и работя с тях“ – Г. Ганев предлага на висшето партийно ръководство конкретни съвети за калибриране на партийната линия към турската общност в страната и конкретно в Кърджалийски окръг.⁶⁰ След като „споделя“ в *Дневника* писмото и *Мислите*, докторът обещава да „помести“ отговора, когато го получи, но до края на записките такъв не се появява.

В следващите бележки Ганев прави утвърдителна ретроспекция на проведената от него *санитарна и културна революция* в Безводно, а малко по-късно обявява, че ще приключва дневника си:

5.07.1965: Дали е необходимо да се пише по-нататък дневник. Струва ми се, че не ще бъде необходимо. Та дейността на здравните служители в района постигна онова, което се извършва в най-развитите здравни служби в страната. Вече дейността на здравната служба в района е равна на образцовите... постигна онова, за което са се борили други здравни служби 30 години...⁶¹

Съществена част от дневниковите записки на д-р Ганев могат да бъдат прочетени в публикуваната му като привидно краеведско изследване книга *Село Безводно в миналото и днес* (Ганев, 1969) – „поръчков творчески проект“, както го определя по-късно репресираният през 1980-те години местен жител – бивш партийен секретар и учител в Безводно – Реджеп Арифов в неговата версия на случилото се с хората в селото през този период (Arifov, 2016: 123).

Заклучение

Случаят с д-р Гани Ганев показва как „културната революция“ от 1960-те години се разгръща не като абстрактна идеологическа програма, а като дълбоко инвазивен, ежедневен и персонализиран режим на *биовласт*.⁶² Лекарят в мюсюлманските села е

⁶⁰ Пак там, л. 200-206.

⁶¹ Пак там, л. 271.

⁶² *Биовластта* се проявява там, където има политическо използване на човешкото тяло в контекста на надзор, обучение, наказание и пр.; „биовластта“

едновременно лечител, администратор, идеологически кадър и дисциплиниращ агент. Трите му функции – медицинска, политическа и административна – се преплитат и произвеждат мощен властови ефект: достъп до интимното, ревизия на културната норма и участие в контролиращите доктринерски механизми. *Дневникът* на Г. Ганев е рядък пример на документ от изследвания период, показващ как биополитиката се разгръща „в действие“ – със специфичен език, стратегии и методи.

Фиксацията върху женските тела не е случайна. Жените и поспециално женските тела се превръщат в основен терен, върху който се упражнява държавната власт – през раждането, през „разузнаването“ на бременните, през атаките срещу традиционното облекло, религиозните практики и семейните роли.⁶³ Ганев създава истинска мрежа за санитарно следене – стратегия не само медицинска, а откровено политическа. Тя става възможна именно защото медицинската професия придава в конкретните контексти и легитимност на иначе дълбоко насилствени интервенции.

Преднамереното изброяване на „смесените“ бракове, поименното проследяване на помашки снахи и аритметиките на „процентна българскост“ показват не визионерство, а амбициозна лоялност към държавната линия. Тези наблюдения не остават изолирани – десетилетие по-късно именно подобни „родословни“ операции стават инструмент на официализираната асимилационна политика от 1980-те години. Така дневникът на Ганев не е просто личен документ, а ранен протокол на бъдещи репресивни практики.

„Геокчайският опит“ и неговото локално приложение в Безводно показват мащаба на идеологическия трансфер между СССР и България: не само политики, но и методи, език, логика на действие. В този смисъл случаят на Ганев е уникален, защото е единственият подробно документиран опит за трансплантация на съветски биополитически модели в микромащаба на едно родопско село.

В крайна сметка, зад пропагандната фигура на „лекаря-герой“ прозира дисциплиниращият режим на *националкомунизма* – власт, която се стреми да прекрои общността и буквално през телата на жените, през интимното, през ежедневието. *Дневникът* не

се упражнява чрез регулиране на живота – здраве, хигиена, възпроизводство, раждаемост, норми на поведение (Фуко, 1993).

⁶³ Никъде в *Дневника* д-р Ганев не споменава да следи, да брой или да порицава обрязването през този период.

показва промяна „отдолу“, а инженерство „отгоре“, което използва медицината като технология на властта. Той свидетелства за едно ранно, агресивно и целенасочено навлизане в частния живот на мюсюлманските семейства – предвестник на онези асимилационни политики, които ще се разгърнат в пълния си мащаб през 1980-те години.

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Iliina Marinova

Department of Anthropology, New Bulgaria University, Sofia
[ilieva.ilina@gmail.com], ORCID ID: 0009-0008-8397-6178

Industrial Heritage without Memory: The Cotton Factory of Varna between Past and Redevelopment

Abstract: *This article examines why one of Varna's largest pre-socialist buildings – the Cotton Factory – remains materially intact while its industrial past has largely disappeared from public memory. Drawing on site observation, archival fragments, interviews and online discussions, the study identifies a set of mechanisms through which memory erodes: fragmented sensory recollection, low occupational prestige, institutional opacity, shifting moral regimes after 1944 and 1989, urban discontinuity, spatial distancing and the emergence of neighbourhood myths. These forces converge, producing a durable silence around the factory's social world. At the same time, certain residual attachments – belonging, aesthetic recognition and projected cultural aspirations – continue to anchor the building in collective imagination. The factory persists as a material form whose past cannot be fully narrated yet has not been culturally concluded.*

Keywords: *industrial heritage; collective memory; institutional opacity; labour history; urban transformation; silence and forgetting; Varna (Bulgaria).*

Introduction

My first visit to the Cotton Factory yard called up memories I had not expected. As a child, I sometimes accompanied my father to the metal-working plant where he spent the largest part of his working life. The hall was loud, the machines struck metal with sharp concussive blows, and workers moved around them with the quick, practiced gestures of people who knew exactly what each sound meant. They had protective headphones but rarely used them because they interfered with the work. I remember the heat, the scattered offcuts of steel they handed me to play with, and the way the yard looked disordered only to an outsider; inside that apparent disorder every object had a purpose.

That memory shaped how I saw the Cotton Factory – a large brick complex dating from 1899, later known as “Prince Boris,” “Tsar Boris,” and after 1943 “Hristo Botev.” In its abandonment, with machines removed and floors cleared, the spatial logic of industry was still visible:

the long sheds, the rhythm of openings, the traces of circulation. The yard, though partly overgrown and partly rearranged, had the same industrial feel I recognised from childhood, the same sense of a place once full of movement and noise. Just like the plant where my father worked, where personal stories existed even if not told, here the stories rarely surfaced at all.

Across conversations, people recalled the oldest building easily – its size, its importance, its place in the city – yet denied to recall its industrial life. The factory had been one of Varna’s major cotton industry workplaces for more than a century, employing thousands and shaping the life of the surrounding neighbourhood. Its architecture remains prominent, and its fate is regularly discussed, but memories of daily work are fragmentary or absent.

This contrast sets the question guiding the article: how did a factory so large and long-standing become a place where the building is remembered but the labour is not?

Theoretical Background

Collective memory depends on social anchors that stabilise experience and make it narratable. Connerton’s distinction between embodied and narrative memory is useful here: practices may leave vivid bodily traces yet fail to become stories when not supported by durable social forms (Connerton, 1989, 2008). In the Cotton Factory, the socialist period maintained a dense ritual life, but these practices did not translate into labour narratives that survived after 1989. The disappearance of commemorative structures left embodied knowledge without the institutional supports needed for transmission.

Mary Douglas’s account of institutional thinking provides a complementary frame. Institutions preserve classificatory forms rather than historical content and generate “shadowed zones” in which certain questions cannot be asked (Douglas, 1986). Their memory is periodically reset through generational turnover, overwriting earlier information while structural categories remain intact. This clarifies how forgetting can arise not from cognitive loss but from routine organisational operations and shifting moral orders. In Varna, ownership opacity, bureaucratic fragmentation and political reclassification created a zone in which the factory’s history became increasingly difficult to articulate.

Halbwachs likewise notes that memory becomes narrative only when linked to stable social figures or purposes (Halbwachs, 1992). In the Cotton Factory, such anchors were either absent or later disrupted.

Taken together, these perspectives situate the Varna case within broader discussions of how institutions shape what is remembered, what becomes unsayable, and how material forms may endure even as the labour that created them recedes from collective account.

Methods

This study uses a small qualitative dataset combining interviews, site observation, archival sources, public discourse and a publicly accessible Facebook discussion about the Cotton Factory. Nine semi-structured interviews were conducted with former workers, neighbourhood residents, a local historian and a municipal employee. They lasted 15–30 minutes and were recorded with consent or documented in notes. Questions addressed work routines, production knowledge and perceptions of the factory's role in the neighbourhood. Transcriptions were read closely, with attention to wording and small self-corrections. No formal interactional analysis was performed. Interviews were conducted jointly by the author and two student researchers. All participants are anonymous.

Fieldwork included two site visits of six to seven hours each. Notes recorded building condition, material traces, circulation patterns and the sensory environment. A basic phenomenological protocol documented what was perceptually available, supported by photographs.

Archival and media materials (approx. twenty items) were collected from library holdings and regional press, providing indicative snapshots of public discourse. They were catalogued by type and date and used according to institutional regulations.

The researcher's background includes familiarity with industrial environments due to childhood proximity to factory labour. This is noted solely as positional information. The memory mentioned in the Introduction served as an initial orientation to spatial cues but was not used as data.

Data handling relied on close reading, phenomenological site description, micro-hermeneutic attention to wording in interviews and documents, and basic multi-scalar organisation of materials.

Positionality

As a researcher arriving from the capital and working within an unfamiliar local framework, my role could be interpreted as structurally privileged: I defined the questions and their purpose. Participants were

informed that their accounts would be anonymised and used for research, yet the act of being recorded can heighten awareness of possible misuse. This, together with the presence of a three-person team, may have increased the sense of intrusion and contributed to the cautious, abbreviated responses. The fieldwork took place within a summer school on urban memory and industrial heritage, and the focus on the building's aesthetic value was likely preferred by participants because it provided the safest, most neutral ground.

Limitations

The study relies on a small and heterogeneous dataset. Access to former workers was constrained by time and by the absence of a stable local network, restricting opportunities for follow-up conversations and depth of narrative material. Archival coverage remains uneven and reflects the survival of documents rather than comprehensive extraction. These constraints shape the analysis: the study identifies the mechanisms through which memory is reduced, reorganised or displaced, rather than attempting a full social history of the factory.

Genealogy of the Cotton Factory in Varna (1896–1944)

Varna's cotton-spinning complex emerged alongside the city's industrial consolidation at the turn of the twentieth century. After the Liberation Varna port became the principal commercial gateway of the Principality, and the 1894 Law for Encouraging Local Industry accelerated the formation of joint-stock enterprises. Within this context, the concession for a large cotton-spinning factory was granted in 1896 to several Varna entrepreneurs, who soon transferred it to the Manchester-based *National Cotton Spinning Company of Bulgaria Ltd* (Denkov, 2024).

The Varna project was the lone success in a period when most Bulgarian attempts to establish cotton-textile enterprises collapsed before opening. Initiatives in Kyustendil, Kazanlak and Sliven stalled for lack of capital or failed in negotiations. Preparation in Varna took five years, during which several Bulgarian initiators went bankrupt – a measure of the venture's scale and fragility before foreign financing arrived (Ivanov, 2021).

The enterprise was registered as the “First Bulgarian Anonymous Privileged Company for Cotton Yarns ‘Prince Boris’,” with a capital of 1,500,000 leva, two-thirds held by English shareholders. Popova (2019)

notes that the site next to the Old Railway Station was chosen to optimise logistics for imported cotton. The municipality provided the land under the industrial-encouragement statute. Production began in January 1899, when the first factory whistle was heard in the city. At opening, the factory had 8,000 spindles, increasing to 11,400 in 1900 and 15,600 by 1908.

Photo 1. The Cotton Factory in Varna, early 20th century. *Postcard showing Varna residents in front of the cotton-spinning factory “Knyaz Boris,” photographed from the lakeside.*

Ivanov (2021) notes an early public-relations effort aimed at countering rumours of immoral behaviour by the English owner toward local girl-workers. Sponsored articles and an explanatory brochure attempted to stabilise public opinion and protect the company’s standing.

The first detailed account of labour relations appears in June 1902: a strike of more than six hundred workers from both shifts, with twelve-hour workdays, employment of children aged eight to fifteen, workplace accidents, routine fines and a printed declaration of new conditions that workers refused to sign (Izvestnik, 1902). This is one of the few pre-war accounts of internal labour relations identified during the research.

Contemporary surveys show that by 1910–1912 Varna had become Bulgaria’s principal cotton-textile centre, with almost ninety per

cent of the national workforce located in the region; compared to other Bulgarian textile enterprises, which averaged fewer than fifty workers, the Varna factory operated on an exceptional scale (Popova, 2019). Production remained below expectations, and imported yarn from İzmir, Lesbos and Britain was consistently cheaper, limiting the factory's ability to dominate the domestic market despite its scale (Ivanov, 2021).

During the First World War, textile production in Varna contracted sharply due to reliance on imported cotton. In 1915 the English owners closed the factory, described as the most serious industrial loss for the city during the war years.

A decade later, a municipal publication from May 1925 reported that the factory at the Old Station would be reactivated by a new Italian company led by Mr. Geller, which had acquired the rights of the former English owners. The factory reopened as "Tsar Boris," an Italian–Bulgarian joint-stock company with a capital of ten million leva; in 1929 the capital was increased to twenty million leva during further modernisation. Archival newspapers record several public appearances of the factory during this period. Denkov notes that the enterprise expanded despite the global economic crisis, reaching its highest output by 1939.

After Bulgaria's accession to the Tripartite Pact, the principal shareholders, Jacques and Rafael Suzan, were compelled to sell their involvement to the newly formed company "Kotonia" (Dekov, 2024). The factory subsequently entered state ownership due to financial difficulties. In 1943 its name was changed to "Hristo Botev." The last documented event in the archival material is a workers' assembly on 21 September 1944, at which an Otechestven Front committee was elected (Byuletin na grad Varna, 1944).

Findings

Only the original brick building of the factory from 1899 carries architectural or historical value and is protected today. It is designed by the architect Dabko Dabkov, and classified as an immovable architectural heritage object (National Institute for Immovable Cultural Heritage, n.d.). The rest of the complex was built incrementally – before and after 1944 – with different materials, styles, and functional intentions. These additions do not form a coherent architectural ensemble.

Photo 2. Aerial view of the Cotton Factory complex, Varna (2020). *Source: varnaheritage.com, declared NKC register.*

The region of Cotton Factory is fairly distant from the centre of Varna. Its terrain is currently accessible from several entry points, including two upper gates that lead into internal streets lined with red brick buildings, providing space for workshops, storage rooms, and warehouses. The terrain accommodates small businesses, storage activities, and occasional creative uses: artistic workshops and exhibitions. During field visits, an upholstery workshop, a screen-printing shop, a frame shop, car washes, and informal parking were visited. Facades show cracks, plant growth, and signs of abandonment. Tenants reported repairing leaking roofs and maintaining their own interiors, as the owner does not provide upkeep. New construction was visible near the administrative building, where foundations for a multi-storey residential block were being laid. A large vinyl print of the new building with a phone number was hanging on the fence.

A mosaic bust of Hristo Botev stands on its original pedestal near a row of small commercial units inside the former cotton factory yard. The monument remains unmarked and partially surrounded by improvised fencing and construction debris, reflecting the site's current use.

Municipal staff started negotiations with the owners to relocate the monument for preservation, as reported in the local press (chernomore.bg, 2025).

Photo 3. Hristo Botev bust in the factory yard. *Photograph by the author.*

Public recollections of the factory varied to a significant extent. Some people recognised it only as “Hristo Botev” and described it as an old cotton plant associated mainly with women’s work. Several respondents mentioned the English origin of the red bricks and their durability. A few recalled the factory as noisy and full of machinery, while others said they knew almost nothing about it beyond its physical presence in the city. Some described large workforces in the past, estimating that thousands of workers were employed, while others remembered only that relatives had worked there briefly. A number of people noted the existence of nearby worker housing or referred to a “Cotton Quarter,” though few provided precise details and I couldn’t confirm which buildings belonged to it. In the interviews available recollections of the factory’s closure were inconsistent, with dates ranging from the early 1990s to around 2000.

Tenants and regular visitors of the site described specific parts of the complex and their own histories within it. One tenant with decades of experience in the buildings described the administrative block, the chimney, the former foundry, and an underground reservoir, as well as a period when mineral water at approximately 27° flowed through indoor pipes. Others referred to discarded machinery, scrapped looms, and features that had once included communal baths or ornate railings. One tenant pointed out that people now come to the oldest red-brick façade for photoshoots because of its distinctive appearance.

Accounts from childhood or family memories added further descriptive details. One woman recalled visiting her mother in the factory as a child and hearing the constant noise of machines. Several people described a kindergarten associated with the factory, remembered variously as weekly or overnight, serving families who worked in three shifts.

A municipal cultural official explained that the city does not have authority over privately owned industrial buildings and cannot require preservation or cultural reuse. She stated that she did not know the detailed ownership of the Cotton Factory and that it is hard to check. She referred to general difficulties associated with protecting older buildings in Varna, including long administrative procedures, restoration costs, and limited specialist capacity. Across all sources, references to owners, heirs, or past directors are usually inconsistent.

Most interviewees didn't respond to questions about the work organisation, ownership, or the socialist period, responses contracted into short formulas. Examples included repeated responses like "*I don't know*" and "*I can't say*" from former workers when asked about leadership, or the life of the factory. In one interview, the respondent stopped almost every line of inquiry with statements such as "*No, not really*" and "*I don't remember*" even when she had worked in the factory for years.

Topic-shifting was frequent. When asked about how the factory functioned, one participant redirected the conversation toward childhood memories, the smell from a baking factory, or the kindergarten, without answering the original question. Another moved from a question about the production process to a general comment about having "*worked a lot*" and therefore having "no memories" ("*they had no memories because they worked a lot*").

Analysis: The layers of forgetting

Cognitive fragmentation: memory reduced to sensory traces

Conversations with former workers and residents show that one layer of forgetting is the fragmentation of memory. People do not describe the factory's purpose, production flow or interactions among workers. This pattern recurs across interviews. One Facebook user recalls the overwhelming noise: "*Inside, from the noise of the spindles you couldn't hear anything, even if someone shouted right in your ear. I don't know how they endured it.*" A respondent remembers entering the factory as a child, but nothing beyond the sound. A woman who grew up in the neighbourhood recalls the atmosphere but not the structure or routine. Another respondent who worked as a cashier for years summarises her experience in a single line: "*most of the time I spent inside with the workers,*" without connecting these fragments into a sequence.

Comparative studies of cotton mills in Britain and the United States show that operatives worked amid heat, humidity, dust, vibrations and constant machine noise; they often relied on lip-reading when conversation was impossible (Greenlees 2007). Although drawn from other contexts, these findings highlight how technical organisation routinely produced sensory pressure that confined memory to bodily experience. The sensory intensity reinforced the separation between what workers did and what they could later narrate.

Another aspect of this fragmentation is that respondents knew only incidentally who supplied the cotton, who graded or transported it, or who used the finished thread. This horizontal facelessness reflects a basic level of cognitive deprivation: the production sequence survives as a technical outline, while the people who supplied raw material or used the product remain invisible.

In this sense, the Cotton Factory resembles other industrial settings. This first form of forgetting appears as memory reduced to disconnected sensory traces. It forms the base layer of the broader forgetting process described in the following sections.

Spatial stigma and boundary silence

The Cotton Factory stands at the edge of Maksuda, Varna's Roma neighbourhood, and this proximity also shapes how the place is spoken about. Historical sources indicate that the neighbourhood of Maksuda

had longstanding informal settlement patterns, with Roma residents occupying the area without legal status already before 1913 (Varnenski obshtinski vestnik, 1913).

One real-estate editorial from 2008 frames the ruins of the “Hristo Botev” factory and the adjacent Maksuda neighbourhood as obstacles to Varna’s “*European future*”, describing the area as the “*ugliest*” and most undesirable part of the city and proposing its complete erasure to enable redevelopment (Tonchev 2008). This discourse situates the factory not as heritage, but as a spatial problem inseparable from the stigmatization of the neighbourhood.

Several respondents mention the area directly, describing it as “*the Roma quarter*” and calling it “*unattractive*” or undesirable for investment. One interviewee states that many families “*sold their houses for almost nothing*” when Roma households “*were moving towards them,*” framing the neighbourhood as a source of social and economic retreat. Another notes that “*no Bulgarian would buy property in the Roma quarter,*” linking the factory’s location to a wider reluctance to engage with the area.

The same pattern appears in public comments. Participants in an online discussion describe the area as “*close to Maksuda*” and therefore “*unappealing,*” suggesting that the building’s environment is reason enough for its neglect.

These observations point to a consistent dynamic: the stigma attached to Maksuda extends to the factory’s immediate surroundings and affects how people describe their relation to the place. Spatial context becomes a factor in what is remembered, what is spoken, and what remains unaddressed.

Community status and public positioning

The early archival materials position the factory’s workforce within a clear social hierarchy. Newspaper articles and notes from the first half of the twentieth century show a contrast between the factory’s economic importance and the low status of its workforce. In 1902, workers are described as coming from “*very poor families*” and standing on “*a very low cultural level*” (Izvestnik, 1902), marking them as marginal within Varna’s social landscape. Municipal appeals from the 1920s call on the public to support the factory’s reopening because of its regional significance, yet mention workers only as an anonymous category whose employment must be secured (Politicheski izvestiya, 1924). Interwar reports present awards, exhibitions and production

quality, but never the people who produced them (Varnenski okrazhen vestnik, 1926; Slavyanin, 1931). Workers appear as a category, not as individuals.

This marginal status partly explains the limited testimony from the socialist and current period. Several respondents avoid extended descriptions of factory life and speak about their work in minimal terms. Some respondents note Varna's social stratification, remarking that certain professions were not considered suitable for "*Varnenets nobility*." Another, when asked if her mother could give an interview, interrupted herself with the unfinished sentence "*She can't know, she would never communicate with such...*," accompanied by visible discomfort. A long-serving worker called the "*biggest event*" in her factory life not any change in the enterprise itself, but completing her education and moving from the production hall to accounting.

Such remarks frame textile work as low-prestige and help explain why it did not accumulate a narrative tradition: it was necessary yet socially undervalued. The result is a consistent historical and contemporary configuration in which the factory is publicly visible, while the status of its workers implies that their stories remain largely unspoken.

Perceived leaderlessness and dispossession without an agent

The historical accounts of Varna's textile sector show clearly identifiable entrepreneurial figures such as Asen Nikolov, whose business trajectory, family background, investments and factory expansions are documented across the interwar period. His role appears with names, dates, capital figures and specific initiatives.

In contrast, the Cotton Factory's owners and managers remain unnamed and untraceable in local memory, leaving no personal profiles or leadership narratives. This visibility gap has two dimensions: the absence of actors whose stories could anchor memory, and the unresolved tensions surrounding ownership – one arising from lack of information, the other from limits on what can be said.

Archival documents list categories of ownership – English, Italian, Jewish shareholders, state control – but not the individuals behind them. Decisions appear as impersonal acts: the "*English*" closed the factory in 1915, "*Italians*" took over in the 1920s, the state "*assumed control*" during wartime. Authority appears only as designation, not as people.

This absence continues under socialism. Former workers recall no leadership structures. The archive preserves the memoir of the 1949–

1950 director (DA – Varna, f. 1517, op. 1), showing that managerial perspectives existed, yet none are remembered.

Socialism elevated the “udarnik” – exemplary workers presented as proof of ideological success (Apostolova, 1957; Udarnik, 1946). They stood as symbolic representatives of the factory when real decision-makers remained distant. Workers recognised this performative logic (Creed 1995); official and private truths coexisted. “The party,” the hegemon, stayed abstract, much like the foreign owners before it.

The current owner appears in public records, but no further information is available. A person identified by tenants declined to meet. Several respondents mentioned TIM as a suspected owner – a large Varna-based conglomerate associated in public discourse with criminal structures.

A municipal official confirms the consequences of this opacity. Responsibility is formally distributed across agencies, ministries and private owners, but in practice no actor can act. The municipality “has no competence,” cannot invest in private property and must defer to higher authorities that do not respond. Some owners allow heritage buildings to deteriorate until demolition becomes legal. Authority is everywhere in principle, nowhere in practice.

Public commentary reflects this pattern. Users describe the factory as “waiting to fall,” “taken for nothing,” or “left to collapse” by unnamed interests, controlled by forces that cannot be contacted.

Institutional opacity is both narrative and practical. Without identifiable authority, no one can be approached, held accountable or form institutional memory. The factory’s history becomes a sequence of events carried out by unrecognisable agents performing unknown actions.

Before 1944 the initiative to build the factory, the municipal land provided and the long-standing efforts to keep it operating express a proprietary attitude framed as serving local livelihood, even though the enterprise was legally private. As noted in the press: “*The company is not important; what is important is the reopening of the factory...*” (Varnenski obshtinski vestnik, 1925). Respondents echo this: they perceive the building as part of “*my childhood,*” “*our neighbourhood,*” or “*our family history.*” To the question what was the factory for her, one responded simply: “*Everything.*” This belonging operates independently of legal ownership.

The strength of this attachment makes the later rupture more consequential. Under socialism, factories were said to be “*in the hands of*

the working class,” though decisions were taken elsewhere. During mass privatisation, a similar symbolic promise resurfaced through vouchers and free shares; in practice, most vouchers ended in privatisation funds and control shifted to a small group of investors (Getova, 2022). This produced a second symbolic affirmation followed by a second loss. As one respondent said: “*It's very disgusting, it's very sad. This was done for the people... Everything that was done is being destroyed.*”

Being told twice that the factory was “*in workers' hands,*” and losing it twice without clear actors, produces a silence shaped by disappointment, guilt and a sense of powerlessness. Under such conditions, silence is not forgetting but a way of avoiding a past that offers no stable ground.

Facebook discussions reinforce this dynamic. Commenters describe the building as “*snatched by private interests*” or “*taken for nothing,*” while still treating it as shared heritage.

This institutional opacity aligns with research on governance. Mary Douglas (1985) notes that institutions sustain themselves by distributing accountability so widely that responsibility becomes unlocatable. The persistent invisibility of the owner produces both administrative paralysis and narrative collapse.

Fear and the consequences of responsible speech

The empirical record shows that contract killings remained a visible feature of public life in Bulgaria into the 2000s – 156 cases between 2000 and 2005, with only 17 resolved – making such violence a relatively low-risk tool for eliminating rivals. Since the 1990s, Bulgaria has lived with the long aftertaste of violent entrepreneurial groups, unresolved contract killings, and the visible penetration of criminal actors into local politics and legitimate business (Shtenov et al, 2007). State institutions were widely perceived as weak or compromised (Gachevska, 2012). These parallel analyses describe the risks as producing “*unfocused fears, perceptions of insecurity, and feelings of unease*” that cannot be precisely located.

This caution is reinforced by older, socialist-era habits of disciplined speech, in which political and institutional topics required careful navigation (Gachevska, 2012). Respondents do not cite these details explicitly, but their hesitations and topic shifts reproduce a wider communicative norm: one avoids specificity when the boundaries of safety are unclear.

Respondents describe the factory as “*taken*,” “*left to fall*,” or “*run down*,” in some cases organisations such as TIM are suspected not as rumour but as a recognised actor in Varna’s economic landscape. The name appears as an implicit boundary: people acknowledge it quietly, without elaboration, and then change the subject. The combination – widespread local knowledge, absence of official confirmation, and reluctance to discuss details – creates a climate in which speaking freely about the factory feels unsafe or simply unwise.

These dynamics do not need to be present in the Cotton Factory itself to influence everyday behaviour. They have produced a diffuse, historically accumulated sense that naming powerful actors, discussing ownership, or criticising institutional decisions may carry unpredictable consequences. Respondents face another constraint, alongside the above mentioned: speaking about the factory may involve social risk.

Moral reclassification and the multiple erasures of memory

The memory pattern around the Cotton Factory follows Maurice Halbwachs’s view that collective memory is reorganised through shifting “social frames”: what can be recalled depends on the authority structure that validates it. It also reflects Mary Douglas’s account of institutional “shadow zones,” where experience becomes unsayable because it no longer fits the classificatory order.

Archival fragments show that this dynamic has deep historical roots. Early twentieth-century accounts classify ownership through national and ethnic labels – English, Italian, Jewish – rather than identifiable individuals or practices. A 1902 newspaper, commenting on the English owner’s behaviour during a strike, notes: “*As you can see, all of this may be very English, but it is not at all Bulgarian.*” (Izvestnik, 1902) A brief note from 1930 reports that “*the factory is in the hands of Jewish shareholders, a pity but a fact.*” (Naroden ratnik, 1930)

Such judgements reflect the moral horizons of their time and anticipate later reclassifications after 1944 and 1989. In each period, the dominant narrative framework determines which aspects of the past are speakable. The literature describes two successive waves of suppression. The first begins after 1944, when the socialist state redefined legitimate memory (Deyanova, 2005). Histories of entrepreneurship, foreign ownership and pre-socialist work cultures became politically unusable.

A parallel mechanism reappears after 1989, but with reversed polarity. Positive memories of socialist life or workplace experience carry

the risk of disapproval. Several respondents shorten their answers or retreat into generalities when the socialist period arises. Moments that could ground personal accounts – workplace dynamics, routines, achievements – are reduced to safe minimal formulas.

This material aligns with Katherine Verdery's observations on the post-1989 moralisation of the past. Public discourse often references socialism through evaluative shorthand – the Facebook comment calling it "*the bad socialism*" is typical – while concrete memories remain unspoken. Interviewees confirm this implicitly: none provide extended descriptions of their work lives under socialism, even when they spent decades in the factory. The 1946 Udarnik newspaper corpus documents a factory saturated with organised activity – brigades, physical-culture units, agitbrigades, memorial rituals. Archival traces from the period, including a photograph of the recreation base of the State Industrial Enterprise "Hristo Botev" (DA – Varna, f. 640, op. 1, a.e. 45), indicate organised leisure facilities existed, yet none appear in interviews; only the kindergarten persists because it still operates.

Asked explicitly about social life in the factory, one respondent whose parents worked there recounts: "*...my father sang in the choir, my mother, they went rowing... There wasn't a factory without them, without a dance troupe, without a choir... It has always been like that.*" Her memories remain descriptive and avoid moral evaluation. At the end she adds emotionally: "*We demolished monuments, we demolished everything. I went to Buzludzha¹ when they opened Buzludzha. I went on the first day. It was so beautiful. Now it's a tomb. It's the same here, a tomb.*" Only one neighbourhood participant offers a spontaneous judgement, and from a third-person position: "*I've only heard that all the people were happy while the factory was working. But when democracy came, the factory closed.*"

Across these transitions, the effect is cumulative. The pre-1944 past is overwritten after 1944; the socialist past is overwritten after 1989; and each new regime reinforces silence around part of what came before. Workers' experiences do not vanish but their narrative expression contracts through repeated cycles of moral sorting. The result is a

¹ Completed in 1981 on the peak linked to the founding of Bulgaria's socialist movement, Buzludzha served as the Bulgarian Communist Party's chief monumental symbol. Its futuristic form and mosaics projected ideological authority; its post-1989 abandonment turned it into a conspicuous ruin and a contested site of memory, illustrating the unresolved legacy of state socialism in Bulgaria.

memory field shaped not by forgetting alone but by successive reorganisations of what counts as acceptable speech.

Urban discontinuity: city growth and the weakening of local memory

Testimonies and public discussions suggest that the transformation of Varna's urban environment has weakened the continuity of memory surrounding the Cotton Factory. Several respondents note that the city has changed "*a great deal*" and that many new residents have settled in the area, altering the neighbourhood's social composition. An architectural history specialist remarked that the district "*is not what it was,*" pointing to the rapid expansion and reconfiguration of Varna's industrial zones in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries. Today's population around the factory is not the population that engaged with it during its operational years.

Several pedestrians told they "*are not from here and don't know anything about the factory,*" despite having lived in the neighbourhood for twenty or thirty years. They recognise the name "Hristo Botev" but associate it only with the building, not with its former function. Inter-generational transmission is missing.

Physical changes reinforce this reclassification of the past. Pedestrians pointed to the disappearance of the small pre-1950s houses once surrounding the site, replaced by new apartment blocks and construction pits. Trucks carrying concrete passed every few minutes during fieldwork. Two men who had stopped for a drink commented: "*These buildings are recent. Here on this street, as you go down, everything was on the left and on the right, there were houses. Yes. Like these houses.*"

In this setting, the old fabric of the neighbourhood is not only erased but treated as obsolete, making the socialist and pre-socialist past appear irrelevant to the shifting present. Online discussions echo this. Commenters describe Varna as "*completely changed*" or "*unrecognisable,*" placing the factory within a city that no longer supports its former social meaning. The building becomes a remnant in an urban landscape with new economic and spatial priorities.

The spatial and demographic reorganisation of Varna thus contributes to the erosion of memory, not through deliberate forgetting but through the dilution of the social environments that once sustained it.

Convergence: how silence becomes structurally produced and culturally stabilised

A final pattern in the material is the way incomplete knowledge about the Cotton Factory becomes filled with conjecture, inherited rumours or circulating neighbourhood myths. When respondents attempt to explain aspects of the factory's history but lack concrete information, they draw on fragments that mix verifiable elements with imaginative or exaggerated claims.

A few examples. Names such as "Prince Boris" and "Prince Kiril" appear interchangeably, and the factory's age varies across recollections. Different respondents attribute the founding to "the English", "Italians" or "Germans". In public discussion, commenters claim the building is protected by UNESCO, or that it was the first industrial site after the Liberation. Tenants recount how striking the brick produces a metallic sound, or describe it as uniquely hard to drill. One respondent attributes this to "*unique English clay*" and concludes that the buildings still stand because "*they cannot be removed*". These claims circulate, despite the fact that the factory could be demolished like any other.

Fragmented sensory memories do not accumulate into narrative. Low occupational prestige discourages elaboration. The invisibility of owners and managers leaves no figures around whom accounts can cohere. Spatial stigma distances the factory from present-day identity. Moral reorganisations after 1944 and 1989 restrict which periods feel speakable. Urban turnover dissolves the communities that once held memory. Fear – shaped by socialist-era disciplined speech and post-1989 perceptions of risk – encourages vagueness when responsibility is unclear. Where factual knowledge is thin, discourse iteration produces improvised explanations and local myths that fill the gaps without restoring the historical record.

This process also stabilises a new cultural centre of gravity. Repeated fragments – foreign origins, architectural quality, exceptional durability – become shared assumptions. These iterations do not reconstruct the factory's past but provide a coherent framework through which the building remains intelligible in the present. The architectural admiration survives, while accounts of work, production and everyday life do not. The Cotton Factory becomes a case where the interplay of these forces produces not misinformation or conflict but a deep, enduring and structurally reinforced silence.

Conclusion

The structure of the Cotton Factory in Varna remains a prominent landmark. The silence around it is not an absence of memory or interest, but the outcome of several converging conditions. Its presence is sustained not by legal protection or deliberate preservation, but by a suspended significance that no institution or community has resolved. It continues to stand partly because it carries a meaning that has not yet been fully articulated.

Despite the many layers of forgetting, the factory persists because certain forms of memory continue to attach to it. These memories are not narrative but structural – the long-standing sense of belonging, the unresolved social conflicts embedded in its history and territory, the cultural aspirations associated with industrial modernity, the neighbourhood legends and the aesthetic appeal of the building itself. People who scarcely recall the work still recognise the façade; those who cannot name its owners still imagine what it could become. The vision of transforming a once noisy and inhospitable interior into a quiet, open space – a gallery, a concert hall, a place for public life – anchors the factory in its constructed past and present, and opens a future horizon.

This mixture of attachment, projection and aesthetic recognition forms the residual memory that continues to hold the building in place, even as the stories that created and animated it have faded. If the remaining relations and latent meanings that tie the factory to the lives around it were ever stripped away, it would become what many other industrial sites have already become – a place detached from memory as it is removed from the landscape.

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Marine Aroshidze

Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University, Batumi, Georgia
[marina.aroshidze@bsu.edu.ge], ORCID ID: 0000-0001-8211-8421

Nino Aroshidze

Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University, Batumi, Georgia
[nino.aroshidze@bsu.edu.ge], ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3358-7955

Mechanisms of Manipulation in the Information Society (linguistic aspect)

Abstract: *In today's information society, mechanisms for manipulating the mental state and behavior of individuals and the broader public are being continuously refined. Among the diverse tools of manipulation, language – the power of words – plays a central role. This article examines the appealing and persuasive power of words through an analysis of Putin's speeches delivered prior to the invasion of Ukraine. Linguistic markers, which we have termed “Putinisms,” are reinforced through their interaction with vivid, memorable visuals, all of which are embedded in the emotional packaging of a falsified interpretation of cultural heritage. The culmination of these manipulative actions is the construction of a new “post-Soviet” myth centered on the Siberianization of Russia.*

Keywords: *linguistic markers; manipulative techniques; public consciousness; “Putinisms”; the birth of a new myth.*

Introduction

Knowledge and information are among the most important resources of the modern information society. Political, social, and economic development are impossible without effective information support. The process of obtaining, processing, transmitting, and using information is **closely connected** to the manipulation of public opinion **through the use of** modern technologies.

Research in social psychology convincingly demonstrates that we live in a world of pervasive manipulation: we are **systematically persuaded** what we should buy, what we should wear, what we should think, and who we should vote for. In their psychological encyclopedia, *The Age of Propaganda: The Mechanisms of Persuasion, Everyday Uses, and Abuses*, Anthony R. Pratkanis and Elliot Aronson **analyze**

the process of manipulating public opinion through the dissemination of distorted or false information, **identifying** such manipulation mechanisms as half-truths, big lies, labels, clichés, demagoguery (ad hominem arguments), emotional manipulation, and others, all aimed at shaping a **predetermined** opinion (Pratkanis, Aronson 2001).

According to the distinguished sociologist and publicist Sergei Georgievich Kara-Murza, humanity has entered a **social order** in which the manipulation of consciousness has become the primary means of domination. In his renowned bestselling nonfiction book, *Manipulation of Consciousness*, the author examines the forms and methods of programming the mental state and behavior of individuals and the public, and **describes** political myths that distort reality. Kara-Murza considers the formation of manipulative rhetoric, disseminated and replicated by public institutions and the media, to be the most important tool for manipulating public consciousness. The author supports his observations and conclusions with **numerous** historical examples, the majority of which **concern** methods of influencing the consciousness of Soviet people and myths about the Soviet system (Kara-Murza 2015).

In separate books (Kara-Murza 2013; Kara-Murza 2015), the author analyzes the speeches of Vladimir Putin and Dmitry Medvedev and **exposes** the distorted and false information presented in them.

Throughout the long history of human civilization, those in power have developed various ways to manipulate public consciousness. **However**, regardless of the variety of techniques and methods used, language – the power of words – **occupies a special place** in influencing human consciousness, as Vadim Shefner emphasized in his poem *Words*:

A word can kill,
A word can save,
A word can lead regiments...
(Shefner n.d.)

The power of words, **and the linguistic markers** that have a special impact on human consciousness, have always **been of particular interest to us** as linguists. We have reflected on certain aspects of this multifaceted problem in the following publications:

We have addressed certain aspects of this multifaceted problem in our previous studies (Aroshidze, Aroshidze 2018; Aroshidze, Aroshidze 2020; Aroshidze, Aroshidze 2021).

In this article, we examine the linguistic means of manipulating public consciousness in the modern information society. The appealing and persuasive power of words is **further enhanced** by their combination with vivid, memorable visuals, all presented within the emotional packaging of **cultural heritage**.

The essence of manipulation

Psychological influence is understood as an effect on the mental state, feelings, thoughts, and behavior of others. Psychologists and sociologists distinguish different types of influence, primarily persuasion and suggestion. Persuasion is based on a conscious and organized influence on a person through their critical judgment, while suggestion, or suggestion, works by reducing or completely eliminating critical thinking about incoming information, implying unlimited trust in its sources.

The authors of the "Great Psychological Dictionary," edited by Boris Guryevich Meshcheryakov and Vladimir Petrovich Zinchenko, interpret these terms as follows:

"Manipulation (from the Latin *manipulus* - handful, *manus* - hand) - 1. Manual operation, manual action, in particular the demonstration of a trick based on sleight of hand. 2. Fraud, deception, fraud, swindle. 3. Communicative influence that leads to the actualization of certain motivational states in the object of influence, prompting them to behave in a manner desirable (beneficial) to the subject of the influence" (Meshcheryakov, Zinchenko 2002: 245).

"Beliefs (English: persuasion) are ideas, knowledge, and beliefs that motivate human behavior and determine their attitude toward various spheres of reality; components of a person's worldview" (Meshcheryakov, Zinchenko 2002: 501).

"Suggestion (English: suggestion) is a type of targeted communicative influence on the behavior and consciousness of a person (or group of people), as a result of which a person (group of people), contrary to available factual information (perceived, retrieved from memory), recognizes the existence of something that does not actually exist, or does something contrary to their intentions or habits" (Meshcheryakov, Zinchenko 2002: 70).

In fact, suggestion is contrasted with persuasion as an unreasoned influence versus a reasoned one. A person under suggestion has either a complete lack of control or a minimal amount of criticism regarding

the information they receive. Psychologists emphasize verbal and mental suggestion, although, even with developed figurative thinking, in our opinion, the primary channel for receiving the next suggested "dose" is still verbal.

Different authors also include emotional contagion, imitation, fashion as a means of standardizing mass behavior, and so on among other means of manipulation. The essence of these different styles of manipulation is the same: a hidden influence on public consciousness.

In dictionaries of European languages, the word is defined as handling objects with specific intentions and goals (for example, manual control, a doctor examining a patient using hands, etc.). This implies that such actions require dexterity and skill. In technology, specialized devices for controlling mechanisms that act as extensions of the hands (levers, handles) are called manipulators. This explains the metaphorical meaning of this word – the deft handling of people as objects. Merriam-Webster defines manipulation as the act of influencing or controlling others in a skillful or calculated manner, often for one's own advantage and typically without the awareness of those being influenced. (Merriam-Webster Dictionary n.d.)

The Role of Language in Manipulating Public Consciousness

We share the view of Israeli historian Yuval Noah Harari, who believes that it was language that allowed *Homo sapiens* to distinguish itself from at least six other human species:

"Of all the ancient humanoids, *Homo sapiens* was able to conquer the world because it possessed such a unique tool as language. The uniqueness of language lies not in its ability to transmit information, but in its ability to communicate things we have never seen, heard, or smelled – that is, to create an imaginary world. It is not surprising that legends, myths, gods, and religions emerged as a result of the cognitive revolution" (Harari 2003).

We live not in a world of realities, but in a linguistic and cultural reality that, contrary to the common formula, does not simply "reflect the world around us," but actively shapes, structures, and evaluates it, recording these evaluations in linguistic markers and cultural connotations. It would seem that cultural heritage consists primarily of facts; however, the same fact is presented and interpreted in radically different ways in different socio-political contexts.

Research into cultural memory conducted by a large consortium of scholars within the European research project MEMORYROW

(2011–2015) has confirmed an important thesis: cultural memory is not a given, but a socio-cultural construct, comparable to an architectural building that is frequently rebuilt, expanded, and whose façade is updated, although the load-bearing walls impose certain limitations on change. Once again, mechanisms of manipulation intervene in the construction of the surrounding world: the powers that be decide what should be brought to the forefront, partially transformed, and what should be consigned to oblivion, silence, or denial.

The material support of cultural memory takes various forms – objects, architectural structures, works of fine art, and others – but the universal means of memorializing any important event in the life of a people is language, a specific semiotic system that performs functions fundamental to every human community. Language not only ensures communication; it is also a means of developing thought, transmitting cultural and historical traditions from generation to generation, and a crucial condition for the preservation of ethnic identity.

Language not only records the most important events in a people's life; it also contains their evaluation. It is no wonder that the popular saying goes, “What’s written with a pen can’t be undone with an axe.” Although quills have long since fallen out of use, we have been able to observe the validity of this statement firsthand. In 2001, Slavic students from Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University took a Russian language course led by professors from the Peoples’ Friendship University of Russia. In addition to Russian language and literature, we were also prepared for an exam in Russian history. When the lecturer described Yermak’s campaigns, he repeatedly emphasized the “annexation of Siberia.” As linguists, we countered that Siberia was not annexed, but “conquered” by Yermak. The most important evidence of this lies in the numerous titles of cultural works: Vasily Surikov’s famous painting *The Conquest of Siberia by Yermak*; the Russian ethnographer P. I. Nebolsin’s scientific and historical essays *The Conquest of Siberia* (1848) and *A Brief Essay on the Conquest of Siberia* (1872); and even the school textbook *Literary Reading* for the 4th grade includes *The Legend of Yermak’s Conquest of Siberia*. The semantics of the words **покорение** (conquest) and **присоединение** (annexation), together with their evaluative connotations, are so different that they cannot be interchanged in this context. In response, we were told that Russian historiography is undergoing a reinterpretation of the nominations of certain historical events. Here, manipulation is evident.

In our previous research, we analyzed changes in language policy in Georgia as a means of manipulating cultural memory, using urban “palimpsests” (the renaming of streets and squares), changes to the official holiday calendar, censorship and propaganda, the two-faced Janus that filters out objectionable material while propagating new realities and desirable personalities, and so on. In this article, however, we focus on the revision of the textual narrative concerning a specific historical period and on the creation of new school and university textbooks.

Censorship and propaganda, as highly effective manipulative techniques, **extend far beyond** the media; **strict control is exercised** at all levels of the education system. For example, in 2023, new unified Russian history textbooks for grades 10 and 11 were introduced. The author of the article, **Candidate of Historical Sciences** Yuri Borisenok, reports on the phased updating of history textbooks in schools of the Russian Federation (**with the release of new textbooks for grades 5–9 planned for 2025**) and notes: “The new unified textbooks are the result of the intensive work of a team of authors, experts, and methodologists, including Vladimir Medinsky, aide to the President of the Russian Federation, and academicians of the Russian Academy of Sciences Alexander Chubaryan and Anatoly Torkunov” (Borisenok 2023).

How do these textbooks differ from previous ones? The author of the article believes that the new textbook does not offer “**an unconditional apology for the Soviet project,**” nor does it contain the anti-Soviet bias **characteristic of** the 1990s, nor does it glorify the autocratic monarchy or the White movement. Instead, it is presented as a “**comprehensive source of information reflecting the current state-approved viewpoint**” on the complex processes of Russian history in the first half of the twentieth century. **As a result,** individual historical events are renamed (for example, *Великая российская революция* (the *Great Russian Revolution*) instead of *Великая октябрьская социалистическая революция* (the *Great October Socialist Revolution*), and there is a noticeable shift in emphasis in the presentation of facts. **However,** the main manipulative factor here is the omission and downplaying of certain “**undesirable**” episodes and facts.

The most important means of manipulating cultural heritage during the renewal of the socio-political structure – censorship and propaganda, a near-monopoly on the media, the dualistic mechanism of “**memory/forgetting,**” control at all levels of the education system, the circulation of new personalities, and others – are aimed at shaping the system of values **deemed “necessary”** by the authorities. Particularly

effective in this regard are outdoor advertising texts (posters, placards) with a mixed semiotic texture, which combine verbal and non-verbal means of expressing information.

The annexation of Crimea to Russia is reflected in propaganda posters such as:

The History of the Incorporation of New Regions into Russia. A. Polegenko, TASS.

Poster: **ОДНА СТРАНА! ОДНА СЕМЬЯ! ОДНА РОССИЯ!**
(ONE COUNTRY! ONE FAMILY! ONE RUSSIA!)

(TASS 2024).

Particularly striking linguistic manipulators are contained in the **speeches** of Putin and the “**Putinists**” who unleashed the war in Ukraine.

“Putinisms” – linguistic markers of the manipulation of public consciousness

We analyze linguistic markers of the manipulation of public consciousness using materials from President Vladimir Putin’s addresses to the citizens of Russia on February 21, 2022 (Putin 2022a) and February 24, 2022 (Putin 2022b).

The first speech begins with a so-called “historical” reference to the Ukrainian state as an “artificial creation of the communist era,” while asserting that some of its territory is “originally Russian.” A classic manipulative tactic is the construction of an enemy image that allegedly plans, in the future, to “weaken, divide, and ultimately destroy our country.” This main enemy is identified as the West, which supposedly controls “Ukrainian neo-Nazis” and supports the Ukrainian regime. Consequently, Russia is presented as being forced to take “urgent steps” to protect its sovereignty, security, and territorial integrity. In practice, this step takes the form of an invasion of Ukraine.

An invasion of a sovereign state is certainly a war. However, during World War II – or, more precisely, its segment known as the Great Patriotic War – the symbol of a “sacred,” just war in defense of the Fatherland, the Motherland, and the native land emerged. Those who unleashed that war were defined as invaders, Nazis, and usurpers. Accordingly, Putin replaces the word “war” with the term “special operation.” This “Putinism” becomes the most important linguistic marker for manipulating public opinion.

These addresses contain a full range of manipulative techniques – half-truths, lies, falsifications, simulations of a terrifying future, and

others – the impact of which on listeners is intensified by emotionally expressive language:

Ukraine, backed by the West: *неонацисты, антироссийский плацдарм, тотальная русофобия, агрессивная политика западных элит, террористические акты против мирных жителей, режим репрессий, геноцид, наследники бандеровцев и нацистских карателей* (neo-Nazis, an anti-Russian stronghold, total Russophobia, aggressive policies of Western elites, terrorist attacks against civilians, a regime of repression, genocide, the heirs of Banderites and Nazi punitive forces), etc.

Russia: *наша великая Родина, большая историческая Россия, настоящие патриоты встали на защиту интересов России* (our great Motherland, great historical Russia, true patriots rising to defend Russia's interests), etc.

Thus, on February 21, a massive verbal bombardment of Ukraine began, and on February 24, "Putinists" were compelled to "defend the integrity of Russia" through a "preemptive" invasion of Ukrainian territory: "In this regard, the decision to launch a preemptive military operation was absolutely necessary and the only possible one." In the president's second speech, delivered on the day of Russia's invasion of Ukraine, linguistic markers of manipulation are superimposed with a dense layer of evaluative vocabulary: *фундаментальные угрозы, безответственные политики, грубо и бесцеремонно, циничный обман, наплевательское, пренебрежительное отношение* (fundamental threats, irresponsible politicians, rude and unceremonious behavior, cynical deception, a dismissive and contemptuous attitude).

In an effort to emphasize the supposed closeness between the ruling elite and the masses, Putin resorts to colloquial language such as *хамски, шулерское поведение, сломали хребет международному терроризму* (boorish, cheating behavior; broke the back of international terrorism) and even jargon like *Несогласных ломают через колено: ... обманули, а выражаясь народным языком просто кинули* (dissenters are forced to bend the knee; deceived, and in common parlance, simply "screwed").

Particularly expressive is the series of prefixed verb forms used to expose the mythical enemy that allegedly contributed to the collapse of the Soviet Union and is said to plan, in the near future, to *дожать* (grind down), *добить* (finish off), and *разрушить уже окончательно* (annihilate completely). The use of the subjunctive mood and future tense forms when listing threats deserves special attention. How could

this not justify a preemptive strike? With only a few linguistic markers, the cultural past of a people who defended their country from fascist invaders is manipulated: Ukrainian government officials are declared direct descendants of Nazis (“neo-Nazis”), while those initiating a so-called special operation on the territory of a sovereign foreign state are proclaimed defenders of the Fatherland.

Even representatives of the Orthodox Church were mobilized to shape the public opinion desired by the Russian authorities. After the war began, Patriarch Kirill, in his statements, endorsed the military actions in Ukraine, praising Russian soldiers as “peace-loving and modest people” who are portrayed as determining Russia’s future.

The Birth of a New Myth

The highest form of manipulative use of language is the creation of political and ideological myths. The great social experiment of building socialism, which was intended to evolve into communism, was based on a number of attractive political myths: the myth of the “most humane society” and that of the “friendly family of equal peoples.” A special symbolic universe was constructed to sustain these myths, employing a wide range of sign systems that ultimately formed the cultural code of *Homo Sovieticus* (Aroshidze 2018).

In analyzing the role of language in myth creation as a socio-cultural phenomenon, we also demonstrated the dynamics of myth destruction, facilitated by texts of a destructive nature: satirical texts criticizing the existing order (anecdotes, cartoons, parodies, political fables, etc.); texts containing reliable information that broke the “information vacuum” in which the builders of socialism existed (photographic documents, archival materials, autobiographies, etc.); and highly artistic texts with a particularly strong impact, including the works of Mikhail Bulgakov, Vladimir Vysotsky, Alexander Solzhenitsyn, Igor Guberman, and others.

Old myths have been destroyed, but the process of myth-making continues. New myths are being constructed and readily accepted by naive users of the information society. At present, a new myth is taking shape – the so-called “Siberianization of Russia” – with renewed emphasis on linguistic manipulators. Sergey Karaganov, Distinguished Professor and Academic Director of the Faculty of World Economy and International Affairs at the National Research University Higher School of Economics, is the author of the article “Siberization: Russia’s Second Turn to the East Lies ‘Beyond the Stone’” (Karaganov 2024).

The author discusses Russia's strategic future, arguing that the war "provoked and unleashed by the West in Ukraine should not distract us from moving south and east – where the center of human development is shifting." One cannot help recalling the "cultural center of the world," Vasyuki, from Ilya Ilf and Yevgeny Petrov's *The Twelve Chairs* (1928).

According to this logic, Russia must return home from its "more than three-hundred-year European journey," which has allegedly exhausted its usefulness. "For these three centuries, we have half-forgotten the eastern roots of our state and people. The Mongols plundered, but they also contributed to development." Once again, the motif of the "conquest" of Siberia is activated, presented as the force that transformed ancient Rus', the Russian kingdom, into a great Russia. Particularly revealing are the linguistic constructions used to describe a single, supra-ethnic community – the Soviet people under new geopolitical conditions:

"Siberia was developed by people of dozens of nationalities, intertwined with the local population. And, of course, collectivism – survival and the conquest of space and the elements were impossible without mutual assistance. This is how the Siberian was formed – a concentration of the best in the Russian person – Russian Russian, Russian Tatar, Russian Buryat, Russian Yakut, Russian Chechen, and so on down the list."

The foundations of a new myth have thus already been laid. The author presents himself as a witness – and even a midwife – to the birth of a new world, while all that remains is to repel the final attack of the retreating West, allegedly seeking to defeat Russia on the battlefields of Ukraine. Consequently, this battle must be won by the most brutal means. Finally, as the culmination of this manipulative strategy, a concealed threat is articulated: "This is necessary not only for the country's victory, but also to prevent the world from sliding into World War III."

Conclusions

The main resource of the modern information society is knowledge and information; therefore, manipulating public consciousness is, first and foremost, a matter of manipulating information and, through it, diminishing a people's cultural heritage.

The most important means of manipulating public consciousness include censorship and propaganda, a near-complete monopoly on the media, the dualistic mechanism of "memory/forgetting," control over

all levels of the educational system, and the influence of the press, television, the film industry, and literature, which together shape the “desired” value systems within mass consciousness.

The highest manifestation of manipulation is the creation of ideological myths – multistructured symbolic universes in which language and so-called linguistic manipulators (metaphorization, theatricalization) play a central role. At the same time, language also functions as a means of exposing and debunking myths.

As a result of myth-making, a complex symbolic universe is formed in which all means of persuasion and suggestion, both verbal and visual, are employed and packaged in an emotional, often pathetic wrapper that does not always successfully conceal half-truths and falsifications.

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Miftar Kurti

Institute of History “Ali Hadri”, Prishtina (Kosovo)
[miftarkurti@hotmail.com], ORCID: 0009-0005-0599-1944

Nuri Bexheti

University of Prishtina “Hasan Prishtina” (Kosovo)
[nuri.bexheti@uni-pr.edu], ORCID: 0009-0004-1235-3521

Ardita Hajdari

Institute of History “Ali Hadri”, Prishtina (Kosovo)
[ardita.hajdari@hotmail.com], ORCID: 0009-0002-1910-040X

Primary Education in the Parallel System of Kosovo (1990–1999)

Abstract: *Kosovo became part of the Socialist Republic of Serbia within the Yugoslav federation at the end of the Second World War in 1945. A unified curriculum was introduced across Yugoslavia by the Federal Law on Elementary and Secondary Education in 1958. The 1963 Constitution further devolved educational powers to the republics, and the 1974 Constitution elevated Kosovo to an autonomous province with its own education-making bodies. From the mid-1970s, Kosovo’s provincial assembly regulated elementary and secondary schools under an eight-grade compulsory system, and the University of Pristina operated with growing autonomy.*

In March 1989, Republic of Serbia, within Yugoslavia revoked Kosovo’s autonomy and imposed Serbo-Croatian as the sole language of instruction, leading to the dismissal of Albanian-language teachers and the collapse of Albanian-medium classes. From 1990 to 1999, Kosovo Albanians established a parallel education network to preserve continuity and prevent the illiteracy intended by Serbian policies. This paper examines how primary education functioned under those extraordinary conditions: the parallel curricula and teaching materials used, the financing mechanisms, and the challenges encountered by students, teachers, parents, and school leaders during this period.

Keywords: *Kosovo; Albanian education; albanian language; parallel system; Yugoslavia.*

Introduction

The history of Albanian-language education in Kosovo is marked by repeated cycles of prohibition, resistance, and adaptation. From the

Ottoman period through the Yugoslav era, Albanian schools were systematically suppressed, yet communities consistently sought ways to preserve instruction in their own language. The culmination of these efforts was the creation of a parallel education system during the 1990s, organized outside the official Serbian state structures. This system, though operating under severe political repression and material scarcity, became a cornerstone of Albanian collective resistance and cultural survival. Within this historical continuum, the emergence of the parallel education system in the 1990s stands as a decisive moment in the struggle to preserve cultural identity under conditions of political repression. Despite formidable obstacles, including state bans, administrative decrees, and the confiscation of school facilities, this system functioned as an effective mechanism for safeguarding instruction in the Albanian language and transmitting national identity across generations.

This article seeks to demonstrate that the parallel education system was not merely a symbolic act of defiance but a practical and resilient structure that ensured continuity of learning. It asks how Albanian schools, organized outside official Serbian state frameworks, sustained their operation during the years 1990 – 1999 and what impact this had on literacy and educational attainment among Albanian children. By situating the parallel system within broader historical and political contexts, the study underscores its role as both an educational and a national project.

The working hypothesis advanced here is that, although informal and lacking state recognition, the parallel education system succeeded in maintaining high levels of literacy and primary education among Albanian children. Its endurance was made possible through the mobilization of community resources, the use of private homes and improvised facilities, and the cultivation of a collective ethos of resistance. In this way, education became both a pedagogical and a political act, reinforcing the cohesion of a society under siege.

To substantiate this hypothesis, the article will draw, where possible, on data from the post-war international administration in Kosovo, including Provisional Institutions of Self-Government (PISG) under the authority of the United Nations Interim Administration Mission in Kosovo (UNMIK), OSCE, and UNICEF reports (Sommers & Buckland,

2004).¹ Statistics on literacy rates and school enrollment among children educated during the parallel system years provide empirical evidence that this improvised network not only functioned but achieved measurable outcomes. Such data will serve to highlight the paradox of an education system that, while denied official legitimacy, nonetheless succeeded in fulfilling its essential mission: the preservation of language, identity, and knowledge under conditions of systematic exclusion.

An Overview of the History of Albanian-language Education in Kosovo

Upon the Ottoman Empire's consolidation of control over all Albanian territories, concerted efforts were undertaken to safeguard the Albanian language and establish schools offering instruction in Albanian. Religious institutions, such as the College of Saint Luke in the village of Stubëll, Vitia, were established early in Kosovo's history, beginning in 1584. It was only during the period of the Albanian National Awakening within the Ottoman Empire that truly national Albanian schools were founded most notably the National Albanian School of Korçë (1887) and the Elbasan Normal School (1909). These institutions form the very foundation of the modern Albanian education system (Koliqi, 2004).

The use of several scripts including Arabic-Ottoman, Greek, Latin, or modified Italo-Latin variants created by Albanian authors was prevalent in Albanian-language schools until 1908. The Latin script was the only one adopted following the Congress of Manastir (1908). The Ottoman-Turkish system remained the primary school system in Kosovo until 1913, followed by the Albanian and Serbian systems (Pupovci, Hyseni, Salihaj, 2000; Hajdari, Bexheti, 2024). Following the establishment of the Albanian state on 28 November 1912 and the subsequent occupation of Kosovo by Serbia and Montenegro in 1913, Albanian-language schools and the use of the Albanian language in Kosovo were systematically banned through a comprehensive array of administrative measures (Koliqi, 2004, pp. 23–24). Prior to the outbreak of the Second World War, education in Albanian was formally prohibited in Kosovo.

¹ Agency of State Archives of Kosovo. (n.d.). Fondi "Government of Kosovo – Commission for the Assessment of Damages," File: Destruction of Archival Material 1989–1999, Pristina, 2003-2004.

During the First World War (1914–1918), Kosovo was divided into two administrative zones: an eastern zone administered by Bulgaria and a western zone administered by Austria-Hungary. Only during this period were Albanian-language schools allowed to be established in Kosovo. Under Austro-Hungarian military-civil administration, around 300 Albanian-language schools were founded, supported and encouraged through financial assistance (Koliqi, 2004). Kosovo was placed under strict police control from 1918 (Lory, 2005). With the establishment of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, a systematic campaign against Albanian-language education in Kosovo was initiated. This policy led to the closure of 55 elementary schools, which had been serving approximately 4,000 pupils and staffed by around 100 teachers. The suppression of Albanian schooling during this period represented a deliberate attempt to curtail linguistic and cultural autonomy. It was only during the Second World War, under the conditions of foreign occupation, that Albanian-language elementary schools were permitted to reopen, marking a temporary reversal of the restrictive measures imposed in the interwar years. They operated in the Italian and German occupation zones, whereas in the Bulgarian-occupied area both schools and the Albanian language were banned. After the end of the war, Kosovo's education system went through several phases: the first phase (1945–1966), the second (1967–1980), the third (1981–1989), and the fourth (1990–1999), which closed out the twentieth century (Pupovci, Hyseni, & Salihaj, 2000). During the 1944/45 school year, Kosovo opened 278 four-grade elementary schools: 135 taught in Albanian (48.56%) and 143 in Serbian (51.44%). A total of 27,400 pupils were enrolled, 11,573 in Albanian and 15,827 in Serbian (Shatri, 2010). In the 1946/47 school year, the total number of Albanian-language elementary schools rose to 467, with 57,578 pupils enrolled (Karastojanov, 2007). By the 1949/50 school year, there were 472 Albanian-language schools with 747 teachers, and 320 Serbian-language schools with 539 teachers (Gjevori, 1998). From 1946 until the 1954/55 school year, pupils and elementary schools were segregated by national affiliation (Albanian and Serbian) and by language (Albanian and Serbian) (Shatri, 2010). In 1951/52, elementary schools teaching in Turkish also opened in Kosovo (Durmuşçelebi & Koro, 2012). Beginning in 1955/56, Kosovo established “territorial schools,” where instruction was organized in two teaching languages. In the 1959/60 school year, 502 elementary schools were operating in Kosovo, of which 159 were full eight-year institutions. By

1966/67, primary education in Kosovo included 204,702 pupils distributed across 6,546 classes. Of these, 133,907 pupils received instruction in Albanian, and 67,742 in Serbo-Croatian. In 1973/74, compared with 1966/67, the total number of pupils had increased by 63,430 (Shatri, 2010). The 1974 constitution greatly reduced the statutory differences between the autonomous provinces (Kosovo and Vojvodina) and the republics (Slovenia, Serbia, Croatia, Macedonia, Montenegro, and Bosnia and Herzegovina). For Kosovo Albanians, this was a major change (Lory, 2005), because under that constitution Kosovo gained the right to regulate its own educational and cultural affairs (A.S.A., 1999). The 1975/76 school year was the first to apply the new education laws based on the 1974 Yugoslav Constitution, granting Kosovo's education system full autonomy. According to Article 182, Chapter III of the 1974 Constitution of Kosovo, primary education was made compulsory and was to last at least eight years.² In this school year, a total of 879 primary schools were in operation. Of these, 422 were full eight-year schools, and the remainder were incomplete schools. A total of 285,969 pupils were enrolled: 225,590 in Albanian-language classes and 58,796 in Serbo-Croatian.

The period 1975/76 – 1980/81 is regarded as the brightest era for education development in general and for Albanian-language education in Kosovo in particular. Net enrollment for the generation aged 7–14 rose above 93.4 percent. First grade achieved full participation of seven-year-olds, while in eighth grade participation was around 85 percent.

In the 1980/81 school year, 895 primary schools operated: 463 fully independent eight-year schools, 30 six-grade schools, 41 five-grade schools, and 361 four-grade schools. This network enabled 321,547 pupils to attend primary education. The national composition of those pupils was: 268,548 Albanians (83.52 %), 34,827 Serbs (10.83 %), 3,462 Montenegrins (1.08 %), 1,466 Turks (0.46 %), 7,127 Bosniaks (2.22 %), 3,880 Roma (1.21 %), and 2,237 others (0.70 %). Enrollment for the 7–14 age group that year reached 94.10 percent. In 1983/84, Kosovo had 928 primary schools serving 1,435 settlements, of which only 489 were eight-grade schools. By the 1988/89 school year, instruction took place in 964 primary schools: 360 four-grade, 14 five-grade, 35 six-grade, and 555 eight-grade schools. That year, 349,114 pupils were enrolled – 304,836 in Albanian, 42,388 in Serbo-

² Constitution of the Socialist Autonomous Province of Kosovo of February 27, 1974, Chapter III, Article 182, p.115.

Croatian, and 1,890 in Turkish (Shatri, 2010). After the death of the Yugoslav leader Tito (4 May 1980), two major changes took place in Yugoslavia: ethnic tensions rekindled with great force, resembling an unforgivable hatred, and dictatorial methods became part of the governing style (Duroselle & Kaspi, 2011).

The Serbian authorities began to express their policies openly and blatantly intensify grievances toward Albanians, withholding support for their culture, education, and language. These injustices culminated in the demonstrations of March and April 1981. After this demonstrations, Serbian and Yugoslav authorities launched a campaign of segregation against Albanians. They organized a broad offensive, aiming specifically at Albanian education and schools in Kosovo. Education itself was labeled a source of irredentism and separatism. The situation worsened further in March 1989, when Serbia abolished Kosovo's autonomy and installed an apartheid system against Albanians (Schmitt, 2008).

From July 1989 to March 1991, Serbia enacted several laws (Marko, 2023), including the "Law on the Functioning of Republican Bodies in Extraordinary Circumstances", as if in wartime (Avdić, 2013). In addition to passing laws, Serbia issued around 500 decrees that affected every sphere of Kosovar society and the entire education system, from preschool institutions and elementary schools up to the university level. These legal and administrative measures resulted in the total removal of Kosovo's autonomy (Marko, 2023).

Thus, a Serbian team assumed control of all political, economic, and cultural decision-making mechanisms, inevitably fostering the creation of a deeply antagonistic parallel Albanian society (Lory, 2005). As a 1990 Human Rights Watch report documents, ethnic Albanians in Kosovo were arrested en masse, beaten and tortured in prisons, and dismissed from their jobs solely because of their ethnicity (Human Rights Watch Staff, 1990). Serbian police units repeatedly used excessive force against ethnic Albanian demonstrators (H.R.W.S., 1990).

Therefore, the Serbian and Yugoslav authorities' intervention in Kosovo was not intended to protect the Serb minority, as officially claimed, but to reassert control over Kosovo (Human Rights Watch Staff, 1990) and to ban Albanian-language education (Hajrizi, 2011).

After these harsh policies by the Serbo-Yugoslav authorities, Albanian parties and cadres in Kosovo strove to seize the initiative. On 2 July 1990, the Albanian delegates of the provincial Parliament gathered, despite being barred by police from entering the building, they read the

Declaration of Independence and on 7 September 1990 they proclaimed the Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo, which would be independent of Serbia but not of Yugoslavia. After Croatia and Slovenia declared their independence, the Albanians took a further step. On 10 October 1991, they organized a referendum in which they declared Kosovo's independence from Yugoslavia. Only Albania recognized this decision; Serbia declared it illegal and immediately began implementing a comprehensive policy of Serbianization. Education, vital in national and political terms, was the first target, followed by television, radio, and newspapers, all brought under state control. Albanian journalists were dismissed; Albanian curricula were removed; books in Albanian were withdrawn from public libraries; street names and monuments were Serbianized. Albanians were again addressed with the slur "shiptari" and in administration the nationalist label "Kosmet" (Kosovo and Metohija) came into use. In March 1990, some 7,000 pupils across 13 Kosovar municipalities and schools showed symptoms of poisoning, a deliberate action, Albanians believed, by Serbian authorities (Schmitt, 2008).

Serbian authorities confiscated school seals, thereby preventing official school documents (registers and diplomas) from being validated. Pupils were barred from attending through repressive measures, and schools were even surrounded by blinded military vehicles to block Albanian students and teachers from entering. Serbian authorities conditioned the entry of Albanian teachers into school buildings on signing a declaration pledging "to accept Serbia as their state and to organize educational work in harmony with the laws and by-laws of the Republic of Serbia" (Sommers & Buckland, 2004). Albanians refused to comply, and they also rejected Serbian curricula and teaching programs because they contained derogatory references to Albanians; every subject had been radically rewritten; Albanian history and culture were demeaned in all subjects, and Kosovo was omitted entirely. In Albanian language courses, celebrated writers such as Ismail Kadare, Dritëro Agolli, and Mark Krasniqi were removed from syllabi, while in Serbo-Croatian language and literature for elementary schools' authors like Rexhep Hoxha, Agim Deva, Migjeni, Naim Frashëri, Esad Mekuli, and Rifat Kukaj were expunged. Albanian writers of the National Renaissance and contemporary literature were replaced by Serbian and Yugoslav authors (Gjoshi, 2016). By the 1990s, this policy culminated in the closure of schools attended by Albanians and the replacement of Albanian teachers with Serbian teachers (Nizich & Laber, 1992).

How and Why the Parallel Education System in Kosovo Was Established and How it Functioned

Since most of the social life had been “Serbianized” (Schmitt, 2008), and the Serbian authorities completely banned instruction in Albanian on 1 September 1991 (Hyseni, 1996), Albanian teachers saw the need for a strategic shift. Through their unions – and with support from dismissed educational administrators and local parent groups – they took the initiative to create an alternative system of schooling (Clark, 2013, pp. 284-286).

To organize this parallel education, a ministerial council of the Government of Kosovo was formed in Pristina, comprising:

A representative of the “Naim Frashëri” Albanian Teachers’ Union;

A delegate from the Kosovo Pedagogical Institute;

A member of the Pristina Inter-municipal Pedagogical Entity;

A delegate from the Kosovo Education Unions;

A representative of the former Kosovo Education Community.

This council decided that all teaching would take place in private homes (Shatri, 2010).

To coordinate these efforts and develop solutions, a further Coordinating Council was established under the leadership of Prof. Dr. Fehmi Agani, who was later executed by Serbian police-military forces in May 1999.³ That Coordinating Council, which also included teams of educational experts, drafted an action plan with three variants: A (A-1, A-2), B (B-1) and C (C-1).

Under Variant A, all Albanian pupils who had not been forcibly expelled from their primary school buildings would attend. Variant B was intended for schools operating in two or three shifts, and in some cases even three to four shifts. Variant C was designed for those schools that had to vacate their premises and were forced to carry out teaching in private homes. The duration of lessons was to be flexible, depending on which variant was in use. According to Variant A (A-1 and A-2), each lesson would last 45 minutes. However, if a school ran three or four shifts, lessons under this variant could be shortened to 30 minutes. This reduction applied only during the winter term; in spring and summer, lessons would return to 45 minutes (Shatri, 2010). Following this

³ Bird, B., Watt, N. (1999, May 10) Kosovan leader's death condemned, *The Guardian*; Husarska, A. (1999, May 25) Death of a Peacemaker, *The Washington Post*.

model, the first “house-school” opened on 6 January 1992. By 15 February 1992, all primary and secondary schools in Kosovo had begun operating in private homes – also referred to as house-schools – according to the planned variants (A, B and C) (Pupovci, Hyseni, Salihaj, 2000). Albanian-language education in Kosovo during the period 1991–1999 is known by the name “parallel educational system”. Leading this initiative were 14,000 primary school teachers, around 4,000 secondary school teachers, and 862 university lecturers, most of whom had previously been dismissed from their positions by the Serbian administration.

At the time, the educational system in Kosovo included 452 full primary schools, 67 secondary schools, and one university comprising 14 faculties and 7 higher education institutions, with approximately 400,000 pupils and students (Koliqi, 2004).

Primary education was divided into two cycles: The **Lower Grade Cycle** and the **Upper Grade Cycle**.

The lower cycle consisted of four grades (I, II, III, and IV). It was also known as “*class-based teaching*”, attended by children aged 7 to 11. It was referred to as *class-based teaching* because the entire teaching process was conducted by a single person, known as the *classroom teacher* (for grades I–IV).

The upper cycle, on the other hand, was referred to as “*subject-based teaching*” and included grades V, VI, VII, and VIII of primary school. After completing grade VIII, students were issued a **certificate of achievement**, which reflected the academic performance of the student from grade one through grade eight. The certificate also included a grade for the student’s behavior (Pupovci, Hyseni, Salihaj, 2000).

Certificates for primary education, secondary school diplomas, and university degrees carried the seal of the “Republic of Kosovo”.

Based on the strategy developed for students excluded from school facilities, teaching was organized into five categories:

First category: schools that operated in facilities with physically separated classes, i.e., in legally recognized school buildings.

Second category: primary schools, mainly with physically separated classes, which, for various reasons, had been completely shut down and, from 1990 to 1999, did not appear on official records as schools.

Third category: schools that conducted lessons both in school facilities and in private homes.

Fourth category: primary schools whose students continuously received instruction in *home-schools*.

Fifth category: primary schools that were burned down by Serbian forces during the War (1998 and 1999), forcing students to relocate to other school facilities in Kosovo or to private homes (Shatri, 2010) and in some cases, even to Albania and Montenegro.

In private homes, from the 1991/92 school year until March 1999, students from over 70 primary schools (grades I–VIII), with separate classes (grades I–IV), were accommodated. In some schools (private homes), instruction was organized only for core subjects, while skill-based subjects (Physical Education, Music, Visual Arts, etc.) were not held at all. In the lower primary cycle, organizing lessons was somewhat easier, as each class was accommodated in one room (within a private house), whereas in the upper primary cycle, one class would be organized within an entire house. There were cases where some lower primary teachers conducted their lessons with their own students in their own homes – such as in Gurakoc of Istog, in Obiliq, in Pozheran of Viti, and elsewhere. Another form of organization was the block-scheduling model. A teacher assigned to a specific class would deliver the entire weekly subject load in one day. For example, the full weekly mathematics curriculum would be taught in one day, while on another day, instruction would focus solely on the Albanian language. In some schools, the learning process took place in rotating locations. On one day, classes would be held in certain homes, usually those of the students' parents, and the next day in another home (in Peja, Prizren, Viti, etc.). There were cases when locations changed daily or weekly. This method of organizing instruction served as a preventive and safety measure, as the police did not know where lessons for each school were being held. This was critical, as students, teachers, parents, and the homeowners of these “schoolhouses” were often mistreated. Instruction also took place in *odas* (traditional guest rooms reserved for men). In such cases, one room was used per class, meaning there were as many “classrooms” as there were classes. Lessons typically began at 8 or 9 in the morning. According to variant C, class periods were reduced to 30 minutes. This shortened duration applied only to core subjects, while other subjects, such as visual culture and music, could be shortened even further, sometimes to under 30 minutes, and were treated as consultative sessions. Oversight by the school administration and other responsible bodies was impossible under such conditions. This form of educational organization also faced other unexpected obstacles. There

were cases when homeowners requested the house to be vacated due to a family death, as the mourning period (*e pamja*, or condolence visits) had to be observed. In other cases, during religious holidays, families would ask that no lessons be held on those specific days (Shatri, 2010).

The Working Conditions in Private Homes and with a Parallel System were Unfavorable for many Reasons

Police violence continued, teachers were paid poorly and with significant delays, there was a lack of material resources, textbooks were missing, and even lesson plans and curricula for some subjects were absent (Pupovci, Hyseni, Salihaj, 2000; Hajrizi, 2011; Clark, 2013, pp. 284-286). The classrooms were far from meeting pedagogical standards; they were overcrowded. The rooms in private homes were not equipped with necessary furnishings, and there were neither chairs nor desks. Students were forced to sit on the floor. Notes were taken in notebooks placed on the floor or on the shoulders of classmates. Later, in many schools, desks and chairs were improvised.

The heating of the rooms was inadequate. The cleanliness of such spaces was difficult to maintain. In urban areas, lessons were often conducted in rooms that one had to pass through the kitchen to reach. The smell of food was always present. In rural areas, many of the rooms used for lessons lacked sufficient clean water, and in some cases, sanitary facilities were not installed. Students and teachers had to walk on foot from one village to another, and in these areas, transportation was lacking because the Serbian authorities, aiming to hinder free movement, intentionally disrupted land communication in Albanian-populated areas.

The power supply was also unreliable, particularly in Albanian-majority villages. In the 1998/99 school year, the organization of the learning process became even more difficult due to the onset of the war in Kosovo. What stands out during the parallel system is that the families, who owned the homes converted into schools, did their best within their means to create the best possible conditions. They took care of the cleanliness of the premises, ensured their heating, and maintained discipline both inside and outside the school. They even defended the students and teachers if they were attacked by the police, regardless of the consequences (Shatri, 2010). There were cases where parents were killed for not allowing their children to be mistreated by the Serbian police (Pupovci, Hyseni, Salihaj, 2000). During the years of the parallel

system, “there was practically no teacher training”; the teaching methods were traditional and outdated. Low-quality education was also a weakness of the parallel system because maintaining quality was impossible. The goal was to prevent the increase of illiteracy despite the difficult conditions. Ultimately, the parallel system was not only about education but also about politics (Sommers, Buckland, 2004). As Howard Clark rightly observes, the movement of parallel structures had four objectives: the survival of the Albanian society in Kosovo, contesting the legitimacy of Serbian state institutions and opposing the imposition of legitimacy by Albanian institutions, committing to civil resistance by refusing to provoke acts of violence, and finally, mobilizing international support (Clark, 2013; Ađır, 2012, p. 115).

Curriculas, Subjects, School Textbooks, and Funding

Up to the 1989/90 school year, when Kosovo still had an independent, autonomous education system, teaching was delivered in three instructional languages (Albanian, Serbian, and Turkish) under unified curricula and syllabi. After two parallel systems emerged, Albanian and Serbian, driven by differing community goals and visions, the gaps between them only widened. The Serbian-managed system moved toward alignment with the Soviet model (introducing Russian as a compulsory subject from grade III) and wove these objectives into its literature, history, music, and art programs. In contrast, the Albanian-language system sought to reweave the domestic ties severed after Serbia and Montenegro’s 1913 occupation of Kosovo: in collaboration with Albanian authorities, it harmonized curricula and syllabi, especially for national-orientation subjects.

In 1993, the Kosovo Pedagogical Institute launched curricular-reform activities. Thus, beginning in the 1994/95 school year, Kosovo introduced these key changes:

- The social-studies subject was added progressively in grades I–IV as “Social Education,” and in grades V–VIII as “Civic Education.”
 - The subjects “Nature and Society” (grades I–III) and “Social Knowledge” (grade IV) were removed.
 - In grade III, “Natural Science” replaced “Nature and Society.”
 - In grade IV, “History” replaced “Social Knowledge.”
- No substantive curricular revisions were made for mathematics, physics, or related subjects, whose syllabi remained virtually unchanged since 1988/89.

After the 1999 war, and in accordance with UN Security Council Resolution 1244, teaching in Albanian, Turkish, and Bosnian took place within a single system, even as it accommodated actual ethnic diversity and upheld equality (Pupovci, Hyseni, Salihaj, 2000). Following Kosovo's declaration of independence on 17 February 2008, the entire education system was overhauled to operate under the new Constitution and the Law on Pre-University Education.

In July 1991, Serbian authorities imposed violent measures against the Kosovo Institute for Textbooks and Teaching Aids, immediately initiating the exclusion of its Albanian staff. Despite immense challenges, from 1992 to 1999 the Institute published a total of 276 titles for primary and preschool-level students and teachers. Publication details by year:

1992: 8 titles (225,000 copies)

1993: 11 titles (197,319 copies)

1994: 24 titles (453,217 copies)

1995: 26 titles (519,846 copies)

1996: 46 titles (908,907 copies) the highest output to date and the year school-reading texts reappeared after many years of hiatus

1997: 43 titles (748,500 copies)

1998: 43 titles (527,770 copies) including pedagogical and school documentation (class diaries, student record books, and primary-education certificates)

1999: 77 titles (2,352,000 copies) the largest single-year print run in the 30-year history of the Institute of Textbooks and Teaching Aids (Pupovci, Hyseni, Salihaj, 2000).

After 1990, funding for Albanian-language education was completely cut off, making it necessary to create special structures to collect contributions and donations for Kosovo's parallel education system. To establish the minimal conditions for successful operation, Kosovo's educational bodies, both governmental and non-governmental (the Pedagogical Institute, the "Naim Frashëri" Albanian Teachers' Union, the Independent Union of Education, Science and Culture, and the Ministry of Education of Kosovo), took the initiative to finance Albanian schools institutionally. On 28 June 1991, the Central Financing Council was founded, composed of cadres delegated by these associations and institutions. In March 1992, municipal sub-councils were also formed to decentralize collection efforts (Hajrizi, 2011).

By Government Decision 01 No. 7/91, dated 15 December 1991, the rules for gathering financial resources were formalized: obligors and

types of contributions, contribution bases and rates, methods for distributing collected funds, and the financial control of expenditures (Gojani, 2009). Three main funding sources were established for the parallel system: remittances from abroad, community-raised funds, and other donations (Sommers & Buckland, 2004). These measures enabled Albanian teachers to begin receiving salaries in 1992, though pay was initially very low. In April 1992 the flat salary was just 20 DM; in April 1993 it rose to 80 DM; in 1994 to 120 DM; and by 1997 it reached 160 DM (Hajrizi, 2011). In 1993 alone, the system funded the salaries of some 20,000 teachers (Schmitt, 2008). Despite an atmosphere of intensified repression and conflict, and just before NATO's air campaign began in 1999 about 267,000 Kosovo Albanian pupils were still attending schools within the parallel education system. That continued operation under such conditions has been regarded as an impressive achievement (Sommers & Buckland, 2004).

The Impact of Repression on Albanian Education in Kosovo (1998-1999)

The Albanian-language curricula, subjects, textbooks, school literature, pedagogical organization of schools, and the close collaboration between Kosovo's educational and scientific institutions and those of Albania (in the 1970s) were perceived by Serbian authorities as primary sources of "counter-revolution" and "Albanian irredentist and separatist indoctrination". One of the earliest forms of state violence was the expulsion of Albanian students from primary schools. In Pristina, for example, a child was expelled after the 1981 demonstrations merely for writing "K.R." (Kosova Republikë) on the blackboard. At the Gurakoc (Istog) primary school, top-performing students were expelled solely because their parents had been imprisoned or politically persecuted. In 1986 alone, authorities imposed ideological-political sanctions on 73 education workers, disciplinary measures on 40, and administrative actions on 24 teachers for alleged "hostile activities." Seven school directors were dismissed, with punitive actions taken against nineteen others. Hundreds of Albanian students, teachers, and education workers suffered convictions or various forms of punishment (Shatri, 2010). During the Kosovo War of 1998-1999, a total of 132 school buildings in several municipalities were destroyed and burned (Frederiksen, Bakken, 2000). Additionally, 689 primary school buildings were damaged. According to the Summary Report from the International Damage and Destruction Assessment Group, the estimated

cost of the damage amounted to €29,105,000 (Osmani, 2010). UNICEF also reported that, along with the destruction of the 132 schools, many school libraries were also obliterated (Frederiksen, Bakken, 2000). Based on several reports, documents such as teaching diaries, student records, protocol books, lesson plans, employee files, financial documentation, and other school records were either taken, damaged, burned, or destroyed between 1989 and 1999. In the Municipality of Mitrovica alone, archival materials from the period 1945-1999 were destroyed or damaged in 27 primary schools. Similar destruction occurred in 10 primary schools in Podujevë, 9 in Klina, 8 in Kaçanik, and other areas.⁴

Conclusion

The case of Kosovo's parallel education system in the 1990s represents not only a unique phenomenon in European history but also a powerful example of how education can serve as a form of collective resistance. What began as an improvised response to repression evolved into a structured network that safeguarded literacy, language, and identity for an entire generation. In this sense, the system was more than a pedagogical arrangement; it was a social contract between teachers, parents, and pupils, grounded in the determination to resist assimilation and cultural erasure. At the same time, the experience highlights the paradox of resilience under duress. While the system succeeded in preventing illiteracy and preserving Albanian-language instruction, the conditions of clandestine schooling inevitably affected the quality of education. This tension between survival and standards underscores the broader costs of political repression on human capital and cultural development. The long-term legacy of the parallel education system is visible today in the many graduates who have become influential figures in politics, culture, and academia. Their trajectories testify to the enduring impact of education, even when conducted under extraordinary circumstances. The system thus stands as both a historical lesson and a reminder of the centrality of education in nation-building and cultural preservation.

Finally, future research could benefit from integrating post-war data collected by international organizations (UNMIK, OSCE,

⁴ Agency of State Archives of Kosovo. (n.d.). Fondi "Government of Kosovo – Commission for the Assessment of Damages," File: Destruction of Archival Material 1989–1999, Pristina 2003-2004.

UNICEF) on literacy rates and educational attainment among those educated in the parallel system. Such evidence would allow scholars to measure more precisely the outcomes of this unique experiment and to situate Kosovo's experience within comparative studies of education under repression. In doing so, the case of Kosovo may contribute to a broader understanding of how marginalized communities mobilize education as a tool of survival, identity, and resistance.

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Selcuk Kursad Koca

Sakarya University (Türkiye)

[skursadkoca@sakarya.edu.tr], ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5974-7553

Yavuz Koktan

Sakarya University (Türkiye)

[ykoktan@sakarya.edu.tr], ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0834-2377

An Analysis of the Shape-Shifting Motif in Turkish Tale Narratives from Macedonia

Abstract: *Turkish folk literature in Macedonia has taken shape since the Ottoman era, emerging as a rich oral cultural heritage through the blending of narrative traditions brought from Anatolia with local elements. Tales, legends, folk stories, and anecdotes form the core components of this narrative tradition and stand out as significant elements reflecting the region's cultural identity. These narratives exhibit parallels with the shared Turkish narrative heritage while also incorporating motifs specific to the region.*

This study focuses on the shape-shifting motif as it appears in Turkish folk narratives collected in Macedonia. The motif involves the transformation of a being or object into another form – such as a human turning into a stone, animal, tree, or bird; or the reverse, where animals and objects take on human form. These transformations may be permanent or temporary and are often symbolic.

The study is based on Makedonya Türk Halk Edebiyatı Metinleri by Nimetullah Hafız. In this work, the shape-shifting motif was identified in twelve tale narratives. The findings indicate that shape-shifting typically serves a functional role within a reward-and-punishment framework, although it occasionally appears as a magical or supernatural phenomenon.

Overall, the motif deepens the symbolic dimension of the narratives and facilitates the transmission of cultural values and collective beliefs. It also marks critical turning points in the stories, reflecting characters' inner transformation or destiny. The study concludes that shape-shifting is a meaningful narrative element in Turkish folk literature in Macedonia, with both individual and cultural significance.

Keywords: *Macedonia Turks; Folk tale narratives; Shape-shifting; Metamorphosis; Motif analysis; Turkish Folk Literature.*

Introduction

The motif of shape-shifting occupies a significant place in Turkic narrative traditions, originating from Central Asian oral cultures where

shamanistic beliefs, animism, and mythological themes were deeply intertwined with everyday life. In early Turkic myths and epics such as the *Oğuz Kağan Destanı* and *Manas*, transformation into animals, celestial bodies, or natural elements served not only as literary devices but also as reflections of cosmological worldviews. These motifs, which symbolized spiritual journeys, heroic trials, or moral transformations, persisted as the Turkic peoples migrated westward. With the Ottoman expansion and the centuries-long presence of Turks in the Balkans, these ancient narrative elements were adapted and localized within the sociocultural fabric of the region. Turkish folk tales in Macedonia, shape-shifting motifs—such as transformation into stone, animals, or plants—continue to echo the symbolic depth and cultural memory of their Central Asian roots while simultaneously integrating new meanings influenced by Balkan folklore and local belief systems. Thus, the study of shape-shifting motifs in Turkish narratives from Macedonia reveals a dynamic continuity between the mythic imagination of Asia and the rich oral traditions of the Balkans.

This continuity is not merely a passive preservation of ancient elements but reflects a living, evolving tradition shaped by historical processes. As Turkish communities firmly established themselves in the Balkans, particularly during the Ottoman period, they carried with them their oral storytelling heritage, adapting it to the new cultural environments they encountered. This evolution laid the groundwork for the rich and distinctive corpus of Turkish folk literature in Macedonia.

Turkish folk literature in Macedonia constitutes an essential element of the rich oral cultural heritage that Turkish communities in the Balkans have cultivated over the centuries. The Turkish presence in the region, which predates the Ottoman era (Hamzaoğlu, 2010; İsen, 1997), became firmly established during Ottoman rule. These communities not only sustained the narrative traditions they had brought primarily from Anatolia but also, through continuous interaction with local cultures, generated new forms of storytelling that reflect a dynamic process of cultural adaptation and innovation.

Research on Turkish folk literature in Macedonia plays a crucial role in documenting the cultural continuity of the Turkish presence in the region and in critically assessing oral narrative traditions through scholarly methods. Particularly from the second half of the twentieth century onward, numerous folk narratives have been collected and incorporated into academic literature through compilation and analytical studies. Researchers such as Hüseyin Süleyman, Sevim Piličkova,

Nimetullah Hafız, Arif Ago, Hamdi Hasan, Suat Engüllü, and Selçuk Kürşad Koca have gathered and published oral cultural products, including fairy tales, legends, folk songs, and manis, offering folkloric, linguistic, and literary analyses of these texts. Furthermore, several academic theses and articles produced in Turkey have examined Turkish folk literature in Macedonia, often conducting comparative analyses with Anatolian folk literature. These studies contribute not only to the documentation of Turkish folk culture in the Balkans but also to the visibility of the shared literary heritage of the Turkic world. In this context, ongoing research highlights the richness of Turkish folk literature in Macedonia, playing a critical role in preserving this cultural legacy for future generations.

Narrative genres such as fairy tales, legends, folk stories, anecdotes, and laments continue to exist in the region as reflections of its cultural diversity and historical continuity within oral memory (Koca, 2017a: 4). Turkish folk narratives of Macedoni exhibit both thematic parallels with the Turkish narrative of Anatolia tradition and variations featuring motifs unique to the region. In this context, the richness of these narratives in terms of content and form offers a distinct area of study within folklore research. As Koca and Çeçi state in their work *Gostivar Fairy Tales* (2021: 8), despite the richness of this tradition, comprehensive academic studies in the field have only recently begun, with earlier efforts primarily consisting of compilations. It can be noted that the collection of folk materials in this area commenced largely due to the *Yücelciler* movement, which contributed significantly to the revival of Balkan Turkish identity following the Ottoman period, particularly through activities related to Turkish culture in Macedonia, language, and literature (Koca, 2017b). A considerable part of these collected materials appeared in the journal *Sesler*, which was widely regarded as the voice of the Turkish community in Macedonia. Serdar Uğurlu, in his presentation titled ‘Turkish Folklore of Macedonia and the Journal *Sesler*’, highlights this development and enumerates the contributions to Turkish folk culture published in *Sesler* (2017: 640-672).

The motif of transformation, referring to the alteration of an individual’s or an object’s physical form into another entity, is a powerful and widespread narrative element. Pertev Naili Boratav defines this phenomenon as “the loss of essential qualities by humans, animals, plants, or inanimate objects, resulting in a transition from one form to another; the animation of the inanimate, or the transformation of the

animate into inanimate matter” (1973: 76). According to Bahaeddin Ögel, transformation or metamorphosis has been a recurring motif in the fairy tales and epics of Turkic peoples for thousands of years (1995: 133). In folk narratives, this motif is often situated within an ethical framework, functioning as part of a reward-and-punishment mechanism, though it also appears in instances of magical or supernatural transformations. Additionally, it symbolically reflects the character’s internal changes, pivotal life moments, or transformations of destiny, thereby adding depth to the narrative. In this regard, transformation serves as a functional motif that both expands the boundaries of the narrative world and facilitates the transmission of cultural values. According to Metin Ergun, transformations in narratives may occur either with or without the hero’s consent (1997: 176-177). In legends, transformations are typically permanent, while “in fairy tales and epics, transformations are often temporary and based on magic or sorcery” (Sakaoğlu & Türkan, 2019: 179). As Küçük suggests, this motif reflects subconscious desires and expectations (2020: 100) and may represent voluntary or involuntary changes experienced by the protagonist. When the transformation occurs by the hero’s will, it is often referred to as ‘don değişimi’ (metamorphosis or assumed transformation) (Aslan, 2004: 38). In the examined fairy tales, divine or supernatural figures that either facilitate or prevent transformations are also encountered. As noted by Nedim Bakırcı, characters such as Hızır, old men, dervishes, and sages frequently assist the heroes (2015: 186).

This study primarily draws on *Turkish Folk Literature Texts in Macedonia*, a compilation by Nimetullah Hafız, as its main source. This book, which includes examples from almost all genres of folk literature, is notably rich in folk narratives as well. Within the scope of the research, fairy tales and legends contained in the book were examined, and the narratives featuring the motif of transformation were identified. The analysis revealed that the motif of transformation appears in one legend and thirteen fairy tales. It was observed that the transformation motif fulfills different functions depending on the literary genre and that the transformations are not limited to humans but also involve various beings. It is evident from our field studies that the book does not encompass all of the legends and fairy tales narrated in Macedonia. Nonetheless, it undoubtedly constitutes a significant corpus Turkish Folklore narratives of Macedonia

Among the motifs observed in folk narratives, transformation manifests in various forms. Based on Ergun’s interpretation (Ergun,

1997: 198) of the motif of transformation classified under the D (Magic) category – specifically within the D800–D899: Transformation subcategory – of Stith Thompson’s *Motif-Index of Folk Literature*, twelve subtypes of transformation have been identified. In addition to these, a new category, ‘returning to human form,’ has been introduced in the present study to facilitate a more comprehensive evaluation of the narratives. In the examined Turkish folk narratives in Macedonia, five distinct forms of transformation are observed: transformation into stone, into an animal, into a plant, into a human, and returning to human form. These instances of transformation illustrate an integrated perception of humanity and nature, reflecting a worldview wherein humans are not perceived as separate from the natural world (Ayaz, 2022: 596).

As is well known, Stith Thompson’s *Motif-Index of Folk Literature* systematically classifies recurring narrative elements (motifs) found in world folk literature. The theme of transformation is one of the key motifs in this index and is examined under various categories. The transformations identified in the analyzed narratives have been evaluated in accordance with the categories listed in the *Motif-Index of Folk Literature*:

- D865 – Transformation to stone,
- D855 – Transformation to animal,
- D860 – Transformation to plant,
- D870 – Transformation to human.

1. D865 – Transformation to Stone

Throughout history, from primitive times to the modern era, stone has carried various symbolic meanings for humanity. It has been revered as a sacred entity and used as a talisman believed to protect against evil. Different societies have utilized stones for diverse purposes, such as marking temples or identifying graves, thereby granting stone a significant place in social life.

In the Turkish narrative tradition, stone also appears as a component of the transformation motif. In these narratives, petrification is not limited to humans; animals, plants, supernatural beings, and objects are also observed to undergo transformation into stone.

The ‘transformation to stone’ motif is widely found in Anatolian and Balkan legends, often occurring within a framework of reward or punishment. Turkish legends such as *Gelin Kayası* (The Bride’s Rock) (Feyzioğlu, 2011: 115–133), *Gelin Alayı* (The Bridal Procession), *Gelin Taşı* (The Bride’s Stone), *Kadın Kayası* (The Woman’s

Rock), and *Asker Taşı* (The Soldier's Stone) (Oğuz & Ersoy, 2007) incorporate this motif in various forms.

In the examination of Turkish folk tales in Macedonia, the 'transformation to stone' motif was identified in two narratives. In the cases analyzed, this transformation was found to be reversible.

1.1. *Kör Adam (The Blind Man)*

The tale *Kör Adam* (The Blind Man), collected from Kalkandelen (Tetovo), features the motif of transformation into stone.

In the story, a blind man has three sons. The man learns that a queen living beyond the ninth mountain possesses a nightingale and a flower; if the flower is brought to him, his sight will be restored. His eldest son sets out to retrieve it but, despite an old man's warning not to look back, he hears his mother's voice, turns around, and is turned to stone. The same fate befalls the second son. The youngest son also embarks on the journey but obeys the warning and reaches the queen's palace. There, he encounters a lion and a goat, with grass placed before the lion and meat before the goat. He switches their food and thus earns the lion's support. Finding the queen asleep, he steals the nightingale, the flower, and the queen's ring, then flees. The magic ring breaks the spell, restoring his brothers to human form. The youngest son returns home with his brothers, washes his father's face with the flower, and the blind man regains his sight. Eventually, the queen arrives, marries the youngest son, and they celebrate with a wedding lasting forty days and forty nights.

In this tale, human transformation into stone is explicitly tied to disobedience: the sons are forbidden from looking back or responding to forbidden sounds, and when they violate this rule, they are turned to stone. Transformation here functions as a punishment for disobedience and failure to adhere to prescribed rules. The success of the youngest son emphasizes the importance of perseverance and forward movement without succumbing to distraction. The motif of transformation into stone in this narrative encapsulates key folkloric elements of trial and punishment, symbolizing the stagnation and impotence of those who fail the test, while highlighting that patience and faith lead to ultimate success (Hafız, 1989: 224-225).

1.2. *Hızır'ın Kızı (Hızır's Daughter)*

Another narrative featuring the motif of transformation into stone is the tale *Hızırın Kızı* (Hızır's Daughter), collected from Gostivar.

The story begins with a state official overhearing the wishes of three sisters. The eldest and middle sisters boast that they could bake bread large enough to feed all the soldiers or weave a tent big enough for the entire army, yet they fail to fulfill their promises. The youngest sister claims she will bear a boy with golden hair and a girl with pearl-like teeth – and she does. Driven by jealousy, the elder sisters place the newborns in a chest and cast them into the sea, replacing them with a dog and a cat. Believing he has been deceived, the ruler punishes his wife. The chest is found by a wise old man, who raises the children.

Years later, the golden-haired boy learns of his true heritage. By purchasing abandoned palaces and horses of the state, he begins to reclaim his rightful place. However, the jealous aunts impose new challenges, demanding that he bring Hızır's Flower and Hızır's Daughter. The young man accomplishes these tasks, aided by a magical seal that protects him from petrification and reverses the stone transformations of others. During a feast, Hızır's Daughter recounts a story revealing the entire truth to the ruler, thereby exposing the boy's true identity. The treacherous aunts are punished, the queen regains her rightful place, and the tale concludes with a happy ending.

In the narrative, the young hero faces the danger of being turned to stone while attempting to retrieve Hızır's Daughter. Hızır's Daughter possesses supernatural powers; at her first cry, the horses turn to stone; at her second cry, the young man is half-petrified; and a third cry would have fully turned him into stone. However, the magical seal he carries prevents complete transformation by neutralizing the curse, also transforming Hızır's Daughter in the process. The ability of the hero to prevent his petrification by kissing the seal highlights the motif of magical objects as instruments of salvation. Hızır's Daughter, obeying the hero's commands, reverses the transformations by sprinkling sherbet over the half-petrified young man, the horses, and the ruler's soldiers. In this tale, the motif of petrification serves as a major trial within the hero's journey. Adherence to rules, patience, and possession of protective magic allow the protagonist to avert his fate, while cursed individuals can be restored to their original state through the correct magical intervention. This reinforces the themes of justice and trials that are central to fairy tale narratives (Hafiz, 1989: 254-256).

2. D855 – Transformation Into an Animal

The motif of transformation into an animal is a prominent element frequently encountered in Turkish folk narratives, particularly in legends and fairy tales. Sometimes this transformation occurs as a reward or punishment through the will of God or the prayers of saints, while at other times it results from the intervention of supernatural beings such as sorcerers or magicians. The meaning attributed to the transformation varies depending on the narrative genre: in legends, it often serves as a moral lesson, whereas in fairy tales, it primarily introduces elements of entertainment and mystery.

The transformation of humans into wolves, birds, snakes, or other animals symbolizes both the human connection to nature and inner psychological change. This motif offers valuable insights into the belief systems, value structures, and imagination of the community. Moreover, “motifs, which hold vital importance in the formation of narratives, contribute not only to the shaping of the plot but also to the enrichment of the narrative” (Demirtaş, 2020: 234).

Within the analyzed narratives, the motif of transformation into animals appears in four fairy tales: in two cases, the protagonist transforms into a bird; in one case, into a donkey; and in another, into a deer. Kadriye Türkan notes that the fate of the transformed hero corresponds to the nature of the animal into which they change (2008: 149). In these tales, the heroes who become birds fly freely, the hero transformed into a donkey becomes subject to the control of whoever holds its halter, and the hero transformed into a deer merges into the wilderness and remains unnoticed. Across numerous folk narratives within the Turkic world, transformations into various animals such as moles, monkeys, rabbits, and birds are frequently observed (Boratav, 1997: 63).

2.1. *Haydutlar (The Tale of the Bandits)*

Among the folk tales featuring shape-shifting, *Haydutlar* (The Tale of the Bandits) addresses the motif of transformation into a bird. The tale can be summarized as follows: A woman has two daughters; she favors her biological daughter while despising her stepdaughter. She deceives the stepdaughter and takes her to the mountains intending to kill her, but the girl survives and seeks refuge in the house of three bandits. The mother attempts to kill her again by poisoning her with a comb. The bandits place the girl in a glass coffin. The prince discovers her, removes the poison from the comb, restores her to life, and marries her. The malicious stepmother poisons the girl once more with a needle,

transforming her into a bird. The prince captures the bird, removes the needle, and the girl returns to human form; they live happily ever after.

The motif of transformation into a bird, as seen in this tale, is a common element in both Turkish and global folk narratives. In this story, the motif is triggered by a malevolent character (the stepmother) using magic or a magical object to transform someone against their will. The transformation occurs beyond the hero's control, symbolizing a temporary withdrawal from the world, a period of trial, and ultimately the attainment of deserved happiness. Moreover, the motif serves as a turning point in the tale, ensuring justice is served. It strengthens the dramatic structure of the story while highlighting the widespread folk narrative themes of magical transformation and eventual return (Hafiz, 1989: 217-218).

2.2. *Gülperyanım Gülperyanım (My Gülperyan, My Gülperyan)*

In Turkish narratives from Macedonia, the theme of human-to-bird transformation is also evident in the tale *Gülperyanım Gülperyanım* (My Gülperyan, My Gülperyan), collected from Üsküp (Skopje).

The tale can be summarized as follows: A sultan's son disappears during childhood and remains missing for many years. One day, while a beautiful girl is sitting at home, a bird approaches and suddenly transforms into a human. The young man and the girl fall in love, but he soon vanishes, leaving behind only his veil. Later, while fetching water, the girl notices a strange-acting rooster, follows it, and arrives at a giant's house. The rooster protects her. The young man, once again appearing as a bird, expresses his love for her. Following his instructions, the girl enters the palace as a servant. Every night, the young man, in bird form, comes to the window to speak with her. One of the other servants observes this and informs the sultan's wife, who realizes that the girl is involved with her lost son. The young man instructs the girl to reveal the way to break his curse: burning forty-one pieces of cloth. Once this is done, he regains his human form and reunites with his family. The tale concludes with a grand wedding.

In the tale, the sultan's son reappears in bird form, although the manner of his transformation is not explicitly explained. It is implied to be the result of a supernatural spell or the workings of fate – an ambiguity common in folk narratives, which adds a layer of mystery and enchantment to the story. The boy's disappearance is thus linked to his transformation into a bird. Despite taking the form of a bird, he retains

his emotional and cognitive human traits, as seen in his love for Gülp-eryan, his ability to speak, and his memories. Although he moves between human and bird forms – first appearing in the garden, then at the giant’s house, and later at the palace window – his human identity remains intact.

In the final part of the tale, the young man reveals that he can be freed from his bird form through a magical act: burning forty-one knotted pieces of cloth. This suggests that his transformation is indeed the result of a spell, reinforcing the motif of magical intervention common in fairy tales (Hafız, 1989: 222-223).

2.3. Humma Kuşu (The Humma Bird)

Another narrative featuring the motif of transformation is the tale *Humma Kuşu* (The Humma Bird), collected from Kalkandelen (Tetovo). In this story, a human transforms into a donkey.

The tale tells of a poor man who finds a Humma bird that lays eggs of gold, leading him to great wealth. However, during his absence, his wife is deceived into killing the bird. Their children consume the bird’s heart and liver, thereby gaining magical powers. When an Arab master notices the missing organs, he orders the children’s execution, but a servant helps them escape. One of the children discovers he can find money every morning. Later, after being tricked by a girl he loves into losing his magical heart, he falls into poverty and wanders into a forest. There, he eats the fig of a magical tree and transforms into a donkey. Upon consuming the fig of another tree, he regains his human form. He subsequently uses the magical fig to transform the deceitful girl into a donkey as an act of punishment. Eventually, he reunites with his brother and father, and the treacherous mother is punished. The boy then transforms the ‘world’s most beautiful girl’ back into human form and marries her.

In this tale, the motif of transformation into a donkey occurs through the consumption of magical figs found in the forest. One child eats the fig of the first tree and transforms into a donkey, but by eating the fig from the second tree, he returns to his human form. The protagonist uses the transformative power of the magical fig to exact revenge on the deceiving girl, illustrating transformation as a means of punishment. However, by later restoring her human form, the tale emphasizes its underlying sense of justice. These transformation motifs demonstrate how fate can be altered through magical objects and enchanted

foods, revealing that transformation can serve both punitive and redemptive functions within the narrative (Hafiz, 1989: 225-226).

2.4. *Yusufcukle Fatmacik (Yusufcuk and Fatmacik)*

Another tale featuring the motif of transformation into an animal is *Yusufcukle Fatmacik* (Yusufcuk and Fatmacik), collected from Üsküp (Skopje). In this tale, the motif of transformation appears at multiple stages.

The story can be summarized as follows: A husband and wife live with their two children. One day, the father accidentally consumes human flesh and subsequently develops the urge to eat his son, Yusuf. Learning of this, the daughter, Fatmacik, convinces her brother to flee. As they escape, their father pursues them, but the magical obstacles created by Fatmacik's thrown objects hinder his chase. During their flight, Yusuf, unable to withstand his thirst, drinks from a forbidden water source and transforms into a deer. Fatmacik is left alone and climbs a tree for safety. A bey (ruler) notices her and attempts various methods to persuade her to come down, including having the tree cut down. However, Yusuf, now a deer, licks the cuts on the tree, magically healing them and preventing its fall.

Eventually, an old woman tricks Fatmacik into descending from the tree, leading to her marriage with the bey. However, jealous servants conspire against her, throwing her into the sea and taking her place. A fish swallows Fatmacik. Upon the bey's return, he is deceived by the impostor. Meanwhile, the impostor demands that Yusuf, the deer, be slaughtered for food. Before his execution, Yusuf requests to be taken to the seaside, where Fatmacik emerges from the fish, revealing the truth. The bey punishes the deceitful servant, and Yusuf and Fatmacik live happily thereafter.

In this tale, the transformation occurs when Yusuf drinks from the forbidden water and becomes a deer. Although Fatmacik warns him not to drink, Yusuf succumbs to his thirst, leading to his transformation. This moment reflects the inevitable working of fate, deeply connected with supernatural elements. The transformation serves two functions: first, it acts as a punishment for disregarding a prohibition, echoing the widespread folkloric concepts of 'taboo' and 'forbidden acts'; second, it functions as a protective mechanism. As a deer, Yusuf is able to evade enemies and survive, demonstrating that transformation is not always a curse but can also serve as a means of protection.

Furthermore, Yusuf's act of licking the wounded tree to heal it suggests that he gains a magical connection with nature, elevating him beyond the status of an ordinary human to that of a magical being. Unlike other tales, no reversal of the transformation – returning to human form – is observed in this narrative (Hafiz, 1989: 229-230).

3. D860 – Transformation into a Plant

Among the various transformation motifs in Turkish folk narratives, transformation into a plant stands out, particularly in the genres of legends and fairy tales. This motif typically involves the transformation of a human into a plant – such as a tree, flower, or vine – as a result of extraordinary events, functioning as a form of punishment, reward, or the effect of magic.

Transformation into a plant often carries symbolic meanings. For instance, a lover who is unable to reunite with their beloved may transform into a tree, flower, or vine, symbolizing eternal love and longing. Such transformations not only intensify the emotional depth of the narrative but also establish a powerful connection between humanity and nature.

As noted by Özcan and Kaval, “transformation into a tree usually occurs outside the hero's will” (Özcan & Kaval, 2019: 321).

Among the narratives examined, one tale incorporates the motif of transformation into a tree. This tale appears to be a folkloric account explaining the origin of the quince and pomegranate trees, combining elements of myth and fairy tale tradition.

3.1. *Ağlayan Ayva ile Gülen Nar (The Crying Quince and the Laughing Pomegranate)*

The motif of transformation into a tree is prominently featured in the tale *Ağlayan Ayva ile Gülen Nar* (The Crying Quince and the Laughing Pomegranate). In this story, humans transform into fruit trees. The narrative centers around Felek, a supernatural figure, who transforms two young individuals into trees as a consequence of their disobedience.

The tale can be summarized as follows: Once upon a time, a young man named Ayva (Quince) and a girl named Nar (Pomegranate) set out to a mill to grind flour. However, they waste time along the way and arrive at the mill in the evening. The miller, an old man named Felek, refuses to let them enter and warns them not to enter the mill, not to drink from the crystal stream, and not to fall asleep, as he must leave

to visit a magical spring. Disregarding his warnings, the youths enter the mill, drink from the stream, and fall asleep. Upon returning at dawn, Felek finds them asleep and, sprinkling them with magical water, transforms them into fruit trees. After the transformation, Ayva begins to weep while Nar laughs. Felek tells them they will remain this way forever, and that they will bear the names they had as humans. Consequently, quince is regarded as a sorrowful fruit and pomegranate as a joyful one.

In this tale, transformation serves as a punitive mechanism. The protagonists are transformed into trees as a direct result of ignoring Felek's warnings. In Turkish folk narratives, the use of transformation as a form of moral enforcement is a common motif. Here, the metamorphosis of Ayva and Nar symbolizes the consequences of disobedience. Additionally, transformation is framed as part of the natural and cosmic order. The name and role of Felek suggest an authority that embodies fate itself. By transforming the youths into trees, Felek not only punishes them but also integrates them into the eternal cycle of nature, aligning with animistic beliefs that emphasize the interconnectedness of humans and the natural world. Furthermore, the weeping of the quince and the laughter of the pomegranate reflect the symbolic extension of the characters' personalities. These emotional characteristics persist even after their transformation, aligning with traditional associations: quince is known for its tart, melancholic flavor, while pomegranate is celebrated for its sweetness and vitality (Hafiz, 1989: 199-200).

4. D870 – Transformation Into a Human

In Turkish folk narratives, the motif of transformation into a human often occurs through supernatural or magical intervention and symbolizes both internal and external transformations of characters. This motif, whether involving an animal or another being transforming into a human, or a human reverting to human form after being transformed into another entity, adds dramatic tension to the narrative while also enhancing its thematic depth.

Beings that become human typically undergo an emotional or moral development; for example, the transformation of a loyal animal into a human often symbolizes a reward for its loyalty and virtue. Moreover, shapeshifting beings frequently serve to instruct human characters, compelling them to make moral choices between good and evil. In

many narratives, such transformations represent a hero's quest for identity or personal evolution, emphasizing the significance of social values and individual responsibilities.

This motif reflects the Turkish people's understanding of the profound connections between humanity, nature, and the cosmos, and contributes a unique richness to folk narratives.

In the tales examined, the motif of transformation into a human appears in four narratives: transformations from a frog, an orange, a snake, and an unspecified animal into human form.

4.1. *Kurbağa Gelin (The Frog Bride)*

The tale *Kurbağa Gelin* (The Frog Bride), collected from Kalkan-delen (Tetovo), offers a significant example of the transformation motif within Turkish folk literature, particularly from the perspective of transformation into a human. In this story, a magical transformation and the revelation of a hidden identity are central elements.

The narrative can be summarized as follows: A man instructs his three sons to shoot arrows at the palace gate in order to win the hand of the sultan's daughters. The two elder sons succeed, but the youngest fails three times and, as a result, must marry a frog. When the two elder brothers set off to attend a wedding with their brides, the youngest and his frog wife also depart. The elder brothers and their wives ride in golden carriages, while the youngest rides in a muddy cart with the frog. Upon entering the cart, however, the frog transforms into a stunningly beautiful woman. Witnessing this, the onlookers remove the youngest couple from the muddy cart and place them in a golden carriage, while relegating the elder brothers to the muddy one.

Later, the father sets an impossible task for the youngest son: to find a tent large enough to cover the entire world. With his wife's help, he succeeds. Following this trial, the father presents a grim ultimatum, declaring that either the son must kill him, or he will kill the son. Left with no choice, the son kills his father, inherits his estate, and lives happily with his wife.

The frog figure at the beginning of the tale initially represents an entity marginalized and undervalued by society. Over time, the frog's inner strength is revealed, culminating in its transformation into human form, which symbolizes the themes of identity and self-worth. The frog's transformation sends the message that true value lies not in external appearances but in inner virtues and strength. In this tale, the function of the transformation motif goes beyond a mere physical

change; it symbolizes the character's internal maturation and acceptance into society as a fully developed individual. The frog's eventual human form offers not only physical but also moral and social rewards to the hero.

This transformation reflects a common theme in folk narratives: the tension and eventual reconciliation between outward appearance and inner value. Additionally, the transformation serves as a metaphor for rebirth and social acceptance, emphasizing the importance of recognizing true worth beneath superficial judgments (Hafiz, 1989: 207).

4.2. Portakal Kızı (The Orange Girl)

Another narrative featuring the motif of transformation is the tale *Portakal Kızı* (The Orange Girl). In this story, the transformation involves the change from a fruit into a human being, highlighting a miraculous birth and a supernatural metamorphosis.

The tale can be summarized as follows: A woman and her husband, unable to have children, pray to God for a child. Their prayers are answered, and the woman gives birth to an orange. Over time, a beautiful young girl grows inside the orange. One day, when the girl emerges from the peel, she is seen by the son of a bey (local ruler). With the help of his mother, the bey's son acquires the orange and places it on a shelf in their home. Whenever the bey's mother and sister attend weddings, the Orange Girl expresses her desire to join them, but each time she is mistreated and prevented from doing so. Nevertheless, she manages to attend the weddings, each time transforming into a beautiful maiden. The bey's mother, unaware of her true identity, eventually proposes her as a bride for her son. Upon realizing the truth, the bey's mother accepts her, and the tale concludes with a joyful wedding.

In *The Orange Girl*, the transformation motif is employed through a direct physical metamorphosis, where the character's identity undergoes a profound change. Initially existing as a fruit, the Orange Girl transforms into a human being as the result of a divine response to a prayer. This supernatural transformation allows her to be recognized and accepted within human society.

The transformation motif in this tale symbolizes not only a physical change but also the broader process of social acceptance and identity formation. Through this transformation, the narrative emphasizes a deep and fundamental development within the character's life. The tale thus highlights transformation as both a literal and metaphorical journey toward self-realization and societal integration (Hafiz, 1989: 208).

4.3. *Kirk Bir Entari (Forty-One Dresses)*

Another narrative that features the motif of transformation into a human is the tale *Kirk Bir Entari* (Forty-One Dresses), collected from Ohrid. This story centers on the revelation of a hidden identity.

The tale can be summarized as follows: A sultan and his wife, unable to have children, one day see a snake and its offspring while on a walk. They declare, 'If only we could have a child, even if it were a snake.' Their wish is granted, and a snake-child is born. As he grows, the snake-child desires to marry. A poor man's daughter is purchased to be his bride. Distraught, the girl is visited by a saintly figure in a dream, who advises her to have forty-one dresses made. On their wedding night, she is to have the snake shed one layer of skin for each dress removed. Following the saint's instructions, the girl succeeds; with each dress, the snake sheds a layer of skin until he finally transforms into a handsome young man. She then burns the discarded skins, declaring, 'A snake cannot live in the palace'.

Later, when the young man travels to a distant land, a deceitful messenger contrives to have his wife expelled. Disguised as a man, the wife journeys to the foreign kingdom, proves her identity through a clever contest, and exposes the messenger's treachery. The story concludes with the husband and wife reunited and justice restored.

The narrative begins with a sultan and his wife who, after fervent prayers, are blessed with a child in the form of a snake. Although the child has the physical appearance of a snake, he possesses human intellect and emotions. This 'animal-form human' motif is common in folk narratives, often symbolizing a test or magical condition. A saintly figure serves as the guiding force in the story, offering critical advice.

The snake's transformation into a human is portrayed through a gradual shedding process involving the removal of forty layers of skin, symbolized by the girl's forty-one dresses. The symbolic use of the numbers forty and forty-one, along with the burning of the snake skins, signifies the irreversible severing of the hero's animalistic past – a common motif in folklore, where destroying an object is necessary to break a spell.

Notably, the transformation is only possible through the intervention of the female character, who is portrayed as intelligent, determined, and courageous. By following the saint's advice, requesting the forty-one dresses, executing the shedding ritual, and destroying the skins, she plays an active, central role in enabling the transformation. In this way,

the female protagonist is not passive but stands as the true catalyst for change within the narrative (Hafiz, 1989: 219-220).

4.4. *Tüvlice Masalı (The Tale of the Furry Creature)*

Another narrative featuring the motif of transformation into a human is the tale *Tüvlice Masalı* (The Tale of the Furry Creature), collected from Üsküp (Skopje). In this tale, the transformation involves a furry, animal-like being (referred to as *tüvlice*, meaning ‘furry’ in Turkish) who ultimately reveals a hidden human identity.

The tale can be summarized as follows: A woman wishes to arrange a marriage for her son, but he prefers hunting and attending nighttime gatherings. One day, during a hunting trip, he captures a mysterious furry creature known as a *Tüvlice*, who is in fact an enchanted girl. Each night, the *Tüvlice* adorns herself in different styles and secretly attends the gatherings, drawing the young man’s attention. When asked where she lives, she enigmatically responds with phrases like ‘where fezzes are worn,’ ‘where sashes are tied,’ and ‘where watches are broken.’ Although the young man’s mother searches for her in these places, she cannot find her. Eventually, the young man falls ill from longing. One day, the *Tüvlice* drops a ring into his soup. Recognizing the ring, the young man summons her. She unveils herself, revealing a beautiful girl, and they marry, celebrating with a wedding that lasts forty days and forty nights.

In this tale, the transformation motif appears through the magical metamorphosis of a furry, undefined creature into a human girl. This repeated transformation highlights the themes of concealed identity, recognition, and ultimate acceptance. The act of dropping a ring into the soup serves as the symbolic catalyst for the full revelation of her true form.

The motif here carries magical, ethical, and symbolic dimensions. Additionally, the motif of the ‘forty days and forty nights’ wedding vividly evokes traditional conceptions of communal celebration within folk culture (Hafiz, 1989: 227-229).

5. Return to Human Form

One of the most striking examples of the transformation motif in folk narratives is the restoration of a character to human form after being transformed into another being. Typically triggered by magic, a curse, or punishment, this transformation is reversed at the end of the tale or legend through the hero’s courage, loyalty, or righteous actions.

Characters who have been turned into stone, animals, or plants are often released from their altered state by means of a miracle, a magical object, or the intervention of a sacred figure.

Thus, the motif of returning to human form not only enhances the dramatic structure of the narrative but also conveys moral or mystical messages. It holds an important place in folk narratives, symbolizing both the realization of justice and the promise of hope and salvation.

As the summaries of the relevant tales have already been provided under earlier sections, they are not repeated here to avoid redundancy. Among the narratives analyzed, five fairy tales feature the motif of return to human form.

5.1. *Haydutlar (The Bandits)*

Among the narratives analyzed, the tale *Haydutlar (The Bandits)*, collected from Üsküp (Skopje), features the motif of transformation occurring in a sequence of human–bird–human.

The central transformation theme in the tale unfolds when the stepdaughter is poisoned with a comb and a needle, leading to her death. She is later revived in her coffin, subsequently transforms into a bird, and finally regains her human form. The transformation motif is triggered by the use of magical objects, with the return to human form achieved by discovering and removing the enchanted needle.

Thus, the narrative illustrates how magical objects both facilitate and resolve transformations, linking the motif of metamorphosis to broader themes of death, rebirth, and restoration (Hafiz, 1989: 217-218).

5.2. *Gülperyanım Gülperyanım (My Gülperyan, My Gülperyan)*

In the Turkish narrative tradition from Macedonia, the tale *Gülperyanım Gülperyanım (My Gülperyan, My Gülperyan)*, collected from Üsküp (Skopje), prominently features the transformation motif, specifically involving a transition from human to bird form and subsequently back to human form. This motif exemplifies the pattern of magical transformation frequently encountered in Turkish folk narratives.

In the tale, the sultan's lost son intermittently appears in bird form. During these appearances, he temporarily regains his human form to reveal himself to a young girl before reverting to a bird and flying away. A similar pattern occurs at the house of the giant, where he again alternates between bird and human forms.

Although the reason for his initial transformation into a bird is not explained, the narrative follows a classic motif of ritual resolution to end the transformation. His mother binds and burns forty-one pieces of cloth – a magical act traditionally used to reverse transformations. The motif of ‘forty’ and the ‘burning ritual’ are deeply rooted in Turkish folk culture and symbolically serve to restore order.

In *My Gülperyan, My Gülperyan*, the return to human form is achieved through the power of love, loyalty, and ritual, reflecting both the mystical and emotional dimensions central to folk beliefs (Hafız, 1989: 222-223).

5.4. Humma Kuşu (The Humma Bird)

Another narrative featuring the motif of return to human form is the tale *Humma Kuşu* (The Humma Bird).

In this story, a sequence of transformation occurs: from human to animal, and then back to human. The animal form chosen is a donkey, and the transformation is triggered by the consumption of a magical fig.

At the beginning of the tale, the Humma Bird – a mystical and magical creature rather than an ordinary bird – lays eggs that generate a small fortune for its owner each day. Two children consume parts of the bird: one eats its heart, the other its liver, thereby acquiring supernatural powers. This motif, where eating the heart, liver, or flesh of a magical being grants special abilities, is a common feature in folk narratives.

The transformation motif appears when one of the children mistakenly eats a fig from a magical tree and turns into a donkey. Later, by consuming a different fig from another tree, he regains his human form. This progression demonstrates not only the direct physical aspect of transformation but also the organic, nature-based means of reversing it.

The child uses this knowledge strategically: he transforms the ‘world’s most beautiful girl’ into a donkey as an act of revenge, illustrating how transformation can also serve as an instrument of justice. In the end, he feeds her another magical fig, restoring her human form, and they marry. Thus, the tale concludes with a happy ending (Hafız, 1989: 225-226).

5.5. Hızırın Kızı (Hızır’s Daughter)

Another narrative featuring the motif of return to human form is the tale *Hızırın Kızı* (Hızır’s Daughter), collected from Gostivar. In this

tale, the transformation involves a progression from human to stone and then back to human form.

The motif of returning to human form is intricately interwoven with classical folk narrative traditions, incorporating themes of magic, moral testing, personal maturation, and the restoration of justice.

In the tale, the young hero sets out to retrieve Hızır's Daughter. However, upon his arrival, Hızır's Daughter, displeased by his presence, curses him by declaring, 'Turn to stone!' On the first occasion, his horse is turned into stone; on the second, the boy himself is turned to stone up to his waist. Just before a third curse would fully petrify him, he remembers the 'seal' left to him by his father. Following his father's advice – that in times of dire need he should kiss the seal to dispel hardship – he kisses the seal, which breaks the spell.

The act of kissing the seal symbolizes respect for ancestry and the importance of recalling the wisdom of the past. Upon recognizing the boy's sincerity and true identity, Hızır's Daughter agrees to fulfill his wishes.

Another magical object featured in the tale is a sherbet. Hızır's Daughter sprinkles sherbet over those who had previously been turned into stone, restoring them to human form. Even the sultan's soldiers, who had been petrified earlier, are revived through this act. Thus, the hero is not only able to reclaim his own fate but also acquires the power to alter the destinies of others. In doing so, the narrative symbolizes the achievement of broader social justice (Hafiz, 1989: 254-256).

Table 1: Analysis of Transformation Motifs

Narrative Title and Type	Type of Transformation	Instrument of Transformation	Instrument of Liberation	Reason for Transformation	Description of Transformation
Kör Adam (The Blind Man)	Human → Stone → Human	Forbidden sound	Magical object (ring, handkerchief)	Punishment, spell breaking	Two brothers turn into stone and then return to human form.
Hızır'ın Kızı (Hızır's Daughter)	Human → Stone → Human	Hızır's Daughter's curse	Magical object (seal)	Magic and sorcery	A child is turned into stone and then restored to

					human form.
Haydutlar (The Bandits)	Human → Bird → Human	Step-mother's attack with poisoned needle	Removal of needles	1- Magic and sorcery 2- Magic and sorcery	The girl transforms into a bird and later returns to human form.
Humma Kuşu (The Humma Bird)	Human → Donkey → Human	Eating magical fig	Eating magical fig	1- Magic and sorcery 2- Punishment	A boy and later a girl transform into donkeys, then return to human form.
Yusufcukle Fatmacik (Yusufcuk and Fatmacik)	Human → Deer	Drinking from a magical water source	None	Punishment	Yusuf, ignoring warnings, drinks water and transforms into a deer.
Ağlayan Ayva ile Gülen Nar (The Crying Quince and the Laughing Pomegranate Trees)	Human → Quince and Pomegranate Trees	Supernatural power	None	Punishment	Ayva and Nar, ignoring the miller's warnings, turn into trees.
Kurbağa Gelin (The Frog Bride)	Frog → Human	Magical transformation	None	Reward	A frog suddenly transforms into a beautiful maiden.
Portakal Kızı (The Orange Girl)	Orange → Human	Magical birth and magical resolution	None	Supernatural origin and hidden identity	A child born as an orange emerges as a beautiful girl.
Kırk Bir Entari (Forty-One Dresses)	Snake → Human	Magical birth and spell breaking	None	Supernatural origin and hidden identity	Through a ritual involving forty-one dresses, the snake child

					becomes human.
Gülperyanım Gülperyanım (My Gülperyan, My Gülperyan)	Human → Bird → Human	1- Unknown cause 2- Magical ritual	Burning forty-one knotted cloths	1- Disappearance 2- Magical love and hidden identity	A lost child transforms into a bird and later returns to human form through love.
Tüvlice Masalı (The Tale of the Furry Creature)	Furry creature → Human	Magical solution, hidden identity	None	Revelation of hidden identity, love	A magical furry creature is captured and later transforms into a beautiful girl, marrying the household's young man.

Conclusion

Turkish folk narratives have, for centuries, served as a powerful medium for transmitting the lifestyle, beliefs, value systems, and historical experiences of communities through oral tradition. These narratives are not merely forms of entertainment; they are foundational elements that preserve collective memory, support identity formation, and ensure cultural continuity. Through these narratives, past societal events, heroic deeds, moral lessons, and religious-mythological elements have been embedded into collective consciousness. At the same time, the people's imagination, linguistic richness, and aesthetic sensibilities have been shaped.

This study examines the motifs of transformation identified in Turkish fairy tales collected from Macedonia. A total of twelve tales containing transformation motifs were analyzed. It is evident that the transformation motif significantly enriches the symbolic and psychological depth of the narratives. These transformations often represent the characters' inner development, quests for identity, or turning points in their destiny.

Thus, the examination of the transformation motif is not merely an exploration of a fantastical element but also provides insights into how folk narratives function as vehicles for transmitting cultural and societal values.

Within the scope of the study, the transformation motifs found in Turkish folk tales from Macedonia were categorized under five main headings: transformation into stone, animal, plant, human, and the return to human form.

The motif of transformation into stone, encountered in two tales, emerges as a significant narrative tool for emphasizing the preservation of individual and communal values.

The motif of transformation into an animal appears in four narratives. This transformation typically occurs when characters violate social norms, break taboos, or undergo certain trials. Transformation into an animal sometimes serves as a form of punishment and, at other times, as a means of protection. Additionally, it reinforces the protagonist's dramatic journey and symbolizes their inner evolution.

The motif of transformation into a plant holds an important place in Turkish folk narratives from Macedonia. Often resulting from extraordinary events linked to punishment, reward, or magical influence, this motif highlights the deep connection between humans and nature. In the single analyzed tale involving plant transformation, the change functions as a moral sanction directly related to the character's choices and actions.

The motif of transformation into a human is found in four tales and typically involves the revelation of a hidden identity, symbolizing a process of self-discovery. This motif reflects the character's inner transformation, quest for identity, and journey toward self-realization.

The motif of return to human form represents a crucial phase in the transformation process in folk narratives. Typically arising from spells, curses, or punishments, these transformations are resolved through the hero's courage, loyalty, or righteous actions. Characters turned into stone, animals, or plants are often restored to human form through miraculous interventions, magical objects, or sacred figures.

Thus, the motif of returning to human form holds an important place as a symbol of justice and salvation in folk narratives.

In the Turkish folk tales from Macedonia analyzed, the motif of return to human form is observed in five tales, each depicting a process of transformation and redemption. This aspect of the transformation motif not only restores the characters' physical existence but also enhances the symbolic messages and universal themes conveyed within the narratives.

It is hoped that this study will contribute to the deeper understanding of transformation motifs in Turkish folk narratives and promote a

broader appreciation of folk culture. Furthermore, it is believed that the preservation and transmission of folk literature will play an essential role in safeguarding cultural heritage for future generations. It is our hope that such research will inspire more comprehensive studies, helping the profound meanings embedded in folk narratives reach a wider audience.

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Dali Doborjginidze**Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University (Georgia)****[dali.doborjginidze@bsu.edu.ge], ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4122-4858****Lela Tavdgiridze****Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University (Georgia)****[lela.tavdgiridze@bsu.edu.ge], ORCID ID: 0000-0001-8108-8718****Anastasia Makharadze****Faculty of Humanities & Social Sciences, Sheridan College (Canada)****[anastasia.mkhr43@gmail.com], ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6452-4044**

Innovations in Language: Principles of Teaching and Translation

Abstract: *The progress of Georgia as a sovereign state is closely linked to the European education system. The intercultural exchange of knowledge and educational ideas, facilitated by translation, is an important pillar of Georgia's integration with the European education system. The accession of the Georgian educational system to the Bologna process, the irreversible aspiration of the Georgian nation towards Europe, should be accompanied by the creation of an advanced European education system in the country, and be based on the analysis and consideration of past experiences, where the formation of a national school, which represents one of the core foundations of the state's national ideology, should naturally contribute to it.*

Translation is vital in fostering a connection between diverse educational traditions and methodologies by translating and adapting educational materials and practices from European systems to align with Georgia's cultural and linguistic context. Teaching methodology is constantly evolving and enhancing teaching effectiveness and student engagement. With modern technologies now an integral part of the younger generation's daily lives, many students expect these tools to be incorporated into their learning experience. As a result, traditional lessons can sometimes seem boring leading to a significant decline in their motivation to learn.

In this study, we employed both quantitative and qualitative research methods. Our approach included analyzing the syllabi of educational programs and reviewing relevant literature. Additionally, we designed a comprehensive questionnaire and conducted interviews with students from diverse specialties, as well as lecturers and teachers from various training centers.

The article discusses resources, strategies, approaches, practical activities, advice, experiences, and research findings on how we can best prepare our future generation for the new world that systems are moving towards. The article will also

present modern methods and principles used to translate linguistic innovations, focusing on neologisms, technical terms, slang, and linguo-culturology.

Keywords: *European Integration; Intercultural Translation; Teaching Methodology; Educational Innovation; Research Methods; Linguistic Adaptation.*

Introduction

The field of education and related issues have always been important and relevant for humanity, as it is the field on which the continuous development of any field and society is based. Education is a prerequisite for a decent life and ensuring social sustainability. Providing education is one thing, but it is more important to know how high-quality is the education we provide and, accordingly, what results we achieve.

The advancement of Georgia as an independent state is closely related to the European education system. The accession of the Georgian educational system to the Bologna Process, the irreversible aspiration of the Georgian nation towards Europe, should be accompanied by the creation of a highly developed European education system in the country, which should be based on the analysis and consideration of past experiences, where the formation of a national school, which represents one of the solid and fundamental foundations of the national ideology of the state, should naturally contribute. Indeed, the teaching methodology determines whether a learner will love the course. It also determines how consciously and thoughtfully the learner will be able to perceive, understand, and apply the material in practice. One of the most important challenges of the teaching process is to stimulate the desire to learn in students. "The development of technologies, globalization and a rapidly changing environment have created a need for education systems and goals to be in line with modern challenges. Therefore, educational institutions must ensure the preparation of educational programs that will help the next generation to be competitive, have the appropriate knowledge, skills, worldview and readiness to independently ensure the creation of decent living conditions, while at the same time being personally developed." (Tavdgiridze, and al., 2019:3).

Teaching methodology is constantly evolving and ensuring teaching effectiveness and engagement. Since modern technologies have become an integral part of the lives of the younger generation, many of them expect to use them in the learning process, so sometimes traditional lessons seem boring, which significantly reduces their motivation to learn.

One of the main goals of education is to develop independent learning skills in students. For representatives of the education sector, one of the most important questions to consider is: what skills should we equip them with so that they can effectively adapt to the modern, competitive environment? (Moir, 2022:16).

Innovations in teaching methodology have emerged as a result of the development of modern technologies, psychology, and education and serve to make the teaching process more effective, flexible, and inclusive. Accordingly, we are trying to actively introduce innovations, innovative teaching methods and approaches into the modern learning process. Along with the development of modern culture and technology, people are more often using language experiments, slang, and Internet language, which often goes beyond the norms.

Language freedom often clashes with linguistic norms. In today's dynamic world, new words, terms, and expressions are rapidly emerging in language. Translating these innovations poses a great challenge to linguists and translators, requiring a deep knowledge of the cultural context, creativity, and the ability to adapt.

The use of translation innovations in learning plays an important role in the development of students' linguistic and intercultural competence. These innovations not only facilitate language learning, but also improve the ability to understand and interpret texts.

Translation innovations in learning help students create effective and engaging learning processes. However, it is important that they use these tools as aids and not as a way to achieve the final result. The right methodology and critical thinking ensure the maximum benefit of innovations.

Translation of linguistic innovations is a dynamic and evolving field that requires creativity, cultural sensitivity, and technological support. Using a variety of methods and following guiding principles, translators fill linguistic gaps and contribute to global understanding. As language evolves, the collaboration of human expertise and technological advancement will play an important role in solving the challenges of translating new words and expressions using correct and valid methods and approaches.

Language norms, freedom, and innovation contribute to the preservation and development of the language. Modern teaching and translation methods ensure the popularization of the language and the simplification of its study. The main challenge is that changes in the language should not contradict its purity and identity.

Research methodology – This study employed both quantitative and qualitative research methods. We studied the syllabi of the following educational programs: translation studies, intercultural communication, and teacher training; relevant literature was studied and translated, in particular, the BSU team (including the co-authors of this article) translated the following books within the framework of the Higher Education Support Program:

1.11.2020-31.12.2021 Grant project within the framework of the “Higher Education Support” sub-program of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports of Adjara: Cathy Nutbrown, Peter Clough, scientific / textbook translation of “Early Childhood Education: History, Philosophy and Experience” from English to Georgian. Project Organizer. Agreement №02-10/III 4.11.2020;

2. 2020-31.12.2021 Grant project within the framework of the “Higher Education Support” sub-program of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports of Adjara: Cathy Nutbrown, Peter Clough, scientific / textbook translation of “Early Childhood Education: History, Philosophy and Experience” from English to Georgian. Project Organizer. Agreement №02-10/III 4.11.2020;

3.12.07.2022-30.07.2023- Grant project within the framework of the “Higher Education Support” sub-program of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports of Adjara: Jan White „Playing and Learning Outdoors. The Practical Guide and Sourcebook for excellence in outdoor provision and practice with young children, Third Edition (2019) from English to Georgian. Project Organizer. Agreement №04-05/185;

4.18.08.203-31.12.2024 Grant project within the framework of the “Higher Education Support” sub-program of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports of Adjara Taryn Moir " How to Create Autonomous Learners: Teaching Metacognitive, Self-regulatory and Study Skills – A Practitioner’s Guide „from English to Georgian. Project Organizer. Agreement №04-07/164 18.08.203

To achieve the set goal, we developed and conducted questionnaires and interviews with students of various disciplines, academic faculty implementing educational programs, and teachers from various training centers.

When interviewing teachers, we asked the following questions: What impact do innovative approaches to language teaching have on the quality of teaching? Do teachers use modern technologies in language teaching and translation? What difficulties do they face in translation? Which language teaching methods do they consider effective?

Do linguistic innovations reflect social and cultural changes? Since in modern society language is no longer considered a static and permanent structure – it is a living and dynamic process, which is constantly undergoing changes under the influence of technological, cultural and social factors. Linguistic innovations are especially noticeable – new vocabulary, semantic changes, slang, forms arising from foreign influence, etc. In the linguistic situation, these changes are manifested not only in everyday communication, but also affect language teaching and translation practice.

For example: post – the publication, chat –online conversation, App – mobile application, update – refresh, renew, game, screenshot – the image of a screen.

There are various reasons for language change. In this article, we will highlight some of the main ones:

Multicultural influence: the connection of different languages.

Technology and social media: the need for fast and easy communication.

Language interference: the mixing of structures by a bilingual society.

Linguistic economy: the desire to simplify speech in order to save time and energy.

These changes are natural and are part of the language evolution process. However, preserving traditional norms is important for maintaining the purity and stability of the language.

Linguistic innovations in the Georgian language in recent years, divided by sources:

Social networks and youth slang

Active linguistic innovations are developing in Georgian social networks – new words or, in the linguistics term, "hybrid constructions" are often born.

Word/phrase	Meaning	Source	Comment
Stuck	confusion, mental freeze	Facebook, Twitter	Metaphorical use (e.g. "I got stuck on the lecturer")
ფლექსაობა/Flexaoba	boasting, showing off	TikTok, YouTube	English "flex" – direct transfer, established in Georgian discourse

2. Media and Opinion journalism

Television and online media often adopt new forms based on foreign influences.

Linguistic neologisms are particularly relevant in technological and political discourse:

Word/phrase	Meaning	Source	Comment
Factchecking	Checking the facts	netgazeti.ge, mythdetector	Literal translation, firmly established term
Debate	discussion, debate	TV debates	Modified form of the English "debate"
Hater	Negative person	TV shows, blogs	Constantly used in slang style

3. Technological discourse and IT environment

With the spread of technology, professional terminology has become firmly established in the language, often in direct (non-translated) form:

Word/phrase	Meaning	Source	Comment
Default	Default setting	IT forums, support groups	Direct transliteration
Lagva (lag)	System interruption	gamer community	"Lag" – a borrowed term in Georgian grammar
Gasheareba	To share	Facebook, Messenger	"Share" + prefix "Ga" inserted in Georgian

As evidenced, in recent years terms based on foreign influences, new slang constructions and professional terminology have been actively spreading in the language, which in many cases adapt to Georgian grammatical norms. These linguistic changes are clearly fueled by social media, youth communication, technological and information space. For example, contenti – content, startupi – startup, posti – post, chati – chat, applicia – application, updaiti – update, gaimi – game, screenshoti

– screenshot, buildi – build, trendi – trend, fasheni – fashion. Identification of these trends is important for both teaching and translation fields, so that modern linguistic reality can be reflected in practice.

The language situation is considered one of the basic concepts of sociolinguistics. According to Charles **Ferguson**, the language situation refers to the overall configuration of language use at a given time and place and includes such data as how many languages there are and which languages are used in a given area, how many people use each and in what circumstances; what moods and attitudes the members of the given society have towards these languages. (Ferguson, 1971:157).

Traditional methods of language teaching often fail to reflect the rapidly evolving linguistic innovations as they develop in real discourse, which frequently results in learners and educators being insufficiently prepared to accurately perceive and analyze the nuances of contemporary discourse. This challenge is particularly significant in contexts where language teaching is accompanied by the need for translation – adequately conveying linguistic changes into another language requires not only knowledge of the language but also an understanding and interpretation of its innovative forms. This, in turn, highlights the necessity for teaching methodology to be flexible, up-to-date, and adapted to the constant transformations of linguistic reality.

This study aims to study trends related to linguistic innovations and analyze their impact on teaching methodology and translation practice. Accordingly, the student questionnaire consisted of the following questions:

What kinds of activities help you in language acquisition?

Do innovative approaches to language teaching enhance the quality of your learning?

How important are videos, audio recordings, and interactive materials to you when learning a language?

In your opinion, what role do the teacher and teaching methods play in the learning process?

What kind of feedback helps you overcome the challenges of language learning?

Do educators use modern technologies in the process of language teaching and translation process?

What would you change?

Analysis of the results of the survey conducted with teachers showed that 58% of teachers believe that innovative approaches to language teaching significantly increase the quality of teaching. 31% –

prefer traditional teaching approaches, 6% refrained from answering, 5% prefer an individual approach to teaching. The answers to the question – do teachers use modern technologies in the language teaching process? were recorded as follows: "Language is constantly changing and developing, therefore the use of modern technologies simplifies the perception of new terms and concepts.", "The use of modern technologies makes it easier for learners to perceive foreign contexts and remember words. "Working on the translation of foreign literature helps learners get closer to the cultures of different countries." "Innovations, media contribute to the improvement of learners' language competencies." "Innovations in language teaching increase learner motivation and engagement"; The following effective language teaching methods were named: playing, communicative method, team projects, simulation of real situations, games and interactive activities, language learning platforms, dialogues on real-life situations, personalized programs that make the learning process more effective. According to respondents, these methods contribute to the upbringing of creative, independent-thinking young people.

In the modern educational space, foreign language teaching is increasingly associated with innovative methods. One of the important directions is the integration of innovative approaches to translation, which helps students learn the language both at the lexical and cultural levels. Translation is no longer considered just a mechanical transfer of text from one language to another, but is an active cognitive process that contributes to the linguistic and cultural competence of the student (Cook, 2010:14-15).

How do translation innovations help students learn and make the teaching process more effective and interesting? First of all, translation innovations involve the use of modern approaches and technologies in the field of translation, for example: **multimodal translation** – incorporating video, audio, subtitles, and visual elements;

Translation applications and platforms – for example, DeepL, Google Translate or special learning apps;

Contextual translation – when words are not translated literally, but according to the context;

AI translation and real-time translation;

When asked what difficulties they encounter when translating, the majority of the students surveyed noted that language learning is directly related to translation activities. The student notes how the text

was translated taking into account the context and better understands the essence of the language, not just grammar;

How modern technologies have increased their level of inter-activity, in particular, the use of apps and platforms has allowed students to try to translate, compare, identify and correct errors on their own.

How their cultural awareness has grown – while translating, students encounter cultural differences, phraseology, and idioms, which help them not only in language, but also in perceiving the diversity of the world.

How their critical thinking developed

When a student sees how the same text can be translated in different ways, they start to think – which version is better? Why?

What also increases students' motivation? Innovative formats (e.g., video translation, game-based translation) make learning more interesting.

Modern platforms such as **DeepL, Google Translate, Mem-source**, and others are already being used in the educational process as learning resources. Students learn how to use these tools critically – comparing results, assessing translation accuracy, and mastering to access and evaluate language (Bowker & Ciro, 2019:31-33).

Translation is a complex process that requires both language knowledge and cultural competence. A literal translation, as mentioned above, often does not reflect the emotional or cultural context of the text. The translator must take into account the nuances of the language and the cultural elements that are present in the text. Often, students turn to automatic translation tools, such as Google Translate, which simplify the general translation process for them, but cannot replace human interpretation and lacks cultural competence.

Translation innovations also contribute to the development of cultural interpretation. Students acquire the ability to understand linguistic context not only at the level of words, but also at the level of culture. This process uses interactive tasks – such as translating dialogue, preparing subtitles, or localizing a poster. (Liddicoat&Scarino, 2013:45-46).

Accordingly, we actively adopt innovations in the modern educational process, introduce innovative teaching methods and diverse approaches, which reflect the challenges of global culture and the digital era (O'Hagan, 2016:88-89).

Analysis of students' responses showed that the most effective language learning approaches for them are: **Task-Based Learning**. They master the practical use of the language in real situations, such as: communication in tourist situations; professional activities, for example, business language. **Gamification (game-based learning)** – the use of games in the language learning process to increase motivation and consolidate knowledge. This includes: accumulating points, team competitions and activities. **Virtual and augmented reality (VR and AR)** – virtual environments help students practice speaking a new language, for example: virtual tours in a foreign country; dialogues in a realistic environment. **Intercultural learning – language learning – different ways of considering context**, in-depth understanding of culture and the importance of intercultural learning. International online connections (for example, PenPal programs); videos, films and audio materials that introduce us to culture. For example, one of the most common models for analyzing culture is the iceberg model. In the iceberg model, the main emphasis is placed on the constituent elements of culture, some of which are visible, while others are difficult to detect. (**Intercultural learning T-Kit**).

Developing critical thinking. Improving students' skills to enable them to deeply analyze and critically use language: discussions and debates; analysis of real-life texts (Blended learning).

In this approach, classical and online learning complement each other, providing a flexible and diverse learning experience. Flipped Classroom Models. Students prepare material in advance (for example, watching videos or reading books) and work on practical application in the classroom.

Dialogue and role-playing games, audio/video materials, independent work and projects, frequent feedback and reminder assessments, use of a variety of technologies such as applications, online courses, language learning platforms – **Duolingo, Babbel, Rosetta Stone**, intuitive applications for independent language learning, and virtual classrooms (for example, Zoom and Google Meet) for direct teacher-student interaction.

Thus, innovative approaches make the process of teaching a foreign language more flexible, effective, and diverse. They should be selected according to the needs of a specific student or group in order to make learning as effective and enjoyable/comfortable as possible.

The analysis of the syllabi showed that the following methods are used within the framework of the training course: oral methods, individualized instruction, discussion/debate; methods of working on a book/source; written methods; analysis of a case/pedagogical situation; cognitive schemes; role-playing, simulations; demonstration/presentation; project/problem-oriented learning; collaborative learning. E-learning method, micro-teaching, etc. Also, the study of teaching methods in syllabi showed that individual curriculums are developed for students with special educational needs, taking into account teaching and assessment tailored to their needs.

Language teaching has become more effective and diverse with modern methods.

Conclusions and recommendations:

The analysis of the research results showed the following: modern approaches, technologies, diverse strategies, innovations in didactics, communicative and interactive methods promote learning creativity, logical, critical thinking, and the upbringing of an independent, meta-cognitively thinking new generation; facilitate the development of linguistic communication, deepen multilingual and multicultural awareness, and bring two languages and cultures closer together, which is important for learning in a multilingual environment in the context of globalization;

Innovative approaches to translation are an important resource in the process of teaching a foreign language. They enrich the learning environment, increase students' linguistic competence, critical thinking, and cultural sensitivity. Proper methodological integration transforms this process for both the student and the teacher.

The integration of innovations in the process of teaching a foreign language changes not only the forms of teaching, but also the principles of understanding and using the language itself. Translation as a teaching method remains relevant even in an innovative environment and allows language learning to be thoughtful, in-depth, communicatively loaded and practice-oriented. Learning in the process of translation promotes in-depth understanding of the language, purposeful and creative learning; simplifies and makes language learning effective; It enlivens the language and gives it a more practical, natural, and flexible form. However, it is impossible to 'translate' the individuality of different cultures into terms that will be acceptable everywhere and to everyone. According to this view, it is impossible to evaluate cultures as 'higher' or 'more

progressive'; cultures are simply different from each other, each with its own unique and irreplaceable value.

Thus, translation, modern teaching principles and innovative approaches complement each other, together creating a powerful and result-oriented educational model that turns language learning into a deep, multifaceted and vibrant process. Maintaining a balance between norms and freedom is essential for the sustainable development of a language. Innovations and new methodologies provide new opportunities for language learning, use and translation.

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Intercultural learning T-Kit

<https://www.nplg.gov.ge/greenstone3/halftone-library/collection/civil2/document/HASHe955485daa78a90f78365d;jsessionid=E92A5CCE11E820685DA10890D9A3A2A4?ed=1>

Egvenia Ivanova
New Bulgarian University (Bulgaria)
[j_lubivanova@abv.bg]

To Play the Game of State

Abstract: *The text examines the question of why, during the Ottoman period, certain distinctly Bulgarian villages evoked in their contemporaries a sense of “unrestricted freedom.” According to the author, the explanation lies in the privileges granted through special sultanic firmans and – above all – in the economic prosperity achieved by many of the villagers. Owing to their extensive commercial activities, they were able to travel across Europe and Asia, cultivating the self-perception of free individuals. Yet the confidence inherited from their forefathers ultimately proved insufficient for the younger generation, who aspired to possess a state of their own.*

The illusion of statehood briefly emerged during the April Uprising – during “the drunkenness of a nation,” a moment in which freedom was realized as a form of play.

Keywords: *Ottoman Rule; Bulgarian Villages; Privileges and Firmans; Economic Prosperity; National Awakening; April Uprising.*

Евгения Иванова
Нов български университет

Игра на държава

Нейните разкошни брегове (на река Тополка в Копривщица – Е. И.) са били свидетели и на бегликчийско величие, и на джелепски кабадайлък¹, па и на неограничена свобода, за която околните клисурци и панагюрци не са сънували даже. Тук, на тия брегове, под кичестите върби, е траял бегликчийският моабет цели дни и ноци, тук ферманлиите чорбаджии Вълковци, Стояновци, Дога-новци, Каравеловци и др. са яли и пили под звука на два̀йсет гайди

¹ Кабадалия (тур.) – наперен, важен.

и цигулки, тук селският ага или субаш² е правил кафе на българските делибашии³, смирен и покорен, учтив и любезен. (Стоянов 1976:754)

Така описва Копривщица от времето на „робството“ Захари Стоянов. А копривщениецът Каравелов добавя характеристиката на дядо си Либен:

Ако би някой от съвременното ситно човечество или някой европеец погледал в онова време на дядо Либена, то той би помислил, че това е... някой рицар, граф или крал, който отива да се бие със своя съсед и да превземе Люксембург. (Каравелов 1965:211)

Откъде идва това усещане за „неограничена свобода“ – именно във времето, срещу чиято не-свобода са се разбунтували и двамата автори? Откъде у дядо Либен самочувствието на крал – в неговото не-свободно отечество?

За дядо Либеновци – българите от „старо време“ – „отечеството“ се простирало до края на селската мера. За дядо Либеновци, както и за „Вълковци, Стояновци, Догановци“, „отечеството“ била Копривщица. Свободната Копривщица, в която селският ага вари кафе на „ферманлиите чорбаджии“?

Освен чорбаджиите, със специални султански фермани били снабдени множество села – благодарение на минали заслуги или заради поемането на определени задължения към държавата. Легендите твърдят, че в тези села не било възможно турчин да влезе на подкован кон и туркиня да роди. Легенди чертаят и образите на основателите, получатели на ферманите – някой прославен витяз или храбра мома (случаят на Копривщица).

Извън легендите, ферманлиите-села притежавали привилегията да се самоуправляват. „Агата“ имал само представителни функции и често бил назначаван с протекцията на някого от видните жители. Освен „агата“, други представители на господстващата религия нямало.⁴

Описанието на Михаил Маджаров съвпада напълно с досега цитираните:

² Субашия (тур.) – полицейски началник на малък град или село.

³ Делибашия (тур.) – буквално „луда глава“. Буен, разпуснат човек.

⁴ М. Маджаров обяснява липсата на мюсюлмани в Копривщица прагматично: Понеже били мързеливи и предпочитали по-лесния живот в полето, турците не се заселвали в Копривщица. За там била нужна предприемчивост, водеща, разбира се, до богатство. (Маджаров 1968:173).

В турско време Копривщица представляваше една независима съдебно-административна единица.

Кооперациите в скотовъдството имали „аристократическа основа“. Управлението било също „аристократично“. Мюдюринът⁵ (помак от Родопите) ходел на черква и станал „част от копривщенското общество“. Жителите се разбирали с него, затова чорбаджиите издействали да не бъде сменян. (Маджаров 1968:91, 163, 172, 312)

А онзи Неджиб ага, който ще предизвика първата пушка в Копривщица, бил препоръчан за службата си от богатия перушеченец Рангел Гичев. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:462)

Самоуправляващите се ферманлии-села постигнали значителен икономически просперитет – основно чрез търговия с добитък и чрез събирането на данъка от продажбите (споменатите от З. Стоянов джелепи и бегликчии). Разбираемо, просперитетът им носел самочувствие:

Търговията е почетено и сладко нещо – казвал бащата на М. Маджаров (един от немалкото копривщенски богаташи). – С търговията можете да пребродите всички морета, да видите всички чужди страни. Търговията е независим занаят. Тя ви дава възможност да заповядате дори на турците. (Маджаров 1968:124)

Копривщенци смятали себе си за граждани⁶, а жителите на околните села наричали „селачи“. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:249)

Най-видимото проявление на „градското“ самочувствие била, разбира се, модата.

Не само цариградските, но и виенските моди се срещаха в нашето малко планинско градче – спомня си М. Маджаров. – Всеки копривщенин, който ходеше по чужбина – а най-малко половината от тях ходеха по чужбина – считаше за дълг да донесе нещо на жена си, с което да я отличи от другите. По едно време модата започна да изпреваря дори Пловдив, който следваше в това отношение Цариград и Виена. (Маджаров 1968:45)

Докато ходели „по чужбина“ и преброждали „всички морета“, бащата Маджаров и съдружникът му Палавеев⁷ решили да

⁵ Мюдюр (тур.) – управител.

⁶ Макар че селище, в което не живеят мюсюлмани, до 60-години на 19. в. нямало право да се нарича град.

⁷ Палавеев – един от най-богатите хора в Копривщица – след освобождението построил мавзолей на падналите през Априлското въстание. Построил си в София и къщата на ул. „Оборище“, която днес е седалище на Британския съвет.

си купят от Кайро две черни робини и да си ги заведат в Копривщица. Възраженията на ревнивите им жени обаче надделели и затова копривщенските „робини“ се отказали от идеята да имат робини. (Маджаров 1968:211)

Михаил Маджаров запомнил от баща си и една знаменателна мисъл:

Ако един ден се освободи България, тя ще се освободи за селяните, а не за нас; ние и сега сме свободни. (Маджаров 1968:175)

Макар че – според З. Стоянов – „клисурци и панагюрци не са сънували даже“ свободата на Копривщица, панагюрецът Найден Дринов казва друго: Панагюрище не само било управлявано от българина Филип Щърбанов, но и също така:

Тук турското владичество даже не се усещаше и никакви натиски от турците не се допускаха, защото за малко забележено такова се правеха постъпки и протести. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:126, 165)

З. Стоянов косвено потвърждава това, забравил сякаш настояването си за уникалността на свободната Копривщица:

По пътя ние (Хвърковатата чета – Е. И.) вървахме без никакъв страх, понеже знаехме, че в тая местност никога не е владял турчинът от покоряването на България. Пеехме, говорехме високо и се смеехме, като че ли не бяхме въстаници. (Стоянов 1976:411)

Първият богаташ на Калугерово дори отказал да отвори вратата на селския ага, защото дошъл през нощта:

Сега не отварям. Нека дойде утре на видело. Аз не познавам сега кол-агасъ. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:415)

Противно на простата логика, онези, които в бунта ще загубят най-много (социално положение, имоти, пари, престиж) – някои от богатите и преди всичко синовете им – били сред най-активните по време на въстанието. Според свидетелствата на участниците, за комитетски дейци нарочно се търсели „по-богатички“. Именно те били комитите. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:297, 440)

Макар че недолюбва богатите, поповете и учените, З. Стоянов също признава, че в революционните комитети на първо място участвали попът и учителят, а след тях се избирали „от по-първа ръка хора с доказана честност и влияние в местността“. (Стоянов 1976:250)

Когато разпитвали заловения Каблешков колко пари е получавал като телеграфист, турците се удивлявали на сумата от „цели

1000 гроша“. А като разбрали, че баща му има „триста и повече“ говеда, изумлението достигнало върха си. Всички се чудели как такъв човек е „тръгнал да прави комитаджилък по Балкана“. (Стоянов 1976:749)

Не се досещали, че този „комитаджилък“ се различавал от дотогавашните.

Почти всичките бунтове отпреди Април избухвали от глад⁸ или – заради повишени данъци, или – заради отнети привилегии, или – заради честта на някоя мома. Априлският бунт вече имал политически претенции – той заявил искането за **собствена** държава.

За синовете на дядо Либеновци, които се чувстваха свободни в границите на селската мера, отечеството неимоверно много се е разширило. Те са свободни навсякъде, където ходят по търговията си и харчат парите си. Тяхното отечество е цялата империя и „всички чужди страни“. Самочувствието им – резултат от богатството – създава усещането им за свобода.

За внуците обаче това самочувствие и тази свобода не са достатъчни. Те искат не само да бъдат свободни благодарение на привилегиите и на парите си, но – да бъдат свободни в **собствената** си държава, която да уреждат според разбиранията си и според наученото в чужбина. Така, в рамките само на три поколения, визиите за отечеството и за свободата претърпяват главоломни метаморфози. Така – в рамките само на три поколения – узрява националната идея. Захранваното от привилегиите и от парите самочувствие на свободни хора – съвсем постижимо за дядовците и за синовете им – има *социална* мотивация. Внуците вече се нуждаят от *национално* самочувствие. За внуците социалната свобода в една чужда империя не може да замести националните възжелания за **собствена** държавност.

Миражът на **собствената** българска държава за кратко се провижда по време на въстанието. Изглежда лесно постижим – като на игра. Или – като на празник.

Още на Великден, който през онази година се паднал в началото на април, бъдещите перушенски въстаници, нарамили пушки, марширували и пеели „Вятър ечи, Балкан стене“. В Брацигово се отказали от традицията великденското хоро да се вие под свирнята на тъпани и зурни, а го изиграли с гайди и кавали. Съседските

⁸ Изключението е, може би, само Велчовата завера.

турци обаче дошли с тъпаните и зурните си и засвирили. Младешките ги изгонили и за малко да обявят въстанието преждевременно. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:462, 542-543)

„Опиянението, съблимвното безумство на народа“ (Вазов) се разразило с още по-голяма сила след първата пушка в Копривщица. Вестта била разпратена навсякъде и:

Всичките пощальони се върнаха и съобщиха, че писмата са връчени благополучно на известни съзаклятници и в Калофер, когато някои от тях върху зелената морава яли печено агне, и в Карлово, когато се водел горещ разговор за бъдещите действия през въстанието, и в Сопот през приятна разходка към манастира, когато се пеели пламенни въстанически песни, а в Троян, когато опитвали сладостта на сливовицата. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:266)

„Пиянството на един народ“ било не толкова резултат от сливовицата, колкото от мярналия се мираж на **собствената** държава. Онази „самонадеяност, която приближава до лудост“ (Вазов) обхващала (съвсем за кратко) не само вдъхновителите на бунта – главни актьори в него, но и публиката им. Изглеждало, като че ли актьори и публика са станали едно. Изглеждало, че **всички** са участници – както в играта.

На една конференция, състояла се в далечната (както биха казали сега) 1986 година, един руски (тогава, все още – съветски) професор ме попита дали е възможно в това „съблимвно безумство на народа“ да има игрово начало. Първоначално ми се стори кощунствено да мисля въстанието като игра на революция. После си казах, че те всъщност празнуват несъстоялата се революция, миражната **собствена** държава. А във всеки празник задължително има игра.

Хоро, пушкане, гуляене, телци, бозайничета и тлъсти ягнета...

Юнаците, които тропаха от всичкото си сърце и душа, гордо и надменно кривяха своите накичени кръстове, за да държат ножовете им по-добра поза.

Притъмня вече, а никой не казваше стига, малко внимание обръщаше на попотеното си чело, като че всичките да бяха пророци за в бъдеще, че Априлското въстание ще да остави добри възпоминания само с той род картини, хора и песни, и пр. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:333, 421)

Игрите на децата и игрите на големите са еднакви – игри на революция.

Влиянието на това общо опиянение се отрази и на самите игри на децата. Те замениха челика, топката, ликото, пумпала с игра на талим⁹, сред улиците, като си правеха пушки от пищели, саби от дръвца... (Вазов)

Опиянението от празника се събира в образа на сватбата:

... гледах как изпращат Рашка – не че отива на бой, но като че отива на сватба – спомня си един копривщенец.

... и ще започнем сватбата... – казва Кочо Честименски в Перушица. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:217, 475)

Кочо често вземал участие в театрални представления, които – според Захари Стоянов – били „като предшествующи причини на българското движение през 1875–1876 год.“ Защото именно от тях Кочо „за пръв път можал да се запознае с българската история и с подвизите на различни герои, които подействали твърде влиятелно на неговата буйна натура“. (Стойнов 1976:894-895)

В празника, впрочем, винаги има и малко театър. Така е в Копривщица:

Около пладне се появи българский пряпорец откъм битпазар, придружен от доволно число млади, които го носеха към конака с бунтовни песни, предводими от даскала Найдена п. Стоянов. Много беше смешно да гледа човек даскал Найдена, облечен с ония калпави и измайсторени дрехи, с които преди една година представляваше той в театра Графа за приказката на Геновева. От рядко платно дрехи, подбръснати, хартиена шапка на главата му и рог окачен... (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:235-236)

Така е и в Батак:

Вънкашната форма е първата слабост на човечеството. Всякой виждал, че за новия войнишки живот турските потури не са сгодни, пък и за самото тържество – неприлични. Случайно тия желания и нови нужди намерили донейде удовлетворението си. В селото имало няколко склада от шарени влашки чували, които се отворили, разграбили и раздали на жените да ги превръщат в панталони, прилични на шопските – като чисто народна форма. Още в същия ден мнозина излезли на назначените позиции с тия дрехи, шарени като дъждовници, с калпаци от цяла овча или козя кожа. Тая вънкашна промяна се счела от самите селяни за такъва необходима, че един сиромах, който по-напред си бил про-

⁹ Талим (тур.) – военно обучение.

дал воловете, за да си купи пушка, като нямал с какво да си промени формата и като не можил да свари влашките складове, зел, та си заклал едничкото свине, одрал му кожата, обшил я с шила и я надянал на главата си. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:496-497)

Така е и в Ботевата чета:

Сините ширити през гърдите им бяха вероятно правени от женска ръка – спомня си капитанът на „Радецки“ Дагоберт Енглендер. – Тези ширити бяха нещо непрактично и аз се надявах, че Ботев ще ги унищожи пред битката, защото те даваха добър прицел за неприятелските куришуми. (Ферманджиев 1986:396)

(Ботев не унищожил ширитите. Не сменил и лачените си бутуши, които го убивали.)

Защото празникът не може да бъде честван с ежедневния вид, облекло, поведение. Празникът е **друг живот**, **различен** от досегашния, затова се налага преобличане и необичайно държане – като влизане в роля. Ролята на въстаници, които празнуват държавата си:

Честитяванията, целувания и прегръщанията той ден нямаха брой и край. Даже и малките деца, по примера на бащите и братята им, по улиците си честитяваха българското царство... (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:550)

Столицата на **собственото** царство е Панагюрище, царят – Бенковски – особено, когато обикаля територията на провидяната държава с Хвърковатата чета:

Четата тържествуваше, тя беше в апогеята на своята слава. Мустакатите въстаници опъваха краищата на своите мустаци и вероятно съжаляваха, че не са по-дълги. Певците напинаха своите гърди да привлекат повече очи върху си, други разиграваха конете си все за същата цел. Но всичко беше напусто: тия бяха съзвездие, голямото светило беше Бенковски. Той ставаше по-величествен от минута на минута, конят му настъпаше на пара, той беше предмет на овацията, той изпитваше най-устремителните и любопитни погледи, за него се извиваха много нежни вратове да го изглеждат от петите до космите. (Стоянов 1976:481)

Хвърковатата чета се мисли като „първата българска войска“... (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:187)

„Държавната територия“, отдавна напуснала селското отечество, се е разпростирила по границите на целия IV революционен

окръг. Територията на тази „държава“ вече не съществувала за Османската империя:

Полицейските наредби, събирането на данокът, раздаването на правосъдието, градските разпоряжения и пр., и пр. бяха напълно преминали под ведомството на революционерния комитет. ... него време по-добре можеше да пропътува човек из района на IV окръг... със свободен билет, издаден от някоя пригответелна комисия, отколкото, ако той беше снабден с туралия тескере, издадено в името на н.в. султана. (Стоянов 1976:298)

Миражът на **собствената** държава постепенно се уплътнява и тя започва да изглежда съвсем реална – с всичките подробности, необходими за съществуването ѝ:

Нашата голяма държава вече беше наредена в най-главните и най-важните ѝ служби. След петстотин години у нас съществуваше народно правителство. И бабите бързаха да поздравяват с „честито царство“!.¹⁰ (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:269)

В столицата на царството Панагюрище Бенковски свикал златарите „да направят голям печат – държавен“. (Стоянов 1976:437)

„Правителство“ обаче заседавало и в съседната „столица“ – Копривщица, в спициерията (аптеката) на д-р Спас Иванов.

Спициерията приличаше на английски парламент – спомня си един от участниците в „правителството“ – в който се събират лордовете да управляват царството си. Тука се развяваха три-четири пандери¹¹, навън стояха стражаре и слуги, извътре се издаваха повеления, крояха се тайни планове... (Юбилеен сборник, т. I, 1926: 688)

В Батак били проведени истински дипломатически преговори. Агите от околните помашки села, изплашени и унижени от миража на баташката „държава“, решили да „паднат на молба пред баташкия войвода“, за да не ги счита за противници.

... те не само нямат нищо против въстанието, но с радостна готовност ще приемат всяко ново положение, което би им

¹⁰ „Царствата“ обаче се оказали повече от едно: за столица претендирали вечните съперници Панагюрище и Копривщица. Когато Хвърковатата чета се установила на Еледжик, се заговорило за ... „въстаническото българско царство в Еледжик“. Баташките ръководители, които очаквали, че селото им ще стане център на въстанието, се уплашили, че – заради стичането на хората в Брацигово – ще „отпадне духът на батачани“. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:359, 504)

¹¹ Пандера (вер. от исп. бандера) – знаме.

се наложило и което ще считат като пратено от самия аллах, стига само да им се оставят домовете, селата и челядта непокътнати.

„Баташкият войвода“ отговорил, че ще изпълни молбите им, ако те помогнат на българите от чепинските села да се пренесат в Батак.

Агите приели това предложение с рабска покорност...

... тая нравствена победа, засвидетелствана от уплашените аги, била известна на малко и голямо. Радостта и ентусиазмът били безпределни. Тоя ден за тях не бил друг, освен златните минути на дванадесетдневното им царуване. В него те като че ли се трудили да преживеят всичката слава и могъщество на новия живот, всичкия блясък на войничеството си! (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:502-506)

„Преговорите“ са разказани от сина на „баташкия войвода“ – Ангел Горанов. А Захари Стоянов добавя:

Както виждате, баташката държавица е била вече припознатата, че има право на съществуване, има свои отделни правдини, което не малко зарадвало въстаналите. Песни, хора и различни други ликувания стоели на първи план. (Стойанов 1976:911)

„Ликуванията“ понякога не били съвсем безкористни и дори можело да завършат с проливане на кръв:

А аз на пета стъпам. Онова черно калпаче от гергьовско ягне, с лев на челото, кривнато на една страна, само на ухото ми се прикрепило. На края на пушката ми здравче, на челото ми и на пояса ми други. В късо време заобиколиха ме моми и булки да ме питат какво има да става. „Царството ще да превземаме!“ – казах аз и турих ръка на своя нож. Много весело прекарахме в Копривщица: сербезлик¹², колкото искаш. Аз се занимавах най-много да къртя по вратата турските нумери и да сека с ножа си фесове. Като захванаха да се колят циганите¹³, то аз бях първи вече – похвалил се бакалинът Ботю от Синджирлий (Веригово), отишъл в Копривщица, за „да се изпъчи пред своята любовница“. (Стойанов 1976:709)

¹² Сербез (тур.) – дързък, смел.

¹³ Това е познатата от бунтовете и в други държави практика на „накървяването“ (убиване на реален или въобразен „враг“, за да няма връщане назад). Копривщенци осъществили „накървяването“, като избили неколцина цигани, помогнали им преди това да леят куршуми.

„Изпъчването“ от „превземането на царството“ било кратко, а клането на циганите, замислено, за да „накърви“ въстаниците и да им отреже пътя за отстъпление, се оказало един от не многото случаи, когато насъбраното оръжие се използвало по предназначение.

После „царуването“ свършило. „Царствата“ падали едно след друго:

Свърши се дотука десетдневното царуване на Копривщица. След десетдневно царуване ние пак се покорихме на турците. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:217, 294)

Захари Стоянов – когато си спомня „апогеята на нашата слава“ – посрещането на „светилото“ Бенковски – печално признава:

Това бляскаво посрещане в Белово на 27 априлий е последното от нашето царуване!... . (Стоянов 1976:481)

Играта на държава – огледално преобърната – се провижда дори в трагедията: докато носят главата на Бенковски към София, турците гърмят салюти и обявяват на събралата се публика: „Хубаво го гледайте! Той щеше да ви стане крал!“ (Стоянов 1976:636-637)

Миражът на **собствената** държава се пръснал „от първата турска пушка“ – казва Константин Величков. Но, все пак, „стигнал, за да смае духовете“. Въстанието...

... беше стихийен взрив на едно опиянение и в минутата, когато се разрази, то изтощи всичката си сила..., защото нямаше друга сила, ако не смяташе черешовите топове, кремъковите пушки, левските знаци на шапките им и бунтовнишките песни. (Гюрова и Тихов 1976:882)

Гладните селски бунтове отпреди Април едва ли са изглеждали като опиянение, като „сублимно безумство на народа“. Едва ли са смайвали духовете с миража на **собствената** държава, при видян като сбъдната действителност.

Само две години след „пиянството на един народ“ държавата наистина се е сбъднала.

Като действителност? Или – като игра?

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INTERVIEW

„I Chose to Become a Doctor without Realizing that I would be Confronted with Human Suffering. Later – and to this Day – this has Motivated me Never to Stop Learning.”

Dr. Margarita Shoylekova and Dr. Ignat Petrov in a conversation with Anelia Kassabova and Kristina Popova

Abstract: *Margarita Shoylekova (b. 1945) and Ignat Petrov (b. 1937) are a family of psychiatrists whose professional careers unfolded during a period of significant changes in psychiatric therapies. New psychiatric techniques and treatments were employed, and later abandoned, including insulin coma therapy, sleep therapy, sulfonazine therapy and other. In Bulgaria child psychiatry became institutionalized. Of decisive importance was the increasingly strong introduction of psychiatric medications (antipsychotics/neuroleptics). Dr. Margarita Shoylekova is a child psychiatrist and one of the first specialists in anorexia in Bulgaria, while Prof. Dr. Ignat Petrov is among the founders of Bulgarian gerontology in the 1960-es. The conversation addresses their personal experiences as professionals during a crucial period in Bulgarian psychiatry under state socialism and after its end.*

Keywords: *child psychiatry in Bulgaria; psychiatry during the Cold War; Margarita Shoylekova; Ignat Petrov.*

„Избрах да стана лекарка, без да осъзнавам, че ще се срещам със страданието на хората. По-късно – и досега - това ме мотивира да не спирам да се уча“

Д-р Маргарита Шойлекова и доц. д-р Игнат Петров в разговор с Анелия Касабова и Кристина Попова

К. П. – Разкажете ни как се насочихте към психиатрия?

М. Шойлекова – Като кръжочничка в кръжока по патологична физиология започнах да работя по една тема, която се отнасяше до болката. И така, първо болката изследвахме на кучета, котки и жаби... Но постепенно се разшири темата към преживяванията, не само усещанията, но и преживяванията, реакциите, ако може да се нарекат чувствени, и така започнах да чета повече за емоциите и постепенно се отклоних от патофизиологията към психиатрията. Когато в 1966 година бях четвърти курс и учехме психиатрия, професор Чолаков¹ беше вече покойник, а ръководител на катедрата беше доцент Тодор Ташев.² Проф. Ташев е от с. Петково, Смолянско, роден е 1921 година и е завършил духовната семинария в Пловдив първо, след това медицина в София, и по разбираеми причини се е ориентирал към психиатрията, след духовната семинария, защо да не се ориентира към науката за душата.

А. К. Какво четяхте?

М. Шойлекова – За жалост, прескочих юношеската литература, нищо не бях чела, един „Конник без глава“ бях чела. Защото майка ми от малки ни четеше „Илиадата“, и ни занимаваше с древногръцките митове. В прогимназията в началото започнах да чета малко патриотична литература – една книга на Стефан Дичев „За свободата“. В седми клас, започнах да чета руската класика, най-напред Тургенев, после Лермонтов, Пушкин, и после зачетех вече с голям интерес Толстой – „Война и мир“, „Ана Каренина“, Достоевски опитах, но не го разбирах, чак като студентка започнах да го чета. След това започнах и френските класици – Виктор Юго – „Клетниците“, „Парижката Света Богородица“, и Александър Дюма съм чела, но може би повече между другото.

А. К. – Това са все и психолози, писатели психолози... Но

¹ Проф. Кирил Чолаков (1897 – 1963) е изтъкнат български психиатър. Завършва медицина във Виена и специализира неврология и психиатрия. В края на 1930-те и началото на 1940-те години издава сп. „Душевно здраве“, в което популяризира своя метод за „психофизиологична декапсулация“. След Втората световна война е професор в Пловдивския медицински институт „Иван Петрович Павлов“ (днес Медицински университет – Пловдив).

² Проф. Тодор Ташев (1921 – 2006), ученик на проф. Кирил Чолаков. Ръководи катедрата по психиатрия и медицинска психология от 1965 до 1987 г. в Пловдивския медицински институт „Иван Петрович Павлов“ (днес Медицински университет – Пловдив).

в гимназията сте се ориентирали към медицина. Как решихте да учите медицина?

Маргарита Шойлекова – Братовчед ми, 15 години по-голям от мен, живееше у нас в Пловдив и следваше медицина. Ние много се разбирахме и бяхме много близки и някак си, по имитация може би, в последната година в гимназията вече бяхме решили със сестра ми да следваме медицина. По това време прочетох *Легенда за Сан Микеле* от Аксел Мунте. Животът на Аксел Мунте е посветен на медицината до всеотдайност. Той стана моят герой и исках да приличам на него.

Биологията ми беше много интересна, въпреки че в гимназията имах подчертани интереси към математика, и по литература също, но особено към математика. Винаги отбелязвам, че по наше време имаше привилегии в приемането в университета – активни борци, окръзите и т.н.³ И ние със сестра ми бяхме две от осемте момичета, които влязоха със свободен конкурс без никакви привилегии. Веднага след завършване на гимназия. Много ми харесваше следването. Беше много интересно. Аз съвсем не насила учех медицина.

А. К. – А там каква литература четяхте?

М. Шойлекова – Учебниците четях, те бяха достатъчно изпълващи времето на човек. А летните ваканции четях по-лека литература, бях изчала класиците, във втори курс прочетох Достоевски, прочетох Ървинг Стоун, четях биографиите на Шопен, на Паганини, на Рафаело, на Микеланджело, на Леонардо да Винчи. Любимни книги, романи почти не съм чела, освен тези на класиците. За жалост.

А. К. – Привличала Ви е явно човешката психика.

М. Шойлекова – Да, много, това всъщност е най-интересно от всичко. След като завърших, бях разпределена в Психоневро-

³ Привилегиите за децата на т.нар. „активни борци против фашизма и капитализма“ са въведени през 1959 г. От общия брой места за студенти по отделните специалности се отделя определен процент за тази категория кандидати. Предвидени са и квоти за някои окръзи, предимства за хора с увреждания и за сираци и деца от многодетни семейства. Привилегиите са отменени с указ на президента Желю Желев през 1990 г.

логичния диспансер в Стара Загора. Там имах един много ерудирани главен лекар, проф. Тимчев, Любомир Константинов Тимчев⁴. След първата година се явих на конкурсен изпит за асистент в Пловдивската детска клиника. Конкурсът беше за асистент по детска психоневрология, не по педиатрия, и там работих пет години, в Пловдивската детска клиника и междуременно ме изпратиха на специализация тук, в Софийската детска психиатрична клиника. Децата и техните проблеми силно ме завладяха, попаднах в тази клиника сред лекари, които бяха забележителни хора, и това ме мотивира да кандидатствам. Освен това, в Пловдивската детска клиника аз вече бях взела специалност по педиатрия, взех специалност и по психиатрия, но някак си детската психиатрия ми беше в недостатъчност, след като видях в София как работят хората, както и голямата широта на темите. Кандидатствах за асистент в катедрата по психиатрия в София, детската психиатрична клиника беше отделение към първа психиатрична клиника на Александровска болница, катедрата по психиатрия, и така...

След конкурса вече дойдох на работа тук, после се ожених и накрая се пенсионирах. В тази клиника. Клиниката се намираше в полите на Витоша, от спирка „Охрид“, три спирки преди Княжево и оттам се качваме нагоре по един баир и стигаме до детската клиника. Тя представляваше една вила, строена около 1940-те години на предишния век заедно със Съдебната палата, собственикът на вилата беше предприемач на построяването на Съдебната палата и горе-долу успоредно са строени. Някъде към 1952 година, или 1951, там се обособява детска психиатрична болница и малко по-късно Медицинска академия я взема за отделение към Психиатричната клиника. Медицинска академия плащаше наема на собственика. Преди да стане клиника, в болницата са работили д-р Лиляна Сахатчиева и д-р Ана Хубавенкова.⁵ След като става клиника, вече се обявяват конкурси, като лекари постъпват 1953-1954 година д-р Мария Светославова Гълъбова, която аз заварих в клиниката през 1970 година, когато отидох на специализация и по-късно работихме заедно; д-р Надежда Дашинова и д-р Меглена Ачкова⁶,

⁴ Проф. Любомир Тимчев е един от създателите на първите дневни центрове за деца с увреждания в България. Главен лекар на Института по неврология и психиатрия, професор в Югозападния университет „Неофит Рилски“.

⁵ Д-р Ана Хубавенкова е сред създателите и първа ръководителка на детската психиатрична болница в Павлово в началото на 1950-те години.

⁶ Проф. Меглена Ачкова (1930 – 2025) е една от основателките на детската психиатрия в България.

която после завеждаше клиниката и стана доцент и професор.

К. П. – *А първата ръководителка на клиниката, д-р Ана Хубавенкова, вие заварихте ли я?*

М. Шойлекова – В клиниката не я заварих, защото тя беше преминала на работа в Първа клиника, с възрастни. Тя беше много способен психиатър. А пък д-р Сахатчиева, беше преминала на работа на „Четвърти километър“⁷ и работеше в геронтологично отделение. И тя беше вече под името Михайлова, Лиляна Михайлова, но също е била много способен лекар.

А. К. – *Основно жени?*

И. Петров – Има и един мъж междуременно. През 1959 година бях стажант лекар в психиатричната клиника, мисля че тогава проф. Узунов⁸ каза, че е основано детско психиатрично отделение към катедрата по психиатрия и съобщи, че е назначен за завеждащ д-р Христозов⁹. Той това го съобщи, може би в 1959 г., и каза: „Завеждащ отделение, по моя заповед, е д-р Христозов“.

М. Шойлекова – Д-р Христозов беше доцент, преди това асистент, той е бил няколко години в Мароко да работи и като се е върнал, са го назначили за завеждащ детската клиника. Той завеждаше клиниката може би до 1980 година. Ние бяхме трима лекари и един професор до 1977 година, в която година се съединихме с детската психиатрична клиника, която беше на „Четвърти километър“. Нашата сграда на спирка „Охрид“ Академията я бе купила, наехме една вила на 20 метра от нашата, малко по-долу, и там се настани детското психиатрично отделение, което дойде от „Четвърти километър“. И станахме една голяма клиника с капацитет 65 - 70 легла, поне 65. В нашата клиника бяха 30 и в долната сграда – тя вече стана една клиника – още толкова или малко повече.

А. К. – *А къде живееше персоналът? Вие, като лекарка,*

⁷ Става дума за болница „Св. Наум“, основана като психиатрична клиника в 1938 г., водещ център за научни изследвания, преподавателска работа и лечебна дейност в областта на психиатрията, неврологията и неврохирургията – <https://svnaum.com/bg/za-nas/istoria>

⁸ Проф. Георги Узунов (1904 – 1971), завършил медицина в София, специализирал в Германия (Марбург). Директор на Психиатричната клиника към Висшия медицински институт в София 1954 – 1968.

⁹ Проф. Христо Христозов, психиатър, ръководител на института по неврология, психиатрия и неврохирургия в първата половина на 1980-те години.

къде живеехте, след като идвате от Пловдив?

М. Шойлекова – Аз живеех известно време в клиниката, след това на ул. „Ангел Кънчев“ 30, и след това, тук, в къщата на Игнат Петров.

А. К. – *Но в клиниката е имало възможност да се живее...*

М. Шойлекова – Да, на тавана. Те, лекарските кабинети, бяха на тавана. И аз живеех на тавана известно време. Аз бях толкова неопитна житейски, защото съм живяла при родителите си дотогава, че просто не смеех да се отделя от колегите, от клиниката.

**I SYMPOSIUM FÜR FORENSISCHE PSYCHIATRIE
IN BULGARIEN VARNA 7-8 OKTOBER '77**

Д-р Маргарита Шойлекова, Първи симпозиум по съдебна психиатрия в България, Варна, 7-8 октомври 1977

К. П. – *А в Стара Загора?*

М. Шойлекова – В Стара Загора живях на квартира. Но то беше – в сряда на обяд заминавам за Пловдив, после в четвъртък сутринта се връщам на работа. В събота на обяд – тогава беше шестдневна работна седмица - заминавам за Пловдив и в понеделник сутринта се връщам на работа.

А. К. – Имаше ли условия за работа в тази вила, приспособена за клиника?

М. Шойлекова – Да, тя беше приспособена. В сутерена беше готварницата, там се готвеше за децата. На първия етаж имаше занималня с телевизор, с играчки, с книги, на втория етаж имаше спални помещения, на втория етаж беше и кабинетът на проф. Христозов, и на таванския етаж бяха лекарските кабинети. Да ви кажа, за социализма, това бяха задоволителни условия, имаше двор, децата можеха да играят, да ги водят по поляните, на Витоша, недалеч от вилата. Изобщо приемливи бяха условията.

К. П. – А възпитателки, сестри, какъв персонал имаше?

М. Шойлекова – Сестрите бяха 6-7, възпитателките бяха две, имахме училище в клиниката, не училище, а учители от 99-то основно училище идваха, то беше болнично училище¹⁰, идваха учители в предобедните часове, като редовно училище, занимаваха децата като редовни ученици, то не бяха помощни занимания, а редовни, като в масовото училище. Следобед възпитателите ги подготвяха за следващия ден, за уроците. Изобщо организацията беше много добра, бих казала.

А. К. – А децата как идваха - с диагнози или в клиниката се поставяха диагнози?

К. П. – Кой ги водеше – от училище, или родителите?

М. Шойлекова – Родителите. Родителите ги довеждаха. Може би учителите са комуникирали с родителите. Родителите ги довеждаха. Ние без родителските наблюдения върху децата им, нищо не можехме да изградим, като предболнично състояние, като история на развитието на детето, това са неща, които от бременността се проследяват: кърмаческа възраст, ранна детска възраст до три години, латентния период, който започва на шест години до предпубертета, предпубертет - това само родителите могат да го кажат, а без да имаме тези данни, само с настоящите отклонения, с които родителите идват, не може да се влезе в дълбочина в разбирането за проблема на детето.

¹⁰ Болничните училища в България се създават през 1950-те години, за да могат децата, които остават за по-продължително лечение, да продължат образованието си. През 2017 г. съществуващите четири болнични училища в София, Пловдив, Плевен и Момин проход са закрити или преобразувани в центрове за подкрепа на личностно развитие.

А. К. – *Те на каква възраст бяха - децата?*

М. Шойлекова – Децата бяха от три до осемнадесет години.

К. П. – *А също и деца с различни степени на изоставане?*

М. Шойлекова – Не, не, съвсем не, с изоставане. За децата, които са с изоставане, нещата се решаваха в извънболничната помощ. Те се приемаха в клиниката за кратко време, за диагностично уточняване, но се лекуваха в извънболничната помощ. Ако се налага по-продължително наблюдение, ако не могат да се уточнят нещата в извънболничната помощ, тогава в клиниката идваха за по седмица – две, най-много. А пък основно при нас идваха деца с емоционални разстройства, поведенчески разстройства и с психози. Те бяха за по-продължително време за наблюдение и за лечение. Лечението, разбира се, не беше само медикаментозно, лечението беше и психотерапевтично, и занимателна терапия, игрова терапия. Имаше възможност за това. Децата с психози се лекуваха с лекарства.

А. К. – *С какви лекарства?*

М. Шойлекова – С невролептици, психозите. Депресии също сме имали, които са по-редки в допубертета. По изключение сме имали деца между 10 и 14 години с депресии, и не само с депресии, но и с други колебания на настроението, те също се лекуваха с медикаменти.

А. К. – *Колко горе-долу време при такива случаи престояваше дете в клиниката?*

М. Шойлекова - При по-тежко болните деца, които имаха нужда от по-продължително лечение, докъм 30 дни се овладяваха острите прояви на болестта и след това се продължаваше в домашна обстановка, като идваха на контролни прегледи и се следеше лечението. Имаше и лежащо болни. Спалните помещения бяха на първия и на втория етаж. На първия момчетата, на втория момичетата.

А. К. – *Постоянни контакти сте имали и с родителите?*

М. Шойлекова – Те винаги бяха довеждани от родителите. В дневния стационар родителите довеждаха децата и следобед ги вземаха. Всеки ден.

К. П. – Родителите имаха ли възможност да остават в клиниката?

М. Шойлекова – Не, нямаше възможност.

А. Касабова – А да посещават децата?

М. Шойлекова – Да ги посещават, да. Всеки ден можеха да идват. След следобедните учебни занимания. Децата почиваха, разбира се, следобед. Но след пет часа те на двора играеха, тогава родителите можеха всеки ден да идват и да се срещат с децата.

А. К. – Децата преди и след клиниката в масовите училища ли учеха?

М. Шойлекова – Да. Изоставашите деца тогава учеха в мощни училища, нямаше ресурсни учители, такава практика нямаше тогава. Сега, мисля, вече няма помощни училища.

К. П. – А как се изследваха децата, с какви методи? С психологично изследване? С електроенцефалографии, пневмоенцефалографии?

М. Шойлекова – Първото изследване, което се провежда, е лекарското клинично изследване: на психичен статус, в който се обследват всички психични сфери, психомоториката, контакта, т.е. комуникацията, речта, съзнанието, мисленето, паметта, емоциите. Лекарят изследва психичния, неврологичния и соматичния статус. Назначават се, ако е необходимо, физикални изследвания, рентгени, лаборатория – обикновената лаборатория беше неотменна, но и рентген, консултации с невролог, консултации с офталмолог, ако е необходимо, ако има проблеми със слуха, съответно – с уши-нос-гърло. Клинично-лабораторното изследване е задължително, а рентген, електроенцефалография (ЕЕГ) и други изследвания – по преценка, ако е необходимо. Ако има сърдечен проблем, консултации с кардиолог, тогава нямаше „клинични пътеки“ и спокойно можехме да изследваме всички системи. Имаше деца, не често и не много, но поне няколко аз си спомням със сърдечен порок, които се следяха и от кардиолог. При тях беше по-деликатно ... и психолог, психологично изследване, то вървеше непосредствено след клиничното изследване. Изследва се емоционалната сфера подробно, проблема на детето, познавателната сфера, когнитивното развитие се оценява, макар да няма данни за изоставане в развитието, все пак степента на развитие се оценява.

А. К. – Как, с някакви тестове ли?

М. Шойлекова – Да, с тестове.

К. П. – Вече се използваха тестове?

М. Шойлекова – Използваха се, вече бяха разрешени. Някъде докъм 1970 година, може би и малко по-късно, психологичните тестове бяха много ограничени по примера на съветската медицина. В детската клиника след това вече се използваха, от седемдесета година със сигурност.

Игнат Петров – Аз мога да кажа, че през 1960-те години имаше структури, където тестовете бяха съвсем желани. Това беше проф. Матеев¹¹, когато аз постъпих в геронтологията през 1964 година, той ми каза – почни с психологични тестове. Не само Матеев, и Узунов поощряваше тестовете...

Декада по геронтология, Плевен. Седнали около масата: Игнат Петров и Драгомир Матеев

Маргарита Шойлекова – да, може би 1960-те години. Но преди това не са били позволени. Но аз не съм работила във времето, когато психологичните тестове не са били практикувани в българската психология.

А. К. – Изследванията при специалисти – вие водехте децата или те идваха при вас?

М. Шойлекова – Обикновено сестра водеше децата. Защото бяхме далече от центъра и идваше линейка, и детето, заедно със сестрата, отиваше в съответния кабинет за преглед, за консултация и това беше много полезно, защото, да кажем, едно соматично, телесно болно дете, е

¹¹ Проф. Драгомир Матеев (1902 – 1971), физиолог, е един от пионерите на българската геронтология.

много деликатно да се лекува с невролептици и една прецизна консултация ще даде възможност да сложим граница: откъде - докъде, с какво, доколко.

К. П. – *А спомняте ли са някои особено впечатляващи случаи?*

М. Шойлекова – Спомням си много случаи. Но... едно момиченце от Пловдив си спомням, което беше на 12 години и дойде с много тежка депресия. Толкова деликатно дете, толкова интелигентно. И потънало в депресия. Но излезе от депресията с лекарства, не се наложи да му се правят електрошокове. После не съм проследила това дете в живота – дали е имало следващи епизоди. Спомням си едно друго дете, на 17 години, което ... аз всичките си ги спомням, но тези на прима виста мога да ги разкажа ... което беше с много неблагоприятно протичащо афективно разстройство, в смисъл, че изпаднаше във фаза на приповдигнато настроение, която успяхме да овладеем, то преминаваше във фаза на депресия, на потиснато настроение. Въпреки че тогава вече се практикуваха тимостабилизаторите, които балансират настроението, ... но имаше и такива случаи, които не се повлияваха, и това дете покъсно го виждах, на 24 години, и то продължаваше да живее с тези проблеми, вече възрастните психиатри го бяха поели. Спомням си едно дете от Пловдив, което много страдаше поради развода на родителите и като протестна реакция или като реакция на всичките му преживявания, то се оформи като анорексия, анорексията за жалост не е лесно лечима болест, но това дете завърши медицина и стана лекарка. Имам още един случай – те са много диференцирани тези случаи, анорексичните – един случай, в който едно дете дойде с тежка анорексия, която съзнателно се опитваше да контролира. Анорексията си остана, но и то завърши медицина и сега е лекарка в София, то беше софийанче.

А. К. – *Анорексията засяга момичета основно.*

М. Шойлекова – Има и момчета, имаше едно момче също с анорексия, но те са много суспектни за това, анорексията да бъде симптом на една пълзяща психоза. Но него не съм го проследила, не знам как се развиха нещата при него. Анорексията може да е синдром на психозата, начална симптоматика на една пълзяща и задълбочаваща се психоза.

А. К. – Как се лекува анорексията?

М. Шойлекова – Анорексията се лекува главно с психотерапия. Главно. Но може би не е чак толкова безнадеждно, защото се получават подобрения, не бих казала ремисии, и децата се социализират, въпреки заболяването и се включват в обществения живот, завършват, някаква професия добиват, започват работа. Разбира се, има много тежки случаи, които завършват много лошо.

А. К. – А електрошок кога се прилагаше?

М. Шойлекова – По изключение, в юношеската възраст, ако една психоза не се повлиява. Но по изключение. Ние, детските психиатри не обичаме електрошока. Ако не се повлиява от медикаментозно лечение, тогава в единични случаи сме изпращали деца долу в клиниката за електрошокова терапия.

К. П. – Вие нямахте такава апаратура?

М. Шойлекова – Ние нямахме такава апаратура, да.

К. П. – А сънна терапия?

М. Шойлекова – Сънна терапия при децата не се прилага, но аз, докато работех в Стара Загора, съм прилагала сънна терапия на зрели хора, жени предимно, с ... тогава се наричаха невротични разстройства, сега се наричат по друг начин – главно на жени с конверсионни разстройства¹², един вид невротични разстройства.

А. К. – Какви са Вашите наблюдения, как действаше?

М. Шойлекова – Сънната терапия ли? Аз не съм ... те се чувстваха доволни, че някой се занимава с тях специално, и имаше, имаше овладяване на симптоматиката донякъде.

К. П. – А имаше ли в детската клиника случаи от съдебната психиатрия, например деца насилници?

М. Шойлекова – Не, не сме имали. При нас имаше деца с поведенчески разстройства, които се лекуваха, но чак с такива зловещи прояви, които сега по телевизията гледаме, при нас не са постъпвали. Имаше съдебно отделение долу в клиниката, имаше голямо съдебно отделение на Четвърти километър, може би там са били приемани.

¹² Конверсионни разстройство: психични разстройства, които се проявяват като неврологични заболявания.

К. П. – *А другите терапии от това време – инсулинова, сулфоназин и други, прилагали ли са се?*

М. Шойлекова – При деца, не. При деца не сме прилагали. Когато аз постъпих, инсулиновата терапия вече беше изоставена, но преди това се е прилагала. В доневролептичната ера се е прилагала и при деца.

Игнат Петров – Аз в онези три години, в които работих в Карлуково¹³, която беше голяма и много добра болница, работех втората година в остро мъжко отделение, правехме инсулинови коми, и аз по указания правех, но аз не останах убеден, че трябва да се правят, повече разчитахме на електрошокове... там имаше обзавеждане за електрошок, тогава не се правеше краткотрайна наркоза, правехме “сухи“ електрошокове. Но ние главно разчитахме на невролептици, които бяха малко, но основно разчитахме на хлорпромазин.

К. П. – *А пневмоенцефалография използваше ли се?*

Игнат Петров – Тя се е използвала в 1940-те години от моя баща, доц. Христо Петров¹⁴, който в това отношение е основна фигура. Хр. Петров в доста отношения е първият, той прави заедно с Ангел Пенчев¹⁵ първия електрошок в София, в България. А заедно с проф. Гоце Тенчов¹⁶ въвеждат пневмоенцефалографията. Те се сприятеляват главно поради стремежа на Хр. Петров, който е инициатор неврохирургичното отделение, да разработи образна диагностика на мозъчните тумори; в последните години много е работил за диагностика на мозъчните тумори включително с пневмоенцефалография. Тя се въвежда тогава, въпреки че тя не е щадяща терапия и е изоставена по-късно (след въвеждането на скенера). При пневмоенцефалография се вкарва въздух, разширява се обемът на дадена област на мозъка и по-добре се виждат туморите. С

¹³ Държавната психиатрична болница в Карлуково е една от най-старите психиатрични институции в България. Създадена е в 1902 г.

¹⁴ Доц. Христо Петров (1901 – 1944), психиатър. Загива при бомбардировките над София на 10 януари 1944г., заедно с още петима лекари от Александровска болница, които остават при своите пациенти въпреки обявената въздушна тревога.

¹⁵ Проф. Ангел Пенчев (1894 – 1975), невролог и психиатър, заедно с д-р Христо Петров въвежда през 1942 г. електро-конвулсивната терапия в България.

¹⁶ Проф. Гоце Тенчов (1906 – 1960), рентгенолог, първи ректор на Института за усъвършенстване на лекарите (ИСУЛ), днешната УМБАЛ „Царица Йоанна – ИСУЛ“, където развива рентгенова диагностика, включително на мозъка..

рентген се визуализира. Сега, като има скенер, няма смисъл. Маргарита е правила пневмоенцефалография при десетина дечица от неврологичната клиника в Пловдив. Пневмоенцефалографията не е терапия, а метод за изследване.

А. К. – *Вие казахте, че възрастовият диапазон на децата е бил от 3 до 18 години, идваха ли деца от домовете „Майка и дете“? Обръщаха ли се към вас за консултация?*

Маргарита Шойлекова – Аз, като работех в Пловдив, правих едно голямо изследване на нервно-психичното развитие на децата от Дом „Майка и дете“ в Пловдив, но то разбира се, за да се правят изводи, трябва да има катамнеза, за да се проследи нататък как ще бъде, за да се проследи дали задръжката ще бъде ситуативна, социална, или пък е от увреждане. Разбира се, грубите отклонения, които говорят за мозъчно увреждане, се диагностицират с тези методи, тогава с пневмоенцефалография, правеха се и електроенцефалографии тогава. Но в клиниката при нас, в София, не сме имали контакт с Дом „Майка и дете“.

А. К. – *А това Ваше изследване имате ли го, публикувано ли е?*

М. Шойлекова – Не, така ми стоят фишовете от изследванията. Там, някъде на тавана в Пловдив са, прашясали.

А. К. – *Това беше Ваш интерес или Ви насочиха към тази тема?*

М. Шойлекова – Когато постъпих в Детска клиника, аз бях на 23 години, така че интересите ми не бяха толкова диференцирани. Това ми го предложи професорът, проф. Иван Вапцаров¹⁷, който беше ръководител на Детска клиника – един забележителен ум и забележителен педиатър. Други проблеми, с които съм се занимавала, това са „минималните мозъчни дисфункции“, занимавала съм се също с „анорексия нервоза“.

К. П. – *Първата ли сте, която се е занимавала с анорексия?*

М. Шойлекова – Да, аз съм първата, която се захвана с тема

¹⁷ Проф. Иван Вапцаров (1908 – 1997), изтъкнат педиатър, завършил медицина в Лозана и Нанси. Дългогодишен директор на клиниката по детски болести във Висшия медицински институт в Пловдив.

за анорексията, но не я завърших. После се родиха децата и за четири години прекъснах, бях по майчинство четири години, те бяха едно след друго, децата. И после не продължих. Занимавах се с плацебо ефекта, с минималната мозъчна дисфункция също – бях първата в темата за минималните мозъчни увреждания. Това е, което сега наричат хиперактивно разстройство – то разбира се, не се изчерпва само с хиперактивност, тук идва и дефицитът на вниманието, като неотменна черта на хиперкинетичното разстройство, и в развитие идват училищните проблеми, голям част от децата с минимална мозъчна дисфункция – „minimal brain damage“, една част от тях попадат в групата на деца с поведенчески разстройства.

К. П. – *Тъй наречените преди това трудновъзпитаеми деца?*

М. Шойлекова – Когато се говореше за трудновъзпитаеми деца, още не съществуваше тази диагноза: за трудновъзпитаеми деца се говореше в края на 1960-те – 1970-те години, а пък минималните мозъчни дисфункции, се наложиха на вниманието на детските психиатри някъде 1972 – 1973 година.

А. К. – *Кога се диференцираха т. нар. днес разстройства от аутистичния спектър?*

М. Шойлекова – Те винаги са били много значими. Ако се интересувате конкретно за ранния детски аутизъм при децата, той горе-долу... някъде към 1970 година вече започват да излизат на български публикации за ранния детски аутизъм. Ранният детски аутизъм е описан от Канер¹⁸ в 1943, а в България добива известност в края на 1960-те. Сегашните имена вече са ми съвсем непознати.

К. П. – *Откъде дойдоха тези нови определения, с какви колеги общувахте?*

М. Шойлекова – Колегите от детската клиника бяха немскоговорящи, аз не бях. Общувахме с Лайпциг и Рощок. И с Берлин, в тези градове имаше детски клиники. Освен това общувахме с Москва и Ленинград, които бяха много определящи политиката в детската психиатрия, политиката в смисъл, доминацията на една

¹⁸ Проф. Лео Канер (1894 – 1981) е австрийски и американски детски психиатър, който заедно с Ханс Аспергер се смята за един от основоположниците на изследванията на ранния детски аутизъм.

или друга диагноза, защото диференциацията не е лесна. Школите опознавахме по книгите, но ходехме по конгреси и симпозиуми и се срещахме с последователите или поддръжниците на тези школи. Например, руснаците – в Москва всяка психоза бяха склонни да я дефинират като шизофрения, а психиатрите от Ленинград повече като депресия. Докато французите изобщо не говореха за шизофрения и за циклофрения, те говореха за синдроми: синдром на повишено настроение, на понижено настроение, параноиден синдром и т.н. А германците бяха по-умерени и по-справедливи, точни, бих казала. Не залитаха нито в едната, нито в другата посока, но сякаш малко повече накланяха към афективните разстройства, към манийно-депресивните състояния, малко повече. Увлечението по шизофренията започва от Снежневски.¹⁹

А. К. – Но вие сте познавали различните школи: съветска, френска, немска школа...

М. Шойлекова – Ходехме по конгреси и познавахме професорите, а и по-ниските степени, се познавахме, защото се виждахме.

А. К. – Конгреси по детска психиатрия?

М. Шойлекова – Да, симпозиуми. В България имаше конгрес по детска психиатрия през 1987 година, във Варна.

А. К. – А преди това къде сте ходили?

М. Шойлекова – Главно в Германия – в ГДР, и в Русия.

К. П. – Помните ли някои от имената?

М. Шойлекова – Всичките имена ги помня. В Германия, най-доминиращият беше проф. Гьолниц²⁰, който завеждаше катедрата в Роцок. В Лайпциг, не му помня името, защото той беше

¹⁹ Андрей Владимирович Снежневски (1904 – 1987), съветски психиатър, директор на Института по психиатрия на АМН на СССР 1962 – 1987, привърженик на концепцията за вяло протичащата шизофрения – диагноза, използвана за политически репресии, с която противници на съветския режим са били изпращани в наказателни психиатрични институции.

²⁰ Герхард Гьолниц (1920 – 2003), професор по психиатрия в Роцок, е създател на първата катедра по детска психиатрия в Германската демократична република (ГДР) и неин ръководител от 1958 до 1983 г. Приносите му са главно в областта на изследванията на мозъчните увреждания в ранното детство.

невролог, там детската психиатрия и детската неврология бяха заедно, но помня имена на колеги. Един от колегите там беше Шолц²¹, който беше от групата на психиатрите, после стана професор и до пенсионирането си завеждаше катедрата в Дрезден. А в Русия имаше много професори. Най-доминиращ беше Ковальов²², който работеше в Детската психиатрична клиника, Ушаков²³, който също работеше в Москва, Вроно²⁴, който работеше в Ленинград ... Това бяха водещите тогава.

А. К. – На тези симпозиуми са идвали и от западни държави, можехте ли там да контактувате свободно?

М. Шойлекова – Имаше и от западните държави, да. Можехме да контактуваме главно с изказванията, с докладите. Проф. Вроно беше много интересен човек и казваше „Симпозиум хоросее дело, но зачеш доклады?“²⁵ Защо то след работните часове се ходеше на забавления и там общувахме, но вече не по научните проблеми. С руснаците не беше трудно, защото в училище много се учеше руски. А моите интереси, в гимназията още, бяха към латинския език. Аз имах доста и все още имам доста познания. Той не е говорим език, но все пак ми помагаше много, помагаше да разбирам, защото той е в основата на романските езици.

К. П. – Достъп имахте ли до литература, до различни издания?

М. Шойлекова – Да, имахме. В Пловдив много се ползваше френска литература, защото професорът беше завършил във Франция и му изпращаха списания и той ги предоставяше, списанията.

²¹ Проф. Михаел Шолц (1941 – 2021) е немски психиатър. Следва медицина в София и Лайпциг. От 1972 г. е професор по детска невропсихиатрия в Лайпциг и е основоположник на семейната терапия в ГДР. Посвещава много усилия за подпомагане за организиране на помощи за България и особено за подпомагане на децата, лишени от родителски грижи през 1990-те години.

²² Александр Григориевич Ковальов (1928 – 2008), ръководител на катедрата по детска психиатрия и психотерапия, от 1980 г. оглавява научноизследователския институт по психиатрия в Москва.

²³ Геннадий Константинович Ушаков (1921 – 1981), съветски педиатър и психиатър, специалист в областта на психичните разстройства в детската възраст.

²⁴ Проф. Моисей Шиманович Вроно (1918 – 1990), съветски психиатър, ръководител на клиниката за детска психиатрия към Академията на медицинските науки от 1965 до 1988 г.

²⁵ „Хубаво нещо е симпозиумът, но за какво са [нужни] докладите?“ (рус.)

Андреев беше завършил в Германия. Английски не толкова се популяризираше в научните среди, но постепенно той настъпи, когато за мен вече беше късно да го уча.

А. К. – *Казвате, че имате материали на тавана. А пазите ли снимки? От клиниката, от тези симпозиуми?*

К. П. – *Това ще е изключително ценно!*

М. Шойлекова – От клиниката, не мога да си спомня. Нямам много снимки – имам снимки в Рошок, имам снимки в Москва, конгресни, разбира се. Може би и в Лайпциг. Но нямам подредени албуми. Никога не се занимавах с това, по кутиите стоят.

К. П. – *А децата от клиниката, ако са рисували, пазят ли се някъде рисунките?*

М. Шойлекова – Затова психолозите могат да ви помогнат.

7ми Конгрес по детска психиатрия, Москва, 1977. Втори ред, от ляво на дясно: трета д-р М. Ачкова, четвърта - д-р М. Шойлекова

К. П. – *Търсила съм архива на тази клиника, но не се намира. Все пак той сигурно се съхранява някъде.*

М. Шойлекова – Да ви кажа, архивът трудно ще го намерите. Осемдесет и трета година, когато беше едно от преименуванията на мюсюлманските българи, на българите мюсюлмани, ни накараха да унищожим всички истории на заболявания, заедно с всички изследвания в тях. Не знам защо. Не само на...на всички,

до 1983 година... До 1983 година трябваше да се унищожат всички листове и истории на заболяванията. Вътре са били и рисунките, и психологичните изследвания, и клиничните описания, абсолютно всичко... тъй че – няма как да се намери.

Игнат Петров – Имаше такова идиотско разпореждане – да се унищожат всички листове... Знам отделни колеги, които имаха далновидността да си запазят документацията.

А. К. – *Това е било общо нареждане, не само за тази клиника.*

М. Шойлекова – А, не само за тази клиника!

И. Петров – В Бяла²⁶ д-р Маринов е запазил документацията, но в нашата психиатрична клиника, проф. Иванов... съвсем така методично да се унищожат... както е заповедта.

М. Шойлекова – То беше заповед!

А. К. – *А имаше ли някакъв аргумент, някаква причина?*

М. Шойлекова – Аз така си спомням, че във връзка с преименуването, но защо всичките се унищожиха, не знам, не се подбираха.

А. К. – *Този факт около т.нар. възродителен процес, не сме и знаели, колко щети е нанесъл.*

А. К. – *Как се чувствахте след като се пенсионирахте, продължихте ли да работите?*

М. Шойлекова – Имаше една акция в Медицинска академия през 2002 година, на която всички, които имат достатъчно трудов стаж, а пък аз имах достатъчно, защото съм започнала на 23 години работа, ги пенсионираха, аз бях тогава на 57 години. Искам, не искам, се пенсионирах, после продължих да работя в кабинет, в ИСУЛ, бях наела кабинет, имах разрешително за кабинет и работих доста активно, разбира се, но когато през 2011 година трябваше да правим някакви административни работи, имаше наредба да се подновяват документи... да се ходи по учреждения. Аз така отпаднах, защото не мога да ходя по учреждения.

А. К. – *Търсеха ли ви за консултации и след това?*

М. Шойлекова – След това ме търсеха по телефона, у нас

²⁶ Държавната психиатрична болница в град Бяла е създадена в 1910 г. и е една от най-големите психиатрични институции в България.

телефонът непрекъснато звънеше, но след като не ги приемах в кабинет, хората полека – лека... пък пациентите, които звънях по телефона, и телефонната консултация ги задоволяваше, и досега правя разговори с пациенти, които познавам от много време. Но вече не приемам.

К. П. – *Липсва ли ви работата?*

М. Шойлекова – Постепенно се свиква. После, мъжът ми продължава да работи. Той идва вкъщи, разказва, какъв е случаят, какво е намерил, какво е предписал, така че, аз все едно, че съм присъствала на прегледа...

А. К. – *А сега, по отношение на диагнози, какво се предписва, как виждате развитията? Има ли голяма промяна?*

М. Шойлекова – В принципите на лечение няма промяна, но сега вече има много препарати, на много фирми. Така че, дали ще се предприше един антидепресант на една фирма, или на друга фирма, дали антидепресант от една група, или от друга група, това не са съществени промени.

К. П. – *А как гледате на психотерапията?*

М. Шойлекова – Аз не мога да кажа, че съм веща в психотерапията, но с рационална психотерапия се справях добре. Това е разговорна психотерапия, според проблема, според случая, разбира се. В психотерапията не се предлагат решения, очаква се пациентът да избистри проблема си и сам до стигне до решение, но това също е голямо майсторство, да му помогнеш да осъзнае някои неща, за да стигне до решение.

А. К. – *Това изисква и по-голяма продължителност.*

М. Шойлекова – Да, психотерапията изобщо иска голяма продължителност.

К. П. – *А психоанализата, Фройд четеше ли се, тайно или явно, във времето докато учехте или работехте?*

М. Шойлекова – С Фройд съм се запознавала доста основно, чела съм книгите му. Всъщност това познание много помага на човек да изясни генезиса на проблемите на пациента. Иначе методите, малко хора практикуват.

Игнат Петров – В нашата психиатрия, която е клинична пси-

хиатрия, психоанализата е била винаги настрана. Христо Димитров²⁷ разработваше идеите на Фройд.

М. Шойлекова – Да, Тинко Димитров. В детската психиатрия съвсем не се пренебрегваше Фройд, съвсем не. Разбира се, през социализма това не се афишираше в никакъв случай, но познаването, доколкото познавахме неговото учение, помагаше в немалка степен.

И. Петров – сега има много психотерапевти, които са вече психолози. Вчера слушах една психоложка, която работи позитивна психотерапия.

М. Шойлекова – Според случая се подхожда конкретно. Тя го разбира така, както науката ѝ го разбира. Това е да се търси позитивното. Например, ако един човек се оплаче, че страда от безсъние, не знам дали това е най-доброто нещо, но, за да му подейства човек позитивно, би казал, ами чудесно, ти имаш възможност да четеш, докато ти се доспи.

А. К. – *Но и сега много медикаментозно се подхожда, конкретно при безсъние често се предписват приспивателни.*

К. П. – *И това, за което вие казахте – разстройство на вниманието, дислексия, това също се лекува медикаментозно...*

М. Шойлекова – хиперактивността, която протича с разстройство на вниманието при децата, може да се подпомага с медикаменти, но голямо място в тази терапия заема поведенческата терапия – болният да се научи как да се справя с проблемите.

А. К. – *Искам да ви попитам за д-р Кръстников, който прилага репродукция на преживяванията, пак по Фройд, но го модифицира.*

И. Петров – Никола Кръстников²⁸ е първият българин избран за ръководител на катедрата по неврология и психиатрия, но още първата година... получава мозъчен кръвоизлив и умира млад.

²⁷ Христо Димитров (1928 – 1974) е психиатър, който през 1960-те и 1970-те години критично изучава психоанализата на Фройд, както и трудовете на Никола Кръстников. Негов ученик е младият асистент д-р Георги Каменов, който през 1980-те години създава една първите групи по психоанализа по време на социализма в България.

²⁸ Д-р Никола Кръстников (1880 – 1936), завършил медицина в Санкт Петербург, Русия, е сред е учредителите на българското психиатрично дружество през 1921 г. Той е сред първите психиатри, които въвеждат психоанализата в България.

Той има разработен такъв метод, репродукция. Неговият син, Ангел Кръстников, психиатър, той също почина, го прилагаше.

М. Шойлекова – Също и проф. Чолаков, подобен метод.

Пред болницата в Карлуково. От ляво на дясно: Недко Попдимитров (син на аптекаря), д-р Тома Данаилов, д-р Константин Константинов, д-р Емил Христофоров – главен лекар, д-р Йонка Дучевска, д-р Игнат Петров, д-р Чергаров (стоматолог)

К. П. – *Може ли да Ви върна към примера Карлуково. Като казахте, че е била добре уредена болницата, какво имахте предвид?*

Игнат Петров – Това беше болница, в която са работили редица способни хора. Проф. Киров, проф. Петко Дончев, Тодор Бостанджиев, Захарина Манолова, Йонка Дучевска – и те като млади лекари са имали амбицията да бъде една добра болница, и беше призната за база за специализация по психиатрия.

К. П. – *Хубави ли бяха условията там за лекарите и за пациентите?*

Игнат Петров – За пациентите, не. Не най-лошите, но общо взето непривлекателни – в стари сгради, по няколко души в стая, специално отделенията, специално двете отделения, в които аз работех бяха сгради, строени някъде през петдесетте години, стаите с повече легла, общи бани и общи тоалетни, неприветливи, нямаше

този лукс, който сега можеш да видиш в нови болници с двама души в стая със собствена тоалетна. Що се отнася до лекарите, ние бяхме много добре. Ние бяхме в т.нар. бяла къща, в която всеки беше в самостоятелна стая или, в началото след постъпването, по двама в стая. Аз живях в началото в една стая със забележителния аптекар Стефан Попдимитров, кратко време с „административния началник“ и най-дълго в самостоятелна стая, която „наследих“ от първата ми началничка, Йонка Дучевска, и досега си мечтая за моята стая в Карлуково – и за Карлуково.

А. К. – Но в детската клиника не е било така – лекарите са били в таванските стаи, а по-добрите стаи – за децата.

М. Шойлекова – Поне в нашата клиника, която беше къща. А в клиниката в Александровска болница нямаше таван. Ние сме на първия и втория етаж, на горния етаж е нервна клиника, неврохирургия, бяха стаи с по десет легла, в Пловдив, в психиатрията имаше стаи с по десет легла.

И. Петров – Условието за болните в Александровска болница и в Карлуково не се различаваха много. В Карлуково – малко по-лошо. Ние се гордеехме, че редица методи на лечение за първи път са въведени в Карлуково. Защото например д-р Мезан²⁹ е ходил във Франция и е донесъл ларгактила (хлорпромазин)³⁰.

И. Петров – Нашият аптекар в Карлуково, който беше изключителна личност, чичо Стефан (Попдимитров), ходеше регулярно в Ловеч да снабдява болницата със ларгактил и серпазил, покъсно и нозинан, и антидепресанта тофранил. И практикувахме също електрошок там.

М. Шойлекова – Когато лекарствата дойдоха, това просто превърна болницата в едни добри отделения. Когато лекарствата дойдоха. Преди това фиксирани болни, вързани за леглото, ... инсулинови терапии... много тежко.

К. П. и А. К. – Имаше ли такива неща и при децата – връзване и други такива...

²⁹ Доц д-р Исак Мезан (192? – 1976), невролог. След специализация в Париж през 1965 г., той за първи път прилага Largactyl в болницата в Карлуково, а след това в болница „Св. Наум“ в София.

³⁰ Хлорпромазинът (*Chlorpromazine*), разработен през 1950г. от френския химик Пол Шарпентие, е антипсихотичен препарат, разпространяван и под търговските марки торазин, ларгактил и аминазин.

М. Шойлекова – Не. Медикаментите много помогнаха психиатрията да добие човешки вид.

Игнат Петров – В Карлуково, която беше болница с 400 легла, аз съм присъствал на връзване ... за няколко часа или денонощие, ако буйства ... да се успокои ...

М. Шойлекова – Ами да, това са млади и силни мъже и жени, без лекарства е трудно...

К. П. – *А алкохолиците, и те ли бяха там?*

И. Петров – Не, по принцип малко алкохолици попадаха в Карлуково. На Четвърти километър³¹ също не е имало алкохолно отделение. В Суходол³², в Раднево³³... В Суходол беше по-късно.

А. К. и К. П. – *Много Ви благодарим за ценните познания, които споделихте с нас. Важен е Вашият път към медицината, към детската психиатрия. Спомените Ви за условията, в които сте работили, за развитията в психиатрията са неоценими при тези изгубени или унищожени архиви.*

М. Шойлекова – Аз нищо не измислям, може да не си спомням добре дати, но...

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³¹ Днес болница „Св. Наум“, вж. бел. 7.

³² Държавната психиатрична болница в Суходол (София) е специализирана за лечение на наркозависимости и алкохолизъм. Създадена е в 1969 г.

³³ Психиатричната болница „Д-р Георги Кисъов“ в Раднево е създадена в 1955 г. Смята се, че тук за първи път е въведена трудотерапията като лечебен метод, използва се и сънна терапия. Въведени са и терапевтични методи за лечение на алкохолни - и наркозависимости.

BOOK REVIEW

Mariyana Piskova

South-West University "Neofit Rilski", Bulgaria

[piskova@gmail.com]

The History of Cinema once Again Encountered its Captivating Narrator

Abstract: *The latest book by the renowned film historian Petar Kardzhilov brings together eight independent studies on the early steps of Bulgarian cinema. The chronological scope of the narrative is limited to the period between the two World Wars, while the thematic framework covers film history from the establishment of the foundational joint-stock company Luna in 1919 to the arrival of cinema in Bulgarian villages. The official history of film institutions is interwoven and enriched with personalities and human destinies of unknown, forgotten, or even overlooked pioneers – trailblazers whose contributions and rightful place belong to the biography of early Bulgarian cinema.*

The book presents the emergence of film schools, as well as Bulgarian feature films produced between 1921 and 1923, and examines the activities of early film institutions in Bulgaria, including associations of film distributors, cinema operators, and cinema owners. For the first time, previously unknown data about Bulgarian films and their creators from the 1920s and 1930s are made public. Attention is also given to the activities of the film departments of the Ministry of Agriculture and the General Directorate of Public Health.

Keywords: *history of early cinema in Bulgaria; institutionalization of cinema in Bulgaria; Bulgarian cinema between the two World Wars; joint-stock company Luna.*

Марияна Пискова

Югозападен университет „Неофит Рилски“

Историята на киното отново среща своя сладкодумен разказвач

Кърджилков, Петър „От Луна АД до кинопросветата по селата. Индустриално и институционално в българското кино между двете световни войни“. София: Институт за изследване на изкуствата, 2025, 408 стр.

Името на Петър Кърджилов е добре известно не само на изследователите и експертите в областта на киноисторията, но и на всички, които проявяват интерес към миналото на българското кино. След неговите многобройни публикации и дългогодишни проучвания, отличаващи се с изключителна прецизност и задълбоченост, сякаш не са останали бели полета в българската киноистория¹. Но, с всяка следваща книга и с всеки нов текст, Петър Кърджилов отново и отново доказва, че киноисторията е неизчерпаема и безкрайна, че ви-

наги има нещо ново, което той може да разкаже, че наглед познати и изследвани теми могат да бъдат осветлени още по-дълбоко, в детайли, с неочаквани и неизвестни до днес подробности. В новата си книга авторът избира периода между двете световни войни – 20-те и 30-те години на миналия век. Неговият увлекателен разказ превежда читателя през зараждащите се институции, свързани с киното в посочените времеви граници, но Петър Кърджилов остава верен на себе си и на своя отличаващ го изследователски подход и отново поставя в центъра на изследването си човека. Официалната история на киноинституциите е преплетена и изпъстрена с човешки съдби на неизвестни, позабравени и дори пропуснати от

¹Петър Кърджилов е автор на 24 книги, голяма част от които по история на българското кино. Сред тях са: *Петър Кърджилов* „Светлопис за Илинден“. София, „Титра“, 2009, 174 стр. *Петър Кърджилов*, Загадките на филма „Балканската война“. София, ИК „Титра“, 2006, 328 стр.; *Петър Кърджилов*, Филмът „Балканската война“ в историята на българското кино. София, Институт за изследване на изкуствата при БАН, 2011, *Петър Кърджилов*. „Озарения в полите на Витоша. Летопис на ранното кино в София (1896 – 1915).“ София: Издателство на БАН „Проф. Марин Дринов“, 2016, 608 стр.; *Петър Кърджилов*. Загадките и времената на „Българан е галант“. Кога, от кого, къде, как и защо е заснет първият български игрален филм? Какво знаем за него? София: Издателство на БАН „Проф.Марин Дринов“, 2017, 737 стр.; *Петър Кърджилов, Ирина Китова, Зорница Кръстева* Летопис на нямото кино в София (1896 –1933), София Културен център G8, 2022, 238 стр.

киноисторията първопроходци, пионери, със свой принос и място в биографията на ранното българско кино.

Първата студия хвърля светлина върху най-ранните институции – Съюз на българските филмодавци, Акционерно дружество „Луна“ (София) и първите киношколи у нас. Тяхната поява и първи стъпки в развитието им се проследяват в контекста на настъпилото общо оживление в киното в София и в България от 1921 г., а като надежден източник на информация от и за това време се използват новопоявилите се тогава немалко специализирани периодични издания, посветени на киното. С присъщата си изчерпателност и задълбоченост в проучването и издирването на максимален брой различни източници, Петър Кърджилов успява да възстанови картината на ранните киношколи: уточнява имената на участниците в обучението в тях, конкретните програми на обучение и лекторите, представя ръководителите на школите и успява да превърне читателите в свидетели и дори съвременници на събитията. Прецизира всеки детайл и шрих от биографията на Акционерно дружество „Луна“. Вписва тази толкова значима за ранното българско кино институция в историческия контекст, разкрива протекционистичните връзки с правителството на БЗНС, обхваща кинопродукцията ѝ. Представя основаната от дружеството киношкола, ръководена от един от първите у нас руски киноактьори, сценаристи и кинорежисьори – белоемигранта Николай Ларин. Отделя специално внимание и на Шарл Кенке, чието име се свързва с 4 български игрални филма, а вероятно и с хроникално-документалните филми на „Луна“.

Непосредствено свързана с първата студия е следващата я, посветена на българските игрални филми от 1921 до 1923 г. Тук отново откриваме почерка на прецизния изследовател, познаващ всяка най-малка подробност, разкриващ противоречивите източници и произнасящ верните и обосновани отговори на въпросите с много неизвестни. В истинския лабиринт от различни източници с противоречиви и често напълно отричащи се твърдения, единствено експерт и познавач на историята на киното като Петър Кърджилов може да изведе читателите към най-вероятния отговор на поредната загадка. На професионален анализ са подложени филмите: „Лиляна“, „Дяволът в София“, „Виновна ли е?“, „Бай Ганьо“, „Военни действия в мирно време“, „Под старото небе“ и „Момина скала“. В пъзела, който Петър Кърджилов подрежда с вещина за тях, намират място данни не само за създателите, актьорите, но и

за състоялите се или несъстоялите се прожекции, както и по-сетнешната съдба на филмите.

В самостоятелна студия под надслов „Организации и институции“ авторът повежда читателите по трудния път на българското кино в този ранен период, когато ясно личи липсата на разбиране и подкрепа от страна на държавата. В нея са събрани историите на учредяване и дейността на Съюза на българските филмодавци (разпространители, 1921 г.), Съюза на българските кинопритежатели (1924), Съюза на Кинооператорите в България (5 декември 1920 г.), обединил прожектиращите филми в киносалоните и ликвидирал през 1944 г. от „народната власт“. Тук намира място и операцията за доставка на филми и кинематографически апарати „Кино-филм“, както и двата конгреса на кинопритежателите в България, свикани на 1 ноември 1924 г. и на 22 септември 1927 г.

Четвъртата студия, озаглавена „Нови данни за стари филми и техните създатели“ е истински приносна нова страница в българската киноистория. Откритите от автора в Българската национална филмотека две машинописни странички за Йохан Розев (Йохан Розенблат) дават само началото, което той доразвива в подробен и бърз разказ за този, недобре познат дори и от професионалните биографи на българското кино, истински пионер в киното. Петър Кърджилов увлекателно представя процеса на създаване на филма „Виновна ли е?“ от Николай Ларин в АД „Луна“. Допълва с историята около игралния филм „В ноктите на пророка“. Талантът на убедителния разказвач се проявява във възстановяването както на историята на този филм, така и на всички подробности, свързани с участниците. Четири запазени кадъра са достатъчно визуално свидетелство, за да се потвърди участието на Иван Касабов. А чрез мемоарите на Васил Гендов, както и всички данни от специализирания печат биографията на филма се дообогатява с информация за оператора Валтер Андерс, за продуцента, а също и за самия сюжет и съдбата на филма. Любопитни щрихи към създаването на непрожектирания и незапазен филм „В ноктите на порока“ добавя в разказа си Петър Кърджилов във връзка с вътрешните (студийни) снимки на филма.

Отделено е внимание и на филмирането на разрушителното Чирпанско земетресение през април 1928 г. Тук надделява хипотезата, че то е заснето по-скоро от Йохан Розенблат и Валтер Андерс и е включено в кинопрегледа „Патé журнал“. Петър Кърджилов привежда доказателства чрез запазените кадри от архива на „Pathé

News“ (днес известен като „British Pathé“), които вече са дигитализирани и достъпни онлайн.

Запазеното кратко животоописание на Розенблат води разказа и към снимането на филмите: „Нежност“ на италианската фирма „Минерва филм“ (1929 г.), „Майка“ – продукция на „Неро филм“ в Париж (1930), снимания през 1931 г. в България (но незавършен) битов филм „Бъдни вечер“ със Стефан Пейчев, Нина Стойчева и Атанас Христов, а през 1933 г. и на филма „Момичето на природата“². Последният филм е сред многото, чиито следи се губят. Въпреки гръмкото му рекламиране като първи български битов и 100% говорещ и музикален тонфилм, аргументите на Петър Кърджилов, че Христо Константинов не е разполагал с техника за заснемане на тонфилм разколебават силно и поставят под въпрос този обявен факт.

Още няколко филма, вписани в кратката биографична справка на Розентал, са подложени на експертния анализ на Петър Кърджилов: „Кадиш“ (1934 г.) – антихитлеристки със сюжет, свързан с гоненията на евреите; културният филм „Сто дни из Африка“ (1935 г.), „Синята Адриатика“; „Червеният ездач“ (1936 г.); „Симфонията на Рила“ (1937 г.) с участието на хор „Гусла“ и музика на Панчо Владигеров или „Великата Рилска пустиня“ (1938 г.) – 600 метра „културен“ филм.³

Розентал е режисьор в „Патé журнал“ до 1940 г. включително. Завръща се в България и до 1960 г. е режисьор в Студия за научно-популярни филми.

Петата самостоятелна студия е фокусирана върху филма „Великата Рилска пустиня“ (1938), споменаван още и като „Симфонията на Рила“, „Рилската симфония“, „Рилски манастир“ и „Българската светиня – Рилският манастир“. Разказът започва с обсъждането на филма на 1 септември 1939 г. по силата на заповед на Министерството на народното просвещение. Комисията, в състава на която влизат завеждащият службата по кината при министерството, председателят на българския писателски съюз и уредникът на Народния етнографски музей, има за задача да присъства на прожектирането на филма „Симфонията на Рила“, продукция на

² За този филм Йохан Розенблат и Хр. Константинов имат официално удостоверение от Министерството на народното просвещение, с което им се разрешава да снимат на филм различни изгледи с исторически, с битов и културен характер от България.

³ В различните източници този филм има различни заглавия.

Йохан Розев. В открития от Петър Кърджилов в Централния държавен архив протокол от обсъждането е отразено заключението, че филмът е сравнително добре замислен, режисиран и изпълнен и заслужава да бъдат откупени копия, които да служат като отлична пропаганда на българската природа и българската култура.

Петър Кърджилов влита в разказа си също и предисторията на филма „Симфонията на Рила“, въвежда името на австрийския кинооператор и режисьор Ханс Тайер. Проследява неговия жизнен път, познанството му с Йохан Розев и общия им филм „Синият ядран“ („Синята Адриатика“). Добавя справка и за художник-фотографа Пенчо Балкански, който според Йохан Розев е участвал в създаването на културния филм „Симфонията на Рила“.

Заедно с историята на филма, предава атмосферата на снимането, съвременните разкази за природата, за Рилския манастир, Хрельовата кула. Описани са монашеските килии, величествената планина, както и неуспешният опит да се заснемат мощите на Свети Иван Рилски.

На подробен анализ са подложени и авторите на текстове за филма „Великата Рилска пустиня“ в периодични издания и тук, благодарение на детайлното проучване на източниците, Петър Кърджилов достига до правдоподобна хипотеза, че всъщност авторът е един, подписвал се с псевдоними.

Картината, представяща създаването на филма, известен и като „Симфонията на Рила“ и като „Великата Рилска пустиня“, завършва с уточненията, че филмът не е прожектиран в София, но е показван в Пловдив през април 1941 г. Като частна продукция не е откупен от Министерството на народното просвещение, а по-нататък следите на филма се губят.

Шестата студия е посветена на фирмата „Паисий филм“ и нейните киношколи. Основава се както на архивни извори от фонда на Министерството на народното просвещение и от Българската национална филмотека, така и на публикации в периодичния печат и мемоарни извори. Специално място е отделено на Васил Пошев – режисьор на „Най-вярната стража“, но същевременно и създател на няколко филмови школи, както и един от основателите на филмовата кооперация „Български кооперативен филм“ и на Съюза на българските филмови дейци. Името му се свързва дори и с идеята за създаване на киноархив.

Веднага след регистрирането на „Паисий филм“, през април 1928 г. започва работата по филма „Най-вярната стража“. Филмът

получава „цензурна карта“ на 1 април 1929 г. и за първи път е прожектиран на 17 април 1929 г. пред публиката в кино „Сан Стефано“. За лошата операторска работа са набедени роденият през 1898 г. и живеещ в България хърватин (австриец) Франц Роберт Вут и руснакът Владимир Термен (заснел ръчениците и хората и няколко сцени от диалозите)... И за режисьора Васил Пошев не е спестена негативната оценка, че е самоук. Филмът е сниман направо върху позитив, финансиран е само от таксите на киношколите и всъщност не е откупен от Министерството на народното просвещение.

В студията са разказани също така и историите на документалните филми на „Паисий филм“: „Столичната пожарна команда“ (1928), „Мис България“ (1930) и „Търново – старопрестолен град“ (1933). Прелюбопитни са историите около самия конкурс за красота, сладкодумно разказани от Петър Кърджилов.

Изключително ценни са поместените програми на киношколите на „Паисий филм“, данните за лекторите, сред които са проф. Николай Райнов с тема на лекцията „История на изкуството“, народният артист проф. Владимир Трендафилов - „Дикция, художествено четене, декламация“, заслужилата артистка Надя Костова, режисьорът Васил Пошев – „Игрална техника, постановка, логика на преживяването, филмов сценарий, стилове, костюми“. Петко Чирпанлиев – „Моторно дело, автомобилизъм и спорт“, Минко Балкански – „Кино-снимачна техника“, Ал Джое (обозначен като негър, хореограф) – „Джазови танци“ и Аспарух Лешников – „Глазова постановка“.

В заключение на проследената близо 20-годишна история на „Паисий филм“ (от 1928 до 1947), оценката е категорична и напълно основателна, че макар и създадените в нея филми да не оставят ярка диря в историята на българското кино, те са неделима част от тази история, а киношколите години наред задоволяват нуждите от кинообразование в България.

Последните **две студии** са посветени на дейността на Министерството на земеделието и Главната дирекция на народното здраве, свързана с киното.

Филми, които популяризират земеделието и неговите модерни форми в България се появяват едва през 20-те години на 20 век. Първоначално те са дело на специално назначени кореспонденти на „Патé журнал“ или на чуждестранни кинооператори и благодарение на тогавашната преса Петър Кърджилов установява

как са били разпространявани тези филми и каква е била зрителската аудитория. В резултат на засиления интерес, към пътуващия кинематограф са отправяни покани за нови посещения. По това време някои от селскостопанските филми са прожектирани и в чужбина в седмични кинопрегледи. И обратно – чуждестранни селскостопански филми се прожектират в България. Разпространението е осъществявано най-добре от Общия съюз на българските земеделски кооперации. Този съюз също продуцира – поръчва, заплаща направата на нови научнопопулярни и документални филми, най-често заснемани от Минко Балкански. Част от тях са запазени в Българската национална филмотека. Специално внимание авторът отделя на заслугите на Васил Бакърджиев и Симеон Симеонов. Представят се данни както за документалните, така и за игралните филми „на кооперативна тематика“.

Заслужено място в студията се отделя и на усилията на Министерството на земеделието за провежданата филмова стопанска и културна пропаганда из селата, както и на обектите в кинопрегледите на Фондация „Българско дело“.

И накрая са филмите на Главната дирекция на народното здраве, дейността на службата за „филмова пропаганда“ към дирекцията и на филмовата лаборатория за производство на здравно-възпитателни и научни филми. Отличени са тримата създатели на филмите на Главната дирекция – режисьорът Васил Бакърджиев, операторът Симеон Симеонов и сценаристът д-р Захари Захариев. Особено любопитно и пространно е представен първият трикфилм в България „Пакостници“, чийто художник е Стоян Венев, а оператор Васил Бакърджиев.

Разказът в обединените осем студии за българското кино между двете световни войни е поредният принос на Петър Кърджилов в прочита на киноисторията. Голяма част от ранните филми не са запазени. За тях има повече неизвестни, отколкото доказани факти, но Петър Кърджилов като истински детектив търси и установява най-верните и възможни отговори на загадките.

Верен на своя талант, авторът поддържа жив интереса от първия до последния ред на книгата и води читателя по нишките на увлекателно разказаните киноистории, поставя го в ролята на откривател на загадките. Привежда мемоарни свидетелства (публикувани или от архивите), някои от които противоречиви, други избледнели и отдалечени от събитията, за които разказват. Но тук също се проявява професионализмът на Петър Кърджилов, който

представя спомените критично, съпоставяйки ги с други извори, с данни от тогавашната преса и накрая се произнася като експерт и следовател, който аргументира и обосновава най-правдоподобната версия.

С привеждането на множество архивни текстове от времето на описваните събития авторът ни прави още по-близки съвременници. Запазва езика и духа на времето, но, от друга страна, където е необходимо, осъвременява разказа и го прецизира до най-малката подробност, превръща го в достоверен, автентичен откъс от историята на киното.

Характерната за Петър Кърджилев научна етичност се проявява и в настоящата книга. Благодарение на добрата осведоменост, но и на уважението към всичко, което е установено и написано преди него, той добросъвестно цитира всеки автор, който е открил и оповестил един или друг биографичен шрих от историята на киното.

С нови имена, факти, взаимовръзки между тях, с нови извори и задълбочен и прецизен анализ, книгата дава отговори, буди размисли и същевременно поставя нови въпроси. А нейният автор без съмнение печели отново доверието на читателите като прецизен и задълбочен изследовател, с присъщата си научна етика и коректност, с таланта си на вдъхновен и обграден от музите писател и сладкодумен разказвач на киноистории.

В ръцете ни е вече поредното ценно, дълбоко, критично и много професионално изследване на историята на ранното българско кино, четивно и сладкодумно като приказка и същевременно с тежестта на научен академичен труд.

BOOK REVIEW

Penka Iv. Peykovska

Institute for Historical Studies – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences

[pykvsk@yahoo.com], ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7979-3258

The Challenges of Integration: Refugees from the Middle East in Bulgaria (2013–2019)

Abstract: The monograph 'The (Im)Possible Integration of Refugees from the Middle East in Bulgaria (2013–2019)' presents and discusses the results of an interdisciplinary study on different aspects of the reception and integration of persons who have sought and granted international protection in Bulgaria. Particular attention is paid to: the contradictions between legislation and policy, and the assessments of a number of national and international organisations; refugees in the public discourse; public attitudes and reactions in a national and local context; and the intentions of refugees themselves to settle and integrate into Bulgarian society. Despite their stigmatization, the author elaborates on the scholarly conceptions made so far and proposes a model for the integration of refugees from the Middle East according to the specific Bulgarian conditions.

Keywords: refugees; 2013–2019; integration; Middle East; Bulgaria.

Пенка Ив. Пейковска

Институт за исторически изследвания – Българска академия на науките

Предизвикателствата на интеграцията: бежанците от Близкия изток в България (2013–2019)

Еролова Йелис. (Не)Възможната интеграция на бежанците от Близкия изток в България (2013–2019). Пловдив 2024. ИЕФЕМ–БАН, АСТАРТА, ISBN 978-954-350-371-1, 332 с.

Темата, разработена в монографията на д-р Йелис Еролова „(Не)Възможната интеграция на бежанците от Близкия изток в

Йелис Еролова

**(НЕ)ВЪЗМОЖНАТА ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ
НА БЕЖАНЦИТЕ
ОТ БЛИЗКИЯ ИЗТОК В БЪЛГАРИЯ
(2013 – 2019)**

България (2013–2019)“, е изключително актуална и социално значима за съвременна България. Страната ни и днес продължава да бъде преимуществено емигрантска, с ниска раждаемост и висока смъртност, което я поставя сред държавите с най-дълбока демографска криза не само в Европа, но и в света. Вследствие на тези процеси цели региони се обезлюдяват, а икономиката изпитва остър недостиг на работна сила. В такъв контекст възниква големият въпрос, който стои в центъра на изследването на Еролова – възможно ли е бежанците да се превърнат в част от решението на демографските и социално-икономическите предизвикателства чрез своята интеграция в българското общество. България има дълбоки исторически традиции в приемането и интегрирането на имигранти и бежанци – още от времето на създаването на Третата българска държава, когато в освободената си родина се завръщат българи от диаспората, а по-късно, след Балканските войни и Първата световна война, страната приема над двеста хиляди бежанци – българи от загубените територии, руси и арменци. Този исторически опит, натрупан в условията на големи социални и политически промени, представлява важен фон за разбирането на съвременните интеграционни процеси. Въпросът за възможната интеграция на бежанците не е само национален, а и общоевропейски – той стои с особена сила пред всички държави членки на Европейския съюз, които търсят устойчиви решения между хуманитарните си ангажменти и обществената стабилност. В страни като Германия и Франция, приели най-големия брой бежанци след 2015 г., се наблюдават едновременно успешни практики на интеграция чрез образование и заетост и трудности, свързани с културната адаптация и възникналото социално напрежение. В този контекст българският опит, макар и развиващ се в по-малък мащаб, може да послужи като ценен сравнителен пример – как една страна с ограничени ресурси, но с богата историческа традиция в интеграцията на

бежанци и имигранти, реагира на съвременните миграционни предизвикателства и какви поуки могат да се извлекат от нейния специфичен контекст.

Авторката д-р Йелис Еролова е утвърден специалист в областта на етнологията, подготвян системно още от студентските си години в Софийския университет „Св. Климент Охридски“. Като изследовател в Института за етнология и фолклористика с Етнографски музей при Българската академия на науките тя участва в редица научни проекти и специализации в престижни международни институции – като Варшавския и Регенбургския университет, както и в изследователски центрове, занимаващи се с миграция и Югоизточна Европа. Натрупаният международен и теренен опит обогатява нейния аналитичен подход и личната ѝ чувствителност към проблемите на хората в движение. Изследователските ѝ интереси са насочени основно към миграционните процеси – бежанство, имиграция и емиграция, адаптация и интеграция на различни общности. Особено ценен е нейният практически опит от доброволческата ѝ работа с бежанци и имигранти в България, който придава на научните ѝ анализи автентичност и дълбочина.

В книгата е изследвана интеграцията на бежанците от Близкия изток в България през периода от 2013 г. до 2019 г. – години, през които миграционните потоци поставят редица предизвикателства пред Европейския съюз и неговите държави членки. Авторката я разглежда не просто като административен или икономически процес, а като дълбоко социално и културно взаимодействие между „домакините“ и „новодошлите“, в което се проявяват нагласи, стереотипи и различия в ценностите. Тя успешно прилага интердисциплинарен подход, обединяващ етнология, културна и социална антропология, социология и историческа перспектива. В първата част на изследването е проследено развитието на бежанските политики и законодателството в България. Внимателно е разгледано нормативното развитие от началото на XX в. до 2019 г., като авторката обособява три периода – до 1989 г., от 1990 до 2007 г. и след присъединяването на страната ни към Европейския съюз. Анализът е задълбочен, изграден върху причинно-следствени връзки и поставен в широк исторически и международен контекст. Особено внимание е отделено на кризисните ситуации след 2013 г., когато България се превръща в една от външните граници на Европейския съюз и е изправена пред сериозен миграционен натиск.

По-нататък в текста акцентът пада върху обществените нагласи спрямо бежанците и върху техните собствени представи за процеса на интеграция. Втората част е посветена на начина, по който медиите и религиозните институции представят бежанците и как тези репрезентации оформят обществените нагласи. Й. Еролова анализира езика на новините, използваните образи и реториката, които често подхранват стереотипи и страхове. В същото време тя отчита различията в позициите на религиозните общности и тяхната роля в изграждането на публичния дискурс.

В третата част фокусът е върху локалните нагласи в конкретни населени места – както такива с бежанско присъствие, така и без него. Подробно е разгледан „случаят Харманли“, който се превръща в емблематичен пример за социалното напрежение, възникващо от недоразбиране и липса на комуникация между местното население и бежанците. Еролова убедително показва, че негативните нагласи често произтичат не от пряко взаимодействие, а от несигурност, икономически страхове и недостатъчна информираност. В последната част на труда са проучени нагласите на самите бежанци към интеграцията. Чрез дълбочинни интервюта, проведени в процеса на теренна работа, авторката представя личните им истории, стремежите и предизвикателствата, с които се сблъскват в България. Анализът обхваща жилищното настаняване, трудовата заетост, изучаването на български език, контактите с местните жители и възможностите за културна адаптация. Особено внимание е отделено на въпроса за съчетаването между запазване на културната идентичност и необходимостта от адаптиране към новата социална среда. Всяка част от монографията завършва с ясно формулирани изводи, които синтезират резултатите от анализа и имат практическа насоченост.

В заключението Еролова обобщава своите наблюдения, подчертавайки, че интеграцията на бежанците е възможна само при взаимни усилия – от страна на институциите и местните общности, но и от самите бежанци, които трябва да участват активно в обществения живот. Особено ценни са трите приложения в края на книгата, съдържащи статистически данни и таблици с трудно достъпна информация за бежанците в България. Те допълват изследването с конкретни емпирични показатели и повишават неговата информативна стойност. Целият труд се отличава с прецизност, аналитична задълбоченост и богата изворова база – законодателни

актове, международни документи, отчети на институции, публикации в медиите, както и собствени теренни наблюдения и интервюта. Опитът на авторката от работата ѝ с бежанци като доброволец допринася за автентичността и реалистичността на представените наблюдения.

Монографията „(Не)Възможната интеграция на бежанците от Близкия изток в България (2013–2019)“ представлява ценен принос към българската и европейската научна литература върху миграцията и социалната интеграция. Трудът на д-р Йелис Еролова впечатлява с интердисциплинарния си подход, богатия емпиричен материал и аналитичната зрялост на изводите. Книгата е полезна не само за изследователи и студенти в областта на етнологията, антропологията и социологията, но и за институции, неправителствени организации и експерти, работещи по проблемите на бежанците и миграцията. С научната си обосновааност, социална чувствителност и практическа насоченост тя се нарежда сред най-стойностните съвременни изследвания върху миграционните процеси в България.

BOOK REVIEW

Milena Angelova

New Bulgarian University (Bulgaria)

[mangelova74@yahoo.com], ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0208-1989

Shadow Modernities and the State's Grey Zones: Three Criminal Regimes in Bulgarian History (1879–1944)

Abstract: *This review examines Dimitar Gyudurov's book *Traders of "White Slaves," Forgers and Smugglers in Bulgaria (1879–1944)* as part of a broader research project on illicit economies and state formation in modern Bulgaria. Drawing on the concepts of "shadow modernities" and "grey zones of governance", the review argues that Gyudurov reconceptualizes trafficking in women, forgery, and smuggling not as marginal criminal phenomena but as structural components of state rationality. By situating the Bulgarian case within international regulatory regimes and interdisciplinary debates, the review highlights the book's contribution to rethinking modern governance through illegality, informality, and institutional ambivalence. Together with the author's earlier monograph on opiates, the book marks a significant shift in Bulgarian social history toward a practice-oriented and transnational perspective.*

Keywords: *shadow modernities; grey zones of governance; illicit economies; social history, Bulgaria (1879–1944); trafficking; forgery; smuggling.*

Милена Ангелова

Нов български университет

Сенчестите модерности и сивите зони на държавата: Три криминални режима в българската история (1879–1944)

Гюдуров, Димитър (2025). *Търговци на „бели робини“, фалшификатори и контрабандисти в България (1879–1944)*. София: НБУ, 339 с., ISBN - 978-619-233-346-1.

Книгата на Димитър Гюдуров *Търговци на „бели робини“, фалшификатори и контрабандисти в България (1879–1944)* предлага систематично изследване на три криминални режима в хронологията на модерната българска държавност. Поставено в контекста на българската историографска традиция, изследването предлага качествено различна перспектива. Авторът не разглежда престъпността като периферия на социалния живот или като следствие от институционални дефицити, а я дефрагментира като поле на взаимодействие между държавата, обществото и международната среда.

Анализът тук измества фокуса от институциите, като завършени структури, към практиките, чрез които държавността се произвежда ежедневно – често в сивите зони между законност и престъпност. Именно тук е заложено основното изследователско предизвикателство – не само в избора на слабо изследвани теми, а в начина, по който тези теми се превръщат във важен лакмус за разбирането на българската модерност.

Вместо да тръгва от държавата и нейните институции като априорно стабилни, Д. Гюдуров фокусира анализа към практиките, конкретните икономики и мрежи, които държавата се опитва да регулира. Така престъпността се очертава не като „враг“ на модерността, а се вписва в нейната вътрешна логика, чрез която се кодифицират граници, идентичности и форми на легитимност. В този смисъл книгата не е семпло допълнение към съществуващата литература, а препозициониране на изследователското поле. Д. Гюдуров насочва анализа си към теми, които дълго време са били маргинализирани или третираны описателно, и ги превръща в ключ към разбирането на модерното българско общество. Именно тук се залага основният му историографски принос – не само в добавянето на нови „случаи“, а в промяната на аналитичната перспектива. Изследването не е само исторически анализ на престъп-

ленията, определени за „социални злини“ (особено в междувоенния период), а и базисен принос към историята на държавността в нейните *сенчести*¹ измерения.

Търговци на „бели робини“, фалшификатори и контрабандисти в България (1879–1944) представлява втора логическа и концептуална част от по-мощен изследователски проект на автора, започнал с публикуването на монографията *Българите и опиатите. Производство и търговия (1879 – 1944)* (Гюдуров, 2022). В рамките на този проект той систематично изследва нелегалните и полулегалните практики и политики, които съпътстват и оформят българската модерност от Освобождението до установяването на просъветски режим на управление в страната.

Първата книга – посветена на производството и търговията с опиати – вече показва ключовите характеристики на изследователския подход на автора: отговорна работа с архивни източници; фокус върху международните регулаторни режими (включително ролята на Обществото на народите); анализ на взаимодействието между националната държава и международните мрежи и експертен анализ, дистанциран от нормативни или морализиращи интерпретации на *криминалното*. В този смисъл *Българите и опиатите...* поставя аналитичните основи за разбирането на престъпността като структурен компонент на държавността, а не като външна заплаха за нея. Втората монография разширява този аналитичен хоризонт, като премества фокуса от специфичен продукт (опиатите) към различни *режими на нелегалност* – трафик на жени, фалшификации и контрабанда. Тази промяна не означава разкъсване с предходния подход, а по-скоро негово методологическо надграждане. Ако първата книга показва как конкретна нелегална стока се вписва в международни икономически и политически мрежи, втората демонстрира как нелегалността като практика функционира в различни сфери на социалния живот. В този смисъл

¹ Терминът *shadow modernities* обозначава онези форми на модерна държавност, икономическа рационализация и бюрократично разширяване, които се развиват *редом с, чрез* или *въпреки* практики, обявени за незаконни, неформални или социално маргинални. Вместо да противопоставят легалното и нелегалното, някои изследватели подчертават, че криминализираните практики нерядко участват активно в консолидирането на държавната власт, в оформянето на пазари и в производството на модерни социални категории. Автори като Van Schendel и Abraham (2005), както и Gingeras (2014), твърдят, че тези „сенки“ не са остатъчни или периферни явления, а структурни елементи на реално съществуващите модерности.

двете книги могат да бъдат четени като цялостен проект за историзиране на *сивите зони на управлението*² в България и като взаимно допълващи се анализи на *сенчестите модерности* на държавата. Опиатите, трафикът на жени, фалшификациите и контрабандата очертават различни, но структурно сходни пространства, които държавата едновременно регулира, толерира или в които даже участва. По този начин проектът на Гюдуров допринася за преориентирането на българската социална история към въпроси, които са централни в актуалните изследователски дебати в по-широк сравнителен прочит.

От една страна, този подход де-екзотизира престъпността, като я изважда от морализиращите и сензационни наративи и я поставя в контекста на социалната и икономическата рационалност. От друга страна, той проблематизира самата държава, показвайки я не като завършен и последователен субект, а като поле на противоречиви практики, селективен контрол и институционална нееднозначност. От тази перспектива *Търговци на „бели робини“*, *фалшификатори и контрабандисти* не просто надгражда първата монография, а разкрива мащаба на изследователска програма на автора: реконструкция на онези полета, в които модерната държава се изгражда не въпреки, а чрез нелегалното. Изследването на Д. Гюдуров задава и интересен ключ към начина, по който може да бъде мислена социалната история на българското общество от късния XIX и първата половина на XX век. Вместо да възпроизведат утвърдената рамка на институционална история, фокусирана върху законодателство, управленски динамики или елити, тук аналитичната тежест е изместена към мрежата от *практики, режими на контрол и неформални икономики*, чрез които държавата реално функционира.

Още във въведението става ясно, че авторът отказва опростеното бинарното противопоставяне между „законно“ и „незаконно“. Той насочва, че трафикът на жени, фалшификациите и

² Концепцията за *grey zones of governance* описва пространства, в които границата между държавно и недържавно, легално и нелегално, формално и неформално управление е размита. Тези зони възникват не поради отсъствие на държавата, а често именно чрез нейното *селективно, непоследователно или противоречиво* упражняване на власт. В тези сиви зони полицаи, митничари, местни чиновници и посредници могат едновременно да утвърждават и да подкопават държавните регулации. Вместо бинарно противопоставяне между ред и безредие, „сивата зона“ представлява континуум от практики на управление. – Вж: Gupta (2012), Das & Poole (2004).

контрабандата ще бъдат анализирани не изолирано, а в постоянно взаимодействие с полицията, медицината, митническата администрация и международните регламенти.

Първата част на книгата е концептуално рамкирана от напрежението между регламентаризма, аболиционизма и санитарния контрол. Проституцията и трафикът на жени са представени като поле, в което се пресичат морални дискурси, медицинска експертиза и полицейска власт. Тук Гюдуров показва как българската държава адаптира европейските модели за контрол върху проституцията – включително чрез санитарни режими, полицейска регистрация и медицински надзор, превръщайки женското тяло в обект на наблюдение и административна интервенция. Този анализ се вписва в аналитичните дебати за държавните проекти на модерността – напр. на административна разпознаваемост, прозрачност и четимост (*legibility*)³ (Scott, 1998) – или за селективното прилагане на власт, които легитимират анализа на *нелегалното* като структурно, а не като „провал“. Участието на България в международните конвенции срещу трафика допълнително показва, че тези практики не са локално отклонение, а част от транснационални режими (Laite, 2017; De Vries, 2005; Attwood 2013). Бюрократичната власт действа чрез „селективност и двусмислие“ (Gupta, 2012)⁴ – наблюдение, което намира пряко потвърждение в анализа на санитарния и полицейския контрол в книгата. Особено важен е анализът на участието на България в международните конвенции срещу трафика на жени, който показва, че страната е активен участник в глобалните правни режими в тази област. Проституцията се явява

³ Както показва Джеймс Скот, модерната държава функционира чрез опростяване и схематизация на социалната реалност, но именно тези „legibility projects“ пораждаат широки полета на неформални практики и адаптации, без които управлението не би могло да работи ефективно (Scott, 1998). Гюдуров разглежда *нелегалното* не като провал, а като структурна част от управлението. В този смисъл неговият прочит резонира и с разбирането на Michael Taussig (1997) за държавата като сенчест и перформативен конструктор, поддържан чрез амбивалентни режими на власт.

⁴ Акил Гупта смята, че бюрокрацията функционира чрез селективно прилагане на законите, непрозрачност и структурно насилие, създавайки зони, в които законността и незаконността съжителстват, вместо да се противопоставят една на друга. Според неговата формула *управлението* се осъществява чрез ежедневни бюрократични практики, които размиват границата между правилата и произвола и че бюрокрацията функционира именно чрез „сиви зони“ между законност и произвол. (Gupta, 2012).

класически пример за *grey zone of governance*: едновременно регулирана, толерирана и криминализирана.

Втората част – „Фалшификаторите“ – предлага един от най-оригиналните приноси в книгата. Тук се вижда как неформалните практики не винаги подкопават институциите, а често представляват тяхна *скрита инфраструктура* (Ledeneva, 2006)⁵. Фалшификатът се явява форма на адаптация към бюрократичната рационалност и средство за социална и политическа мобилност, особено в периоди на война и криза. В същото време той има и символно измерение, близко до разбирането за държавата като перформативен и „магически“ конструктор (Taussig, 1997)⁶, чиито символи на легитимност винаги могат да бъдат имитирани.

Третата част анализира контрабандата като икономическа и социална практика, неразривно свързана с граничните режими и митническата администрация. Авторът доказва, че границите функционират не просто като линии на контрол, а като *ресурси*, които различни актьори използват стратегически. Изведен е и проблемът за „Контрабандистите в униформа“ (247-276) – държавните служители се оказват част от нелегалните мрежи. Този анализ, положен сравнително в контекста на изследванията за *нелегалните потоци* и *граничните икономики* (Schendel & Abraham, 2005; Gingeras, 2014; Gallien, & Weigand, 2022), най-плътно материализира понятието „сива зона на управлението“ и поставя под въпрос опростеното противопоставяне между държава и престъпност.

В епилога трите режима се обединяват в цялостен анализ на институционалната нееднозначност. Именно тук най-ясно се вижда *проектната* логика на изследването и връзката му с предходната книга за опиятите. Държавата се разкрива не като последователен арбитър, а като участник в мрежи от компромиси, селективен контрол и неформални практики.

Изследването на Д. Гюдуров не разглежда престъпността като симптом на „слаба държавност“ или социална патология, той

⁵ Според А. Леденева неформалните практики не подкопават институциите, а често представляват тяхната скрита инфраструктура, особено в контекста на бърза модернизация и институционално претоварване (Ledeneva, 2006) – перспектива, която е напълно приложима към анализите на фалшификацията и контрабандата в труда на Гюдуров.

⁶ Майкъл Таусиг концептуализира държавата не само като институционален апарат, но и като „спектрална“ и перформативна единица, поддържана чрез ритуали на власт, страх и двусмислие, а не само чрез прозрачна законност. (Taussig, 1997).

я използва като аналитичен вход към самите механизми на управление. Този подход препозиционира престъпността от периферията към центъра на анализа. *Търговци на „бели робини“, фалшификатори и контрабандисти* е концептуално зрял и методологически последователен труд, който убеждава, че модерната българска държава се изгражда не въпреки, а чрез своите сенчести практики. Заедно с *Българите и опиатите* книгата очертава изследователски проект, който променя начина, по който може да се пише социална история в България – от гледната точка на нормата към тази на нейните *гранични режими*. През този концептуален хоризонт анализът на трафика на жени, фалшификациите и контрабандата се вписва успешно в по-широкия дебат за това, как се формират модерните държави. Емпиричната реконструкция на полицейски архиви, съдебни дела, дипломатическа кореспонденция и международни конвенции демонстрира, че българската модерност е произведена не само чрез законодателни реформи и институционално консолидиране, но и чрез нелегалните икономики и двусмислените практики, които циркулират в и около държавните структури. В този смисъл българският случай отразява глобални модели, при които „сенчестото“ и „официалното“ не просто съществуват паралелно, а понякога се сътворяват взаимно.

Търговци на „бели робини“, фалшификатори и контрабандисти е важен труд за българската хуманитаристика. Книгата е пример за успешен академичен трансфер: тя въвежда международни дебати в националната научна среда и предлага нови инструменти за разбирането на сивите зони, които неизбежно съпътстват модерността.

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Pro Memoria: Grigor Grigorov (1969–2025)

Д-р Григор Бориславов Григоров – изследовател, преподавател и най-вече – пътешественик по дух, посветил голяма част от живота си на българския език и културното наследство, особено там, където то пулсира най-силно, сред българските общности в чужбина.

Роден е на 25 септември 1969 г. в София. Средното си образование завършва в Перник, а висшето – в Югозападния университет „Неофит Рилски“, специалност Българска филология. След като защитава докторска степен по културология и спечелва конкурс за главен асистент в едноименната катедра на университета в Благоевград, той поема

значима академична и културна мисия в чужбина, която го отвежда в сърцето на българската диаспора. Професионалният му път включва дългогодишна преподавателска дейност в университети в Молдова, Беларус, Румъния и Унгария. Този пряк контакт с нашите сънародници и другите етнокултурни общности в чужбина, в съчетание с неговия обширен теренен опит, го утвърди като водещ специалист по въпросите на етническата идентичност, езиковото функциониране и съхраняването на културната памет в Северното Причерноморие и Бесарабия.

Научното наследство на гл. ас. д-р Григор Григоров се отличава с широк обхват и подчертан интердисциплинарен подход, развит около две основни изследователски теми. Първата е посве-

тена на **културната история на тялото и медицината** в славянските и балканските земи, анализирана чрез средновековната и ранномодерната писмена традиция. Работата му в тази област, синтезирана в монографията „Човешкото тяло според ръкописните книги лековници“, разглежда човешкото тяло като културен феномен. Той изследва как символиката на цветовете, употребата на севивата и невербалните изражения на идентичност са били закодирани в ръкописите-лековници. Този подход, съчетаващ фолклористика, текстология и историческа антропология, разкрива устойчиви представи за здраве, болест и ритуал в българската писмена култура.

Втората значима линия в неговите изследвания е концентрирана върху **българските и гагаузките общности в Бесарабия и Северното Причерноморие**. Д-р Григоров има съществен принос в документирането на езиковото и културното функциониране на българския език в Молдова, както и в анализирането на сложната национална и езикова идентичност сред гагаузите. Публикациите му обхващат теми като езиковото развитие, паметта за преселението, етноутвърждаващите идеи и ролята на културни дейци в региона. Чрез този обширен теренно базиран анализ, той допринася за

разбирането на малцинствените култури, межкултурния диалог и динамиката на паметта в граничните пространства. Завършена е книгата му „Културна история на бесарабските гагаузи“, чието второ издание подготвят съпругата му Оля и негови съмишленици.

Изследователският му път е неотделим от активната му роля като преподавател по български език и литература в чужбина. Той

работи в университети в **Молдова, Беларус, Румъния и Унгария**, като този опит му позволява да живее и общува пряко с българската диаспора и с другите култури в региона. Тези продължителни престои не са просто академичен ангажи-мент, а мисия за културно взаимодействие, което обогатява изследванията му с живи впечатления и пряк

контакт с темата. По време на тази дейност, той съставя сборници и участва в инициативи за укрепване на връзките между България и местните общности, като същевременно спомага за съхраняването и популяризирането на кирило-методиевските традиции и българския език. Особено запомнящо се години след това е пълнокръвното му присъствие в Букурещкия университет и сред българите в районите на румънската столица и Банат, където той беше приет като събрат.

В Молдова Григор преподава едновременно в Комрат – столицата на независимия район Гагаузия, и в Тираспол – столицата на непризнатата Приднестровска република. Личните му впечатления от периода са събрани в книгата „Комратското тефтерче: Културно-антропологични записки от Молдова“ (2010). Тя съдържа фрагментарни записки и размисли, водени в личния му бележник, които имат документална стойност. „Тефтерчето“ отразява задъхания му живот сред българската диаспора и гагаузката общност в Молдова, предлагайки по-сложен и нюансиран поглед от стереотипите, с които често се мисли за тези сънародници. То е

опит да се погледне на собствената култура „през очите на диаспората“, превръщайки личния му престой в ценен източник на антропологично познание за средата и хората, които го заобикалят.

Григор ни напусна внезапно на 12 юни 2025 г. Беше човек с изключително широки научни интереси, необозрими културни познания, дълбоко житейско любопитство към всеки човек и всяка тема и учудваща липса на каквато и да е суета. Неговата работа е пример за това как хуманитарната наука може да бъде жива, теренна и проникващо интердисциплинарна. Неговото наследство е урок по чиста ерудиция и човешка доброта и споменът за неуязвимата му усмивка, дръзновения му дух, любовта към музиката, пътя, хората и живота е енергия, която ще продължава да свързва и вдъхновява всички, които го познаваха.

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